

A Compendium of Regulated Concentrated Animal Feeding Operation (CAFO) Manure Land Application Regulations

2nd Edition

Produced by the Sustainable Phosphorus Alliance and STEPS

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NOTE: Regulations are “living” data in that they are always being updated. While we will do our best to update the database when we have resources available, some data may not be up to date. Additionally, as we improve the quality assurance of the existing data, the compendium may be updated.

Preface

Applying animal wastes (manures) as an organic form of fertilizer is not a new concept. However, currently, the use of manures in U.S. agriculture has been focused primarily as a way to deal with excess manure generated from large-scale animal production, rather than as a viable, alternative nutrient source to energy-intensive, but cheap, inorganic fertilizer options. While most animal manure produced in the U.S. is land applied for agricultural purposes, much of the applications are not subject to regulation, and there are many cases of over-application of these rich nutrient sources.

Manures, which in this report can also mean litter, process wastewater, and other solid or liquid by-products of animal agriculture production, can provide phosphorus, nitrogen, and organic matter, all of which can benefit soil health and agricultural productivity. However, existing federal regulations governing the land application of manures from regulated farms, called concentrated animal feeding operations (CAFOs), allow for substantial flexibility in state interpretation of how farms are regulated.

The U.S. Environmental Protection Agency defines animal feeding operations (AFOs) as agricultural operations where animals are kept and raised in confined situations. Specifically, an AFO has animals that have been, are, or will be stabled or confined and fed or maintained for a total of 45 days or more in any 12-month period, and where the operation does not have crops, vegetation, forage growth, or post-harvest residues sustained during normal growing season over any portion of the lot or facility. If an AFO meets animal number specifications set in Table 1, then these are considered CAFOs and may then be subject to NPDES permitting, depending on the state.

Table 1. CAFO size categories from 40 CFR.

Animal type	Sizes Defined by Animal Numbers		
	Large CAFO	Medium CAFO	Small CAFO
Cattle or cow/calf pairs	> 1000	300-999	< 300
Mature dairy cattle	> 700	200-699	< 200
Veal calves	> 1000	300 – 999	< 300
Swine (weighing over 55 pounds)	> 2500	750 – 2499	< 750
Swine (weighing less than 55 pounds)	> 10000	3000 – 9999	< 3000
Horses	> 500	150 – 499	< 150
Sheep or lambs	> 10000	3000 – 9999	< 3000
Turkeys	> 55000	16500 – 54999	< 16500
Laying hens or broilers (liquid manure handling systems)	> 30000	9000 – 29999	< 9000
Chickens other than laying hens (other than liquid manure handling systems)	> 125000	37500 – 124999	< 37500
Laying hens (other than liquid manure handling systems)	> 82000	25000 – 81999	< 25000
Ducks (other than liquid manure handling systems)	> 30000	10,000 – 29999	< 10000

Even in this base definition, there are variations by state. For example, some states require all CAFOs to have a National Pollutant Discharge Elimination (NPDES) permit while others only require an NPDES permit if the CAFO has actual discharges to waters of the U.S. Additionally, the animal type categories and size numbers may vary by state. For instance, Wyoming has a “buffalo” animal type category.

The federal regulations require that CAFOs with NPDES permits submit a nutrient management plan (NMP) in an effort to better manage the runoff occurring from the land application of CAFO manures. The federal regulations set minimum standards for what should be required in the NMP, but specific rules are left up to the states. Many states choose to follow explicitly or implicitly the Natural Resource Conservation Service Conservation Practice Standard for Nutrient Management (Code 590). Other states adopt additional practices based on state extension guidance.

Additional federal regulations include procedures for transferring manure produced to third parties, annual report record-keeping, and required setbacks from waterways for land application. States can and do augment these regulations to be more stringent or to include other restrictions for land application of manures, such as weather or seasonal restrictions. While the flexibility provided to the states in federal regulations may allow for location-based guidelines to prevail, the result is a patchwork of regulations that can be difficult to navigate.

This compendium of state-level regulations is meant to provide a summary of state-level regulations related to the land application of manures produced from regulated animal feeding operations. This is version 2 of a compendium that was first produced in 2019. We have tried to obtain updates to the regulations from the relevant state agencies, and those updates are reflected here. However, many states did not respond to our multiple requests for updates. We have listed the latest update date within the state tables presented in this document.

Our focus here is on regulations that directly affect nutrient flows through the environment that result from land application. We are specifically interested in what agronomic practices are prescribed and what limits are placed on the use of manures. We deliberately chose not to treat regulations that deal with administrative details, including monitoring and permitting requirements, labeling and reporting requirements, and other aspects of the regulations related to discharges from production areas, though we do recognize that some these have implications for nutrient flows. As such, we do provide reference to the appropriate regulations to guide more trenchant research.

Given the extreme variability from state-to-state, we do not provide state regulations in comparison to federal. To aid those who wish to complete this comparison on their own, we provide the U.S. federal regulations as the first document. Regulations related to land application from CAFOs are provided in the following federal codes:

- 40 CFR Part 412 – Concentrated animal feeding operations (CAFO) point source category
- 40 CFR 122.23 – Concentrated animal feeding operations
- 40 CFR 122.42 (e) – Additional conditions applicable to specified categories of NPDES permits

The summary documents are each divided into three sections. The first provides details about the regulations and regulators. The second provides key definitions that states have adopted, focusing on permitting processes, and definitions of CAFOs. The third section contains the state-level regulations of land application, which may be explicitly from the CFR, vary slightly from CFR, or extend beyond the CFR. A brief key to the row headers follows.

Regulator	
Regulating Agency	The state agency that oversees the CAFO permitting. May be a combination of agencies that work together.
Regulation Links	Links to regulations as written and/or guidance documents describing permitting process
Other Regulatory Details	Additional details regarding regulation of manures applications
Definitions	
CAFO Definition	Definitions of AFO, CAFO, and any subsequent size categories used. Might be same or slightly different from federal definitions
Animal Unit Definition	While the federal regulations (and many states) have switched to size categories for defining CAFOs by animal numbers, some states still use “animal units” which are used to calculate relative impacts of different kinds and classes of animals
CAFO Permit Summary	Details on which operations are required to have NPDES permits and other permits required by the states
Other Definitions	Other definitions needed to better understand state-level regulatory details
Regulatory Details	
Setbacks Regulations	State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some geographical feature
Weather and Seasonal Regulations	State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather, seasons, or land characteristics (such as slope)
Manure Transfer Regulations	Requirements related to the transfer of manures to other persons
Nutrient Management Plans	Additional details on the NMP requirement. Note that some of this information may overlap with other sections.
Application Rate Regulations	State regulations that restrict the rates at which manures are applied and methods needed to determine appropriate rates.
Composition Testing Regulations	State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on manures before application
Other Land Application Regulations	Additional restrictions for land application of manures
Other CAFO Regulations	Additional information on the regulation of land application of manures

Finally, while we have done our best to provide a faithful and, as of January 2025, up-to-date account of these state regulations, we make no guarantee of accuracy. As mentioned above, many of the states that we contacted for updates since 2019 did not provide them and, as a result, some of the data below can only be confirmed as correct as of March 2019. Clearly, this document should not be used to determine the legality of any practice.

This compendium is a companion to our Compendium of Biosolids Land Application Regulations. We hope that these guides provide a resource that ultimately helps increase the *sustainable* reuse of organic residuals through thoughtful, cross-audience discussion of existing regulations governing their use.

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It should be noted that the authors of the report are solely responsible for the content and responsibility should not be assigned to any of the aforementioned organizations.

U.S. FEDERAL REGULATIONS

Regulator	
Regulating Agency	US Environmental Protection Agency (US EPA)
Regulation Links	<p>40 CFR Part 412 – CAFO Point Source Category https://www.law.cornell.edu/cfr/text/40/part-412</p> <p>40 CFR 122.23 – CAFOs (applicable to State NPDES programs) https://www.law.cornell.edu/cfr/text/40/122.23</p> <p>40 CFR 122.42 – Additional conditions applicable to specified categories of NPDES permits https://www.law.cornell.edu/cfr/text/40/122.42</p>
Other Regulatory Details	NA
Definitions	
CAFO Definition	<p>Animal feeding operation (“AFO”) means a lot or facility (other than an aquatic animal production facility) where the following conditions are met: (i) Animals (other than aquatic animals) have been, are, or will be stabled or confined and fed or maintained for a total of 45 days or more in any 12-month period, and (ii) Crops, vegetation, forage growth, or post-harvest residues are not sustained in the normal growing season over any portion of the lot or facility.</p> <p>Concentrated animal feeding operation (“CAFO”) means an AFO that is defined as a Large CAFO or as a Medium CAFO by the terms of this paragraph, or that is designated as a CAFO in accordance with paragraph (c) of this section. Two or more AFOs under common ownership are considered to be a single AFO for the purposes of determining the number of animals at an operation, if they adjoin each other or if they use a common area or system for the disposal of wastes.</p> <p>Large concentrated animal feeding operation (“Large CAFO”). An AFO is defined as a Large CAFO if it stables or confines as many as or more than the numbers of animals specified in any of the following categories: (i) 700 mature dairy cows, whether milked or dry; (ii) 1,000 veal calves; (iii) 1,000 cattle other than mature dairy cows or veal calves. Cattle includes but is not limited to heifers, steers, bulls and cow/calf pairs; (iv) 2,500 swine each weighing 55 pounds or more; (v) 10,000 swine each weighing less than 55 pounds; (vi) 500 horses; (vii) 10,000 sheep or lambs; (viii) 55,000 turkeys; (ix) 30,000 laying hens or broilers, if the AFO uses a liquid manure handling system;</p>

	<p>(x) 125,000 chickens (other than laying hens), if the AFO uses other than a liquid manure handling system;</p> <p>(xi) 82,000 laying hens, if the AFO uses other than a liquid manure handling system;</p> <p>(xii) 30,000 ducks (if the AFO uses other than a liquid manure handling system); or</p> <p>(xiii) 5,000 ducks (if the AFO uses a liquid manure handling system).</p> <p>Medium concentrated animal feeding operation (“Medium CAFO”). The term Medium CAFO includes any AFO with the type and number of animals that fall within any of the ranges listed below and which has been defined or designated as a CAFO. An AFO is defined as a Medium CAFO if:</p> <p>(i) The type and number of animals that it stables or confines falls within any of the following ranges:</p> <p>(A) 200 to 699 mature dairy cows, whether milked or dry;</p> <p>(B) 300 to 999 veal calves;</p> <p>(C) 300 to 999 cattle other than mature dairy cows or veal calves. Cattle includes but is not limited to heifers, steers, bulls and cow/calf pairs;</p> <p>(D) 750 to 2,499 swine each weighing 55 pounds or more;</p> <p>(E) 3,000 to 9,999 swine each weighing less than 55 pounds;</p> <p>(F) 150 to 499 horses;</p> <p>(G) 3,000 to 9,999 sheep or lambs;</p> <p>(H) 16,500 to 54,999 turkeys;</p> <p>(I) 9,000 to 29,999 laying hens or broilers, if the AFO uses a liquid manure handling system;</p> <p>(J) 37,500 to 124,999 chickens (other than laying hens), if the AFO uses other than a liquid manure handling system;</p> <p>(K) 25,000 to 81,999 laying hens, if the AFO uses other than a liquid manure handling system;</p> <p>(L) 10,000 to 29,999 ducks (if the AFO uses other than a liquid manure handling system); or</p> <p>(M) 1,500 to 4,999 ducks (if the AFO uses a liquid manure handling system); and</p> <p>(ii) Either one of the following conditions are met:</p> <p>(A) Pollutants are discharged into waters of the United States through a man-made ditch, flushing system, or other similar man-made device; or</p> <p>(B) Pollutants are discharged directly into waters of the United States which originate outside of and pass over, across, or through the facility or otherwise come into direct contact with the animals confined in the operation.</p> <p>Small concentrated animal feeding operation (“Small CAFO”). An AFO that is designated as a CAFO and is not a Medium CAFO.</p>
Animal Unit Definition	Not used
CAFO Permit Summary	Land application discharges from a CAFO are subject to NPDES requirements. The discharge of manure, litter or process wastewater to waters of the United States from a CAFO as a result of the application of that manure, litter or process wastewater by the CAFO to land areas under its control is a

	<p>discharge from that CAFO subject to NPDES permit requirements, except where it is an agricultural storm water discharge as provided in 33 U.S.C. 1362(14). For purposes of this paragraph, where the manure, litter or process wastewater has been applied in accordance with site specific nutrient management practices that ensure appropriate agricultural utilization of the nutrients in the manure, litter or process wastewater, as specified in § 122.42(e)(1)(vi)-(ix), a precipitation-related discharge of manure, litter or process wastewater from land areas under the control of a CAFO is an agricultural stormwater discharge.</p> <p>(1) For unpermitted Large CAFOs, a precipitation-related discharge of manure, litter, or process wastewater from land areas under the control of a CAFO shall be considered an agricultural stormwater discharge only where the manure, litter, or process wastewater has been land applied in accordance with site-specific nutrient management practices that ensure appropriate agricultural utilization of the nutrients in the manure, litter, or process wastewater, as specified in § 122.42(e)(1)(vi) through (ix).</p> <p>(2) Unpermitted Large CAFOs must maintain documentation specified in § 122.42(e)(1)(ix) either on site or at a nearby office, or otherwise make such documentation readily available to the Director or Regional Administrator upon request.</p>
Other Definitions	NA
Regulatory Details	
Setbacks Regulations	<p>Setback requirements. Unless the CAFO exercises one of the compliance alternatives provided for in paragraph (c)(5)(i) or (c)(5)(ii) of 40 CFR 412.4, manure, litter, and process wastewater may not be applied closer than 100 feet to any down-gradient surface waters, open tile line intake structures, sinkholes, agricultural well heads, or other conduits to surface waters.</p> <p>(i)Vegetated buffer compliance alternative. As a compliance alternative, the CAFO may substitute the 100-foot setback with a 35-foot wide vegetated buffer where applications of manure, litter, or process wastewater are prohibited.</p> <p>(ii)Alternative practices compliance alternative. As a compliance alternative, the CAFO may demonstrate that a setback or buffer is not necessary because implementation of alternative conservation practices or field-specific conditions will provide pollutant reductions equivalent or better than the reductions that would be achieved by the 100-foot setback.</p>
Weather and Seasonal Regulations	None specific, outside of broad details in NMP guidelines
Manure Transfer Regulations	<p>Requirements relating to transfer of manure or process wastewater to other persons. Prior to transferring manure, litter or process wastewater to other persons, Large CAFOs must provide the recipient of the manure, litter or process wastewater with the most current nutrient analysis. The analysis provided must be consistent with the requirements of 40 CFR part 412. Large CAFOs must retain for five years records of the date, recipient name and address, and approximate amount of manure, litter or process wastewater transferred to another person.</p>

<p>Nutrient Management Plans</p>	<p>[40 CFR 412.4] (1)Nutrient Management Plan. The CAFO must develop and implement a nutrient management plan that incorporates the requirements of paragraphs (c)(2) through (c)(5) of this section based on a field-specific assessment of the potential for nitrogen and phosphorus transport from the field and that addresses the form, source, amount, timing, and method of application of nutrients on each field to achieve realistic production goals, while minimizing nitrogen and phosphorus movement to surface waters. (2)Determination of application rates. Application rates for manure, litter, and other process wastewater applied to land under the ownership or operational control of the CAFO must minimize phosphorus and nitrogen transport from the field to surface waters in compliance with the technical standards for nutrient management established by the Director. Such technical standards for nutrient management shall: (i) Include a field-specific assessment of the potential for nitrogen and phosphorus transport from the field to surface waters, and address the form, source, amount, timing, and method of application of nutrients on each field to achieve realistic production goals, while minimizing nitrogen and phosphorus movement to surface waters; and (ii) Include appropriate flexibilities for any CAFO to implement nutrient management practices to comply with the technical standards, including consideration of multi-year phosphorus application on fields that do not have a high potential for phosphorus runoff to surface water, phased implementation of phosphorus-based nutrient management, and other components, as determined appropriate by the Director.</p> <p>[40 CFR 412.4] (1)Requirement to implement a nutrient management plan. Any permit issued to a CAFO must include a requirement to implement a nutrient management plan that, at a minimum, contains best management practices necessary to meet the requirements of this paragraph and applicable effluent limitations and standards, including those specified in 40 CFR part 412. The nutrient management plan must, to the extent applicable: (i) Ensure adequate storage of manure, litter, and process wastewater, including procedures to ensure proper operation and maintenance of the storage facilities; (ii) Ensure proper management of mortalities (i.e., dead animals) to ensure that they are not disposed of in a liquid manure, storm water, or process wastewater storage or treatment system that is not specifically designed to treat animal mortalities; (iii) Ensure that clean water is diverted, as appropriate, from the production area; (iv) Prevent direct contact of confined animals with waters of the United States; (v) Ensure that chemicals and other contaminants handled on-site are not disposed of in any manure, litter, process wastewater, or storm water storage or treatment system unless specifically designed to treat such chemicals and other contaminants;</p>
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- (vi) Identify appropriate site specific conservation practices to be implemented, including as appropriate buffers or equivalent practices, to control runoff of pollutants to waters of the United States;
- (vii) Identify protocols for appropriate testing of manure, litter, process wastewater, and soil;
- (viii) Establish protocols to land apply manure, litter or process wastewater in accordance with site specific nutrient management practices that ensure appropriate agricultural utilization of the nutrients in the manure, litter or process wastewater; and
- (ix) Identify specific records that will be maintained to document the implementation and management of the minimum elements described in paragraphs (e)(1)(i) through (e)(1)(viii) of this section.

(5)Terms of the nutrient management plan. Any permit issued to a CAFO must require compliance with the terms of the CAFO's site-specific nutrient management plan. The terms of the nutrient management plan are the information, protocols, best management practices, and other conditions in the nutrient management plan determined by the Director to be necessary to meet the requirements of paragraph (e)(1) of this section. The terms of the nutrient management plan, with respect to protocols for land application of manure, litter, or process wastewater required by paragraph (e)(1)(viii) of this section and, as applicable, 40 CFR 412.4(c), must include the fields available for land application; field-specific rates of application properly developed, as specified in paragraphs (e)(5)(i) through (ii) of this section, to ensure appropriate agricultural utilization of the nutrients in the manure, litter, or process wastewater; and any timing limitations identified in the nutrient management plan concerning land application on the fields available for land application. The terms must address rates of application using one of the following two approaches, unless the Director specifies that only one of these approaches may be used:

(i)Linear approach. An approach that expresses rates of application as pounds of nitrogen and phosphorus, according to the following specifications:

(A) The terms include maximum application rates from manure, litter, and process wastewater for each year of permit coverage, for each crop identified in the nutrient management plan, in chemical forms determined to be acceptable to the Director, in pounds per acre, per year, for each field to be used for land application, and certain factors necessary to determine such rates. At a minimum, the factors that are terms must include: The outcome of the field-specific assessment of the potential for nitrogen and phosphorus transport from each field; the crops to be planted in each field or any other uses of a field such as pasture or fallow fields; the realistic yield goal for each crop or use identified for each field; the nitrogen and phosphorus recommendations from sources specified by the Director for each crop or use identified for each field; credits for all nitrogen in the field that will be plant available; consideration of multi-year phosphorus application; and accounting for all other additions of plant available nitrogen and phosphorus to the field. In addition, the terms include the form and

source of manure, litter, and process wastewater to be land-applied; the timing and method of land application; and the methodology by which the nutrient management plan accounts for the amount of nitrogen and phosphorus in the manure, litter, and process wastewater to be applied.

(B) Large CAFOs that use this approach must calculate the maximum amount of manure, litter, and process wastewater to be land applied at least once each year using the results of the most recent representative manure, litter, and process wastewater tests for nitrogen and phosphorus taken within 12 months of the date of land application; or

(ii) Narrative rate approach. An approach that expresses rates of application as a narrative rate of application that results in the amount, in tons or gallons, of manure, litter, and process wastewater to be land applied, according to the following specifications:

(A) The terms include maximum amounts of nitrogen and phosphorus derived from all sources of nutrients, for each crop identified in the nutrient management plan, in chemical forms determined to be acceptable to the Director, in pounds per acre, for each field, and certain factors necessary to determine such amounts. At a minimum, the factors that are terms must include: the outcome of the field-specific assessment of the potential for nitrogen and phosphorus transport from each field; the crops to be planted in each field or any other uses such as pasture or fallow fields (including alternative crops identified in accordance with paragraph (e)(5)(ii)(B) of this section); the realistic yield goal for each crop or use identified for each field; and the nitrogen and phosphorus recommendations from sources specified by the Director for each crop or use identified for each field. In addition, the terms include the methodology by which the nutrient management plan accounts for the following factors when calculating the amounts of manure, litter, and process wastewater to be land applied: Results of soil tests conducted in accordance with protocols identified in the nutrient management plan, as required by paragraph (e)(1)(vii) of this section; credits for all nitrogen in the field that will be plant available; the amount of nitrogen and phosphorus in the manure, litter, and process wastewater to be applied; consideration of multi-year phosphorus application; accounting for all other additions of plant available nitrogen and phosphorus to the field; the form and source of manure, litter, and process wastewater; the timing and method of land application; and volatilization of nitrogen and mineralization of organic nitrogen.

(B) The terms of the nutrient management plan include alternative crops identified in the CAFO's nutrient management plan that are not in the planned crop rotation. Where a CAFO includes alternative crops in its nutrient management plan, the crops must be listed by field, in addition to the crops identified in the planned crop rotation for that field, and the nutrient management plan must include realistic crop yield goals and the nitrogen and phosphorus recommendations from sources specified by the Director for each crop. Maximum amounts of nitrogen and phosphorus from all sources of nutrients and the amounts of manure, litter, and process wastewater to be applied must be determined in accordance with the methodology described in paragraph (e)(5)(ii)(A) of this section.

	<p>(C) For CAFOs using this approach, the following projections must be included in the nutrient management plan submitted to the Director, but are not terms of the nutrient management plan: The CAFO's planned crop rotations for each field for the period of permit coverage; the projected amount of manure, litter, or process wastewater to be applied; projected credits for all nitrogen in the field that will be plant available; consideration of multi-year phosphorus application; accounting for all other additions of plant available nitrogen and phosphorus to the field; and the predicted form, source, and method of application of manure, litter, and process wastewater for each crop. Timing of application for each field, insofar as it concerns the calculation of rates of application, is not a term of the nutrient management plan.</p> <p>(D) CAFOs that use this approach must calculate maximum amounts of manure, litter, and process wastewater to be land applied at least once each year using the methodology required in paragraph (e)(5)(ii)(A) of this section before land applying manure, litter, and process wastewater and must rely on the following data:</p> <p>(1) A field-specific determination of soil levels of nitrogen and phosphorus, including, for nitrogen, a concurrent determination of nitrogen that will be plant available consistent with the methodology required by paragraph (e)(5)(ii)(A) of this section, and for phosphorus, the results of the most recent soil test conducted in accordance with soil testing requirements approved by the Director; and</p> <p>(2) The results of most recent representative manure, litter, and process wastewater tests for nitrogen and phosphorus taken within 12 months of the date of land application, in order to determine the amount of nitrogen and phosphorus in the manure, litter, and process wastewater to be applied.</p>
<p>Application Rate Regulations</p>	<p>Determination of application rates. Application rates for manure, litter, and other process wastewater applied to land under the ownership or operational control of the CAFO must minimize phosphorus and nitrogen transport from the field to surface waters in compliance with the technical standards for nutrient management established by the Director. Such technical standards for nutrient management shall:</p> <p>(i) Include a field-specific assessment of the potential for nitrogen and phosphorus transport from the field to surface waters, and address the form, source, amount, timing, and method of application of nutrients on each field to achieve realistic production goals, while minimizing nitrogen and phosphorus movement to surface waters; and</p> <p>(ii) Include appropriate flexibilities for any CAFO to implement nutrient management practices to comply with the technical standards, including consideration of multi-year phosphorus application on fields that do not have a high potential for phosphorus runoff to surface water, phased implementation of phosphorus-based nutrient management, and other components, as determined appropriate by the Director.</p>
<p>Composition Testing Regulations</p>	<p>Manure and soil sampling. Manure must be analyzed a minimum of once annually for nitrogen and phosphorus content, and soil analyzed a minimum of once every five years for phosphorus content. The results of these</p>

	analyses are to be used in determining application rates for manure, litter, and other process wastewater.
Other Land Application Regulations	NA
Other CAFO Regulations	NA

Alabama Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2019
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Alabama Department of Environmental Management (ADEM)
Links to regulations	ADEM CAFO program:_ https://adem.alabama.gov/alEnviroRegLaws/files/Division6Vol1.pdf _ Chapter 335-6-5: Indirect Discharge Permits and Pretreatment Rules_ Chapter 335-6-6 & Chapter 335-6-7: Alabama National Pollutant Discharge Elimination System
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	More than one agency
Other regulator info	No other information
Definitions	
How CAFOs are defined or categorized:	<p>335-6-7-.02 (h) "Animal Feeding Operation" (AFO) means a lot or facility (other than an aquatic animal production facility) where animals (does not have to be the same animals) have been, are, or will be stabled, confined, gathered, or concentrated and fed or maintained (watered, cleaned, groomed, medicated, etc.) for a total of 45 days (days do not have to be consecutive) or more in any 12-month period (period does not have to correspond to the calendar year), and the animal confinement areas do not sustain crops, vegetation, forage growth, or post-harvest residues in the normal growing season as generally described in 40 CFR (Code of Federal Regulations) 122.23(b)(1). Two or more AFOs under common ownership are considered a single AFO and may require Registration as a CAFO if they adjoin, or are in close proximity to each other as determined by the Director or his designee. Unless determined otherwise by the Director or his designee, two or more AFOs under common ownership or under different ownership are considered a single AFO and may require Registration as a CAFO, separately or together, if they are operated as a single operation, if they use a common area or system for the disposal of waste/wastewater, if they significantly share resources, storage or treatments systems, equipment, etc., or otherwise significantly link operations. Each owner/operator of an AFO that adjoins or is in close proximity to another AFO, or shares resources or has links to other operations, can contact the Department for clarification in writing of the status of their facility(s)._</p> <p>_</p> <p>335-6-7-.02 (r) "Concentrated Animal Feeding Operation" (CAFO) means an Animal Feeding Operation (AFO) as generally described in 40 CFR 122.23 Appendix B, 40 CFR 122.23(c), and defined in Rule</p>

	<p>335-6-7-.10. For purposes of this Chapter, an AFO, regardless of size or number of animals, that has experienced a point source discharge after April 1, 1999 is considered to be included in this definition._</p> <p>–</p> <p>335-6-7-.10 (b) An AFO with more than the following number(s) and type(s) of animals and where there is a point source or nonpoint source discharge or a point source or nonpoint source discharge has occurred after April 1, 1999, of pollutants into groundwater or surface waters of the State through a man-made ditch, flushing system, other similar man-made devices, or improper handling, storage, transport, distribution, or land application of wastes:_</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. 300 slaughter or feeder cattle,_ 2. 200 mature dairy cattle (whether milked or dry cows),_ 3. 750 swine each weighing equal to or greater than 25 kilograms (approximately 55 pounds),_ 4. 1,200 swine each weighing equal to or greater than 7 kilograms and less than 25 kilograms (approximately between 15 pounds and 55 pounds), _ 5. 3,000 swine each weighing less than 7 kilograms (approximately 15 pounds or less),_ 6. 1,875 goats,_ 7. 150 horses,_ 8. 3,000 sheep or lambs,_ 9. 16,000 turkeys,_ 10. 37,500 laying hens, broilers, or other poultry,_ 11. 1,875 emus,_ 12. 18,000 rabbits,_ 13. 1,500 ducks, or_ 14. 300 animal units of any other type/size animal as generally described in 40 CFR 122, Appendix B, or as determined by the Director.
<p>How animal units are defined (if used):</p>	<p>335-6-7-.02 (i) "Animal Unit" (AU) means a unit of measurement for any AFO calculated by adding the following numbers: the number of slaughter and feeder cattle and dairy heifers multiplied by 1.0, plus the number of manure dairy cattle multiplied by 1.4, plus the number of swine weighing greater than 335-6-7-.02 7-5 or equal to 55 pounds multiplied by 0.4, plus the number of swine weighing greater than or equal to 15 pounds and less than 55 pounds multiplied by 0.25, plus the number of swine weighing less than 15 pounds multiplied by 0.1, plus the number of goats multiplied by 0.16, plus the number of emus multiplied by 0.16, plus the number of rabbits multiplied by 0.016, plus the number of sheep multiplied by 0.1, plus the number of horses multiplied by 2.0, and as designated in rule 335-6-7-.10. Where an AU is not specifically defined in this Chapter for an animal (e.g. nutria, other ratites, reptiles, brood cows, etc.), an appropriate AU is determined comparing live weight equivalent waste quantity and constituent</p>

	composition (limiting nutrients, moisture, additive compounds, etc.) from the most similar type animal with a defined AU.
NPDES permitting or other permitting requirements:	<p>All CAFOs are required to register with ADEM. Except as specifically provided otherwise by AAC Chapter 335-6-7, discharge of any wastewater from an CAFO to waters of the State at any time is prohibited, except as a direct result of periods of chronic or catastrophic precipitation or weather conditions as determined by the Director or his designee, including precipitation equivalent to or in excess of the 25-year, 24-hour storm event._</p> <p>_</p> <p>CAFOs the currently or plan to have a NPDES permit, must complete a comprehensive Waste Management System Plan (WMSP) that meets or exceeds NRCS technical standards and guidelines._</p> <p>_</p> <p>Other permits include ADEM UST permit for any underground storage tanks; Alabama Department of Agriculture and Industries (ADAI) permits for emergency mortality burial, diseased animal management, transport, etc.</p>
Does the state require an NPDES permit for all Large CAFOs?	Yes
Does the state issue individual or general CAFO permits?	Both
Are any other permits required for CAFOs or other large farms?	Yes
Other definitions needed to understand these regulations:	No other information
Regulatory Details	
Setbacks: <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some geographical feature</i>	335-6-7-.26 (c) Application of waste/wastewater shall be conducted in a manner that meets or exceeds NRCS technical standards and guidelines, the approved WMSP, the requirements of this Chapter, the requirements of the AWPCA, CWA, and regulations promulgated pursuant thereto, and is protective of water quality, but in no case shall be made within 50 feet of surface waters of the State including, but not limited to, perennial or intermittent streams, ponds, lakes, springs, or sinkholes; or within 100 feet of non-potable water wells and water supplies, or within 200 feet of PWS, ONRW, or OAW classified/designated waters, or potable water wells and water supplies. Buffer distances for streams, ponds and lakes shall be measured from the ordinary high water mark. Buffer distances in excess of 50, 100, or 200 feet may be required according to site specific conditions or according to NRCS guidelines. The Department may require additional buffer distances deemed

	<p>necessary to protect waters of the State on an individual facility basis._</p> <p>335-6-7-.26 (1) (p) Aerial or spray irrigation, or other type pumped or pressurized surface land application of wastewater shall be done in a manner that meets or exceeds NRCS technical standards and guidelines, but in no case shall be closer than 500 feet from the nearest existing occupied dwelling, church, school, hospital, or park. Non-pumped surface application, or soil subsurface injection/application of wastewater shall be done in a manner that meets or exceeds NRCS technical standards and guidelines, but in no case shall be closer than 200 feet from the nearest existing occupied dwelling, church, school, hospital, or park._</p> <p>335-6-7-.26 (1) (q) The restrictions regarding property lines or neighboring buildings shall not apply if the adjoining property is also approved as a land application site under this Chapter and if the adjoining property owner consents in writing. Listed buffers:_</p> <p>https://adem.alabama.gov/alEnviroRegLaws/files/Division6Vol1.pdf</p>
<p>Are setbacks more restrictive than CFR?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Timing, weather, or conditional application restrictions: <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather, seasons, or land characteristics (like slope)</i></p>	<p>335-6-7-.26 (1) (k) Land application of waste/wastewater shall not be undertaken or continue when soil is saturated as defined in NRCS technical standards and guidelines, frozen, covered with ice or snow, during precipitation, or when significant precipitation as defined in NRCS technical standards and guidelines is reasonably expected within the next 72 hours. Waste/wastewater shall be applied in accordance with NRCS technical standards and guidelines and the WMSP. Waste/wastewater shall only be applied on days of the year and during times consistent with NRCS technical standards and guidelines and the WMSP. Land application shall be conducted when vegetation on the site is actively growing or waste/wastewater can be applied to land up to 30 days prior to planting a crop (row or forage). If applied to conventional tillage (farm tillage practices which result in complete surface disturbance and/or soil inversion or minimal surface residues) cropland or to pasture or hay land being renovated or established, the waste/wastewater shall be incorporated immediately after application. Waste/wastewater does not have to be incorporated when applied to conservation tillage (farm tillage practices which manage and maintain plant residues on the soil surface) crop, hay, or pastureland._</p> <p>335-6-7-.26 (1) (l) Waste/wastewater shall not be applied on slopes with a steep grade as defined by NRCS technical standards and guidelines and in any manner that will allow waste/wastewater to enter drainage conveyance structures, enter waters of the State or to run onto adjacent property without the written consent of the affected adjacent property owner. Effective vegetative filters that meet or exceed NRCS technical standards and guidelines and the requirements of this Chapter shall be maintained between</p>

	application sites and waters of the State.
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to saturated soils?	Yes
Is there a restriction for land application of manure within floodplains?	No
Is there a restriction for land application of manure related to future rainfall?	Yes
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to frozen or snow-covered ground?	Yes
Are there restrictions to manure applications based on time of year or time of day?	Yes
Are there restrictions to manure application based on slope?	Yes
Are there any other seasonal, timing, weather, or physical restrictions to manure applications not captured above?	335-6-7-.26 Land Application and Manure Management Requirements
Transfer of manure off-site: <i>Requirements related to the transfer of manures to other persons</i>	335-6-7-.20 (20) If the waste is sold or given away in good faith, the owner/operator or CAWV shall retain detailed, complete records of the transaction and provide the receiver of the waste information explaining the requirements of this Chapter. AFO waste management system BMPs must meet or exceed NRCS technical standards and guidelines._ 335-6-7-.26 (1) (d) Unless responsibility for wastes are properly assumed by a CAWV, the owner/operator shall ensure that the land owner of any offsite land application site not owned or controlled by the registrant, abides by the_ applicable requirements of this Chapter.
Are receivers of manure transfers from CAFOs required to follow the same regulations?	Undetermined
Nutrient or manure management plans: <i>Additional details on the NMP requirement. Note that some of this</i>	335-6-7-.13 (2) Owners/operators of AFOs defined or designated as CAFOs by the requirements of this Chapter who intend to, are required to, or have obtained NPDES permit coverage under this Chapter shall submit to the Department certification/evaluation by a QCP that the facility has been designed, constructed, or has been

<p><i>information may overlap with other sections</i></p>	<p>updated, and can reasonably be operated in accordance with an approved WMSP that meets or exceeds NRCS technical standards and guidelines and as required by this Chapter and the Director or his designee. The type, format, and content of the certification/evaluation required shall be determined by the Director or his designee considering facility construction, site conditions, operational history and any potential impacts to groundwater and surface waters of the state.</p> <p>335-6-7-.26 (1) The WMSP, prepared by the QCP with the NOR prior to construction and operation of a new CAFO, prior to construction and operation of additional facilities at an existing CAFO, as required to continue operation of an existing CAFO, or as otherwise required by the Director or his designee, are incorporated into the requirements of this Chapter by reference. All provisions of the WMSP accepted by the Department become enforceable conditions of this Chapter. Only areas identified in the approved WMSP shall be used for the disposal of animal liquid wastes, manure, litter, and mortality compost, and shall be located to prevent any pollutant from such materials from entering waters of the State to the maximum extent practicable. Unless waste disposal and land application responsibilities are contracted in writing to a valid CAWV, all new sites not identified in the approved WMSP at the time of registration under this Chapter must be accepted by the Department prior to its use as a land application site.</p>
<p>Do your NMP/MMPS follow, comply with, or based on NRCS Technical Standard 590?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Application rates: <i>State regulations that restrict the rates at which manures are applied and methods needed to determine appropriate rates.</i></p>	<p>335-6-7-.26 (4) The rate of land application of waste/wastewater can be based on either a laboratory analysis of a representative waste/wastewater sample or on the average nutrient values according to NRCS technical standards and guidelines for the type waste and animal operation. If NRCS approved average nutrient/component values for the appropriate animal type are used, a representative sample of waste and/or wastewater to be land applied need only be collected as often as is determined necessary by the QCP to ensure consistency with NRCS approved average nutrient/component values.</p> <p>335-6-7-.26 (5) The surface soils (0-3 inches in sod crops and depth of plow layer in cultivated crops) of each field where waste/wastewater has been or will be land applied shall be sampled according to accepted standard soil sampling procedures. Soils shall be evaluated and analyzed using analytical methodology appropriate for the soils and nutrients to be tested as outlined in: (a) Soil Test Methods for the Southern Region of the United States, 1983, Southern Cooperative Service Bulletin, 289, University of Georgia,</p>

	<p>Athens, Georgia, or_</p> <p>1. Reference Soil and Media Diagnostic Procedures for the Southern_ Region of the United States, 1992, S.J. Donahue (ed.), Southern Cooperative_ Service Bulletin 374, Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University,_ Blacksburg, Virginia, or_</p> <p>2. Soil Test Fertilizer Recommendations For Alabama Crops, 1994,_ J.F. Adams, C.C. Mitchell, and H.H. Bryant, Agronomy And Soils Department_ Series No. 178 (as amended), Auburn University, Alabama, or_</p> <p>3. Other analytical methodology(s) as may be approved by the_ Director or his designee._</p> <p>(b) Soil samples shall be collected and analyzed at a frequency that_ meets NRCS technical standards and guidelines, and as often as is necessary to ensure protection of groundwater and surface water quality. Analyses shall_ include:_</p> <p>1. Soil pH and lime requirement for the soil and crop to be grown._</p> <p>2. Extractable phosphorus._</p> <p>3. Extractable zinc, copper, arsenic, and other selected metals, if it is_ determined by the QCP that it is probable that one or more metals (which could become concentrated in animal wastes and in some cases are added to the animal feed producing the waste being tested) are present in sufficiently high concentrations in the land applied waste or wastewater, or naturally present in the soil, that further soil accumulation could become toxic to plants or animals or potentially impact groundwater or surface water quality._</p> <p>4. Any parameter(s) as may be required by the Director or his designee._</p> <p>_</p> <p>Nutrient caps are based on agronomic uptake rates for the time of year for the specific crop/vegetation that the waste is being applied.</p>
<p>Manure application rates for phosphorus are based on:</p> <p>1) <i>Phosphorus Index Only</i></p> <p>2) <i>Soil Test Phosphorus Only</i></p> <p>3) <i>Either PIO or STPO</i></p> <p>4) <i>Other</i></p>	<p>Phosphorus index only</p>
<p>Are there any nutrient “caps” to manure application?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Composition testing:</p>	<p>335-6-7-.26 (4) Unless NRCS approved average nutrient/component</p>

<p><i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on manures before application</i></p>	<p>values are used, a representative sample of waste and/or wastewater to be land applied shall be collected periodically, but at least annually, and analyzed using an analytical methodology accepted by the Department for the following parameters:_ (a) pH_ (b) Total Nitrogen_ (c) Ammonium Nitrogen._ (d) Total Phosphorus_ (e) Total Potassium_ (f) Percent Solids_ (g) Selected metals (e.g. zinc, copper, arsenic, etc.) which could become concentrated in animal wastes and in some cases are added to the animal feed producing the waste being tested._ (h) Any parameter(s) as may be required by the Director or his designee.</p>
<p>Does your state require testing of manure for anything beyond nutrients, such as metals, pathogens, antibiotics, etc.?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Other land application highlights: <i>Additional restrictions for land application of manures</i></p>	
<p>Other regulatory details: <i>Additional information on the regulation of land application of manures</i></p>	<p>No other information</p>
<p>General Assessment Questions</p>	
<p>Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change:</p>	<p>Undetermined</p>
<p>Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of manures that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links:</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Within your state, are there any jurisdictions</p>	<p>No</p>

<p>(e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of manures beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so:</p>	
<p>Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.</p>	<p>No other information</p>

Alaska	
Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2019
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Alaska Department of Environmental Conservation (ADEC)
Links to regulations	18 AAC Chapter 83:_ http://www.akleg.gov/basis/aac.asp#18.83
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Environmental
Other regulator info	Currently, no CAFOs in the state.
Definitions	
How CAFOs are defined or categorized:	Refer to 40 CFR
How animal units are defined (if used):	Refer to 40 CFR
NPDES permitting or other permitting requirements:	CAFOs in Alaska are subject to the requirements of 18 AAC Chapter 83, which details the Alaska Pollutant Discharge Elimination System (APDES)
Does the state require an NPDES permit for all Large CAFOs?	Undetermined
Does the state issue individual or general CAFO permits?	Undetermined
Are any other permits required for CAFOs or other large farms?	Undetermined
Other definitions needed to understand these regulations:	No other information
Regulatory Details	
Setbacks: <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some geographical feature</i>	Refer to 40 CFR
Are setbacks more restrictive than CFR?	Undetermined
Timing, weather, or conditional application restrictions: <i>State regulations that restrict land application</i>	None

<i>under certain weather, seasons, or land characteristics (like slope)</i>	
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to saturated soils?	No
Is there a restriction for land application of manure within floodplains?	No
Is there a restriction for land application of manure related to future rainfall?	No
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to frozen or snow-covered ground?	No
Are there restrictions to manure applications based on time of year or time of day?	No
Are there restrictions to manure application based on slope?	No
Are there any other seasonal, timing, weather, or physical restrictions to manure applications not captured above?	No
Transfer of manure off-site: <i>Requirements related to the transfer of manures to other persons</i>	No
Are receivers of manure transfers from CAFOs required to follow the same regulations?	No
Nutrient or manure management plans: <i>Additional details on the NMP requirement. Note that some of this information may overlap with other sections</i>	Refer to 40 CFR
Do your NMP/MMPS follow, comply with, or	Not Applicable

based on NRCS Technical Standard 590?	
Application rates: <i>State regulations that restrict the rates at which manures are applied and methods needed to determine appropriate rates.</i>	Refer to 40 CFR
Manure application rates for phosphorus are based on: 1) <i>Phosphorus Index Only</i> 2) <i>Soil Test Phosphorus Only</i> 3) <i>Either PIO or STPO</i> 4) <i>Other</i>	No method
Are there any nutrient “caps” to manure application?	No
Composition testing: <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on manures before application</i>	Refer to 40 CFR
Does your state require testing of manure for anything beyond nutrients, such as metals, pathogens, antibiotics, etc.?	Undetermined
Other land application highlights: <i>Additional restrictions for land application of manures</i>	No other information
Other regulatory details: <i>Additional information on the regulation of land application of manures</i>	No other information
General Assessment Questions	
Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory	Undetermined

details that may potentially change:	
Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of manures that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links:	No
Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of manures beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so:	No
Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.	No other information

Arizona Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2019
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Arizona Department of Environmental Quality (ADEQ)
Links to regulations	CAFO details, links to regulations, permits, etc. https://azdeq.gov/node/2710 Title 18. Environmental Quality Chapter 09. Dept. of Environmental Quality - Water Pollution Control https://legacy.azdeq.gov/envIRON/water/engineering/download/rules/oss_septic_design.pdf
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Environmental
Other regulator info	No other information
Definitions	
How CAFOs are defined or categorized:	A Concentrated Animal Feeding Operation (CAFO), is an Animal Feeding Operation that meets one or more of the following criteria:_ >Large CAFO: confines 1,000 beef animals; 700 dairy cows; 2,500 or 10,000 swine depending on waste system type; 500 horses; 10,000 sheep or lambs; 55,000 turkeys; 30,000, 82,000 or 125,000 chickens depending on waste system type._ – >Medium CAFO: confines fewer than the number listed for a large CAFO, but equal to or greater than 300 beef; 200 dairy cattle; 750 or 3,000 swine; 150 horses; 3,000 sheep or lambs; 16,500 turkeys; or 9,000, 25,000 or 37,500 chickens and discharges pollutants into "waters of the United States" (either directly into on-site water, or indirectly by channeling wastes through a ditch, flushing system, or other device)._ – >It is designated by ADEQ upon determination that the operation, regardless of its size, is a significant source of pollution following A.A.C R18-9-D901(B) through (E).
How animal units are defined (if used):	Not used
NPDES permitting or other permitting	All CAFO owners or operators are subject to the APP Nitrogen Management General Permit for CAFOs. This APP general permit (18 A.A.C. 9 Article 4) protects groundwater by minimizing discharges of nitrogen to groundwater from waste impoundments and other CAFO activities through the use of Best Management

requirements :	Practices (BMPs). A CAFO owner or operator does not have to submit any paperwork to ADEQ to apply for this permit, but is covered under the general permit if the owner or operator complies with BMPs outlined in the rule, that minimize the discharge of nitrogen to the aquifer._ – A CAFO is not required to apply for an AZPDES permit unless the owner/operator informs ADEQ there will be a discharge of pollutants to U.S. waters. If there will be a discharge to U.S. waters or tributaries, an individual AZPDES permit is required.
Does the state require an NPDES permit for all Large CAFOs?	No
Does the state issue individual or general CAFO permits?	Undetermined
Are any other permits required for CAFOs or other large farms?	Undetermined
Other definitions needed to understand these regulations:	No other information
Regulatory Details	
Setbacks: <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some geographical feature</i>	Refer to 40 CFR
Are setbacks	Undetermined

more restrictive than CFR?	
Timing, weather, or conditional application restrictions: <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather, seasons, or land characteristics (like slope)</i>	None
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to saturated soils?	No
Is there a restriction for land application of manure within floodplains?	No
Is there a restriction for land application of manure related to future rainfall?	No
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to	No

frozen or snow-covered ground?	
Are there restrictions to manure applications based on time of year or time of day?	No
Are there restrictions to manure application based on slope?	No
Are there any other seasonal, timing, weather, or physical restrictions to manure applications not captured above?	No
Transfer of manure off-site: <i>Requirements related to the transfer of manures to other persons</i>	Refer to 40 CFR
Are receivers of manure transfers from CAFOs required to follow the same regulations?	No
Nutrient or manure management plans:	Refer to 40 CFR

<p><i>Additional details on the NMP requirement. Note that some of this information may overlap with other sections</i></p>	
<p>Do your NMP/MMPS follow, comply with, or based on NRCS Technical Standard 590?</p>	<p>Not Applicable</p>
<p>Application rates: <i>State regulations that restrict the rates at which manures are applied and methods needed to determine appropriate rates.</i></p>	<p>For all APP permits: An owner or operator may apply a nitrogen fertilizer under this general permit without submitting a notice to the Director, if the_ owner or operator complies with the following best management_ practices:_</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Limit application of the fertilizer so that it meets projected crop or plant needs;_ 2. Time application of the fertilizer to coincide to maximum crop or plant uptake;_ 3. Apply the fertilizer by a method designed to deliver nitrogen to the area of maximum crop or plant uptake;_ 4. Manage and time application of irrigation water to minimize nitrogen loss by leaching and runoff; and_ 5. Use tillage practices that maximize water and nitrogen uptake by a crop or plant._ <p>–</p> <p>For CAFO APP permits specifically: An owner or operator may discharge from a concentrated Animal Feeding Operation without submitting a notice to the Director, if the owner or operator complies with the following best management practices:_</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Harvest, stockpile, and dispose of animal manure from a concentrated Animal Feeding Operation to minimize discharge of any nitrogen pollutant by leaching and runoff
<p>Manure application rates for phosphorus are based on: 1) <i>Phosphorus Index Only</i></p>	<p>No method</p>

<p>2) <i>Soil Test Phosphorus Only</i> 3) <i>Either PIO or STPO</i> 4) <i>Other</i></p>	
<p>Are there any nutrient “caps” to manure application?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Composition testing: <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on manures before application</i></p>	<p>Refer to 40 CFR</p>
<p>Does your state require testing of manure for anything beyond nutrients, such as metals, pathogens, antibiotics, etc.?</p>	<p>Undetermined</p>
<p>Other land application highlights: <i>Additional restrictions for land application of manures</i></p>	<p>No other information</p>
<p>Other regulatory details:</p>	<p>No other information</p>

<p><i>Additional information on the regulation of land application of manures</i></p>	
General Assessment Questions	
<p>Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change:</p>	<p>Undetermined</p>
<p>Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of manures that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links:</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of manures beyond</p>	<p>No</p>

<p>state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so:</p>	
<p>Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.</p>	<p>No other information</p>

Arkansas Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2019
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Arkansas Department of Environmental Quality (ADEQ)
Links to regulations	Links to APC&EC regulations for ADEQ permitting https://www.adeq.state.ar.us/regs Regulation No. 6 -Regulations for state administrations of NPDES https://www.adeq.state.ar.us/downloads/regs/oldregs/reg06_final_060722.pdf Regulation No. 5 -Liquid Animal Waste Management Systems https://www.adeq.state.ar.us/regs/files/reg05_final_150918.pdf
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Environmental
Other regulator info	No other information
Definitions	
How CAFOs are defined or categorized:	Concentrated Animal Feeding Operation (CAFO)- ² means an AFO that is defined as a Large CAFO or as a Medium CAFO pursuant to 40 C.F.R. §122.23, or that is designated as a CAFO in accordance with 40 C.F.R. §122.23(c). Two or more AFOs under common ownership are considered to be a single AFO for the purposes of determining the number of animals at an operation, if they adjoin each other or if they use a common area or system for the disposal of wastes. _ Animal Feeding Operation (AFO)-means a lot or facility (other than an aquatic animal production facility) where the following conditions are met: animals (other than aquatic animals) have been, are or will be stabled or confined and fed or maintained for a total of 45 days or more in any 12-month period, and crops, vegetation, forage growth, or post-harvest residues are not sustained in the normal growing season over any portion of the lot or facility.
How animal units are defined (if used):	Not used
NPDES permitting or other permitting requirements:	The State of Arkansas has been authorized by the U. S. Environmental Protection Agency to administer the National Pollutant Discharge Elimination System (NPDES) Program in Arkansas, including the issuance of general permits to categories of dischargers under the provisions of 40 CFR 122.28, as adopted by reference in Arkansas Pollution Control and Ecology Commission Regulation (Reg.) 6.104. Under this authority, ADEQ may issue a single general permit to a category of point sources located within the same geographic area_ whose discharges warrant similar pollution control measures. Specifically, in accordance with 40 CFR 122.28, the ADEQ is authorized to issue a general NPDES permit if there are a number of point sources operating in a geographic

	<p>area that:_</p> <p>1.1. involve the same or substantially similar types of operations;_</p> <p>1.2. discharge the same types of wastes;_</p> <p>1.3. require the same effluent limitations or operating conditions;_</p> <p>1.4. require the same or similar monitoring requirements; and_</p> <p>1.5. in the opinion of the Director, are more appropriately controlled under a general permit than under individual permits.</p>
Does the state require an NPDES permit for all Large CAFOs?	No
Does the state issue individual or general CAFO permits?	Individual
Are any other permits required for CAFOs or other large farms?	Yes
Other definitions needed to understand these regulations:	No other information
Regulatory Details	
<p>Setbacks:</p> <p><i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some geographical feature</i></p>	<p>Application of waste/wastewater shall not be made within 100 feet of streams including intermittent streams, ponds, lakes, springs, sinkholes, rock outcrops, wells and water supplies; or 300 feet of extraordinary resource waters as defined by the Arkansas Pollution Control and Ecology Commission Regulation No. 2. Buffer distances for streams, ponds and lakes shall be measured from the ordinary high water mark. The Department may require additional buffer distances deemed necessary to protect the waters of the state._</p> <p>Application of waste/wastewater shall not be made within 50 feet of property lines or 500 feet of neighboring occupied buildings existing as of the date of the permit. The restrictions regarding property lines or neighboring occupied buildings shall not apply if the adjoining property is also approved as a land application site under a permit issued by the Department or if the adjoining property owner consents in writing._</p> <p>Application of waste/wastewater shall not be made in areas where the land application of waste/wastewater is prohibited by Arkansas Department of Health regulations for the protection of public water supplies.</p>
Are setbacks more restrictive than CFR?	Yes
Timing, weather,	Land application of waste/wastewater shall not be undertaken when soil is

<p>or conditional application restrictions: <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather, seasons, or land characteristics (like slope)</i></p>	<p>saturated, frozen, covered with ice or snow, or when significant precipitation is reasonably anticipated in the next twenty-four hours._ Waste/wastewater shall not be applied on slopes with a grade of more than fifteen percent (15%) or in any manner that will allow waste to enter waters of the State or to run onto adjacent property without the written consent of the affected adjacent property owner.</p>
<p>Is there a restriction for land application of manure to saturated soils?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Is there a restriction for land application of manure within floodplains?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Is there a restriction for land application of manure related to future rainfall?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Is there a restriction for land application of manure to frozen or snow-covered ground?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Are there restrictions to manure applications based on time of year or time of day?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Are there restrictions to manure application based on slope?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Are there any other seasonal, timing, weather,</p>	<p>No</p>

or physical restrictions to manure applications not captured above?	
Transfer of manure off-site: <i>Requirements related to the transfer of manures to other persons</i>	Refer to 40 CFR
Are receivers of manure transfers from CAFOs required to follow the same regulations?	No
Nutrient or manure management plans: <i>Additional details on the NMP requirement. Note that some of this information may overlap with other sections</i>	CAFOs are required to develop an NMP in accordance with federal regulations.
Do your NMP/MMPS follow, comply with, or based on NRCS Technical Standard 590?	Yes
Application rates: <i>State regulations that restrict the rates at which manures are applied and methods needed to determine appropriate rates.</i>	The soils of each field where liquid animal waste has been land applied shall be sampled and analyzed at least once every five (5) years for the following parameters: pH, Potassium, Phosphorous and Nitrates. The soils analysis shall be submitted with the updated Waste Management Plan required in Reg. 5.405(C).
Manure	Phosphorus index or soil test

<p>application rates for phosphorus are based on:</p> <p>1) <i>Phosphorus Index Only</i></p> <p>2) <i>Soil Test Phosphorus Only</i></p> <p>3) <i>Either PIO or STPO</i></p> <p>4) <i>Other</i></p>	
<p>Are there any nutrient “caps” to manure application?</p>	No
<p>Composition testing:</p> <p><i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on manures before application</i></p>	<p>A representative sample of the waste/wastewater to be land applied shall be collected periodically, at a minimum of once each year, and analyzed for the following parameters: pH, Total Nitrogen, Potassium, Total Phosphorous, Soluble Phosphorous and percent solids. The Department may require more frequent testing deemed necessary to protect waters of the state._</p> <p>– Sampling of dry manure and soils will be performed in accordance with Acts 1059, 1060, and 1061 of 2003, and the regulations promulgated thereunder by the Arkansas Soil & Water Conservation Commission, in lieu of the annual manure and soil sampling requirements pursuant to 40 CFR 412.4(c)(3).</p>
<p>Does your state require testing of manure for anything beyond nutrients, such as metals, pathogens, antibiotics, etc.?</p>	No
<p>Other land application highlights:</p> <p><i>Additional restrictions for land application of manures</i></p>	No other information
<p>Other regulatory details:</p> <p><i>Additional information on the regulation of land application of manures</i></p>	No other information

General Assessment Questions

<p>Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change:</p>	<p>Undetermined</p>
<p>Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of manures that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links:</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of manures beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so:</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.</p>	<p>No other information</p>

California	
Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2019
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	California State Water Boards (includes nine semiautonomous Regional Water Quality Control Boards)
Links to regulations	California Code of Regulations - Title 27, Division 2, Chapter 7, Subchapter 2, Article 1 SWRCB -Confined Animal Facilities:_ https://www.calrecycle.ca.gov/laws/regulations/title27
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Other
Other regulator info	There many variations to these rules across the Regional Water Quality Control Boards. When there are, the more stringent regulation applies.
Definitions	
How CAFOs are defined or categorized:	<p>A discharger required to submit a report of waste discharge shall provide the following general information and shall report any material changes as defined in Section 2210 of Title 23 of this code:_</p> <p>(1) average daily volume of facility wastewater and volume or weight of manure;_</p> <p>(2) total animal population at the facility, and types of animals;_</p> <p>(3) location and size of use or disposal fields and retention ponds, including animal capacity; and_</p> <p>(4) animal capacity of the facility._</p> <p>(c) Regulations Are Minimum Standards -The RWQCB shall impose additional requirements, if such additional requirements are necessary to prevent degradation of water quality or impairment of beneficial uses of waters of the state._</p> <p>_</p> <p>Discharge To Disposal/Use Fields -The RWQCB shall allow the discharge of facility wastewater and of collected precipitation and drainage waters to use or disposal fields only if such discharge is in accordance with s22563. Absent an NPDES permit for discharge to surface waters, the only other allowable discharge is to wastewater treatment facilities approved by the RWQCB.</p>
How animal units are defined (if used):	Not used
NPDES permitting or other permitting requirements:	<p>A discharger required to submit a report of waste discharge shall provide the following general information and shall report any material changes as defined in Section 2210 of Title 23 of this code:_</p> <p>(1) average daily volume of facility wastewater and volume or weight of manure;_</p> <p>(2) total animal population at the facility, and types of animals;_</p> <p>(3) location and size of use or disposal fields and retention ponds,</p>

	including animal capacity; and_ (4) animal capacity of the facility._ (c) Regulations Are Minimum Standards -The RWQCB shall impose additional requirements, if such additional requirements are necessary to prevent degradation of water quality or impairment of beneficial uses of waters of the state.
Does the state require an NPDES permit for all Large CAFOs?	Undetermined
Does the state issue individual or general CAFO permits?	Undetermined
Are any other permits required for CAFOs or other large farms?	Undetermined
Other definitions needed to understand these regulations:	No other information
Regulatory Details	
Setbacks: <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some geographical feature</i>	Refer to Regional Water Quality Control Boards and 40 CFR
Are setbacks more restrictive than CFR?	No
Timing, weather, or conditional application restrictions: <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather, seasons, or land characteristics (like slope)</i>	Run-Off & Percolation -Discharges of facility wastewater to disposal fields shall not result in surface runoff from disposal fields and shall be managed to minimize percolation to ground water._ - Manured areas shall be managed to minimize infiltration of water into underlying soils._
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to saturated soils?	Undetermined
Is there a restriction for land application of manure within floodplains?	Undetermined
Is there a restriction for land application of manure related to future rainfall?	Undetermined

Is there a restriction for land application of manure to frozen or snow-covered ground?	Undetermined
Are there restrictions to manure applications based on time of year or time of day?	Undetermined
Are there restrictions to manure application based on slope?	Undetermined
Are there any other seasonal, timing, weather, or physical restrictions to manure applications not captured above?	Undetermined
Transfer of manure off-site: <i>Requirements related to the transfer of manures to other persons</i>	Refer to Regional Water Quality Control Boards and 40 CFR
Are receivers of manure transfers from CAFOs required to follow the same regulations?	Undetermined
Nutrient or manure management plans: <i>Additional details on the NMP requirement. Note that some of this information may overlap with other sections</i>	Refer to Regional Water Quality Control Boards and 40 CFR
Do your NMP/MMPS follow, comply with, or based on NRCS Technical Standard 590?	Undetermined
Application rates: <i>State regulations that restrict the rates at which manures are applied and methods needed to determine appropriate rates.</i>	Reasonable Soil Amendment Rate -Application of manure and wastewater to disposal fields or crop lands shall be at rates which are reasonable for the crop, soil, climate, special local situations, management system, and type of manure. Manured areas shall be managed to minimize infiltration of water into underlying soils.
Manure application rates for phosphorus are based on: <i>1) Phosphorus Index Only 2) Soil Test Phosphorus</i>	Other

<p><i>Only</i> 3) <i>Either PIO or STPO</i> 4) <i>Other</i></p>	
<p>Are there any nutrient “caps” to manure application?</p>	<p>Undetermined</p>
<p>Composition testing: <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on manures before application</i></p>	<p>Refer to Regional Water Quality Control Boards and 40 CFR</p>
<p>Does your state require testing of manure for anything beyond nutrients, such as metals, pathogens, antibiotics, etc.?</p>	<p>Undetermined</p>
<p>Other land application highlights: <i>Additional restrictions for land application of manures</i></p>	<p>No other information</p>
<p>Other regulatory details: <i>Additional information on the regulation of land application of manures</i></p>	<p>No other information</p>
General Assessment Questions	
<p>Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change:</p>	<p>Undetermined</p>
<p>Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of manures that we haven’t captured? If yes, please describe or provide links:</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of</p>	<p>No</p>

manures beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so:	
Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.	No other information

Colorado	
Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2019
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Colorado Department of Public Health and Environment (CDPHE)
Links to regulations	<p>General Information, Policy, Guidance, etc. https://www.sos.state.co.us/pubs/CCR/CCRHome.html 5 CCR 1002-81 (Regulation No. 81) - AFO Control Regulations https://www.colorado.gov/pacific/cdphe/animal-and-livestock-feeding-operations 5 CCR 1002-61 (Regulation No. 61) - CO Discharge Permit System Regulations https://www.sos.state.co.us/pubs/CCR/CCRHome.html 5 CCR 1001-2 (Regulation No. 2) - Odor Emission https://www.sos.state.co.us/pubs/CCR/CCRHome.html</p>
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Environmental
Other regulator info	No other information
Definitions	
How CAFOs are defined or categorized:	<p>An Animal Feeding Operation means a facility or lot (other than an aquatic animal production facility) where the following conditions are met: Animals have been, are or will be stabled or confined and fed or maintained for a total of 45 days or more in any 12-month period; and Crops, vegetation, forage growth or post-harvest residues aren't sustained in the normal growing season over any portion of the lot or facility. All Animal Feeding Operations in Colorado must implement applicable best management practices in Regulation No. 81 for protecting waters._</p> <p>A concentrated Animal Feeding Operation may be defined as either a large or medium concentrated Animal Feeding Operation, or otherwise designated as a concentrated Animal Feeding Operation by the Environmental Agriculture Program pursuant to the Water Quality Control Commission Regulation No. 81. A defined large concentrated Animal Feeding Operation stables or confines at least the number of animals listed below:_</p> <p>A LARGE CONCENTRATED ANIMAL FEEDING OPERATION means an AFO that stables or confines as many as or more than the number of animals specified in any of the following categories:_</p> <p>700 mature dairy cows._ 1,000 cattle (including but not limited to heifers, steers, bulls and cow/calf pairs)._ 1,000 veal calves._ 2,500 swine, each weighing 55 pounds or more._ 10,000 swine, each weighing less than 55 pounds._ 500 horses._</p>

	<p>10,000 sheep or lambs._ 55,000 turkeys._ 30,000 laying hens or broilers using a liquid manure handling system._ 82,000 laying hens if using a manure handling system other than liquid._ 125,000 chickens (other than laying hens) if using a manure handling system other than liquid._ 30,000 ducks using a manure handling system other than liquid (5,000 if liquid)._ MEDIUM CONCENTRATED ANIMAL FEEDING OPERATION (Medium CAFO) means an AFO with the type and number of animals that fall within any of the ranges listed in (a) below and which has been defined or designated as a CAFO. An AFO is defined as a Medium CAFO if:_ (a) The type and number of animals that it stables or confines falls within any of the following_ ranges:_ (I) 200 to 699 mature dairy cows, whether milked or dry;_ (II) 300 to 999 veal calves;_ (III) 300 to 999 cattle other than mature dairy cows or veal calves. Cattle includes but is not limited to heifers, steers, bulls, and cow/calf pairs._ (IV) 750 to 2,499 swine each weighing 55 pounds or more;_ (V) 3,000 to 9,999 swine each weighing less than 55 pounds;_ (VI) 150 to 499 horses;_ (VIII) 3,000 to 9,999 sheep or lambs;_ (IX) 16,500 to 54,999 turkeys;_ (X) 9,000 to 29,999 laying hens or broilers, if the AFO uses a liquid manure handling system;_ (XI) 37,500 to 124,999 chickens (other than laying hens), if the AFO uses other than a liquid manure handling system;_ (XII) 25,000 to 81,999 laying hens, if the AFO uses other than a liquid manure handling system;_ (XIII) 10,000 to 29,999 ducks (if the AFO uses other than a liquid manure handling system); or_ (XIV) 1,500 to 4,999 ducks (if the AFO uses a liquid manure handling system); and_ (b) Either one of the following conditions are met:_ (I) Pollutants are discharged into surface waters of the state through a man-made drainage system; or_ (II) Pollutants are discharged directly into surface waters of the state which originate outside of and pass over, across, or through the facility or otherwise come into direct contact with the animals confined in the operation.</p>
How animal units are defined (if used):	Not used
NPDES permitting or	[CAFOs] Concentrated Animal Feeding Operations are defined as

<p>other permitting requirements:</p>	<p>point sources of pollution under the Colorado Water Quality Control Act. Any discharge from a CAFO requires a permit except those that are agricultural storm water discharges as defined in Regulation 61.17(2)(c). The owner or operator of a CAFO must seek coverage under a permit if the CAFO discharges to Waters of the United states. Specifically, the CAFO owner or operator must either apply for an individual permit or submit a notice of intent for coverage under a general permit (See section 61.17 of Regulation No. 61.) A concentrated Animal Feeding Operation whose operator is not required to apply for a permit or decides not to apply for a permit must protect surface water by adhering to the surface water protection elements of Regulation No. 81. All concentrated Animal Feeding Operations, whether permitted or not, must adhere to the groundwater protection elements of Regulation No. 81._</p> <p>[Non-permitted CAFOs] The discharge of manure and wastewater to waters of the U.S. from a CAFO as the result of the application of that manure or wastewater by the CAFO to a land application site is a discharge from that CAFO subject to permit requirements, except where it is an agricultural stormwater discharge. Where the manure or wastewater has been applied in accordance with the requirements of Regulation 81.6(2)(a-d), a precipitation-related discharge of manure or wastewater from the site to waters of the U.S. is an agricultural stormwater discharge._</p> <p>[Permitted CAFOs] The discharge of manure or process wastewater to surface water from a CAFO as a result of the application of that manure or process wastewater by the CAFO to land areas under its control is a discharge from that CAFO subject to permit requirements, except where it is an agricultural storm water discharge. Where the manure or process wastewater has been applied in accordance with site specific nutrient management practices that ensure appropriate agricultural utilization of the nutrients in the manure or process wastewater, as specified in those parts of the nutrient management plan that address Regulation 61.17(8)(b), a precipitation-related discharge of manure or process wastewater from land areas under the control of a CAFO is an agricultural stormwater discharge._</p> <p>[Housed Commercial Swine Feeding Operations/HCSFOs]_ All housed commercial swine feeding operations must hold an individual discharge permit under Section 61.13 of Regulation No. 61 (Colorado Discharge Permit System Regulations) and hold an odor emissions permit under Colorado Regulation No. 2, Part B._</p> <p>Land Application Discharges from a housed commercial swine feeding operation -“ The discharge of residual solids or swine feeding process wastewater to surface water from a housed commercial swine feeding operation (HCSFO) as a result of the application of that residual solids or swine feeding process wastewater by the HCSFO to land areas under its control is a discharge from that HCSFO subject to permit requirements, except</p>
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	where it is an agricultural storm water discharge. Where the residual solids or swine feeding process wastewater has been applied in accordance with site specific nutrient management practices that ensure appropriate agricultural utilization of the nutrients in the residual solids or swine feeding process wastewater, as specified in those parts of the swine waste management plan that address Regulation 61.13(3)(f)(viii), (ix),(x), and (xvi), a precipitation-related discharge of residual solids or swine feeding process wastewater from land areas under the control of a HCSFO is an agricultural stormwater discharge.
Does the state require an NPDES permit for all Large CAFOs?	No
Does the state issue individual or general CAFO permits?	Both
Are any other permits required for CAFOs or other large farms?	No
Other definitions needed to understand these regulations:	<p>"Housed Commercial Swine Feeding Operation" means a housed swine feeding operation that is capable of housing eight hundred thousand pounds or more of live animal weight of swine at any one time or is deemed a commercial operation under local zoning or land use regulations. "Capable of housing" means the combined maximum capacities of the individual housing units that are included in the operation. Unless the owner of the operation provides information about the specific operation to the Division which demonstrates that an alternative capacity calculation is appropriate for that operation, operations will be presumed capable of housing 800,000 pounds or more of live animal weight If they have the capacity to house:_ (a) 11,500 weaned swine (70 pounds or less); or_ (b) 3,020 feeder swine (more than 70 pounds, up to finish weight); or_ (c) 2,000 breeding sows and/or boars._ Where more than one of the above-listed size categories of swine are present, operations will be deemed capable of housing 800,000 pounds or more of live animal weight if, by dividing the capacity for the number of each type of swine by the respective limit from (a), (b), and/or (c), above, the sum of the resulting numbers is one or greater.</p>
Regulatory Details	
Setbacks: <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land</i>	[Permitted and Non-permitted CAFOs]_ Manure or wastewater shall not be land-applied within 150 feet of_ domestic water supply wells, and within 300 feet of community domestic water supply wells._ Setback Requirements -“ Unless the operator exercises one of the

<p><i>application and some geographical feature</i></p>	<p>alternatives provided below, manure and wastewater shall not be applied closer than 100 feet to any down-gradient surface waters, open tile line intake structures, sinkholes, agricultural well heads, or other conduits to surface water._</p> <p>(i) As a setback alternative, the operator may substitute the 100-foot setback with a 35-foot wide vegetated buffer where applications of manure or wastewater are prohibited._</p> <p>(ii) The Division may approve an alternative setback or buffer based on a demonstration by the operator that a required setback or buffer is not necessary because implementation of alternative conservation practices or land application site conditions will provide pollutant reductions equivalent or better than the reductions that would be achieved by the 100-foot setback._</p> <p>[HCSFOs]_</p> <p>Water Quality Setbacks - Water quality setbacks shall be established for housed commercial swine feeding operations such that swine feeding process wastewater collection systems in housed units, swine feeding process wastewater conveyance, treatment, storage, and evaporation structures, land application sites, and residual solids stockpiles and impoundments, shall not be located:_</p> <p>(i) Within ten feet vertically of the seasonally high ground water level as determined in the monitoring plan;_</p> <p>(ii) Up-gradient and within 300 feet of a reservoir classified for Class I Recreational Use by the Water Quality Control Commission;_</p> <p>(iii) For land application systems only, within 200 feet of any body of surface water, including intermittent streambeds when standing or running water is present in the streambed, unless land application is made by either subsurface injection, or by surface application which is followed by incorporation within 48 hours, weather permitting, or the swine waste management plan describes measures which will be implemented to prevent runoff from the application site into the water body;_</p> <p>(iv) Within 50 feet of any body of surface water, including intermittent streambeds when standing or running water is present in the streambed;_</p> <p>(v) Within 150 feet of a private domestic water supply well or within 300 feet of a community domestic water supply well;</p>
<p>Are setbacks more restrictive than CFR?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Timing, weather, or conditional application restrictions: <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather, seasons, or land characteristics (like</i></p>	<p>[Non-permitted CAFOs]_</p> <p>* Solid manure shall be incorporated as soon as possible after application, unless the application site has perennial vegetation or is no-till cropped, or except where the operator adequately demonstrates that surface water quality will be protected where manure is not so incorporated._</p> <p>* Where wastewater is applied to a land application site via furrow- or flood-irrigation, it shall be applied in a manner that prevents any</p>

<p>slope)</p>	<p>wastewater runoff into surface water._ * There shall be no discharge to surface water from land application activities when the ground is frozen or saturated._ * When process wastewater is sprinkler-applied, the soil water holding capacity of the soil shall not be exceeded._ [Permitted CAFOs]_ * Solid manure shall be incorporated as soon as possible after application, unless the application site has perennial vegetation or is no-till cropped, or except where the nutrient management plan adequately demonstrates that surface water quality will be protected where manure is not so incorporated._ * Process wastewater to furrow- or flood-irrigated land application sites shall be applied in a manner that prevents any process wastewater runoff into surface waters._ * When process wastewater is sprinkler-applied, the soil water holding capacity of the soil shall not be exceeded._ * Process wastewater shall not be applied to either frozen or flooded land application sites._ [HCSFOs]_ * No land application of residual solids or swine feeding process wastewater shall occur on lands which are saturated or on land with a snow depth of greater than one inch._ * No land application of residual solids or swine feeding process wastewater shall occur on lands which are frozen unless a site-specific analysis demonstrates that runoff will not occur._ * Land application of residual solids and swine feeding process wastewater shall not occur:_ (A) More than 30 days prior to or subsequent to the normal growing season for the crop to which the wastewater is being applied; or_ (B) Outside of the period March 1 through October 31;_ whichever is less restrictive, except pursuant to approved odor management, swine waste management, and monitoring plans.</p>
<p>Is there a restriction for land application of manure to saturated soils?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Is there a restriction for land application of manure within floodplains?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Is there a restriction for land application of manure related to future rainfall?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Is there a restriction for land application of manure to frozen or snow-covered ground?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Are there restrictions to</p>	<p>Yes</p>

manure applications based on time of year or time of day?	
Are there restrictions to manure application based on slope?	No
Are there any other seasonal, timing, weather, or physical restrictions to manure applications not captured above?	No
Transfer of manure off-site: <i>Requirements related to the transfer of manures to other persons</i>	<p>[Permitted CAFOs] Prior to transferring manure or process wastewater to other persons, Large CAFOs must provide the recipient of the manure or process wastewater with the most current nutrient analysis. The analysis provided must be consistent with the requirements of the nutrient management plan in Regulation 61.17(8)(b)). Large CAFOs must retain for five years records of the date, recipient name and address, and approximate amount of manure or process wastewater transferred to another person._</p> <p>[HCSFOs] The swine waste management plan shall quantify the disposition of all residual solids and swine feeding process wastewater produced at the facility whether put to beneficial use through land application on-site or transported off-site. If swine waste is to be applied on property not owned by the permittee, written agreements with landowners for off-site land application must be included in the plan. Agreements entered into after March 30, 1999, with landowners for land application shall allow the Division or its agent to assume the rights of the permittee under the agreement in the event that a facility must be brought to final closure by the state unless alternative treatment and disposal are provided for under the financial assurance plan). The permittee shall provide notice to each landowner of property on which off-site land application occurs of the Division's authority to enter and inspect premises pursuant to section 25-8-306, C.R.S. The permittee shall provide evidence that any agreement with the landowner entered into after March 30, 1999, provides a right of entry to the Division to monitor for compliance with the permit, either directly in the agreement or by assignment of the permittee's rights under the agreement. The Division may require that the permittee cease land application on any off-site lands to which the Division is denied entry; CAFOs</p>
Are receivers of manure transfers from CAFOs required to follow the same regulations?	Yes
Nutrient or manure	[Non-permitted CAFOS] The operator of a non-permitted Large

<p>management plans: <i>Additional details on the NMP requirement. Note that some of this information may overlap with other sections</i></p>	<p>CAFO shall compile and maintain on-site a facility management plan (FMP) that includes, to the extent applicable, the information specified in sections 81.6(1), 81.6(2), 81.6(3) and 81.6(4) of Regulation No. 81. This includes surface water protection elements for production area runoff and any land application areas._ [Permitted CAFOS] Any permit issued to a CAFO must include a requirement to implement a nutrient management plan that, at a minimum, contains best management practices and procedures necessary to meet the requirements of Regulation 61.17(8) and applicable effluent limitations and standards._ [HCSFOs] Swine Waste Management Plan -“ A housed commercial swine feeding operation (HCSFO-2) shall develop and implement a complete swine waste management plan as of the date of permit coverage. The swine waste management plan must comply with the provisions of Regulation 61.13(4)(e) and 61.13(4)(f)(iii). The plan shall be prepared under the supervision of a professional engineer registered in the State of Colorado, by the Natural Resources Conservation Service, by a qualified Cooperative Extension Agent, by a certified crop advisor certified by the American Society of Agronomy or by an independent crop consultant certified by the National Alliance of Independent Crop Consultants. The plan shall include sufficient site-specific hydrologic and agronomic information, supplemented by other scientifically supported information, to document that land application of all residual solids and swine feeding process wastewater will be conducted and sustained at or below the agronomic rate of application for crops or vegetation to be grown on the application site(s). The plan shall quantify the disposition of all residual solids and swine feeding process wastewater produced at the facility whether put to beneficial use through land application on-site or transported off-site.</p>
<p>Do your NMP/MMPS follow, comply with, or based on NRCS Technical Standard 590?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Application rates: <i>State regulations that restrict the rates at which manures are applied and methods needed to determine appropriate rates.</i></p>	<p>[Permitted CAFOs]_ Soil Testing. A field-specific determination of soil levels of nitrogen and phosphorus, including, for nitrogen, a concurrent determination of nitrogen that will be plant available consistent with the methodology required by Regulation 61.17(8)(b)(xii)(B)(IV)(6), and for phosphorus, the results of the most recent soil test conducted in accordance with soil testing requirements approved by the Division; _ Rates of application of manure, litter, and process wastewater to be land applied, according to the following specifications:_ (1) Maximum amounts of nitrogen and phosphorus derived from all sources of nutrients, for each crop identified in the nutrient management plan, in chemical forms determined to be acceptable</p>

to the Division, in pounds per acre, for each field;_

(2) The outcome of field-specific assessment of potential for nitrogen and phosphorus transport to surface water for each field, using the USDA, NRCS Colorado Phosphorus Index Risk Assessment tool or other Division-approved method;_

(3) The crops to be planted in each field or any other uses such as pasture or fallow fields (including alternative crops identified in accordance with Regulation 61.17(8)(b)(xii)(B)(IV)(7);_

(4) The realistic yield goal for each crop or use identified for each field;_

(5) The nitrogen and phosphorus recommendation for each crop or use identified for each field from a method approved by the Division. Such methods may include, but are not limited to, the most current published fertilizer suggestions of the Cooperative Extension in Colorado or adjacent states, or the most current nutrient management planning guidelines for Colorado as published by the USDA, NRCS._

[Non-permitted CAFOs]_

Soil Testing: The soil of land application sites shall be sampled and analyzed a minimum of once annually for available nutrients, including nitrate-nitrogen. The top one foot of soil of land application sites shall be sampled and analyzed for available phosphorus a minimum of once every five years, or as specified in Regulation 81.6(2)(b)(v)._

Protocols established by the operator for land applying manure or wastewater in accordance with site specific nutrient management practices that ensure appropriate utilization of the nutrients in the manure or wastewater. Such protocols shall include, but are not limited to:_

(A) No application of manure or wastewater shall be made to a land application site at a rate that will exceed the capacity of the soil and the planned crops to assimilate plant available nitrogen within 12 months of the manure or wastewater being applied._

(B) Manure and wastewater shall be applied as uniformly as possible with properly calibrated equipment._

(C) Application rates of manure and wastewater shall be calculated using one of the following methods: the most current published fertilizer suggestions of Cooperative Extension in Colorado or adjacent states; the most current nutrient management planning guidelines for Colorado as published by the USDA, NRCS; or an alternative method approved by the Division._

[HCSFOs]_

The disposal or land application of all residual solids and swine feeding process wastewater produced at the facility, whether put to beneficial use on-site or transported off-site, must minimize phosphorus and nitrogen transport from the land application sites to surface waters and shall be in accordance with the approved swine waste management plan._

(ii) The owner or operator of a housed commercial swine feeding operation shall ensure that no residual solids or swine feeding process wastewater generated by it shall be applied to land by any person at a rate that exceeds, in amount or duration, the agronomic rate of application. The agronomic rate of application shall be as specified by the most current published fertilizer suggestions of Colorado State University Cooperative Extension for the plants, or most closely related plant type, to which the nutrients are applied and: _

(A) No application of residual solids or swine feeding process wastewater shall be made to lands if the soil nitrate level and other appropriate nitrogen credits (as specified by Colorado State University Cooperative Extension) in the agronomic root zone exceed the agronomic rate of nitrogen application for the crop to be grown; _

(B) Application rates of residual solids and swine feeding process wastewater shall be based on a field-specific assessment of the potential for nitrogen and phosphorus transport from the field and that addresses the form, source, amount, timing, and method of application of nutrients on each field to achieve realistic yield goals, while minimizing nitrogen and phosphorus movement to surface waters. _

(C) Residual solids, swine feeding process wastewater, and soils shall be sampled and analyzed quarterly for nitrogen and phosphorus content, in accordance with the monitoring requirements specified in Regulation 61.13(4)(k)(vi). The results of these analyses are to be used in determining application rates for residual solids and swine feeding process wastewater. _

(D) Assessments shall be made for each land application site of the potential for phosphorus and nitrogen transport from the site to surface waters and that address the form, source, amount, timing, and method of application of nitrogen and phosphorus to achieve realistic yield goals, while minimizing nitrogen and phosphorus movement to surface water. Phosphorus transport risk assessments shall be made using a transport risk-screening tool approved by the Division and that is current, readily available, peer-reviewed, and appropriate for use in Colorado. The screening tool shall provide for off-site transport risk scores of either low, medium, high, or very high. An initial assessment of the potential for nitrogen transport to surface water shall be made prior to residual solids or swine feeding process wastewater being applied to an application site after the operator implements the swine waste management plan that meets the requirements of Regulation 61.13(3)(f), as revised effective June 30, 2004. _

(I) After an initial assessment is made of the potential for phosphorus an/or nitrogen transport from a land application site to surface water, additional assessments shall be made at the following frequency, whichever is sooner: _

	<p>(1) Of both phosphorus and nitrogen transport risk, every five (5) years; or_</p> <p>(2) Where a crop management change has occurred, assess phosphorus transport risk within one (1) year after a crop management change would reasonably result in an increase in the phosphorus transport risk assessment score, and assess nitrogen transport risk within one (1) year after such a change would reasonably result in the nitrogen transport to surface water not being minimized; or_</p> <p>(3) Where the top one foot of soil on an application site exceeds 80 mg/kg of sodium bicarbonate extractable phosphorus and the phosphorus transport risk assessment score was very high, assess phosphorus transport risk within six (6) months of intending to apply residual solids or swine feeding process wastewater._</p> <p>(4) Where a nitrogen transport risk assessment reveals that nitrogen transport to surface waters is not minimized, assess nitrogen transport risk within six (6) months of intending to apply residual solids or swine feeding process wastewater._</p> <p>(II) No application of swine feeding process wastewater or residual solids shall be made to a land application site if the sodium bicarbonate extractable phosphorus in the top one-foot of soil exceeds 80 mg/kg, unless the off-site phosphorus transport risk score for the site is high or less._</p> <p>(III) No application of residual solids or swine feeding process wastewater shall be made to a land application site where the risk of off-site nitrogen transport is high or very high._</p> <p>(IV) Where a multi-year phosphorus application was made to a land application site, no additional residual solids or swine feeding process wastewater shall be applied to the same site in subsequent years until the applied phosphorus has been removed from the site via harvest and crop removal._</p> <p>(E) If the soil nitrate-nitrogen level in the four- to six-foot or six- to eight-foot increment within the monitoring zone exceeds the comparative concentration, established in accordance with Regulation 61.13(4)(k)(ii), by greater than ten milligrams per kilogram, the permittee will be presumed to have exceeded the agronomic rate of application and shall notify the Division in writing of this exceedance within 30 days of discovering it._</p> <p>(I) The permittee shall, in consultation with the Division, develop and submit to the Division within ninety (90) days of discovering the exceedance an approvable intervention protocol, unless an extension of time is granted by the Division. The intervention protocol shall describe adjustments to the swine waste management plan that provide for strict minimization of future nitrogen loading within the monitoring zone. The Division may specify that appropriate measures for the purpose of remediating excessive nitrogen within the monitoring zone be included in the protocol._</p>
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	<p>(II) The protocol shall be implemented by the permittee within 30 days of it being approved by the Division. If remediation measures in an approved intervention protocol are not being implemented in accordance with the protocol, application of swine feeding process wastewater and/or residual solids to the applicable land application site shall immediately cease._</p> <p>(III) The agronomic rate of application shall not be presumed to have been exceeded and the intervention protocol shall not be required if the result of confirmation sampling pursuant to a procedure approved by the Division demonstrate that the comparative concentration has not been exceeded by greater than ten milligrams per kilogram, or if the permittee submits to the Division a report that adequately documents that a force majeure was the cause of the nitrate-nitrogen exceedance. This report shall be submitted for approval no later than 30 days after discovering an exceedance caused by a force majeure event._</p> <p>(IV) Status of intervention protocol activities shall be documented in quarterly monitoring reports._</p> <p>(iii) All land application activities at housed commercial swine feeding operations shall be conducted in a manner that does not result in impairment of existing beneficial uses of state waters or exceedances of applicable water quality standards for surface water or ground water._</p> <p>(iv) Where land application sites are not supporting active plant growth:_</p> <p>(A) Applications of swine feeding process wastewater and residual solids shall not at any time cause soil nitrate levels and other appropriate nitrogen credits in the agronomic root zone to exceed the agronomic rate for the upcoming growing season for the crop for which the solids or wastewater is applied._</p> <p>(B) Swine feeding process wastewater and residual solids shall not be applied to land not supporting active plant growth except as provided under an approved Swine Waste Management Plan that includes appropriate best management practices for such applications. Best management practices shall be specified in a guidance document cooperatively developed by the Division and stakeholders, and presented in a public hearing before the Water Quality Control Commission.</p>
<p>Manure application rates for phosphorus are based on:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) <i>Phosphorus Index Only</i> 2) <i>Soil Test Phosphorus Only</i> 3) <i>Either PIO or STPO</i> 4) <i>Other</i> 	<p>Phosphorus index only</p>
<p>Are there any nutrient “caps” to manure</p>	<p>No</p>

application?	
<p>Composition testing: <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on manures before application</i></p>	<p>[Permitted CAFOs] The results of most recent representative manure, litter, and process wastewater tests for nitrogen and phosphorus taken within 12 months of the date of land application, in order to determine the amount of nitrogen and phosphorus in the manure, litter, and process wastewater to be applied._ [Non-permitted CAFOs] Manure and wastewater shall be sampled and analyzed a minimum of once annually for nitrogen and phosphorus content._ [HCSFOs] Concentrations of specific constituents including, but not limited to, nitrogen, phosphorus, heavy metals, and salts present in the residual solids or swine feeding process wastewater as a result of the housed commercial swine feeding operation_ Swine feeding process wastewater and residual solids produced at housed commercial swine feeding operations which are applied to land shall not exceed the cumulative pollutant loading limits for heavy metals as set forth in Table 1, of Regulation 61.3(4) . Cumulative metal loading limits shall be calculated as the product of the total elemental analysis (concentration) of the residual solids and swine feeding process wastewater and the quantity of residual solids and volume of swine feeding process wastewater applied, respectively. Compliance with cumulative pollutant loading limits shall be documented by the permittee in reports submitted in accordance with Regulation 61.13(4)(j). Documentation shall consist of data which quantifies cumulative loadings of the heavy metals to each land application site. If the cumulative loading limit specified in Table 1 of Regulation 61.3(4) is reached, no further residual solids or swine feeding process wastewater will be applied to the application site.</p>
<p>Does your state require testing of manure for anything beyond nutrients, such as metals, pathogens, antibiotics, etc.?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Other land application highlights: <i>Additional restrictions for land application of manures</i></p>	<p>No other information</p>
<p>Other regulatory details: <i>Additional information on the regulation of land application of manures</i></p>	<p>No other information</p>
General Assessment Questions	
<p>Do you anticipate changes in these</p>	<p>Undetermined</p>

<p>regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change:</p>	
<p>Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of manures that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links:</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of manures beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so:</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.</p>	<p>No other information</p>

Connecticut Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2019
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Connecticut Department of Energy and Environmental Protection (DEEP)
Links to regulations	Title 22a - Environmental Protection:_ https://www.law.cornell.edu/regulations/connecticut/title-22a
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Environmental
Other regulator info	Connecticut does not have a specific set of regulations devoted to AFOs and CAFOs._ – Concentrated Animal Feeding Operations, concentrated aquatic animal production facilities, aquaculture projects, and silvicultural activities, as defined in 40 CFR 122.23, 40 CFR 122.24, 40 CFR 122.25, 40 CFR 125 Subpart B, and 40 CFR 122.27 respectively and after any case-by-case review as specified therein, shall be subject to the requirements of this section and section 22a-430-3 of the Regulations of Connecticut State Agencies, as amended.
Definitions	
How CAFOs are defined or categorized:	Refer to 40 CFR
How animal units are defined (if used):	Not used
NPDES permitting or other permitting requirements:	The state of Connecticut has assumed the NPDES program from the federal government. CT DEEP has developed a General Permit for Concentrated Animal Feeding Operations and will move forward with issuance in the near future.
Does the state require an NPDES permit for all Large CAFOs?	Yes
Does the state issue individual or general CAFO permits?	Individual

Are any other permits required for CAFOs or other large farms?	No
Other definitions needed to understand these regulations:	No other information
Regulatory Details	
Setbacks: <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some geographical feature</i>	Under proposed CAFO GP required compliance with CTNRCS CPS 590: _ Manure injection or incorporation the same day, 75ft;_ Manure applications surface applied (no incorporation), 150ft;_ Wells: Public/Private/Agricultural _ < 10 gpm output: Applied up gradient, permanently vegetated buffer ? 35 feet 35 _ < 10 gpm output: Applied up gradient and no permanently vegetated buffer ? 35 feet 100ft;_ ? 10 gpm and < 50 gpm output: All applications 100ft;_ ? 50 gpm output or stratified drift: All applications 200ft.
Are setbacks more restrictive than CFR?	Yes
Timing, weather, or conditional application restrictions: <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather, seasons, or land characteristics (like slope)</i>	Under proposed CAFO GP required compliance with CTNRCS CPS 590: _ Nutrients must not be surface-applied immediately before, during, or after precipitation events likely to create surface runoff offsite._ Spreading is not allowed when conditions when the top 2 inches of soil are saturated from rainfall or snow melt._ Applications of nutrients to cultivated fields with soils in flooding frequency classes occasional- ² , frequent- ² , or very frequent- ² shall be by injection or limited to periods within 24 hours of tillage and/or planting operations. Any non-injected manure applications shall be incorporated within 24 hours. _ Flooding frequency classes are defined in Section 618.26(b) (1) of the current NRCS National Soil Survey Handbook (GM Title 430-VI-NSSH, Part 618, 2010)._ Nutrients must not be surface-applied immediately before, during, or after precipitation events likely to create surface runoff offsite._ Timing and placement of all nutrients must correspond as closely as possible with plant nutrient uptake (utilization by crops), and consider nutrient source, cropping system limitations, soil properties, weather conditions, drainage system, soil biology, and nutrient risk assessment results._ A field level evaluation of the potential for nitrogen and/or phosphorus losses will

	<p>be completed for all fields. _</p> <p>When there is a high risk of transport of nutrients, conservation practices must be coordinated to avoid, control, or trap manure and nutrients before they can leave the field by surface or subsurface drainage (e.g., tile).</p>
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to saturated soils?	Yes
Is there a restriction for land application of manure within floodplains?	Yes
Is there a restriction for land application of manure related to future rainfall?	Yes
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to frozen or snow-covered ground?	Yes
Are there restrictions to manure applications based on time of year or time of day?	Yes
Are there restrictions to manure application based on slope?	Yes
Are there any other seasonal,	Yes

<p>timing, weather, or physical restrictions to manure applications not captured above?</p>	
<p>Transfer of manure off-site: <i>Requirements related to the transfer of manures to other persons</i></p>	<p>Refer to 40 CFR. Receivers of manure transfers from CAFOs required to follow the same regulations only if the facility is a permitted CAFO.</p>
<p>Are receivers of manure transfers from CAFOs required to follow the same regulations?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Nutrient or manure management plans: <i>Additional details on the NMP requirement. Note that some of this information may overlap with other sections</i></p>	<p>The General Permit for Concentrated Animal Feeding Operations is currently being developed by the DEEP. Once issued, this General Permit will regulate manure management activities practiced on CAFOs which meet the definitions in the permit. CTDEEP has adopted CtNRCS CPC 590 Nutrient Management as the technical standards for land application of nutrients. The NRCS requires a Comprehensive Nutrient Management Plan (CNMP) as part of approval for funding under the EQIP funding program. When the General Permit is issued, CAFOs with recently developed NRCS CNMPs will meet permit requirements _</p> <p>_</p> <p>(i) For concentrated Animal Feeding Operations: _</p> <p>(a) The type and number of animals in open confinement and housed under roof._</p> <p>(b) The number of acres used for confinement feeding._</p> <p>(c) The design basis for the runoff diversion and control system, if one exists, including the number of acres of contributing drainage, the storage capacity, and the design safety factor. _</p> <p>(ii) For concentrated aquatic animal production facilities: _</p> <p>(a) The maximum daily and average monthly flow from each discharge location._</p> <p>(b) The number of ponds, raceways, and similar structures._</p> <p>(c) For each species of aquatic animals, the total yearly and maximum harvestable weight. _</p> <p>(d) The calendar month of maximum feeding and the total mass of food fed during that month._</p> <p>_</p> <p>Under proposed CAFO GP CTDEEP has adopted CtNRCS CPC 590 Nutrient Management as the technical standards for land application of nutrients. Refer to</p>

	CtNRCS CPC 590_ https://portal.ct.gov/-/media/deep/permits_and_licenses/water_discharge_general_permits/cafogp.pdf
Do your NMP/MMPS follow, comply with, or based on NRCS Technical Standard 590?	Yes
Application rates: <i>State regulations that restrict the rates at which manures are applied and methods needed to determine appropriate rates.</i>	Under proposed CAFO GP: _ Management as the technical standards for land application of nutrients._ For fields receiving manure, where phosphorus risk assessment results equate to: VERY HIGH risk, there are three options per Standard 590 : _ * No Phosphorus Application to the field, or _ * Implement a soil phosphorus drawdown strategy for the field, with mitigating practices to protect water quality, or _ * any deviation from these high risk requirements must have the approval of the Chief of the NRCS.
Manure application rates for phosphorus are based on: 1) <i>Phosphorus Index Only</i> 2) <i>Soil Test Phosphorus Only</i> 3) <i>Either PIO or STPO</i> 4) <i>Other</i>	Phosphorus index only
Are there any nutrient “caps” to manure application?	Yes
Composition testing: <i>State regulations that govern the</i>	Refer to 40 CFR

<p><i>physical and chemical tests that must be performed on manures before application</i></p>	
<p>Does your state require testing of manure for anything beyond nutrients, such as metals, pathogens, antibiotics, etc.?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Other land application highlights: <i>Additional restrictions for land application of manures</i></p>	<p>No other information</p>
<p>Other regulatory details: <i>Additional information on the regulation of land application of manures</i></p>	<p>No other information</p>
<p>General Assessment Questions</p>	
<p>Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that</p>	<p>Undetermined</p>

<p>may potentially change:</p>	
<p>Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of manures that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links:</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of manures beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so:</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.</p>	<p>No other information</p>

Delaware Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2019
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Delaware Department of Agriculture_ Department of Natural Resources and Environmental Control_
Links to regulations	Title 3 Agriculture -1200 Nutrient Management_ http://regulations.delaware.gov/AdminCode/title3/1200/#TopOfPage _ _ Title 7 NREC - 7200 Surface Water Dischargers Section_ http://regulations.delaware.gov/AdminCode/title7/7000/7200/7201.shtml
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	More than one agency
Other regulator info	No other information
Definitions	
How CAFOs are defined or categorized:	<p>"Concentrated Animal Feeding Operation" Or "CAFO" means an Animal Feeding Operation, feedlot or animal production facility that meets the criteria in Appendix B to 40 CFR Part 122 or which is designated as such by the Secretary in accordance with 40 CFR 122.23(c)._</p> <p>_</p> <p>An Animal Feeding Operation (AFO) is a Large CAFO if the number of animals equal or exceed the following criteria:_</p> <p>1,000 Cattle other than mature dairy cows or veal calves. Includes but is not limited to heifers, steers, bulls, and cow/calf pairs. 700 mature dairy cattle (whether milked or dry cows), 2,500 swine each weighing over 55 pounds, 10,000 swine weighing under 55 pounds, 500 horses, 10,000 sheep or lambs, 55,000 turkeys, 30,000 laying hens or broilers, if the AFO uses a liquid manure handling system, 125,000 chickens except laying hens (if other than a liquid manure handling system), 82,000 laying hens (if other than a liquid manure handling system), 1,000 veal calves. 30,000 ducks (if the AFO uses other than a liquid manure handling system), 5,000 ducks (if the AFO uses a liquid manure handling system)._</p> <p>_</p> <p>An Animal Feeding Operation (AFO) is a Medium CAFO if the number of animals equal or exceed the following criteria: 300 to 999 Cattle other than mature dairy cows or veal calves. Includes but is not limited to heifers, steers, bulls, and cow/calf pairs. 200 to 699 mature dairy cattle (whether milked or dry cows), 750 to 2,499 swine each weighing over 55 pounds, 3,000 to 9,999 swine weighing under 55 pounds, 150 to 499 horses, 3,000 to 9,999 sheep or lambs, 16,500 to 54,999 turkeys, 9,000 to 29,999 laying hens or broilers, if the AFO uses a liquid manure handling system, 37,500 to 124,999 chickens except laying hens (if other than a liquid manure handling system), 25,000 to 81,999 laying hens (if other than a liquid manure handling system), 300-999 veal calves. 10,000 to 29,999 ducks (if the AFO uses other than a liquid manure handling</p>

	<p>system), 1,500 to 4,999 ducks (if the AFO uses a liquid manure handling system)._</p> <p>_</p> <p>Designation of a CAFO. The Secretary or his designee, may designate any AFO as a CAFO upon determination that it is a significant contributor of pollutants to Waters of the State.</p>
How animal units are defined (if used):	Not used
NPDES permitting or other permitting requirements:	All CAFO operations must be covered by NPDES individual permits.
Does the state require an NPDES permit for all Large CAFOs?	Yes
Does the state issue individual or general CAFO permits?	Undetermined
Are any other permits required for CAFOs or other large farms?	Undetermined
Other definitions needed to understand these regulations:	No other information
Regulatory Details	
<p>Setbacks:</p> <p><i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some geographical feature</i></p>	<p>Identify manure and processed wastewater application setbacks to be implemented on the CAFO in accordance with State Technical Standards. The direct application of manure or processed wastewater to Waters of the State is prohibited. The following three setback standards are provided as_</p> <p>three options:_</p> <p>_</p> <p>One-hundred (100) foot application setback measured from the top of the bank of the water of the state to be protected, (Unless the CAFO exercises one of the compliance alternatives provided for in paragraphs 5.1.4.6.1.2, or 5.1.4.6.1.3, of this section, manure, litter and process wastewater may not be applied closer than 100 feet to any down-gradient surface waters, open tile intakes structures, sinkholes, agricultural well heads or other conduits to surface water) and/or_</p> <p>_</p> <p>Thirty-five (35) foot vegetated buffer measured from the top of the bank of the water of the state to be protected, where applications of manure, litter, and process wastewater are prohibited, and/or_</p> <p>_</p> <p>Alternative compliance practices as follows: Minimum ten (10) foot vegetated buffer measured from the top of the bank of the water of the state to be protected, and plant a winter cover crop in accordance with State Technical Standards following the crop receiving manure, litter or</p>

	process wastewater for fields with high phosphorus soils and;_ or_ Minimum ten (10) foot application setback measured from the top of the bank of the water of the state to be protected, and plant a winter cover crop in accordance with State Technical Standards following crops receiving manure, litter or process wastewater in areas without high phosphorus soils.
Are setbacks more restrictive than CFR?	Undetermined
Timing, weather, or conditional application restrictions: <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather, seasons, or land characteristics (like slope)</i>	None
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to saturated soils?	No
Is there a restriction for land application of manure within floodplains?	No
Is there a restriction for land application of manure related to future rainfall?	No
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to frozen or snow-covered ground?	No
Are there restrictions to manure applications based on time of year or time of day?	No
Are there restrictions to manure application based on slope?	No
Are there any other seasonal, timing, weather, or physical restrictions to manure	Undetermined

<p>applications not captured above?</p>	
<p>Transfer of manure off-site: <i>Requirements related to the transfer of manures to other persons</i></p>	<p>Delaware Department of Agriculture's (DDA) Nutrient Management Relocation Program (Program) provides financial assistance for transporting manure from areas of excess manure to areas in need, both within and outside Delaware, or to alternative use projects such as Perdue Agri Recycle. _ https://www.epa.gov/sites/production/files/2017-01/documents/b_delaware_manure_relocation_program.pdf _</p> <p>Off site use of manure, litter or process wastewater. If manure, litter or process wastewater is sold or given to other persons for disposal or utilization, the following information shall be maintained at the CAFO generating the manure, litter or process wastewater: _</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * The date of manure, litter or process wastewater removal._ * Name of receiver and contact information._ * Quantity (tons/gallons) of manure, litter or process wastewater removed._ * A copy of the most recent manure, litter and process wastewater nutrient analysis shall be given to the receiver on or before the date of transfer._ * The annual report and supporting documents.
<p>Are receivers of manure transfers from CAFOs required to follow the same regulations?</p>	<p>Undetermined</p>
<p>Nutrient or manure management plans: <i>Additional details on the NMP requirement. Note that some of this information may overlap with other sections</i></p>	<p>Delaware requires nutrient management plan (NMP) development and implementation for: All Animal Feeding Operations (AFO) with greater than eight animal units (an animal unit is equal to 1000 pounds of live weight), or any person who owns, leases or otherwise controls property in excess of 10 acres upon which nutrients are applied (3 Del. C. §2247).</p>
<p>Do your NMP/MMPS follow, comply with, or based on NRCS Technical Standard 590?</p>	<p>Undetermined</p>
<p>Application rates: <i>State regulations that restrict the rates at which manures are applied and methods needed to determine appropriate rates.</i></p>	<p>Crop and Nutrient Information required on:_</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Realistic yield goal in accordance with State Technical Standards. These standards are established by the Secretary and in consultation with a collaborative group of technical experts representing technical resources and endorsed by the Delaware Nutrient Management Commission. State Technical Standards are available at the Department._ * Soil test results using protocols established in the State Technical

	<p>Standards._</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Current and planned crop rotation._ * Determine the rate of application of nitrogen and phosphorus using the narrative rate approach or the linear rate approach in accordance with State Technical Standards._ * Determine nitrogen application rates for each field based on realistic yield goal of crop(s) to be grown and in accordance with State Technical Standards._ * Determine the phosphorus application rates for each field in accordance with State Technical Standards.
<p>Manure application rates for phosphorus are based on:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) <i>Phosphorus Index Only</i> 2) <i>Soil Test Phosphorus Only</i> 3) <i>Either PIO or STPO</i> 4) <i>Other</i> 	Soil test phosphorus only
Are there any nutrient “caps” to manure application?	Undetermined
<p>Composition testing: <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on manures before application</i></p>	<p>Large CAFOs that use the linear rate approach must calculate the maximum amount of manure, litter, and process wastewater to be land applied at least once each year using the results of the most recent representative manure, litter, or process wastewater tests for nitrogen and phosphorus taken within 12 months of the date of land application._</p> <p>CAFOs that use the narrative rate approach must calculate maximum amounts of manure, litter, and process wastewater to be land applied at least once each year using the methodology required in State Technical Standards before land applying manure, litter, and process wastewater._</p> <p>The narrative rate approach must include the maximum amounts of nitrogen and phosphorus derived from all sources of nutrients, for each crop identified in the nutrient management plan, in chemical forms determined to be acceptable by the Secretary, in pounds per acre, for each field, and certain factors necessary to determine such amounts.</p>
Does your state require testing of manure for anything beyond nutrients, such as metals, pathogens, antibiotics, etc.?	Undetermined
Other land application highlights: <i>Additional restrictions for land application of</i>	No other information

<i>manures</i>	
Other regulatory details: <i>Additional information on the regulation of land application of manures</i>	No other information
General Assessment Questions	
Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change:	Undetermined
Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of manures that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links:	No
Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of manures beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so:	No
Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.	No other information

Federal Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2019
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	US Environmental Protection Agency (US EPA)
Links to regulations	<p>40 CFR Part 412 - CAFO Point Source Category_ https://www.law.cornell.edu/cfr/text/40/part-412 _</p> <p>–</p> <p>40 CFR 122.23 - CAFOs (applicable to State NPDES programs)_ https://www.law.cornell.edu/cfr/text/40/122.23 _</p> <p>–</p> <p>40 CFR 122.42 - Additional conditions applicable to specified categories of NPDES permits_ https://www.law.cornell.edu/cfr/text/40/122.42</p>
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Other
Other regulator info	No other information
Definitions	
How CAFOs are defined or categorized:	<p>Animal feeding operation (AFO) means a lot or facility (other than an aquatic animal production facility) where the following conditions are met:_</p> <p>(i) Animals (other than aquatic animals) have been, are, or will be stabled or confined and fed or maintained for a total of 45 days or more in any 12-month period, and_</p> <p>(ii) Crops, vegetation, forage growth, or post-harvest residues are not sustained in the normal growing season over any portion of the lot or facility._</p> <p>–</p> <p>Concentrated Animal Feeding Operation (CAFO) means an AFO that is defined as a Large CAFO or as a Medium CAFO by the terms of this paragraph, or that is designated as a CAFO in accordance with paragraph (c) of this section. Two or more AFOs under common ownership are considered to be a single AFO for the purposes of determining the number of animals at an operation, if they adjoin each other or if they use a common area or system for the disposal of wastes._</p> <p>–</p> <p>Large concentrated Animal Feeding Operation (Large CAFO-⁽²⁾). An AFO is defined as a Large CAFO if it stables or confines as many as or more than the numbers of animals specified in any of the following categories:_</p> <p>(i) 700 mature dairy cows, whether milked or dry;_</p> <p>(ii) 1,000 veal calves;_</p> <p>(iii) 1,000 cattle other than mature dairy cows or veal calves. Cattle includes but is not limited to heifers, steers, bulls and cow/calf</p>

- pairs;_
- (iv) 2,500 swine each weighing 55 pounds or more;_
- (v) 10,000 swine each weighing less than 55 pounds;_
- (vi) 500 horses;_
- (vii) 10,000 sheep or lambs;_
- (viii) 55,000 turkeys;_
- (ix) 30,000 laying hens or broilers, if the AFO uses a liquid manure handling system;_
- (x) 125,000 chickens (other than laying hens), if the AFO uses other than a liquid manure handling system;_
- (xi) 82,000 laying hens, if the AFO uses other than a liquid manure handling system;_
- (xii) 30,000 ducks (if the AFO uses other than a liquid manure handling system); or_
- (xiii) 5,000 ducks (if the AFO uses a liquid manure handling system)._

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 Medium concentrated Animal Feeding Operation (Medium CAFO-²). The term Medium CAFO includes any AFO with the type and number of animals that fall within any of the ranges listed below and which has been defined or designated as a CAFO. An AFO is defined as a Medium CAFO if:_

- (i) The type and number of animals that it stables or confines falls within any of the following ranges:
 - (A) 200 to 699 mature dairy cows, whether milked or dry;_
 - (B) 300 to 999 veal calves;_
 - (C) 300 to 999 cattle other than mature dairy cows or veal calves. Cattle includes but is not limited to heifers, steers, bulls and cow/calf pairs;_
 - (D) 750 to 2,499 swine each weighing 55 pounds or more;_
 - (E) 3,000 to 9,999 swine each weighing less than 55 pounds;_
 - (F) 150 to 499 horses;_
 - (G) 3,000 to 9,999 sheep or lambs;_
 - (H) 16,500 to 54,999 turkeys;_
 - (I) 9,000 to 29,999 laying hens or broilers, if the AFO uses a liquid manure handling system;_
 - (J) 37,500 to 124,999 chickens (other than laying hens), if the AFO uses other than a liquid manure handling system;_
 - (K) 25,000 to 81,999 laying hens, if the AFO uses other than a liquid manure handling system;_
 - (L) 10,000 to 29,999 ducks (if the AFO uses other than a liquid manure handling system); or_
 - (M) 1,500 to 4,999 ducks (if the AFO uses a liquid manure handling system); and_
- (ii) Either one of the following conditions are met:
 - (A) Pollutants are discharged into waters of the United States through a man-made ditch, flushing system, or other similar man-made device; or_

	<p>(B) Pollutants are discharged directly into waters of the United States which originate outside of and pass over, across, or through the facility or otherwise come into direct contact with the animals confined in the operation._</p> <p>– Small concentrated Animal Feeding Operation (Small CAFO). An AFO that is designated as a CAFO and is not a Medium CAFO.</p>
How animal units are defined (if used):	Not used
NPDES permitting or other permitting requirements:	<p>Land application discharges from a CAFO are subject to NPDES requirements. The discharge of manure, litter or process wastewater to waters of the United States from a CAFO as a result of the application of that manure, litter or process wastewater by the CAFO to land areas under its control is a discharge from that CAFO subject to NPDES permit requirements, except where it is an agricultural storm water discharge as provided in 33 U.S.C. 1362(14). For purposes of this paragraph, where the manure, litter or process wastewater has been applied in accordance with site specific nutrient management practices that ensure appropriate agricultural utilization of the nutrients in the manure, litter or process wastewater, as specified in § 122.42(e)(1)(vi)-(ix), a precipitation-related discharge of manure, litter or process wastewater from land areas under the control of a CAFO is an agricultural stormwater discharge._</p> <p>(1) For unpermitted Large CAFOs, a precipitation-related discharge of manure, litter, or process wastewater from land areas under the control of a CAFO shall be considered an agricultural stormwater discharge only where the manure, litter, or process wastewater has been land applied in accordance with site-specific nutrient management practices that ensure appropriate agricultural utilization of the nutrients in the manure, litter, or process wastewater, as specified in § 122.42(e)(1)(vi) through (ix)._</p> <p>(2) Unpermitted Large CAFOs must maintain documentation specified in § 122.42(e)(1)(ix) either on site or at a nearby office, or otherwise make such documentation readily available to the Director or Regional Administrator upon request.</p>
Does the state require an NPDES permit for all Large CAFOs?	Yes
Does the state issue individual or general CAFO permits?	NA
Are any other permits required for CAFOs or other large farms?	NA
Other definitions needed to understand these	No other information

regulations:	
Regulatory Details	
<p>Setbacks: <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some geographical feature</i></p>	<p>Setback requirements. Unless the CAFO exercises one of the compliance alternatives provided for in paragraph (c)(5)(i) or (c)(5)(ii) of 40 CFR 412.4, manure, litter, and process wastewater may not be applied closer than 100 feet to any down-gradient surface waters, open tile line intake structures, sinkholes, agricultural well heads, or other conduits to surface waters._</p> <p>(i)Vegetated buffer compliance alternative. As a compliance alternative, the CAFO may substitute the 100-foot setback with a 35-foot wide vegetated buffer where applications of manure, litter, or process wastewater are prohibited._</p> <p>(ii)Alternative practices compliance alternative. As a compliance alternative, the CAFO may demonstrate that a setback or buffer is not necessary because implementation of alternative conservation practices or field-specific conditions will provide pollutant reductions equivalent or better than the reductions that would be achieved by the 100-foot setback.</p>
Are setbacks more restrictive than CFR?	Not Applicable
<p>Timing, weather, or conditional application restrictions: <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather, seasons, or land characteristics (like slope)</i></p>	None specific, outside of broad details in NMP guidelines
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to saturated soils?	NA
Is there a restriction for land application of manure within floodplains?	NA
Is there a restriction for land application of manure related to future rainfall?	NA
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to frozen or snow-covered ground?	NA
Are there restrictions to manure applications based on time of year or time of day?	NA

Are there restrictions to manure application based on slope?	NA
Are there any other seasonal, timing, weather, or physical restrictions to manure applications not captured above?	Undetermined
Transfer of manure off-site: <i>Requirements related to the transfer of manures to other persons</i>	Requirements relating to transfer of manure or process wastewater to other persons. Prior to transferring manure, litter or process wastewater to other persons, Large CAFOs must provide the recipient of the manure, litter or process wastewater with the most current nutrient analysis. The analysis provided must be consistent with the requirements of 40 CFR part 412. Large CAFOs must retain for five years records of the date, recipient name and address, and approximate amount of manure, litter or process wastewater transferred to another person.
Are receivers of manure transfers from CAFOs required to follow the same regulations?	Not Applicable
Nutrient or manure management plans: <i>Additional details on the NMP requirement. Note that some of this information may overlap with other sections</i>	<p>[40 CFR 412.4] _</p> <p>(1)Nutrient Management Plan. The CAFO must develop and implement a nutrient management plan that incorporates the requirements of paragraphs (c)(2) through (c)(5) of this section based on a field-specific assessment of the potential for nitrogen and phosphorus transport from the field and that addresses the form, source, amount, timing, and method of application of nutrients on each field to achieve realistic production goals, while minimizing nitrogen and phosphorus movement to surface waters._</p> <p>(2)Determination of application rates. Application rates for manure, litter, and other process wastewater applied to land under the ownership or operational control of the CAFO must minimize phosphorus and nitrogen transport from the field to surface waters in compliance with the technical standards for nutrient management established by the Director. Such technical standards for nutrient management shall:_</p> <p>(i) Include a field-specific assessment of the potential for nitrogen and phosphorus transport from the field to surface waters, and address the form, source, amount, timing, and method of application of nutrients on each field to achieve realistic production goals, while minimizing nitrogen and phosphorus movement to surface waters; and_</p> <p>(ii) Include appropriate flexibilities for any CAFO to implement nutrient management practices to comply with the technical standards, including consideration of multi-year phosphorus application on fields that do not have a high potential for phosphorus runoff to surface water, phased implementation of</p>

phosphorus-based nutrient management, and other components, as determined appropriate by the Director._

[40 CFR 412.4]_

(1) Requirement to implement a nutrient management plan. Any permit issued to a CAFO must include a requirement to implement a nutrient management plan that, at a minimum, contains best management practices necessary to meet the requirements of this paragraph and applicable effluent limitations and standards, including those specified in 40 CFR part 412. The nutrient management plan must, to the extent applicable: _

(i) Ensure adequate storage of manure, litter, and process wastewater, including procedures to ensure proper operation and maintenance of the storage facilities; _

(ii) Ensure proper management of mortalities (i.e., dead animals) to ensure that they are not disposed of in a liquid manure, storm water, or process wastewater storage or treatment system that is not specifically designed to treat animal mortalities; _

(iii) Ensure that clean water is diverted, as appropriate, from the production area; _

(iv) Prevent direct contact of confined animals with waters of the United States; _

(v) Ensure that chemicals and other contaminants handled on-site are not disposed of in any manure, litter, process wastewater, or storm water storage or treatment system unless specifically designed to treat such chemicals and other contaminants; _

(vi) Identify appropriate site specific conservation practices to be implemented, including as appropriate buffers or equivalent practices, to control runoff of pollutants to waters of the United States; _

(vii) Identify protocols for appropriate testing of manure, litter, process wastewater, and soil; _

(viii) Establish protocols to land apply manure, litter or process wastewater in accordance with site specific nutrient management practices that ensure appropriate agricultural utilization of the nutrients in the manure, litter or process wastewater; and _

(ix) Identify specific records that will be maintained to document the implementation and management of the minimum elements described in paragraphs (e)(1)(i) through (e)(1)(viii) of this section. _

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(5) Terms of the nutrient management plan. Any permit issued to a CAFO must require compliance with the terms of the CAFO's site-specific nutrient management plan. The terms of the nutrient management plan are the information, protocols, best management practices, and other conditions in the nutrient management plan determined by the Director to be necessary to meet the requirements of paragraph (e)(1) of this section. The terms of the nutrient management plan, with respect to protocols for land application of manure, litter, or process wastewater required by

paragraph (e)(1)(viii) of this section and, as applicable, 40 CFR 412.4(c), must include the fields available for land application; field-specific rates of application properly developed, as specified in paragraphs (e)(5)(i) through (ii) of this section, to ensure appropriate agricultural utilization of the nutrients in the manure, litter, or process wastewater; and any timing limitations identified in the nutrient management plan concerning land application on the fields available for land application. The terms must address rates of application using one of the following two approaches, unless the Director specifies that only one of these approaches may be used: _

(i) Linear approach. An approach that expresses rates of application as pounds of nitrogen and phosphorus, according to the following specifications: _

(A) The terms include maximum application rates from manure, litter, and process wastewater for each year of permit coverage, for each crop identified in the nutrient management plan, in chemical forms determined to be acceptable to the Director, in pounds per acre, per year, for each field to be used for land application, and certain factors necessary to determine such rates. At a minimum, the factors that are terms must include: The outcome of the field-specific assessment of the potential for nitrogen and phosphorus transport from each field; the crops to be planted in each field or any other uses of a field such as pasture or fallow fields; the realistic yield goal for each crop or use identified for each field; the nitrogen and phosphorus recommendations from sources specified by the Director for each crop or use identified for each field; credits for all nitrogen in the field that will be plant available; consideration of multi-year phosphorus application; and accounting for all other additions of plant available nitrogen and phosphorus to the field. In addition, the terms include the form and source of manure, litter, and process wastewater to be land-applied; the timing and method of land application; and the methodology by which the nutrient management plan accounts for the amount of nitrogen and phosphorus in the manure, litter, and process wastewater to be applied. _

(B) Large CAFOs that use this approach must calculate the maximum amount of manure, litter, and process wastewater to be land applied at least once each year using the results of the most recent representative manure, litter, and process wastewater tests for nitrogen and phosphorus taken within 12 months of the date of land application; or _

(ii) Narrative rate approach. An approach that expresses rates of application as a narrative rate of application that results in the amount, in tons or gallons, of manure, litter, and process wastewater to be land applied, according to the following specifications: _

(A) The terms include maximum amounts of nitrogen and phosphorus derived from all sources of nutrients, for each crop

	<p>identified in the nutrient management plan, in chemical forms determined to be acceptable to the Director, in pounds per acre, for each field, and certain factors necessary to determine such amounts. At a minimum, the factors that are terms must include: the outcome of the field-specific assessment of the potential for nitrogen and phosphorus transport from each field; the crops to be planted in each field or any other uses such as pasture or fallow fields (including alternative crops identified in accordance with paragraph (e)(5)(ii)(B) of this section); the realistic yield goal for each crop or use identified for each field; and the nitrogen and phosphorus recommendations from sources specified by the Director for each crop or use identified for each field. In addition, the terms include the methodology by which the nutrient management plan accounts for the following factors when calculating the amounts of manure, litter, and process wastewater to be land applied: Results of soil tests conducted in accordance with protocols identified in the nutrient management plan, as required by paragraph (e)(1)(vii) of this section; credits for all nitrogen in the field that will be plant available; the amount of nitrogen and phosphorus in the manure, litter, and process wastewater to be applied; consideration of multi-year phosphorus application; accounting for all other additions of plant available nitrogen and phosphorus to the field; the form and source of manure, litter, and process wastewater; the timing and method of land application; and volatilization of nitrogen and mineralization of organic nitrogen._</p> <p>(B) The terms of the nutrient management plan include alternative crops identified in the CAFO's nutrient management plan that are not in the planned crop rotation. Where a CAFO includes alternative crops in its nutrient management plan, the crops must be listed by field, in addition to the crops identified in the planned crop rotation for that field, and the nutrient management plan must include realistic crop yield goals and the nitrogen and phosphorus recommendations from sources specified by the Director for each crop. Maximum amounts of nitrogen and phosphorus from all sources of nutrients and the amounts of manure, litter, and process wastewater to be applied must be determined in accordance with the methodology described in paragraph (e)(5)(ii)(A) of this section._</p> <p>(C) For CAFOs using this approach, the following projections must be included in the nutrient management plan submitted to the Director, but are not terms of the nutrient management plan: The CAFO's planned crop rotations for each field for the period of permit coverage; the projected amount of manure, litter, or process wastewater to be applied; projected credits for all nitrogen in the field that will be plant available; consideration of multi-year phosphorus application; accounting for all other additions of plant available nitrogen and phosphorus to the field; and the predicted form, source, and method of application of manure, litter, and</p>
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	<p>process wastewater for each crop. Timing of application for each field, insofar as it concerns the calculation of rates of application, is not a term of the nutrient management plan._</p> <p>(D) CAFOs that use this approach must calculate maximum amounts of manure, litter, and process wastewater to be land applied at least once each year using the methodology required in paragraph (e)(5)(ii)(A) of this section before land applying manure, litter, and process wastewater and must rely on the following data:_</p> <p>(1) A field-specific determination of soil levels of nitrogen and phosphorus, including, for nitrogen, a concurrent determination of nitrogen that will be plant available consistent with the methodology required by paragraph (e)(5)(ii)(A) of this section, and for phosphorus, the results of the most recent soil test conducted in accordance with soil testing requirements approved by the Director; and_</p> <p>(2) The results of most recent representative manure, litter, and process wastewater tests for nitrogen and phosphorus taken within 12 months of the date of land application, in order to determine the amount of nitrogen and phosphorus in the manure, litter, and process wastewater to be applied.</p>
<p>Do your NMP/MMPS follow, comply with, or based on NRCS Technical Standard 590?</p>	<p>Not Applicable</p>
<p>Application rates: <i>State regulations that restrict the rates at which manures are applied and methods needed to determine appropriate rates.</i></p>	<p>Determination of application rates. Application rates for manure, litter, and other process wastewater applied to land under the ownership or operational control of the CAFO must minimize phosphorus and nitrogen transport from the field to surface waters in compliance with the technical standards for nutrient management established by the Director. Such technical standards for nutrient management shall:_</p> <p>(i) Include a field-specific assessment of the potential for nitrogen and phosphorus transport from the field to surface waters, and address the form, source, amount, timing, and method of application of nutrients on each field to achieve realistic production goals, while minimizing nitrogen and phosphorus movement to surface waters; and_</p> <p>(ii) Include appropriate flexibilities for any CAFO to implement nutrient management practices to comply with the technical standards, including consideration of multi-year phosphorus application on fields that do not have a high potential for phosphorus runoff to surface water, phased implementation of phosphorus-based nutrient management, and other components, as determined appropriate by the Director._</p>
<p>Manure application rates for phosphorus are based on:</p>	<p>No method</p>

<p>1) <i>Phosphorus Index Only</i> 2) <i>Soil Test Phosphorus Only</i> 3) <i>Either PIO or STPO</i> 4) <i>Other</i></p>	
<p>Are there any nutrient “caps” to manure application?</p>	No
<p>Composition testing: <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on manures before application</i></p>	<p>Manure and soil sampling. Manure must be analyzed a minimum of once annually for nitrogen and phosphorus content, and soil analyzed a minimum of once every five years for phosphorus content. The results of these analyses are to be used in determining application rates for manure, litter, and other process wastewater.</p>
<p>Does your state require testing of manure for anything beyond nutrients, such as metals, pathogens, antibiotics, etc.?</p>	Not Applicable
<p>Other land application highlights: <i>Additional restrictions for land application of manures</i></p>	No other information
<p>Other regulatory details: <i>Additional information on the regulation of land application of manures</i></p>	No other information
General Assessment Questions	
<p>Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list regulatory details that may potentially change:</p>	Undetermined
<p>Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of manures that we haven’t captured? If yes, please describe or provide links:</p>	No
<p>Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties,</p>	No

watersheds) that regulate land application of manures beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so:	
Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.	No other information

Florida	
Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2019
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Florida Department of Environmental Protection
Links to regulations	Florida Administrative Code (FAC) Chapter 62-620.100(3)(r)-(w) _ https://www.flrules.org/gateway/ChapterHome.asp?Chapter=62-620 _ _ Chapter 62-670 Feedlot and Dairy Wastewater Treatment and Management Requirements. https://www.flrules.org/gateway/ChapterHome.asp?Chapter=62-670 _ 62-670.500 Requirements for Dairy Farms in the Lake Okeechobee Drainage Basin
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Environmental
Other regulator info	Florida has adopted the federal CAFO rule, but Florida's 1996 rule provides additional regulations for AFOs in the Lake Okeechobee Drainage Basin.
Definitions	
How CAFOs are defined or categorized:	"Concentrated Animal feeding Operation" - means a feeding operation where more animals are confined than are specified in the categories listed below. Any Animal Feeding Operation that contains process wastewater and runoff from the 25-year, 24-hour storm event, is not considered a concentrated Animal Feeding Operation regardless of the number of animals at the facility. (a) 1,000 slaughter and feeder cattle; (b) 700 mature dairy cattle (whether milked or dry cows), except that dairy farms located in the Lake Okeechobee Drainage Basin as defined in subsection 62-670.200(8), F.A.C., shall be regulated pursuant to Rule 62-670.500, F.A.C.; (c) 2,500 swine weighing over 55 pounds each; (d) 500 horses; (e) 10,000 sheep or lambs; (f) 55,000 turkeys; (g) 100,000 laying hens or broilers (if the facility has continuous overflow watering); (h) 30,000 laying hens or broilers (if the facility has a liquid manure handling system); (i) 5,000 ducks, or (j) 1,000 animals units. Same as 40 CFR in 62-620.100(3)(r)-(w).
How animal units are defined (if used):	Not used
NPDES permitting or other permitting requirements:	FDEP administers the National Pollutant Discharge Elimination System (NPDES) program. Florida Department of Agriculture and Consumer Services (FDACS) Office of Agricultural Water Policy develops and adopts best management practices (BMPs) focused on water quantity (water conservation) and water quality issues for the agricultural industry

Does the state require an NPDES permit for all Large CAFOs?	No
Does the state issue individual or general CAFO permits?	Undetermined
Are any other permits required for CAFOs or other large farms?	Undetermined
Other definitions needed to understand these regulations:	No other information
Regulatory Details	
Setbacks: <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some geographical feature</i>	Specific setbacks are determined for dairies within the Okeechobee Drainage Basin: Distance from land application areas (feet):_ Drinking water supply wells - 200 ft_ Natural water courses - 50 ft_ Drainage ditches - 50 ft_ – All other CAFOs follow 40 CFR.
Are setbacks more restrictive than CFR?	Undetermined
Timing, weather, or conditional application restrictions: <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather, seasons, or land characteristics (like slope)</i>	Refer to 40 CFR
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to saturated soils?	No
Is there a restriction for land application of manure within floodplains?	No
Is there a restriction for land application of manure related to future rainfall?	No
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to frozen or snow-covered ground?	No
Are there restrictions to manure applications based	No

on time of year or time of day?	
Are there restrictions to manure application based on slope?	No
Are there any other seasonal, timing, weather, or physical restrictions to manure applications not captured above?	Undetermined
Transfer of manure off-site: <i>Requirements related to the transfer of manures to other persons</i>	Refer to 40 CFR
Are receivers of manure transfers from CAFOs required to follow the same regulations?	No
Nutrient or manure management plans: <i>Additional details on the NMP requirement. Note that some of this information may overlap with other sections</i>	Florida adopted federal requirements for NMPs: All CAFOs must develop and implement a nutrient management plan (NMP) that includes BMPs and procedures necessary to meet applicable effluent limitations and standards.
Do your NMP/MMPS follow, comply with, or based on NRCS Technical Standard 590?	Not Applicable
Application rates: <i>State regulations that restrict the rates at which manures are applied and methods needed to determine appropriate rates.</i>	<p>Dairy farms within the Okeechobee Drainage Basin that land apply wastes (solids, sludge, runoff and wastewater) are required to maximize water quality benefits derived from plant uptake of nutrients and must meet the following requirements: _</p> <p>Land Application. Land application of all wastes (solids, sludge, runoff and wastewater) shall be managed to maximize water quality benefits derived from plant uptake of nutrients. _</p> <p>1. The nutrient content of all wastes shall be determined at least quarterly before spreading and the wastewater and runoff shall be applied to meet nutrient requirements of the crops. If the nutrient analyses show consistent results, the frequency of the analysis may be reduced. The degree of consistency required and the specific changes in the frequency of analysis shall be specified in the permit. _</p> <p>2. All sources of nutrients applied shall not exceed the annual nutrient requirements of the grasses or crops in the area. _</p> <p>3. The water table shall be eighteen (18) inches or deeper below the normal ground surface when wastes are applied to the land. _</p>

	<p>4. Irrigation with wastewater and runoff shall be managed so that no irrigation water is discharged to the surface waters of the state._</p> <p>5. The frequency and rate of land application shall be managed to avoid secondary environmental problems such as severe odors, insect and pest problems, and other nuisance conditions. If wastes are to be disposed of on property not owned by the permittee, evidence of an appropriate lease or contract shall be provided for inclusion in the management plan._</p> <p>(e) Alternative to Land Application. As an alternative to land application, the Department may consider other methods of treatment and disposal of barn wastewater and runoff from high intensity areas. Limits for such treatment or disposal methods will be based on applicable Department rules._</p> <p>–</p> <p>All other CAFOs follow 40 CFR.</p>
<p>Manure application rates for phosphorus are based on:</p> <p>1) <i>Phosphorus Index Only</i></p> <p>2) <i>Soil Test Phosphorus Only</i></p> <p>3) <i>Either PIO or STPO</i></p> <p>4) <i>Other</i></p>	No method
<p>Are there any nutrient “caps” to manure application?</p>	No
<p>Composition testing: <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on manures before application</i></p>	<p>Specific to Okeechobee Drainage Basin: The nutrient content of all wastes shall be determined at least quarterly before spreading and the wastewater and runoff shall be applied to meet nutrient requirements of the crops. If the nutrient analyses show consistent results, the frequency of the analysis may be reduced. The degree of consistency required and the specific changes in the frequency of analysis shall be specified in the permit. _</p> <p>–</p> <p>All other CAFOs follow 40 CFR</p>
<p>Does your state require testing of manure for anything beyond nutrients, such as metals, pathogens, antibiotics, etc.?</p>	Not Applicable
<p>Other land application highlights: <i>Additional restrictions for land application of manures</i></p>	No other information
<p>Other regulatory details:</p>	No other information

<p><i>Additional information on the regulation of land application of manures</i></p>	
General Assessment Questions	
<p>Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change:</p>	<p>Undetermined</p>
<p>Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of manures that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links:</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of manures beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so:</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.</p>	<p>No other information</p>

Georgia Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2019
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Georgia Department of Natural Resources, Environmental Protection Division (EPD)
Links to regulations	<p>391-3-6. Waste Treatment and Permit Requirements._ http://rules.sos.state.ga.us/GAC/391-3-6 _</p> <p>_</p> <p>Rule 391-3-6-.20 Swine Feeding Operation Permit Requirements For Operations With More Than 3000 Animal Units_</p> <p>_</p> <p>Rule 391-3-6-.21 Animal Feeding Operation Permit Requirements_</p> <p>_</p> <p>GA Reg. 391-3-6-.19 General Permit - LAS Requirements_ http://rules.sos.ga.gov/gac/391-3-6</p>
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Natural Resources
Other regulator info	No other information
Definitions	
How CAFOs are defined or categorized:	"Concentrated Animal Feeding Operation," or "CAFO," means an AFO which is defined as a Large CAFO or Medium CAFO by 40 CFR 122.23(4) and (6), or that is designated as a CAFO.
How animal units are defined (if used):	<p>"Animal Unit" (AU) is a unit of measurement for any AFO calculated by adding the following numbers: the number of slaughter and feeder cattle multiplied by 1.0, plus the number of mature dairy cattle multiplied by 1.4, plus the number of swine weighing over 25 kilograms (approximately 55 pounds) multiplied by 0.4, plus the number of sheep multiplied by 0.1, plus the number of horses multiplied by 2.0._</p> <p>_</p> <p>"300 AU" means three hundred animal units. Paragraph 391-3-6-.21 (2) (c) notwithstanding, the numbers of animals in any of the following categories are equivalent to 300 AU: 200 mature dairy cows, whether milked or dry, 300 veal calves, 750 swine each weighing 55 pounds or more. 300 cattle other than mature dairy cows or veal calves. Cattle includes but is not limited to heifers, steers, bulls, and cow/calf pairs, 150 horses, 3,000 sheep or lambs, 16,500 turkeys, 9,000 laying hens or broilers, if the AFO uses a liquid manure handling system, 1,500 ducks, if the AFO uses a liquid manure handling system._</p> <p>_</p> <p>"1000 AU" means one thousand animal units. Paragraph 391-3-6-.21 (2) (c) notwithstanding, the numbers of animals in any of the following categories are equivalent to 1000 AU: 700 mature dairy cows, whether milked or dry, 1,000 veal calves, 2,500 swine each</p>

	<p>weighing 55 pounds or more, 10,000 swine each weighing less than 55 pounds (immature swine or nursery pigs), 1,000 cattle other than mature dairy cows or veal calves. Cattle includes but is not limited to heifers, steers, bulls, and cow/calf pairs, 500 horses, 10,000 sheep or lambs, 55,000 turkeys, 30,000 laying hens or broilers, if the AFO uses a liquid manure handling system, 125,000 chickens or broilers (other than laying hens), if the AFO handles dry manure only, 82,000 laying hens, if the AFO handles dry manure only, 30,000 ducks, if the AFO handles dry manure only, 5,000 ducks, if the AFO uses a liquid manure handling system.</p> <p>–</p> <p>"3000 AU" means three thousand animal units. Paragraph 391-3-6-.21 (2) (c) notwithstanding, the numbers of swine in any of the following categories are equivalent to 3000 AU: 7,500 swine each weighing 55 pounds or more, 30,000 swine each weighing less than 55 pounds (immature swine or nursery pigs).</p>
NPDES permitting or other permitting requirements:	Any person who is the owner of an AFO with more than 300 AU and uses liquid manure handling must apply for an LAS permit from the Division. The Division may issue an individual or general permit. Any person who is the owner of an AFO is not required to obtain an NPDES permit unless the AFO is defined as a CAFO per 40 CFR 122 and discharges to a water of the State excluding subsurface water (groundwater), or the Division has made a case-by-case designation as a CAFO and NPDES permitting is required for discharges to a water of the State excluding subsurface water (groundwater) by 40 CFR 122.23. Georgia has a General NPDES CAFO permit as well as two General State Permits (Land Application System), one for medium operations and one for large operations.
Does the state require an NPDES permit for all Large CAFOs?	No
Does the state issue individual or general CAFO permits?	Both
Are any other permits required for CAFOs or other large farms?	No
Other definitions needed to understand these regulations:	No other information
Regulatory Details	
Setbacks: <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land</i>	<p>New barns and new waste storage lagoons or structures for all new AFOs shall not be located within a 100-year flood plain.</p> <p>–</p> <p>For new operations with more than 1000 AU, it is required that a minimum of 1 foot of freeboard plus storage for the 25 year 24 hour</p>

<p><i>application and some geographical feature</i></p>	<p>storm event be maintained in the waste storage lagoons or structures. The liquid level must not rise into this design storage level for lesser storms._</p> <p>The following buffers and setbacks shall be maintained: 100 feet between wetted areas and water wells that supply water for human consumption; 100 feet between waste storage lagoons, waste storage structures, or barns and waters of the State excluding subsurface water; 500 feet between waste storage lagoons, waste storage structures, or barns and any existing wells that supply water to a public water system, or any other existing well off the owner's property that supplies water for human consumption._</p> <p>–</p> <p>For all operations with more than 1000 AU, a setback shall be maintained of 100 feet between wetted areas or waste disposal areas and waters of the State excluding subsurface water (ground water). As a compliance alternative, the owner may substitute the 100 feet setback with a 35 feet wide vegetated buffer where waste disposal is prohibited._</p> <p>The following buffers shall be maintained: 750 feet between disposal area and any residence or places of public assembly under separate ownership, 200 feet between disposal area and property lines, 200 feet between disposal area and water wells, 150 feet between disposal area and drainage ditches, surface water bodies, or wetlands, 1,750 feet between waste storage lagoons, structures, or barns and any occupied residence, 1,750 feet between waste storage lagoons, structures, or barns and any public use area, church, picnic area, playground, school, hospital, outdoor recreational facility, national park, state park, historic property or child care center, 1,750 feet between waste storage lagoons, structures, or barns and any property boundary, 1,750 feet between waste storage lagoons, structures, or barns and any wells that supply water to a public water system, or any other well that supplies water for human consumption, and 2,640 feet between waste storage lagoons, structures, or barns and waters of the State (not including ephemeral and intermittent streams)._</p> <p>–</p> <p>Swine Feeding Operations with more than 3000 AU:_</p> <p>The following buffers shall be maintained:750 feet between disposal area and any residence or places of public assembly under separate ownership, 200 feet between disposal area and property lines, 200 feet between disposal area and water wells, 150 feet between disposal area and drainage ditches, surface water bodies, or wetlands, 1,750 feet between waste storage lagoons, structures, or barns and any occupied residence, 1,750 feet between waste storage lagoons, structures, or barns and any public use area, church, picnic area, playground, school, hospital, outdoor recreational facility, national park, state park, historic property or child care center, 1,750 feet between waste storage lagoons,</p>
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	structures, or barns and any property boundary, 1,750 feet between waste storage lagoons, structures, or barns and any wells that supply water to a public water system, or any other well that supplies water for human consumption, and 2,640 feet between waste storage lagoons, structures, or barns and waters of the State (not including ephemeral and intermittent streams).
Are setbacks more restrictive than CFR?	No
Timing, weather, or conditional application restrictions: <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather, seasons, or land characteristics (like slope)</i>	None
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to saturated soils?	No
Is there a restriction for land application of manure within floodplains?	No
Is there a restriction for land application of manure related to future rainfall?	No
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to frozen or snow-covered ground?	No
Are there restrictions to manure applications based on time of year or time of day?	No
Are there restrictions to manure application based on slope?	No
Are there any other seasonal, timing, weather, or physical restrictions to manure applications not captured above?	Undetermined
Transfer of manure off-site: <i>Requirements related to the transfer of manures to other persons</i>	Any person who removes and transports animal waste from its point of origin shall conform to the animal manure handler rules of the Georgia Department of Agriculture._ Animal Manure Handlers Rule 40-13-8.

Are receivers of manure transfers from CAFOs required to follow the same regulations?	Undetermined
Nutrient or manure management plans: <i>Additional details on the NMP requirement. Note that some of this information may overlap with other sections</i>	Nutrient Management Plan: The NMP should address activities related to compliance with effluent limitations and other permit requirements, including manure handling and storage, land application of manure and wastewater, site management, record keeping, and management of other utilization options. For an AFO with a liquid manure handling system, the NMP must be developed or modified by a "certified specialist" as defined by the Division. The Division will specify the requirements for certification. For an AFO that handles dry manure, the NMP must be developed by a person trained in the subject by an academic or trade organization. It should include emergency response planning and a closure plan for abandonment of any facility used for the treatment or storage of animal waste._
Do your NMP/MMPS follow, comply with, or based on NRCS Technical Standard 590?	No
Application rates: <i>State regulations that restrict the rates at which manures are applied and methods needed to determine appropriate rates.</i>	Refer to 40 CFR
Manure application rates for phosphorus are based on: 1) Phosphorus Index Only 2) Soil Test Phosphorus Only 3) Either PIO or STPO 4) Other	No method
Are there any nutrient "caps" to manure application?	No
Composition testing: <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on manures before application</i>	For all operations with more than 1000 AU, the permit will contain specific requirements for monitoring the waste storage effluent to be land applied and for the ground water monitoring wells. This will usually consist, at a minimum, of semiannual monitoring of the effluent for Total Kjeldahl Nitrogen (TKN), Nitrate Nitrogen (NO ₃ -N) and Total Phosphorus (TP) as well as semiannual monitoring of the wells for TKN and NO ₃ - N

Does your state require testing of manure for anything beyond nutrients, such as metals, pathogens, antibiotics, etc.?	No
Other land application highlights: <i>Additional restrictions for land application of manures</i>	No other information
Other regulatory details: <i>Additional information on the regulation of land application of manures</i>	No other information
General Assessment Questions	
Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change:	Undetermined
Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of manures that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links:	Yes
Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of manures beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so:	No
Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.	No other information

Hawaii	
Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2019
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Environmental Management Division of the Hawaii State Department of Health
Links to regulations	DH Standard NPDES Permit Conditions_ http://health.hawaii.gov/cwb/files/2013/05/stdcond15.pdf _ OR_ http://health.hawaii.gov/cwb/clean-water-branch-home-page/standard-npdes-permit-conditions/
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Other
Other regulator info	No other information
Definitions	
How CAFOs are defined or categorized:	Refer to 40 CFR
How animal units are defined (if used):	Not used
NPDES permitting or other permitting requirements:	EPA's Pacific Southwest (Region 9) issues all NPDES permits for any discharges into federal ocean waters in Hawaii. All other NPDES permits are issued by the Hawaii Department of Health. Hawaii only issues NPDES permits to CAFOs that discharge.
Does the state require an NPDES permit for all Large CAFOs?	No
Does the state issue individual or general CAFO permits?	Undetermined
Are any other permits required for CAFOs or other large farms?	Undetermined
Other definitions needed to understand these regulations:	No other information
Regulatory Details	
Setbacks: <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some geographical feature</i>	Refer to 40 CFR
Are setbacks more restrictive than CFR?	No
Timing, weather, or	None

conditional application restrictions: <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather, seasons, or land characteristics (like slope)</i>	
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to saturated soils?	No
Is there a restriction for land application of manure within floodplains?	No
Is there a restriction for land application of manure related to future rainfall?	No
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to frozen or snow-covered ground?	No
Are there restrictions to manure applications based on time of year or time of day?	No
Are there restrictions to manure application based on slope?	No
Are there any other seasonal, timing, weather, or physical restrictions to manure applications not captured above?	No
Transfer of manure off-site: <i>Requirements related to the transfer of manures to other persons</i>	Refer to 40 CFR
Are receivers of manure transfers from CAFOs required to follow the same regulations?	No
Nutrient or manure management plans: <i>Additional details on the NMP requirement. Note that some of this</i>	Nutrient management requirements and technical standards for concentrated Animal Feeding Operations in 40 CFR §123.36, 40 CFR §122.42, and 40 CFR Part 412

<i>information may overlap with other sections</i>	
Do your NMP/MMPS follow, comply with, or based on NRCS Technical Standard 590?	Not Applicable
Application rates: <i>State regulations that restrict the rates at which manures are applied and methods needed to determine appropriate rates.</i>	Refer to 40 CFR
Manure application rates for phosphorus are based on: 1) <i>Phosphorus Index Only</i> 2) <i>Soil Test Phosphorus Only</i> 3) <i>Either PIO or STPO</i> 4) <i>Other</i>	No method
Are there any nutrient “caps” to manure application?	No
Composition testing: <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on manures before application</i>	Refer to 40 CFR
Does your state require testing of manure for anything beyond nutrients, such as metals, pathogens, antibiotics, etc.?	Not Applicable
Other land application highlights: <i>Additional restrictions for land application of manures</i>	No other information
Other regulatory details: <i>Additional information on the regulation of land application of manures</i>	No other information
General Assessment Questions	
Do you anticipate	Undetermined

<p>changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change:</p>	
<p>Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of manures that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links:</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of manures beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so:</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.</p>	<p>No other information</p>

Idaho Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2019
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Idaho Department of Environmental Quality (IDEQ)_ Idaho State Department of Agriculture (ISDA)_ US Environmental Protection Agency (USEPA)_
Links to regulations	Links to CAFO rules, regs, and information_ https://www2.deq.idaho.gov/water/swpag/?type=activity&id=84&scategory=2&acategory=#scrollTo _ - 02.04.32 - Rules Governing Poultry Operations_ https://adminrules.idaho.gov/rules/current/02/020432.pdf _ - NRCS 590 - IDAHO - Nutrient Management_ https://www.nrcs.usda.gov/sites/default/files/2022-09/E590C%20-%20Improving%20nutrient%20uptake%20efficiency%20and%20reducing%20risk%20of%20nutrient%20losses%20on%20pasture.pdf _ Authorization to Discharge under NPDES for CAFOS - Idaho_ https://www.epa.gov/npdes-permits/npdes-general-permit-concentrated-animal-feeding-operations-cafos-idaho _ - 02.04.15 - Rules Governing Beef Cattle Animal Feeding Operations_ https://adminrules.idaho.gov/rules/2007/02/0415.pdf _ - 02.04.14 - Rules of the Dept. of Ag. Governing Dairy Waste_ https://adminrules.idaho.gov/rules/2000/02/0414.pdf
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	More than one agency
Other regulator info	No other information
Definitions	
How	Animal Feeding Operation. A lot or facility where the following conditions are met: _

<p>CAFOs are defined or categorized:</p>	<p>a. Poultry have been, are, or will be confined and fed or maintained for a total of forty-five (45) days or more in any twelve-month period; and _</p> <p>b. Crops, vegetation, forage growth or post-harvest residues are not sustained in the normal growing season over any portion of the lot or facility._</p> <p>[Poultry]_</p> <p>Large Poultry CAFO. A poultry AFO that confines as many or more than the number of poultry specified in the following categories: _</p> <p>a. Fifty-five thousand (55,000) turkeys; _</p> <p>b. Thirty thousand (30,000) laying hens or broilers, if the AFO uses a liquid manure handling system;_</p> <p>c. One hundred twenty-five thousand (125,000) chickens, other than laying hens, if the AFO uses other than a liquid manure handling system; _</p> <p>d. Eighty-two thousand (82,000) laying hens, if the AFO uses other than a liquid manure handling system; _</p> <p>e. Thirty thousand (30,000) ducks, if the AFO uses other than a liquid manure handling system; or_</p> <p>f. Five thousand (5,000) ducks, if the AFO uses a liquid manure handling system. _</p> <p>Medium Poultry CAFO. A poultry AFO that confines as many or more than the number of poultry specified in the following categories: _</p> <p>a. Sixteen thousand five hundred (16,500) to fifty-four thousand nine hundred ninety-nine (54,999) turkeys;_</p> <p>b. Nine thousand (9,000) to twenty-nine thousand nine hundred ninety-nine (29,999) laying hens or broilers, if the AFO uses a liquid manure handling system; _</p> <p>c. Thirty-seven thousand five hundred (37,500) to one hundred twenty-four thousand nine hundred ninety-nine (124,999) chickens, other than laying hens, if the AFO uses other than a liquid manure handling system._</p> <p>d. Twenty-five thousand (25,000) to eighty-one thousand nine hundred ninety-nine (81,999) laying hens, if the AFO uses other than a liquid manure handling system; _</p> <p>e. Ten thousand (10,000) to twenty-nine thousand nine hundred ninety-nine (29,999) ducks, if the AFO uses other than a liquid manure handling system;_</p> <p>f. One thousand five hundred (1,500) to four thousand nine hundred ninety-nine (4,999) ducks, if the AFO uses a liquid manure handling system;_</p> <p>_</p> <p>Designation of Animal Feeding Operations. The director may designate any poultry AFO as a CAFO if, after inspection, the director determines that the AFO is a significant contributor of pollution to waters of the state. The director will consider the following factors when making a designation: _</p> <p>a. The size of the AFO and the amount of manure, process wastewater and runoff reaching waters of the state; b. Location of the AFO relative to waters of the state; c. Means of conveyance of manure, process wastewater, and runoff into waters of the state; d. Slope, vegetation, precipitation and other factors that affect the likelihood or frequency of discharge of manure, process wastewater and runoff into waters of the state; e. Unauthorized discharges into waters of the state through a man-made ditch, flushing system, or other similar man-made device; f. Unauthorized discharges directly into waters of the state that originate outside of and pass over, across or through the facility or otherwise come into contact with the animals confined in the AFO; and g. Repeated instances of noncompliance._</p> <p>_</p>
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	<p>[Beef]_ Beef Cattle Animal Feeding Operation. An Animal Feeding Operation, as defined in 40 CFR Sections 122.23 (b)(1), (b)(2), (b)(4), (b)(6) or (b)(9), which confines slaughter and feeder cattle or dairy heifers._</p> <p>_ Designation of [Beef Cattle] Animal Feeding Operations. The Director, on a case by case basis, may designate any Animal Feeding Operation that confines slaughter and feeder cattle as a beef cattle Animal Feeding Operation if, after an inspection, the Director determines that the Animal Feeding Operation is a significant contributor of pollution to waters of the state. The designation shall be provided to the operator of the Animal Feeding Operation in writing setting forth the basis for the Director's decision. When designated, these operations shall be considered existing beef cattle Animal Feeding Operations. The Director shall consider the following factors when making such designation: a. Size of the Animal Feeding Operation and the amount of manure, process wastewater, and runoff reaching waters of the state; b. Location of the Animal Feeding Operation relative to waters of the state; c. Means of conveyance of manure, process wastewater, and runoff into waters of the state; and d. Slope, vegetation, precipitation, and other factors affecting the likelihood or frequency of discharge of manure, process wastewater, or runoff into waters of the state.</p>
<p>How animal units are defined (if used):</p>	<p>Not used</p>
<p>NPDES permitting or other permitting requirements:</p>	<p>In Idaho, the NPDES permit program is administered by EPA, which means EPA is responsible for issuing and enforcing all NPDES permits in Idaho. EPA has issued a general NPDES permit for CAFOs in Idaho._</p> <p>_ Idaho's Rules Governing Beef Cattle Animal Feeding Operations (IDAPA 02.04.15) require beef cattle animal-feeding operations to have wastewater storage and confinement facilities to control runoff and nutrient management plans to manage land application of nutrients or soil amendments. The rules are administered by ISDA and also give ISDA inspection and enforcement authority._</p> <p>_ Rules of the Department of Agriculture Governing Dairy Waste (IDAPA 02.04.14) require dairies to have an approved dairy waste system in plan and to obtain a permit or farm certification from ISDA. In addition, the rules authorize ISDA to conduct inspections and enforcement actions._</p> <p>_ DEQ is authorized to regulate swine facilities to ensure animal waste is properly controlled so as not to adversely affect public health or the environment. New or expanding swine facilities having a one-time animal unit capacity of 2,000 or more animal units must be permitted whether or not the capacity is currently being met. No such facilities are currently located in Idaho._</p> <p>_ A poultry facility is considered a Confined Animal Feeding Operation (CAFO) if it is captively raising a large number of birds. These facilities are regulated under IDAPA 02.04.32 Rules Governing Poultry Operations-2 and require a permit issued by the</p>

	Idaho State Department of Agriculture (ISDA).
Does the state require an NPDES permit for all Large CAFOs?	No
Does the state issue individual or general CAFO permits?	Undetermined
Are any other permits required for CAFOs or other large farms?	Undetermined
Other definitions needed to understand these regulations:	No other information
Regulatory Details	
Setbacks : <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between</i>	Refer to 40 CFR_ Land application setback requirements. Manure, litter, or process wastewater must not be applied closer than 100 feet to any down-gradient water of the United States, open tile line intake structures, sinkholes, agricultural well heads, or other conduits to waters of the United States. The permittee may elect to use a 35-foot vegetated buffer where applications of manure, litter, or process wastewater are prohibited as an alternative to the 100-foot setback to meet this requirement. As an alternative, the permittee may demonstrate to the permitting authority that the use of an alternative practice will result in equivalent or better pollutant reductions than would be achieved by the use of the 100-foot setback_ The NMP require identifying appropriate site specific conservation practices to be

<p><i>the site of land application and some geographical feature</i></p>	<p>implemented, including as appropriate buffers or equivalent practices, to control runoff of pollutants to waters of the United States and specifically, to minimize the runoff of nitrogen and phosphorus. These practices may include, but are not limited to, residue management, conservation crop rotation, grassed waterways, strip cropping, vegetated buffers, riparian buffers, setbacks, terracing, and diversions.</p>
<p>Are setbacks more restrictive than CFR?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Timing, weather, or conditional application restrictions: <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather, seasons, or land characteristics (like slope)</i></p>	<p>Nutrients shall not be applied to frozen, snow-covered or saturated soil if the potential risk for runoff exists._ _ Winter application of solids on 0 -“ 2% slope fields can be considered if there is no potential for runoff._ _ Fall and winter application of solid wastes on shallow and/or sandy soils should be made when soil temperatures are <50 o F to minimize loss of nitrogen._ _ Application of liquid wastes through surface or sprinkler irrigation systems will be timed to prevent deep percolation or runoff. The application rate (in/hr) of liquids shall not exceed the soil intake/infiltration rate and shall be adjusted to minimize ponding and to avoid runoff. The total application volume shall not exceed the soil water holding capacity of the soil and shall be adjusted, as needed, to minimize nutrient loss below the root zone.</p>
<p>Is there a restriction for land application of manure to saturated soils?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Is there a</p>	<p>No</p>

restriction for land application of manure within floodplains?	
Is there a restriction for land application of manure related to future rainfall?	No
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to frozen or snow-covered ground?	Yes
Are there restrictions to manure applications based on time of year or time of day?	Yes
Are there restrictions to manure application based on slope?	Yes
Are there any other seasonal,	Undetermined

<p>timing, weather, or physical restrictions to manure applications not captured above?</p>	
<p>Transfer of manure off-site: <i>Requirements related to the transfer of manures to other persons</i></p>	<p>The name and address of any third party receiving manure or process wastewater from the facility, including the dates of the transfer and the amount of manure or process wastewater transferred must be kept on record.</p>
<p>Are receivers of manure transfers from CAFOs required to follow the same regulations?</p>	<p>Undetermined</p>
<p>Nutrient or manure management plans: <i>Additional details on the NMP requirement. Note</i></p>	<p>[General] A Nutrient Management Plan (NMP) for nitrogen (N), phosphorus (P) and potassium (K) shall be developed when nutrients are applied. NMPs shall be developed in accordance with policy requirements of the Natural Resources Conservation Service (NRCS) General Manual Title 450, Part 401.03 (Technical Guides, Policy and Responsibilities) and Title 190, Part 402 (Ecological Sciences, Nutrient Management, Policy); technical requirements of the Idaho NRCS Field Office Technical Guide (FOTG); procedures contained in the National Planning Procedures Handbook (NPPH) and the NRCS National Agronomy Manual (NAM), Section 503.</p> <p>[Poultry] Nutrient Management Plan. NMPs must be prepared in conformance with the Nutrient Management Standard or other equally protective standard for managing the</p>

<p><i>that some of this information may overlap with other sections</i></p>	<p>amount, source, placement, form and timing of the land application of nutrients or soil amendments._ – Nutrient management plans must be amended in accordance with IDAPA 02.04.30.000 et seq. Rules Governing Nutrient Management.-²</p>
<p>Do your NMP/MMPS follow, comply with, or based on NRCS Technical Standard 590?</p>	<p>Undetermined</p>
<p>Application rates: <i>State regulations that restrict the rates at which manures are applied and methods needed to determine appropriate rates.</i></p>	<p>[General from Code 590]_ Soil Sampling and Laboratory Analyses (Testing). Soil samples shall be collected and prepared such that they are representative of the entire Conservation Management Unit (CMU), field or portion of the field to be managed separately. Requirements for soil sampling shall follow the specifications outlined in the UI publication Soil Sampling² (CES Number 704_ http://info.ag.uidaho.edu/resources/pdfs/ext0704.pdf) or crop-specific soil sampling requirements outlined in the UI Fertilizer Recommendations_ (http://info.ag.uidaho.edu:591/catalog/fertilizers.html)._ – Laboratory analysis shall include the components:_ * Northern Idaho (0-12 inches): NO3-N, NH4-N, P, K, pH, %SOM, EC every 9 months_ * Northern Idaho (12-24 inches): NO3-N every 9 months_ * Southern Idaho (0-12 inches): NO3-N, NH4-N every 3 months, P, K, pH, %SOM, %free lime, EC every 9 months_ * Southern Idaho (12-24 inches): NO3-N, NH4-N every 3 months_ – Soil samples will be analyzed for P using the test methods specified in the_ applicable UI Fertilizer Guides or other UI production publications containing nutrient guidelines._ – Nutrient Application Rates. The planned rates of nutrient application, as documented in the nutrient budget, shall be applied to meet the crop needs except when manure or organic byproducts are a source of nutrients. _ In addition to previously detailed criteria, manure and organic by-product_ application methods shall be selected to minimize the risk of nutrient transport to surface and ground water, into the atmosphere and to reduce_</p>

negative impacts on plant health. NMPs that address land application of animal waste shall comply with the Idaho Waste Management Guidelines for Confined Animal Feeding Operations (CAFOs), 1993, amended 1997 and other applicable Federal, State and local rules and regulations._

–
Nutrient Application Timing. Timing and method of nutrient application (particularly nitrogen) shall correspond as closely as possible with plant nutrient uptake characteristics while considering cropping system limitations, weather and climatic conditions, risk analysis and field accessibility._

–
Nutrient Application Methods. Application methods to reduce the risk of nutrient transport to surface and ground water or into the atmosphere_ shall be employed. To minimize nutrient losses:_

- * Apply nutrient materials uniformly to application area(s). Nutrients shall not be applied to frozen, snow-covered or saturated soil if the potential risk for runoff exists._
- * Nutrients shall be applied considering the plant growth habits, irrigation practices and other conditions so as to maximize availability to the plant and minimize the risk of runoff, leaching and volatilization losses._
- * Calibrate waste and fertilizer application equipment to ensure recommended rates are applied._

–
Application of Solid Wastes. Solid waste shall be incorporated into the soil unless applications are made on frozen ground, perennial crops or cropland under no-till. In these cases, emergency tillage (i.e., chiseling and disking cross slope), construction of berms or other containment practices will be applied as necessary to prevent surface runoff._

–
Application of Liquid Wastes. For purposes of this standard, animal waste containing less than 10% solids will be classified as a liquid. Application of liquid waste shall not be made outside the active crop growing period unless a_ site-specific water budget shows that deep percolation of wastewater or runoff will not occur prior to the next crop-growing season._

–
Manure and Organic By-Product Nutrient Application Rates. Nutrient budgets which include application of animal waste shall be based upon the NRCS Idaho Phosphorus Threshold (IDPTH)._

–
Where phosphorus-based applications are made, the application rate shall:_

- * Not exceed the recommended nitrogen application rate for the current crop during the year of application, and_
- * Not be made on sites considered vulnerable to off-site phosphorus transport unless appropriate conservation practices, best management practices or management activities are used to reduce the vulnerability._

–
Nitrogen-based manure applications are allowed on sites where the soil test phosphorus levels are below the IDPTH. The nitrogen availability of the planned application shall match plant uptake characteristics as closely as possible, taking into consideration the timing of nutrient application(s) in order to minimize leaching and

	<p>atmospheric losses. Management activities and technologies shall be used that effectively utilize mineralized nitrogen_ and minimize nitrogen losses through denitrification and ammonia volatilization._</p> <p>–</p> <p>[Poultry] Soil tests must be conducted annually on all land application sites owned or leased by the permittee to determine compliance with the NMP and NMS. The director may require more frequent soil tests if he deems it necessary.</p>
<p>Manure application rates for phosphorus are based on:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) <i>Phosphorus Index Only</i> 2) <i>Soil Test Phosphorus Only</i> 3) <i>Either PIO or STPO</i> 4) <i>Other</i> 	<p>Phosphorus index only</p>
<p>Are there any nutrient “caps” to manure application?</p>	<p>Undetermined</p>
<p>Composition testing: <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed</i></p>	<p>Manure Testing. Nutrient values of manure and organic by-products shall be determined prior to land application. Samples will be taken and analyzed with each hauling/emptying cycle for a particular storage/treatment facility. Manure sampling frequency may vary based on the operation's manure handling strategy and spreading schedule. If there is no prior sampling history, the manure shall be analyzed at least annually for a minimum of three consecutive years. A cumulative record shall be developed and maintained until a consistent (i.e., maintaining a certain nutrient concentration with minimal variation) level of nutrient values is realized. Significant changes in feed P ration or manure storage and handling procedures will require additional manure sampling. Samples shall be collected and prepared according to UI Manure and Wastewater Sampling-guidance (CIS 1139)_ http://info.ag.uidaho.edu/pdf/CIS/CIS1139.pdf _</p> <p>–</p> <p>At a minimum, manure analyses shall identify total N, P₂O₅ and K₂O in pounds per ton</p>

<i>d on manures before application</i>	for solids and pounds per 1,000 gallons for liquids. Percent moisture for solids and percent solids for liquids will also be identified. In planning for new operations, acceptable book values-recognized by the Idaho NRCS and/or the University of Idaho may be used (e.g., NRCS Agricultural Waste Management Field Handbook).
Does your state require testing of manure for anything beyond nutrients, such as metals, pathogens, antibiotics, etc.?	Undetermined
Other land application highlights : <i>Additional restrictions for land application of manures</i>	The Idaho NRCS Nutrient Management Conservation Practice Standard (Code 590) has additional recommended practices to those described.
Other regulatory details: <i>Additional information on the regulation of land application of manures</i>	No other information
General Assessment Questions	
Do you	

<p>anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change:</p>	<p>Undetermined</p>
<p>Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of manures that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links:</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate</p>	<p>No</p>

<p>land application of manures beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so:</p>	
<p>Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.</p>	<p>No other information</p>

Illinois Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2019
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Illinois Environmental Protection Agency (IEPA)
Links to regulations	IL Rules and Regulations Page_ http://www.ilga.gov/default.asp _ _ Title 35, Subtitle E, Chapter 1_ ftp://www.ilga.gov/JCAR/AdminCode/035/03500502sections.html
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Environmental
Other regulator info	No other information
Definitions	
How CAFOs are defined or categorized:	<p>A "Large" CAFO if your operation has at least:_</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * 700 mature dairy cows_ * 1,000 veal calves_ * 1,000 beef cattle or heifers_ * 500 horses_ * 2,500 swine (each 55 lbs. or more)_ * 10,000 swine (each under 55 lbs.)_ * 10,000 sheep or lambs_ * 55,000 turkeys_ * 30,000 ducks (other than liquid manure handling systems)_ * 5,000 ducks (liquid manure handling systems)_ * 30,000 chickens (liquid manure handling systems)_ * 125,000 chickens except laying hens (other than liquid manure handling systems)_ * 82,000 laying hens (other than liquid manure handling systems)_ <p>You are a "Medium" CAFO if you have:_</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * A man-made ditch or pipe carrying manure or wastewater from your operation to surface waters; OR_ * Animals in contact with surface water in the areas in which they are confined._ <p>and_</p> <p>A "Medium" CAFO must also have between:_</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * 200 - 699 mature dairy cows_ * 300 - 999 veal calves_ * 300 - 999 beef cattle or heifers_ * 150 - 499 horses_ * 750 - 2,499 swine (each 55 lbs. or more)_ * 3,000 - 9,999 swine (each under 55 lbs.)_ * 3,000 - 9,999 sheep or lambs_ * 16,500 - 54,999 turkeys_ * 10,000 - 29,999 ducks (other than liquid manure handling

	<p>systems)_</p> <p>* 1,500 - 4,999 ducks (liquid manure handling systems)_</p> <p>* 9,000 - 29,999 chickens (liquid manure handling systems)_</p> <p>* 37,500 - 124,999 chickens except laying hens (other than liquid manure handling systems)_</p> <p>* 25,000 - 81,999 laying hens (other than liquid manure handling systems)_</p> <p>* Discharge pollutant into the water of US.(Title 35 Illinois Administrative Code Section 502.104)_</p> <p>* http://www.epa.illinois.gov/topics/water-quality/watershed-management/cafos/index</p>
How animal units are defined (if used):	<p>"Animal unit" means a unit of measurement for any Animal Feeding Operation calculated as follows: _</p> <p>(1) Brood cows and slaughter and feeder cattle multiplied by 1.0. _</p> <p>(2) Milking dairy cows multiplied by 1.4. _</p> <p>(3) Young dairy stock multiplied by 0.6. _</p> <p>(4) Swine weighing over 55 pounds multiplied by 0.4. _</p> <p>(5) Swine weighing under 55 pounds multiplied by 0.03. _</p> <p>(6) Sheep, lambs, or goats multiplied by 0.1. _</p> <p>(7) Horses multiplied by 2.0. _</p> <p>(8) Turkeys multiplied by 0.02. _</p> <p>(9) Laying hens or broilers multiplied by 0.01 (if the facility has continuous overflow watering). _</p> <p>(10) Laying hens or broilers multiplied by 0.03 (if the facility has a liquid manure handling system). _</p> <p>(11) Ducks multiplied by 0.02. _</p> <p>(Source: P.A. 89-456, eff. 5-21-96.)</p>
NPDES permitting or other permitting requirements:	<p>You will need to apply for a CAFO NPDES permit if you own or operate a "Large" CAFO that discharges._</p> <p>You will need to apply for a CAFO NPDES permit if you own or operate a "Medium" CAFO that discharges._</p>
Does the state require an NPDES permit for all Large CAFOs?	No
Does the state issue individual or general CAFO permits?	Both
Are any other permits required for CAFOs or other large farms?	Yes
Other definitions needed to understand these regulations:	No other information
Regulatory Details	
Setbacks: <i>State regulations that</i>	Distance from Residences_ Livestock waste shall not be land applied within ¼ mile of any

<p><i>indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some geographical feature</i></p>	<p>residence not part of the CAFO, unless it is injected or incorporated on the day of application._</p> <p>–</p> <p>Setbacks from Waters_</p> <p>Livestock waste shall not be land applied within 200 feet of surface water, unless the water is upgrade or there is adequate diking, which includes, but is not limited to, diking that prevents runoff from the land application from entering surface waters that are within 200 feet of the land application area._</p> <p>–</p> <p>Livestock waste shall not be land applied within 100 feet of down gradient open subsurface drainage intakes, agricultural drainage wells, sinkholes, grassed waterways or other conduits to surface waters, unless a 35 foot vegetative buffer exists between the land application area and the grassed waterways, open subsurface drainage intakes, agricultural drainage wells, sinkholes or other conduits to surface water._</p> <p>–</p> <p>The setback requirements in subsection (b)(2) do not apply if the CAFO is able to demonstrate to the Agency that a setback or buffer is not necessary because implementation of alternative conservation practices (including, but not limited to, injection and incorporation) or field-specific conditions will provide pollutant reductions equivalent to or better than the reductions that would be achieved by the 100-foot setback._</p> <p>–</p> <p>Livestock waste shall not be land applied to waters of the United States, grassed waterways or other conduits to surface waters._</p> <p>–</p> <p>Livestock waste shall not be land applied within 150 feet of potable water supply wells.</p>
<p>Are setbacks more restrictive than CFR?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Timing, weather, or conditional application restrictions: <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather, seasons, or land characteristics (like slope)</i></p>	<p>Livestock waste shall not be applied in a 10-year flood plain unless the injection or incorporation method of application is used._</p> <p>–</p> <p>Surface land application of livestock waste shall not occur within 24 hours preceding a forecast of 0.5 inches or more of precipitation in a 24-hour period as measured in liquid form. The CAFO owner or operator shall use one of the following two methods for determining whether these conditions exist and shall maintain a record of the forecast from the source used. _</p> <p>* A prediction of a 60 percent or greater chance of 0.5 inches or more of precipitation in a 24-hour period as measured in liquid form, obtained from the National Weather Service's Meteorological Development Laboratory, Statistical Modeling Branch, 1325 East West Highway, Silver Spring MD 20910 for the location nearest to the land application area; or_</p>

* A prediction of 0.5 inches or more of precipitation in a 24-hour period as measured in liquid form and identified as higher than Quantitative Precipitation Forecast(QPF) category 3, obtained from the National Weather Service's Meteorological Development Laboratory, Statistical Modeling Branch, 1325 East West Highway, Silver Spring, MD 20910 for the land application area location._

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Section 502.630 Protocols to Land Apply Livestock Waste During Winter_

Winter Application Prohibition. Surface land application of livestock waste on frozen, ice-covered, or snow-covered ground is prohibited except as specified in subsection (a)(1). _

Notwithstanding the winter application prohibition in subsection (a), surface land application of livestock waste on frozen, ice-covered or snow-covered ground is allowed if all of the following conditions are met:_

A) No practical alternative measures are available to handle the livestock waste within storage facilities or to dispose of the livestock waste at other sites. Examples of practical alternative measures may include, but are not limited to, the transfer of waste to another waste handling facility or sewage treatment plant, rental or acquisition of a storage tank, reduction of herd size or depopulation, and protection of the facility from direct precipitation and clean stormwater runoff;_

B) Liquid livestock waste cannot be injected or incorporated within 24 hours after application due to soil conditions;_

C) Prior to December 1, the owner or operator has taken steps to provide 120 days of available storage capacity of manure storage areas. Examples of steps that could be taken may include, but are not limited to, land application of livestock waste, transfer of waste to another party, protection of waste storage structures from direct precipitation and stormwater runoff, and depopulating facilities to reduce the amount of waste generated;_

D) The owner or operator has complied with subsection (a)(1)(C) and yet the storage volume available on December 1 of that winter season is less than 120 days of storage;_

E) The owner or operator has notified the Agency in writing on December 1 of that winter season that the CAFO has less than 120 days storage available; and_

F) The discharge of livestock waste from the structure to the surface waters is expected to occur due to shortage in storage capacity._

2) The storage volume calculation in subsection (a)(1)(C) must include runoff and direct precipitation plus the volume of livestock excreta, wash water and other process wastewater generated and expected to enter the storage structure during the period of December 1 to April 1. Runoff volume calculations must meet the following requirements:_

A) Runoff calculations must be based on the runoff transferred into the storage structure under frozen ground conditions;_

B) Direct precipitation that will reduce the available storage volume must be based on normal precipitation for the December 1 to April 1 period for the nearest weather station and, for facilities exposed to precipitation, the 25-year, 24-hour storm event volume or the design storm event volume determined under Subpart H for swine, poultry and veal large CAFOs that are new sources. The determination of normal precipitation shall be based on National Weather Service or State Water Survey Records;_

C) The owner or operator shall keep a record of the precipitation value used and the source from which the value was obtained; and_

D) Calculations must allow for a freeboard of two feet._

3) In the event winter land application is necessary, it must be conducted pursuant to a winter application plan described in subsection (b) and according to the conditions of subsection (c)._

b) Winter Application Plan_

In order to conduct surface land application on frozen, ice covered, or snow covered ground, the requirements of this subsection (b) must be met._

1) No land application may occur within ¼ mile of a non-farm residence._

2) No discharge may occur during land application of livestock waste._

3) Surface land application on frozen ground shall not occur within 24-hours preceding a forecast of 0.25 inches or more of precipitation in a 24-hour period as measured in liquid form. The CAFO owner or operator shall use one of the following two methods for determining whether these conditions exist and shall maintain a record of the forecast from the source used._

A) A prediction of a 60 percent or greater chance of 0.25 inches or more of precipitation in a 24-hour period as measured in liquid form, obtained from the National Weather Service's Meteorological Development Laboratory, Statistical Modeling Branch 1325 East West Highway, Silver Spring MD 20910, for the location nearest to the land application area; or_

B) A prediction of 0.25 inches or more of precipitation in a 24-hour period as measured in liquid form and identified as higher than QPF category 2 obtained from the National Weather Service Meteorological Development Laboratory, Statistical Modeling Branch, 1325 East West Highway, Silver Spring MD 20910, for the land application area location._

4) Surface land application of livestock waste on ice covered or snow covered land shall not occur within 24 hours preceding a forecast of 0.1 inches or more of precipitation in a 24 hour period as measured in liquid form. The CAFO owner or operator shall use one of the two methods provided below for determining whether or not these conditions exist and shall maintain a record of the forecast

from the source used._

A) A prediction of a 60 percent or greater chance of 0.1 inches or more of precipitation in a 24-hour period as measured in liquid form obtained from the National Weather Service's Meteorological Development Laboratory, Statistical Modeling Branch, 1325 East West Highway, Silver Spring MD 20910 for the location nearest to the land application area; or_

B) A prediction of 0.1 inches or more of precipitation in a 24-hour period as measured in liquid form and identified as higher than QPF category 1 obtained from the National Weather Service's Meteorological Development Laboratory, Statistical Modeling Branch, 1325 East West Highway, Silver Spring MD 20910 for the land application area location._

5) If the land application of livestock waste is on ice covered or snow covered land, surface land application shall not occur when the predicted high temperature exceeds 32 degrees F on the day of land application or on any of the 7 days following land application as predicted by the National Weather Service's Meteorological Development Laboratory, Statistical Modeling Branch, 1325 East West Highway, Silver Spring MD 20910 for the location nearest to the land application area. The owner or operator shall maintain a record of the forecast from the source used._

6) If the surface land application of livestock waste is on ice covered or snow covered land, the CAFO owner or operator shall visually monitor for runoff from the site. The CAFO owner or operator daily must monitor each ice covered or snow covered field where land application has been conducted when the ambient temperature is 32 degrees F or greater following winter land application until all the ice or snow melts from the land application area._

7) If the surface land application of livestock waste is on ice covered or snow covered land and a runoff from the land application area occurs, the CAFO owner or operator shall report any discharge of livestock waste within 24 hours after the discovery of the discharge as follows:_

A) The report shall be made to the Agency through the Illinois Emergency Management Agency by calling 1-800-782-7860 or 1-217-782-7860;_

B) Within 5 days after this telephone report, the CAFO owner or operator shall file a written report with the Agency that includes the name and telephone number of the person filing the report, location of the discharge, an estimate of the quantity of the discharge, time and duration of the discharge, actions taken in response to the discharge, and observations of the condition of the discharge with regards to turbidity, color, foaming, floatable solids and other deleterious conditions of the runoff for each day of each runoff event until the ice or snow melts off the site._

c) Availability of Individual Fields for Winter Application_

If livestock waste is to be surface applied on frozen ground, ice

	<p>covered land or snow covered land, the land application may only be conducted on land that meets the following requirements: _</p> <p>1) Adequate erosion and runoff control practices exist, including, but not limited to, vegetative fence rows around the site, contour farming, terracing, catchment basins and buffer areas that intercept surface runoff from the site; _</p> <p>2) A crop stubble, crop residue or vegetative buffer of 200 feet exists between the land application area and surface waters, waterways, open tile line intake structures, sinkholes, agricultural wellheads, or other conduits to surface water and the vegetative buffer zone is down gradient of the livestock waste application area; _</p> <p>3) Application on land with slopes greater than 5% is prohibited; _</p> <p>4) Application may only occur on sites that have field specific soil erosion loss calculated using Revised Universal Soil Loss Equation less than Erosion Factor T, and have a median Bray P1 or Mehlich 3 soil level of phosphorus, in accordance with Recommended Chemical Soil Test Procedures for the North Central Region, incorporated by reference in 35 Ill. Adm. Code 501.200, equal to or less than 300 pounds per acre; _</p> <p>5) Surface application may only occur if the setbacks equal three times the otherwise applicable setbacks by Sections 502.615 and 502.645 if the slope of the field is between 2 percent and 5 percent. This setback requirement does not include the quarter mile distance from residences contained in Section 502.645(a); and _</p> <p>6) For fields with slopes of less than 2 percent, the surface application may only occur if the setbacks equal two times the otherwise applicable setbacks required by Sections 502.615 and 502.645. This setback requirement does not include the quarter mile distance from residences contained in Section 502.645(a). _</p> <p>(Source: Added at 38 Ill. Reg. 17687, effective August 11, 2014)</p>
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to saturated soils?	Yes
Is there a restriction for land application of manure within floodplains?	Yes
Is there a restriction for land application of manure related to future rainfall?	Yes
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to frozen or snow-covered ground?	Yes
Are there restrictions to manure applications based on time of year or time of	Yes

day?	
Are there restrictions to manure application based on slope?	Yes
Are there any other seasonal, timing, weather, or physical restrictions to manure applications not captured above?	Yes, Liquid livestock waste shall not be applied to land with less than 36 inches of soil covering fractured bedrock, sand or gravel. Section 502.620(h)_ Livestock waste shall not be applied to bedrock outcrops. Section 502.620(i)_ _ Livestock waste shall
Transfer of manure off-site: <i>Requirements related to the transfer of manures to other persons</i>	Prior to transferring livestock waste to other persons, CAFOs must provide the recipient of the livestock waste with the most current nutrient analysis. The land application by manure receiver needs to be included in the CAFO's nutrient management plan as a permit requirement.
Are receivers of manure transfers from CAFOs required to follow the same regulations?	Yes
Nutrient or manure management plans: <i>Additional details on the NMP requirement. Note that some of this information may overlap with other sections</i>	The Livestock Management Facilities Act (LMFA), requires an NMP be developed if the facility has more than 1,000 AUs and plans to apply manure to land._ _ Any permit issued to a CAFO must require compliance with the terms of the CAFO's site-specific nutrient management plan. NMPs can use a linear or narrative approach. The NMP for NPDES permit has more detailed requirements for the purpose of the water pollution prevention, such as stormwater management at the CAFO's production areas, freeboard at storage structures, slopes of the land application fields, land application methods (surface, incorporated, or injection application), etc.
Do your NMP/MMPS follow, comply with, or based on NRCS Technical Standard 590?	Yes
Application rates: <i>State regulations that restrict the rates at which manures are applied and methods needed to determine appropriate rates.</i>	Nitrogen-based application of livestock waste must be conducted consistent with the following requirements:_ available soil phosphorus (median Bray P1 or Mehlich 3 in accordance with Recommended Chemical Soil Test Procedures for the North Central Region, incorporated by reference in 35 Ill. Adm. Code 501.200) is equal to or less than 300 pounds per acre;_ the soil loss calculated using the Revised Universal Soil Loss Equation 2 (RUSLE2) is less than the Erosion Factor T;_ Phosphorus-based application of livestock waste must be conducted consistent with the following requirements:_ if the soil contains greater than 50 pounds of available soil

	<p>phosphorus per acre (median Bray P1 or Mehlich 3 in accordance with Recommended Chemical Soil Test Procedures for the North Central Region, incorporated by reference in 35 Ill. Adm. Code 501.200), phosphorus-based application rates must maintain or lower the soil test phosphorus during the nutrient management plan period;_</p> <p>if the soil contains greater than 300 pounds of available soil phosphorus per acre (median Bray P1 or Mehlich 3 in accordance with Recommended Chemical Soil Test Procedures for the North Central Region, incorporated by reference in 35 Ill. Adm. Code 501.200), the amount of phosphorus applied in the livestock waste must not exceed the amount of phosphorus removed by the next year's crop grown and harvested; and livestock waste shall not be applied to fields with available soil phosphorus (median Bray P1 or Mehlich 3 in accordance with Recommended Chemical Soil Test Procedures for the North Central Region, incorporated by reference in 35 Ill. Adm. Code 501.200) greater than 400 pounds per acre._</p> <p>–</p> <p>No surface land application on frozen, ice or snow covered fields unless a winter application is included in the NMP and in Section compliance with Section 502.630. _</p> <p>–</p> <p>Section 502.625. Livestock waste application shall not exceed the agronomic nitrogen rate, which is defined as the annual application rate of nitrogen that can be expected to be required for a realistic crop yield goal._</p> <p>–</p> <p>Section 502.615(d)(5). and livestock waste shall not be applied to fields with available soil phosphorus (median Bray P1 or Mehlich 3 in accordance with Recommended Chemical Soil Test Procedures for the North Central Region, incorporated by reference in 35 Ill. Adm. Code 501.200) greater than 400 pounds per acre.</p>
<p>Manure application rates for phosphorus are based on:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) <i>Phosphorus Index Only</i> 2) <i>Soil Test Phosphorus Only</i> 3) <i>Either PIO or STPO</i> 4) <i>Other</i> 	<p>Soil test phosphorus only</p>
<p>Are there any nutrient “caps” to manure application?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Composition testing: <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on manures</i></p>	<p>Operator shall annually obtain a laboratory analysis of the nutrient content representative of the livestock waste to be land applied as provided within the nutrient management plan Multiple subsamples shall be obtained and combined into one sample so that a representative sample is obtained for analysis. Results of a sample</p>

<i>before application</i>	<p>taken during waste application the previous year can be used for plan preparation unless there has been a change in the waste management practices during the year. The analytical results of livestock waste samples shall be used for calculation of the application rate allowed by the NPDES permit._</p> <p>– The laboratory analysis of the livestock waste sample shall include total kjeldahl nitrogen, ammonia or ammonium nitrogen, total phosphorus, total potassium, and percent total solids. The nutrient results shall be reported on the laboratory analysis sheet on a lb./ton or mg/kg dry weight basis or lb./1000 gal or mg/L wet weight basis. The results of these analyses are to be used in determining application rates for livestock waste.</p>
Does your state require testing of manure for anything beyond nutrients, such as metals, pathogens, antibiotics, etc.?	No
Other land application highlights: <i>Additional restrictions for land application of manures</i>	The Nutrient Management Plan shall include a plan for the inspection, monitoring, management and repair of subsurface drainage systems at the livestock waste application site. Inspection of subsurface drainage systems shall include visual inspection prior
Other regulatory details: <i>Additional information on the regulation of land application of manures</i>	No other information
General Assessment Questions	
Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change:	Undetermined
Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of manures that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links:	No
Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate	No

land application of manures beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so:	
Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.	No other information

Indiana	
Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2025
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Indiana Department of Environmental Management (IDEM); The Office of the Indiana State Chemist (OISC)
Links to regulations	Concentrated Animal Feeding Operation (CAFO) Rule - 327 IAC 15-16 ARTICLE 15:_ http://www.in.gov/legislative/iac/T03270/A00150.PDF _ Confined Feeding Operation (CFO) Rule -327 IAC 19:_ http://www.in.gov/legislative/iac/iac_title?iact=327&iaca=19
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	More than one agency
Other regulator info	No other information
Definitions	
How CAFOs are defined or categorized:	Confined feeding operation" or "CFO" defined Authority: IC 13-14-8-7; IC 13-15-2-1; IC 13-18-10-4 Affected: IC 4-21.5; IC 13-11-2-40; IC 13-14; IC 13-15; IC 13-18-10; IC 13-30 Sec. 7. "Confined feeding operation" or "CFO", as defined in IC 13-11-2-40, means any:_ (1) confined feeding of at least:_ (A) three hundred (300) cattle;_ (B) six hundred (600) swine or sheep;_ (C) thirty thousand (30,000) fowl; or_ (D) five hundred (500) horses;_ (2) AFO electing to be subject to IC 13-18-10; or_ (3) AFO that is causing a violation of:_ (A) water pollution control laws;_ (B) any rules of the water pollution control board; or_ (C) IC 13-18-10._ A determination by the department under this subdivision is appealable under IC 4-21.5._ (Water Pollution Control Division; 327 IAC 19-2-7; filed Feb 6, 2012, 2:58 p.m.: 20120307-IR-327090615FRA, eff Jul 1, 2012;_ readopted filed Jun 6, 2018, 1:59 p.m.: 20180704-IR-327180171BFA
How animal units are defined (if used):	Not used
NPDES permitting or other permitting requirements:	All regulated Animal Feeding Operations in Indiana are considered confined feeding operations (CFO). To be regulated under the Confined Feeding Control Law in Indiana, you must meet the following size of any one livestock group listed below:_ 300 or more cattle_ 600 or more swine or sheep_ 30,000 or more poultry (chicken, turkey or ducks)_ 500 horses in confinement_ _ The concentrated Animal Feeding Operation (CAFO) designation is

	<p>strictly a size designation in Indiana. Farms of this size are permitted under the CFO rule, but have a few added requirements under Indiana regulations. A CFO that meets the size classification as a CAFO is a farm that meets or exceeds an animal threshold number in the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency's definition of a large CAFO._</p> <p>–</p> <p>Only farms with ongoing discharges need an NPDES permit. CAFOs that are not discharging chose to enter the CFO program instead._</p> <p>There are zero NPDES CAFO permits in Indiana._</p> <p>Other permits may occur in cases where a state regulated CAFO has a digester defined in 329 IAC 11.5 and accepts an appropriate feedstock-² approved by the IDEM may be required to land apply the digestion residue under a permit issued through 327 IAC 6.1</p>
Does the state require an NPDES permit for all Large CAFOs?	No
Does the state issue individual or general CAFO permits?	Individual
Are any other permits required for CAFOs or other large farms?	Yes
Other definitions needed to understand these regulations:	No other information
Regulatory Details	
<p>Setbacks:</p> <p><i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some geographical feature</i></p>	<p>Manure application setbacks_</p> <p>Authority: IC 13-14-8; IC 13-15-2-1; IC 13-18-10-4_</p> <p>Affected: IC 13-15; IC 13-18-10; IC 13-30_</p> <p>Sec. 6. (a) Except as otherwise provided under this section, application of manure and process wastewater must be in accordance with the setbacks in Table 1: Manure Application Setback Distances, from Indiana NRCS Conservation Practice Standard 590: Nutrient Management, October 2013*, as follows:_</p> <p>(1) All setback distances must be measured from the edge of the area of actual placement of manure or process wastewater on the land._</p> <p>(2) The property line setback distances in this subsection may be waived in writing by the owner of the adjoining property._</p> <p>(3) The setback is the width of the filter strip if a properly designed and maintained filter strip of at least fifty (50) feet in width is located between the application site and any of the following:_</p> <p>(A) Surface water._</p> <p>(B) Any known private well._</p> <p>(C) The surface opening or lowest point of any sinkhole._</p> <p>(D) Any drainage inlet, including water and sediment control</p>

	<p>basins._</p> <p>(4) The setback is ten (10) feet if a gradient barrier is located between the application site and any of the following:_</p> <p>(A) Surface water._</p> <p>(B) Any known well._</p> <p>(C) The surface opening or lowest point of any sinkhole._</p> <p>(D) Any drainage inlet, including water and sediment control basins._</p> <p>(b) To ensure that manure and process wastewater are not applied before, during, or immediately following a rain event that, when combined with soil conditions, would likely result in runoff, the owner/operator must take into account the:_</p> <p>(1) weather forecast and likelihood of precipitation events for the twenty-four (24) hour period before and after the application; and (2) site soil conditions._</p> <p>(c) Land application sites must be inspected to identify any field tile outlets, grassed waterways, and surface water conveyance channels under or immediately bordering the land application site as follows:_</p> <p>(1) Monitoring of identified field tile outlets, waterways, and surface water conveyance channels must occur during and immediately following land application of the manure or process wastewater based on:_</p> <p>(A) color;_</p> <p>(B) flow;_</p> <p>(C) volume and volume change; and_</p> <p>(D) odor and change in odor._</p> <p>(2) If there is evidence of manure or process wastewater discharging from the field tile outlet, the land application must cease immediately and the flow must be stopped or captured. Any flow that is captured must be either land applied or returned to an approved manure storage facility._</p> <p>(d) The monitoring activities conducted in accordance with subsection (c) must be documented and placed in the operating record.</p>
<p>Are setbacks more restrictive than CFR?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Timing, weather, or conditional application restrictions: <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather, seasons, or land characteristics (like slope)</i></p>	<p>Small CFOs with 120 days or less storage may apply for frozen ground or snow-covered ground spreading of manure under 327 Indiana Administrative Code (IAC) 19-14-4(i). These applications are considered on a case-by-case basis for approval through an alternate compliance approach under 327 IAC 19-5-1. CAFO sized operations are not eligible to apply for the IDEM commissioner's approval because of the explicit prohibition under 327 IAC 19-14-4(e). The only option for CAFO farmers who feel that they need an approval to surface apply to frozen or snow-covered ground is to apply for a National Pollutant Discharge Elimination System CAFO Individual Permit under 327 IAC 15-16._</p>

	<p>– When soils meet frozen or snow-covered ground conditions, injection or incorporation of manure into the soil on the same day is not considered surface application and is not prohibited._</p> <p>– Farm operators who have an emergency that creates an immediate need to surface apply manure to frozen or snow-covered ground due to unforeseen circumstances beyond their control should contact their CFO Compliance Inspector for assistance prior to application.- https://www.in.gov/idem/cfo/2333.htm _</p> <p>Regulated facilities are prohibited from applying to saturated ground 327 IAC 19-14-4(d) The application of manure is prohibited in the following conditions: (1) saturated Ground.</p>
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to saturated soils?	Yes
Is there a restriction for land application of manure within floodplains?	No
Is there a restriction for land application of manure related to future rainfall?	No
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to frozen or snow-covered ground?	Yes
Are there restrictions to manure applications based on time of year or time of day?	No
Are there restrictions to manure application based on slope?	No
Are there any other seasonal, timing, weather, or physical restrictions to manure applications not captured above?	The application of manure is prohibited on soils with greater than 200 ppm of Phosphorous. It is restricted to P crop removal on soils with soil test P of 50-199 ppm. Under 50 ppm soil test P the manure application would be based on manure Nitrogen conten
Transfer of manure off-site: <i>Requirements related to the transfer of manures to other persons</i>	Indiana allows the marketing and distributing of manure from a permitted facility as long as they comply with the marketing and distributing requirements under 327 IAC 19-14-7. Through 355 IAC 7 all CFO/CAFO are required to have a category 14 application certification and a Business license if they market or distribute their manure. Marketed and distributed manure and manures from AFOs (amounts >10 cu,yds. solid or 4,000 liquid) not regulated through the CFO program are required to follow 355 IAC 8. Also, if a facility

	<p>receives marketed or distributed manure the manure must be applied by a person or business that has a category 14 certification and must follow the land application requirement under 355 IAC 8.</p>
<p>Are receivers of manure transfers from CAFOs required to follow the same regulations?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Nutrient or manure management plans: <i>Additional details on the NMP requirement. Note that some of this information may overlap with other sections</i></p>	<p>A manure management plan must be developed and submitted to the commissioner that contains the following: _</p> <p>(1) Procedures for soil testing as described in subsection (c). _</p> <p>(2) Procedures for manure testing as described in subsection (d). _</p> <p>(3) Plot maps as described in section 2(a)(1) and 2(b) of this rule. _</p> <p>(4) If applicable, the land application acreage requirements waiver, as described in 327 IAC 19-14-2(d). _</p> <p>(b) If applicable, the manure management plan must also contain a description of any: _</p> <p>(1) alternate methods proposed by the applicant for managing of the manure; and _</p> <p>(2) other practices to be used that assure the CFO meets the performance standards in this article. _</p> <p>(c) A soil test must be obtained that provides sufficient information about soil fertility to allow for nutrient recommendations _ for existing or planned crops. Soil tests may not represent more than twenty (20) acres per sample. The frequency of this testing _ must be: _</p> <p>(1) specified in the manure management plan; and _</p> <p>(2) conducted a minimum of once every four (4) years unless a different frequency is approved by the department in writing and is included in the manure management plan. _</p> <p>(d) A manure test must be obtained that provides sufficient information about the manure content to allow for nutrient recommendations for existing or planned crops and to minimize nutrient leaching. The frequency of this testing must be: _</p> <p>(1) specified in the manure management plan; and _</p> <p>(2) conducted a minimum of once every year. _</p> <p>(e) Manure samples must be representative of the manure that is land applied. If manure is mixed from separate manure storage facilities prior to land application, a composite sample may be taken. If manure is land applied from separate and distinct storage facilities, a sample must be taken from each unique production system. _</p> <p>(f) A manure management plan must be submitted to the department at least one (1) time every five (5) years and with any approval application and renewal application to maintain a valid approval for the CFO. A copy of the current manure management plan must be maintained in the operating record. (Water Pollution Control Division; 327 IAC 19-7-5; filed Feb 6, 2012, 2:58 p.m.:20120307-IR-327090615FRA, eff Jul 1, 2012; readopted filed</p>

	Jun 6, 2018, 1:59 p.m.: 20180704-IR-327180171BFA)
Do your NMP/MMPS follow, comply with, or based on NRCS Technical Standard 590?	Yes
Application rates: <i>State regulations that restrict the rates at which manures are applied and methods needed to determine appropriate rates.</i>	Soil and manure tests must be conducted in accordance with the manure management plan that is submitted to the commissioner to meet the requirement in 327 IAC 19-7-1(c)(5).(above)_ The application rate of nitrogen (N) must not exceed the N requirements based on:_ 1) Purdue University Cooperative Extension Service publication ID-101: Animal Manure as a Plant Nutrient Resource, February 2001._ 2) Tri-State Fertilizer Recommendations for Corn, Soybeans, Wheat and Alfalfa, Extension Bulletin E-2567 (New), July 1995. Minimum N loss estimates must be used unless otherwise justified. This justification must be kept in the operating record. _ For the first manure application only, nutrient content of manure from facilities constructed after the effective date of this article must be: (1) based on either:(A) manure test values as described in 327 IAC 19-7-5(d); or (B) values in the NRCS Agricultural Waste Management Field Handbook (AWMFH) Chapter 4, March 2008; and (2) applied at fifty percent (50%) of the rate listed in subsection (b). For all subsequent manure application events, nutrient content values must be based on manure test values. _ Manure application rates based on phosphorus application rates are within 327 IAC 19-14-3 Table 1 and 2._ Records must show total amount of nitrogen and phosphorus actually applied to each field, including documentation of calculations for the total amount applied.
Manure application rates for phosphorus are based on: 1) <i>Phosphorus Index Only</i> 2) <i>Soil Test Phosphorus Only</i> 3) <i>Either PIO or STPO</i> 4) <i>Other</i>	Soil test phosphorus only
Are there any nutrient “caps” to manure application?	Yes
Composition testing: <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on manures before application</i>	A manure test must be obtained that provides sufficient information about the manure content to allow for nutrient recommendations for existing or planned crops and to minimize nutrient leaching. The frequency of this testing must be:_ (1) specified in the manure management plan; and_ (2) conducted a minimum of once every year.
Does your state require	No

testing of manure for anything beyond nutrients, such as metals, pathogens, antibiotics, etc.?	
Other land application highlights: <i>Additional restrictions for land application of manures</i>	No other information
Other regulatory details: <i>Additional information on the regulation of land application of manures</i>	No other information
General Assessment Questions	
Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change:	Undetermined
Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of manures that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links:	No
Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of manures beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so:	No
Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.	No other information

Iowa	
Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2019
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Iowa Department of Natural Resources (IDNR)
Links to regulations	Iowa Administrative Code:_ http://www.legis.iowa.gov/law/administrativeRules/agencies
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Natural Resources
Other regulator info	No other information
Definitions	
How CAFOs are defined or categorized:	<p>Animal feeding operation-² means a lot, yard, corral, building, or other area in which animals are confined and fed and maintained for 45 days or more in any 12-month period, and all structures used for the storage of manure from animals in the operation. Except as required for an NPDES permit required pursuant to the Act, an Animal Feeding Operation does not include a livestock market. Open feedlots and confinement feeding operations are considered to be separate Animal Feeding Operations._</p> <p>– Confinement Feeding Operation - means an Animal Feeding Operation in which animals are confined to areas which are totally roofed and includes every Animal Feeding Operation that is not an open feedlot operation - as defined in 567-65.100(459A)._</p> <p>– Open Feedlot Operation - means an unroofed or partially roofed Animal Feeding Operation if crop, vegetation, or forage growth or residue is not maintained as part of the Animal Feeding Operation during the period that animals are confined in the Animal Feeding Operation. Open feedlot operation- includes a partially roofed Animal Feeding Operation - as defined in this rule.</p>
How animal units are defined (if used):	<p>Animal unit-² means a unit of measurement based upon the product of multiplying the number of animals of each category by a special equivalency factor as follows:_</p> <p>a. Slaughter or feeder cattle - 1.000 _</p> <p>b. Immature dairy cattle - 1.000 _</p> <p>c. Mature dairy cattle - 1.400 _</p> <p>d. Butcher or breeding swine weighing more than fifty-five pounds 0.400 _</p> <p>e. Swine weighing fifteen pounds or more but not more than fifty-five pounds - 0.100 _</p> <p>f. Sheep or lambs - 0.100 _</p> <p>g. Horses - 2.000 _</p> <p>h. Turkeys weighing one hundred twelve ounces or more - 0.018 _</p> <p>i. Turkeys weighing less than one hundred twelve ounces - 0.0085 _</p>

	<p>j. Chickens weighing forty-eight ounces or more - 0.010_</p> <p>k. Chickens weighing less than forty-eight ounces -0.0025 _</p> <p>l. Fish - 0.001_</p> <p>_</p> <p>From the above AU, we can calculate the small animal confinement operations-☐ which are not subject to most regulations, which according to 459.312A is 500 AU or less. The numbers below are animal #s not units: _</p> <p>a. Slaughter or feeder cattle - 500 _</p> <p>b. Immature dairy cattle - 500 _</p> <p>c. Mature dairy cattle- 357.1_</p> <p>d. Butcher or breeding swine weighing more than fifty-five pounds - 1250 _</p> <p>e. Swine weighing fifteen pounds or more but not more than fifty-five pounds - 5,000 _</p> <p>f. Sheep or lambs - 5,000 _</p> <p>g. Horses - 250 _</p> <p>h. Turkeys weighing one hundred twelve ounces or more - 27,777.8_</p> <p>i. Turkeys weighing less than one hundred twelve ounces - 58,823.5_</p> <p>j. Chickens weighing forty-eight ounces or more- 50,000_</p> <p>k. Chickens weighing less than forty-eight ounces - 200,000_</p> <p>l. Fish -500,000</p>
<p>NPDES permitting or other permitting requirements:</p>	<p>The DNR's NPDES section issues NPDES permits and storm water permits to Animal Feeding Operations. The NPDES section provides technical assistance to Animal Feeding Operation owners and operators. State construction permits are required for facilities with over 1000 animal units; Nutrient Management Plans for Open Feedlots with over 1000 animal units; and Manure Management Plans for Confinement Feeding Operations with over 500 animal units.</p>
<p>Does the state require an NPDES permit for all Large CAFOs?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Does the state issue individual or general CAFO permits?</p>	<p>Individual</p>
<p>Are any other permits required for CAFOs or other large farms?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Other definitions needed to understand these regulations:</p>	<p>"Designated Area" - means a known sinkhole, abandoned well, unplugged agricultural drainage well, agricultural drainage well cistern, agricultural drainage well surface tile inlet, drinking water well, designated wetland, or water source. Designated area-☐ does not include a terrace tile inlet or surface tile inlet other than an agricultural drainage well surface tile inlet.</p>
<p>Regulatory Details</p>	

<p>Setbacks: <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some geographical feature</i></p>	<p>Land application must be set back 750 feet from a business, church, school, public use area or residence unless it is injected or incorporated within 24 hours, they have permission from owner, they are a small Animal Feeding Operation, or they use low-pressure spray irrigation equipment._ For low-pressure irrigation systems, 250 ft separation is required._ A 200 feet separation is required for designated areas and an 800 ft from a high quality water resource unless injected or incorporated on the same date . Separation distance for surface application is reduced to 50 feet with vegetated buffer._ Different setbacks may apply to NPDES holders: For confinement feeding operations with NPDES permits, the following is adopted by reference: 40 CFR 412.4(a), (b) and (c)(5).</p>
<p>Are setbacks more restrictive than CFR?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Timing, weather, or conditional application restrictions: <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather, seasons, or land characteristics (like slope)</i></p>	<p>Liquid manure application to snow covered ground from 12/21 to April 1 is only allowed in an emergency._ From Feb 1 to Apr 1 only can apply liquid manure to frozen ground in an emergency._ An emergency must be something beyond the control of the owner causing them to need to land apply._ These rules do not apply to small Animal Feeding Operations or if manure is incorporated or injected within 24 hours.</p>
<p>Is there a restriction for land application of manure to saturated soils?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Is there a restriction for land application of manure within floodplains?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Is there a restriction for land application of manure related to future rainfall?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Is there a restriction for land application of manure to frozen or snow-covered ground?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Are there restrictions to manure applications based on time of year or time of day?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Are there restrictions to manure application based on slope?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Are there any other seasonal, timing, weather,</p>	<p>No</p>

<p>or physical restrictions to manure applications not captured above?</p>	
<p>Transfer of manure off-site: <i>Requirements related to the transfer of manures to other persons</i></p>	<p>* All manure removed from an Animal Feeding Operation or its manure control facilities shall be land-applied in a manner which will not cause surface or groundwater pollution. Application in accordance with the provisions of state law, and the rules and guidelines in this chapter, shall be deemed as compliance with this requirement._</p> <p>* Manure that is sold has to fill out a sales form that includes the following information: 1. A place for the name and address of the buyer of the manure. 2. A place for the quantity of manure purchased. 3. The planned crop schedule and optimum crop yields. 4. A place for the manure application methods and the timing of manure application. A place for the location of the field including the number of acres where the manure will be applied. 6. A place for the manure application rate. 7. A place for a phosphorus index of each field receiving manure, as defined in paragraph 65.17(17)a, including the factors used in the calculation. A copy of the NRCS phosphorus index detailed report shall satisfy the requirement to include the factors used in the calculation._</p> <p>- Certain solid manures can be registered as a soil amendment and sold to a broker who then sells the manure to farmers. Most chicken litter in the state is handled in this manner. This program is regulated by the Iowa Dept. of Agriculture._</p> <p>Manures that are registered as soil amendments do not have the same requirements.</p>
<p>Are receivers of manure transfers from CAFOs required to follow the same regulations?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Nutrient or manure management plans: <i>Additional details on the NMP requirement. Note that some of this information may overlap with other sections</i></p>	<p>* People who have to submit a manure management plan -“ applicant for confinement feeding operation if it was constructed or expanded after May 31, 1985 or if the owner constructs a manure storage structure. Small Animal Feeding Operations do not have to submit a plan. _</p> <p>* A person who applies manure in Iowa that was produced in a confinement feeding operation (not a small operation) located outside of Iowa_</p> <p>* Research colleges are exempt._</p> <p>* Manure management plans should include the following information for all manure not sold:_</p> <p>a. Calculations to determine the land area required for manure application. _</p> <p>b. The total nitrogen and total phosphorus (as P2O5) available to be applied from the confinement feeding operation. _</p> <p>c. The planned crop schedule and optimum crop yields. _</p> <p>d. Manure application methods and timing of the application. _</p>

	<p>e. The location of manure application. _</p> <p>f. An estimate of the annual animal production and manure volume or weight produced. _</p> <p>g. Methods, structures or practices that will be used to reduce soil loss and prevent surface water pollution. _</p> <p>h. Methods or practices that will be utilized to reduce odor if spray irrigation equipment is used to apply manure. _</p> <p>i. A phosphorus index of each field in the manure management plan, as defined in paragraph 65.17(17)a, including the factors used in the calculation. A copy of the NRCS phosphorus index detailed report shall satisfy the requirement to include the factors used in the calculation._</p> <p>-The NMPs/MMPs use the Iowa Phosphorus Index, which is a NRCS developed tool.</p>
<p>Do your NMP/MMPS follow, comply with, or based on NRCS Technical Standard 590?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Application rates: <i>State regulations that restrict the rates at which manures are applied and methods needed to determine appropriate rates.</i></p>	<p>* Application rate based on crop nitrogen use. A confinement feeding operation that is required to submit a manure management plan to the department under rule 567-65.16(459,459B) shall not apply manure in excess of the nitrogen use levels necessary to obtain optimum crop yields. Calculations to determine the maximum manure application rate allowed under this subrule shall be performed pursuant to rule 567-65.17(459,459B). _</p> <p>* To determine optimum yield (which sets the nutrients that can be applied), they can either use: (1) interpretation from soil survey based on soil map units, (2) county crop yields from IASS, or (3) actual yields from most recent three years. There are multiple options for using actual yields: verified data from FSA, from multiperil crop insurance, or other methods. They even allow optimum yields to either drop the lowest yield or allow for a 10% increase. _</p> <p>* Have to submit a crop schedule, but this can change for weather, farm program changes, markets, or unforeseeable circumstances. _</p> <p>* Soil samples (pH and P) must be taken for each field where the P index is to be used. Methods include the need to take at least 10 cores from top six inch every ten acres. Fields of 15 acres or less need only one set of ten samples. Acceptable soil sampling strategies include, but are not limited to, grid sampling, management zone sampling, and soil type sampling. Procedural details can be taken from Iowa State University extension publication PM 287, Take a Good Soil Sample to Help Make Good Decisions, NCR-13 Report 348, Soil Sampling for Variable-Rate Fertilizer and Lime Application, or other credible soil sampling publications. _</p> <p>* Iowa uses a P-index approach to guide manure applications w.</p>

	<p>respect to P for all fields in a manure management plan (fields must be contiguous). Specific details on P index include: _</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">* Use an average of STP's from each field (arithmetic mean)_* STP data must be four years old or less_* Using ratings from NRCS Iowa Technical Note No. 25, the following are rules for manure application: _* Very Low (0-1). _<ul style="list-style-type: none">* 1. Manure shall not be applied in excess of a nitrogen-based rate in accordance with 65.17(18). _* 2. If, pursuant to 65.17(19), manure is applied at phosphorus-based rates within soil sampling periods on fields in the Very Low risk category, each soil sample may represent up to 20 acres for the next required soil sampling. _* Low (>1-2). _<ul style="list-style-type: none">* 1. Manure shall not be applied in excess of a nitrogen-based rate in accordance with 65.17(18). _* 2. If, pursuant to 65.17(19), manure is applied at phosphorus-based rates within soil sampling periods on fields in the Low risk category, each soil sample may represent up to 20 acres for the next required soil sampling. _* Medium (>2-5). _<ul style="list-style-type: none">* 1. Manure may be applied at a nitrogen-based rate in accordance with 65.17(18) if current or planned soil conservation and phosphorus management practices predict the rating of the field to be not greater than 5 for the next determination of the phosphorus index as required by 65.17(17)h-2(3). _* 2. Manure shall not be applied in excess of two times the phosphorus removed with crop harvest over the period of the crop rotation_* 3. If, pursuant to 65.17(19), manure is applied at phosphorus-based rates within soil sampling periods on fields in the Medium risk category, each soil sample may represent up to 20 acres for the next required soil sampling. _* High (>5-15). Manure shall not be applied on a field with a rating greater than 5 and less than or equal to 15 until practices are adopted which reduce the phosphorus index to at least the Medium risk category._* Very High (>15). Manure shall not be applied on a field with a rating greater than 15. _* An operation does not have to update their P-index for a field if nothing changes except every four years._* Rules for N application: use total N content unless submit calculations showing N crop use > plant-available N. Includes correction factors depending on application method. Says optimum crop yield should be used to determine N rates unless applying to or before soybeans; in this case available N cannot exceed 100lbs/acre. Also notes that N rates should account for previously planted legume and any planned fertilizer applications. Manure
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	<p>application to land that will be planted with soybeans can not exceed 100 lbs. N/acre._</p> <p>* Must calculate P applied based on optimum yield and crop removal from Table 4a. Cannot exceed N requirement of planned crop, and cannot exceed P removed in next 4 crops in schedule (eg a 4 yr rate)_</p> <p>* Manure can't be applied to a field with a high-2 or very high-2 P index value. No cap-2 based on soil test alone.</p>
<p>Manure application rates for phosphorus are based on:</p> <p>1) <i>Phosphorus Index Only</i></p> <p>2) <i>Soil Test Phosphorus Only</i></p> <p>3) <i>Either PIO or STPO</i></p> <p>4) <i>Other</i></p>	Phosphorus index only
Are there any nutrient “caps” to manure application?	No
Composition testing: <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on manures before application</i>	Determining amount of N&P in manure can be done in multiple ways. Can either calculate based on Table 3 of this code, or other credible sources for standard table values or the actual N and P content-2. OR they can use an actual sample of manure and measured volume or weight from storage structure. Manure sample must be taken in accordance with Iowa State extension PM 1558
Does your state require testing of manure for anything beyond nutrients, such as metals, pathogens, antibiotics, etc.?	No
Other land application highlights: <i>Additional restrictions for land application of manures</i>	Open feedlots are treated differently as they may or may not collect their effluent and land apply. Generally they have to follow the same rules as above if collecting and applying manure. However, there are additional rules in terms of feedlot design so
Other regulatory details: <i>Additional information on the regulation of land application of manures</i>	No other information
General Assessment Questions	
Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may	Undetermined

potentially change:	
Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of manures that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links:	No
Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of manures beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so:	No
Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.	No other information

Kansas	
Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2025
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Kansas Department of Health and Environment (KDHE)
Links to regulations	KAR 28-18-1: regulates animal and related waste control_ KAR 28-18a-1: regulates swine and related waste control_ https://www.kdhe.ks.gov/490/Statutes-Regulations-for-Livestock-Waste
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Environmental
Other regulator info	No other information
Definitions	
How CAFOs are defined or categorized:	"Confined Feeding Facility" means any lot, pen, pool or pond: (A) Which is used for the confined feeding of animals or fowl for food, fur or pleasure purposes; (B) which is not normally used for raising crops; and (C) in which no vegetation intended for animal food is growing.
How animal units are defined (if used):	"Animal unit" means a unit of measurement calculated by adding the following numbers: The number of beef cattle weighing more than 700 pounds multiplied by 1.0; plus the number of cattle weighing less than 700 pounds multiplied by 0.5; plus the number of mature dairy cattle multiplied by 1.4; plus the number of swine weighing more than 55 pounds multiplied by 0.4; plus the number of swine weighing 55 pounds or less multiplied by 0.1; plus the number of sheep or lambs multiplied by 0.1; plus the number of horses multiplied by 2.0; plus the number of turkeys multiplied by 0.018; plus the number of laying hens or broilers, if the facility has continuous overflow watering, multiplied by 0.01; plus the number of laying hens or broilers, if the facility has a liquid manure system, multiplied by 0.033; plus the number of ducks multiplied by 0.2. However, each head of cattle will be counted as one full animal unit for the purpose of determining the need for a federal permit. "Animal unit" also includes the number of swine weighing 55 pounds or less multiplied by 0.1 for the purpose of determining applicable requirements for new construction of a confined feeding facility for which a permit or registration has not been issued before January 1, 1998, and for which an application for a permit or registration and plans have not been filed with the secretary of health and environment before January 1, 1998, or for the purpose of determining applicable requirements for expansion of such facility. Except as otherwise provided, animal units for public livestock markets shall be determined by using the average annual animal units sold by the market during the past five calendar years divided by 365. Such animal unit determination may be adjusted by

	the department if the public livestock market submits documentation that demonstrates that such adjustment is appropriate based on the amount of time in 24-hour increments or partials thereof that animals are at the market.
NPDES permitting or other permitting requirements:	A permit shall be required for:_ (1) Any confined feeding facility with an animal unit capacity of 300 to 999 if the secretary determines that the facility has significant water pollution potential; and_ (2) any confined feeding facility with an animal unit capacity of 1,000 or more.
Does the state require an NPDES permit for all Large CAFOs?	Yes
Does the state issue individual or general CAFO permits?	Both
Are any other permits required for CAFOs or other large farms?	Undetermined
Other definitions needed to understand these regulations:	No other information
Regulatory Details	
Setbacks: <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some geographical feature</i>	Facilities that are required to have a nutrient utilization plan shall not apply manure or wastewater to any areas to which the separation distance requirements of subsection (f) apply. [subsection (f): each swine facility that is required to have a nutrient utilization plan shall include in such plan, and thereafter comply with, the requirements that manure or wastewater shall not be applied on bare ground by any process, other than incorporation into the soil during the same day, within 1,000 feet of any habitable structure, wildlife refuge or city, county, state or federal park unless: (A) The manure or wastewater has been subjected to physical, biological or biochemical treatment or other treatment method for odor reduction approved by the department of health and environment; (B) the manure or wastewater is applied with innovative treatment or application that is best available technology for swine facilities and best management practices for swine facilities or other technology approved by the department of health and environment; or (C) the owner of the habitable structure has provided a written waiver to the facility.
Are setbacks more restrictive than CFR?	Yes
Timing, weather, or conditional application restrictions: <i>State regulations that</i>	Facilities that are required to have a nutrient utilization plan shall not apply manure or wastewater:_ (A) To lands classified as highly erodible according to the conservation compliance provisions of the federal food security act

<p><i>restrict land application under certain weather, seasons, or land characteristics (like slope)</i></p>	<p>of 1985, as in effect on the effective date of this act, and classified as highly erodible on the basis of erosion resulting from water runoff, except where soil conservation practices to control erosion and runoff in compliance with the requirements of this section are identified in the facility's nutrient utilization plan and are followed by the facility;_</p> <p>(B) during rain storms, except where soil conservation practices to control erosion and runoff in compliance with the requirements of this section are identified in the facility's nutrient utilization plan and are followed by the facility;_</p> <p>(C) to frozen or saturated soil, except where soil conservation practices to control runoff in compliance with the requirements of this section are identified in the facility's nutrient utilization plan and are followed by the facility; and_</p> <p>(D) to any areas to which the separation distance requirements of subsection (f) apply._</p> <p>_</p> <p>Swine facilities that are required to have a nutrient utilization plan and that conduct wastewater irrigation shall:_</p> <p>(A) Employ measures to irrigate under conditions that reasonably prevent surface runoff; and_</p> <p>(B) use reasonable procedures and precautions to avoid spray drift from the land to which it is applied.</p>
<p>Is there a restriction for land application of manure to saturated soils?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Is there a restriction for land application of manure within floodplains?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Is there a restriction for land application of manure related to future rainfall?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Is there a restriction for land application of manure to frozen or snow-covered ground?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Are there restrictions to manure applications based on time of year or time of day?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Are there restrictions to manure application based on slope?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Are there any other seasonal, timing, weather, or physical restrictions to</p>	<p>No</p>

manure applications not captured above?	
Transfer of manure off-site: <i>Requirements related to the transfer of manures to other persons</i>	Refer to CFR
Are receivers of manure transfers from CAFOs required to follow the same regulations?	No
Nutrient or manure management plans: <i>Additional details on the NMP requirement. Note that some of this information may overlap with other sections</i>	Each applicant for a permit for construction of a new swine facility having an animal unit capacity of 1,000 or more or expansion of an existing swine facility to an animal unit capacity of 1,000 or more shall submit with the application for a permit a manure management plan and shall comply with the plan when the permit is issued by the department.
Do your NMP/MMPS follow, comply with, or based on NRCS Technical Standard 590?	Yes
Application rates: <i>State regulations that restrict the rates at which manures are applied and methods needed to determine appropriate rates.</i>	<p>Soil Testing_ Conduct soil tests, including but not limited to tests for nitrogen, phosphate, chloride, copper and zinc, on the land application areas prior to preparation of the nutrient utilization plan and at least annually thereafter, or as often as required by best available soil science and standards relative to the soils of, and crops to be grown on, the land application areas or as required by the secretary of health and environment._</p> <p>– Rates_ Each swine facility that has a manure management plan that includes land application of manure or wastewater shall:_ (A) Compare the manure nutrient analyses required by subsection (c)(2) with the soil tests required by subsection (c)(1) to calculate needed fertility and application rates for pasture production and crop target yields on the land application areas prior to the preparation of the nutrient utilization plan and each time thereafter when new soil tests or manure nutrient analyses are conducted_</p> <p>– If a swine facility is required to have a nutrient utilization plan and finds that the soil tests required pursuant to this act indicate that the phosphorus holding capacity for any soils in the facility's land application areas may be exceeded within five years, the facility shall promptly initiate the process to obtain access to the additional land application areas needed, or make other adjustments, to achieve the capability to apply manure or wastewater at appropriate</p>

	<p>agronomic rates._</p> <p>– Swine facilities that are required to have a nutrient utilization plan shall follow procedures and precautions in the land application of manure or wastewater to prevent discharge of manure or wastewater to surface water and groundwater due to excess infiltration, penetration of drainage tile lines, introduction into tile inlets or surface runoff, including appropriate soil conservation practices to protect surface water from runoff carrying eroded soil and manure particles.</p>
<p>Manure application rates for phosphorus are based on:</p> <p>1) <i>Phosphorus Index Only</i> 2) <i>Soil Test Phosphorus Only</i> 3) <i>Either PIO or STPO</i> 4) <i>Other</i></p>	Soil test phosphorus only
<p>Are there any nutrient “caps” to manure application?</p>	No
<p>Composition testing: <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on manures before application</i></p>	<p>Each facility that has a manure management plan that includes land application of manure or wastewater or sells or gives manure or wastewater to third persons pursuant to subsection (h) of K.S.A. 65-1,181 and shall conduct manure nutrient analyses of its manure and wastewater prior to preparation of its nutrient utilization plan and at least every two years thereafter.</p>
<p>Does your state require testing of manure for anything beyond nutrients, such as metals, pathogens, antibiotics, etc.?</p>	No
<p>Other land application highlights: <i>Additional restrictions for land application of manures</i></p>	No other information
<p>Other regulatory details: <i>Additional information on the regulation of land application of manures</i></p>	No other information
General Assessment Questions	
<p>Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please</p>	Undetermined

list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change:	
Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of manures that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links:	No
Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of manures beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so:	No
Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.	No other information

Kentucky Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2025
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Kentucky Energy and Environment Cabinet: Department for Environmental Protection, Division of Water
Links to regulations	401 KAR 5:005. Permits to construct, modify, or operate a facility._ https://apps.legislature.ky.gov/law/kar/titles/401/005/005/ _ _ Links to regulations:_ https://eec.ky.gov/Environmental-Protection/Water/PermitCert/KPDES/Pages/AFOs-and-CAFOs.aspx
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Environmental
Other regulator info	No other information
Definitions	
How CAFOs are defined or categorized:	CAFO is defined as large concentrated Animal Feeding Operation, medium concentrated Animal Feeding Operation, and small concentrated Animal Feeding Operation, and the requirements for each are found in 401 KAR 5:002
How animal units are defined (if used):	Animal Units are no longer used.
NPDES permitting or other permitting requirements:	If an Animal Feeding Operation does not discharge, or intend to discharge, the Cabinet shall not consider it a CAFO, regardless of size. _ If an Animal Feeding Operation does not discharge, does not intend to discharge, and obtains a Kentucky No-Discharge Operational Permit pursuant to this section, the cabinet shall not consider the Animal Feeding Operation a CAFO._ _ Operations that are defined as Concentrated Animal Feeding Operations (CAFOs) pursuant to 401 KAR 5:060, Section 10, are required to obtain a Kentucky Pollutant Discharge Elimination System (KPDES) permit._ Any AFO with a liquid manure handling system is required to have a state operational permit.
Does the state require an NPDES permit for all Large CAFOs?	No
Does the state issue individual or general CAFO permits?	Individual
Are any other permits required for CAFOs or other large farms?	Yes

Other definitions needed to understand these regulations:	No other information
Regulatory Details	
Setbacks: <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some geographical feature</i>	Refer to 40 CFR
Are setbacks more restrictive than CFR?	No
Timing, weather, or conditional application restrictions: <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather, seasons, or land characteristics (like slope)</i>	No regulations, but the typical state operational permit issued to AFOs does have restrictions based on our Best Professional Judgment
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to saturated soils?	Yes
Is there a restriction for land application of manure within floodplains?	No
Is there a restriction for land application of manure related to future rainfall?	No
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to frozen or snow-covered ground?	Yes
Are there restrictions to manure applications based on time of year or time of day?	No
Are there restrictions to manure application based on slope?	No
Are there any other seasonal, timing, weather, or physical restrictions to manure applications not	Land application that results in runoff is prohibited. Buffer strips shall be maintained around land application areas. A land application area shall not be located in a state or national park, forest, nature preserve or a wellhead protection area.

captured above?	
Transfer of manure off-site: <i>Requirements related to the transfer of manures to other persons</i>	Refer to CFR
Are receivers of manure transfers from CAFOs required to follow the same regulations?	No
Nutrient or manure management plans: <i>Additional details on the NMP requirement. Note that some of this information may overlap with other sections</i>	<p>An Animal Feeding Operation shall have a nutrient management plan consistent with the Agriculture Water Quality Act, KRS 224.71-100 through 224.71-145 and the NRCS Conservation Practice Standard Code 590 for Kentucky._</p> <p>– General Permits in the state have required the submittal of a Comprehensive Nutrient Management Plan (CNMP). The CNMP is based upon the Natural Resources Conservation Service (NRCS) 590 guideline for Kentucky updated in January 2013 or equivalent (NRCS, 2013). Note: If all components of the CNMP required by the General Permit are incorporated into the AWQP, then a separate CNMP is not necessary and the permittee may operate under one comprehensive AWQP. Regulation 401 KAR 5:005 Section 25 indicates that facilities applying for KNDOPs must have an NMP to be consistent with the Agriculture Water Quality Act or the NRCS Conservation Practice Standard Code 590._</p> <p>– The Kentucky Agriculture Water Quality Plan: If greater than 10 acres in size are required to adhere to the BMPs specified in the Kentucky Agriculture Water Quality Plan (AWQP) The AWQP consists of BMPs from the following areas: silviculture; pesticides and fertilizers; farmstead; crops; livestock; and streams and other waterbodies. Each BMP includes definitions and descriptions, regulatory requirements, Agriculture Water Quality Authority requirements, design information, practice maintenance, technical assistance, cost share assistance, recommendations and references.</p>
Do your NMP/MMPS follow, comply with, or based on NRCS Technical Standard 590?	Yes
Application rates: <i>State regulations that restrict the rates at which manures are applied and methods needed to determine appropriate rates.</i>	NRCS Conservation Practice Standard Code 590

<p>Manure application rates for phosphorus are based on:</p> <p>1) <i>Phosphorus Index Only</i> 2) <i>Soil Test Phosphorus Only</i> 3) <i>Either PIO or STPO</i> 4) <i>Other</i></p>	Soil test phosphorus only
<p>Are there any nutrient “caps” to manure application?</p>	No
<p>Composition testing: <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on manures before application</i></p>	Refer to CFR
<p>Does your state require testing of manure for anything beyond nutrients, such as metals, pathogens, antibiotics, etc.?</p>	No
<p>Other land application highlights: <i>Additional restrictions for land application of manures</i></p>	No other information
<p>Other regulatory details: <i>Additional information on the regulation of land application of manures</i></p>	No other information
General Assessment Questions	
<p>Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change:</p>	Undetermined
<p>Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of manures that we haven’t captured? If yes, please describe or provide links:</p>	Yes

<p>Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of manures beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so:</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.</p>	<p>No other information</p>

Louisiana Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2019
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Louisiana Department of Environmental Quality (LDEQ)
Links to regulations	Title 33: Environmental Quality Part IX. Water Quality Subpart 1. Water Pollution Control:_ http://deq.louisiana.gov/assets/docs/Legal_Affairs/ERC/33v09wq.docx
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Environmental
Other regulator info	No other information
Definitions	
How CAFOs are defined or categorized:	<p>"Animal Feeding Operation" (AFO)- a lot or facility (other than an aquatic animal production facility) where the following conditions are met: a. animals (other than aquatic animals) have been, are, or will be stabled or confined and fed or maintained for a total of 45 days or more in any 12-month period; and b. crops, vegetation, forage growth, or post-harvest residues are not sustained in the normal growing season over any portion of the lot or facility._</p> <p>–</p> <p>"Concentrated Animal Feeding Operation" (CAFO)- an AFO that is defined as a Large CAFO or as a Medium CAFO by the terms of this Subsection, or that is designated as a CAFO in accordance with Subsection C of this Section. Two or more AFOs under common ownership are considered to be a single AFO for the purposes of determining the number of animals at an operation, if they adjoin each other or if they use a common area or system for the disposal of wastes._</p> <p>–</p> <p>"Large Concentrated Animal Feeding Operation" (Large CAFO) - an AFO that stables or confines as many as or more than the numbers of animals specified in any of the following categories: _</p> <p>a. 700 mature dairy cows, whether milked or dry; _</p> <p>b. 1,000 veal calves; _</p> <p>c. 1,000 cattle other than mature dairy cows or veal calves (Cattle includes but is not limited to heifers, steers, bulls, and cow/calf pairs.);</p> <p>–</p> <p>d. 2,500 swine, each weighing 55 pounds or more; _</p> <p>e. 10,000 swine, each weighing less than 55 pounds; _</p> <p>f. 500 horses; _</p> <p>g. 10,000 sheep or lambs; _</p> <p>h. 55,000 turkeys; _</p> <p>i. 30,000 laying hens or broilers, if the AFO uses a liquid manure handling system; _</p> <p>j. 125,000 chickens (other than laying hens), if the AFO uses other than</p>

	<p>a liquid manure handling system; _</p> <p>k. 82,000 laying hens, if the AFO uses other than a liquid manure handling system;_</p> <p>l. 30,000 ducks, if the AFO uses other than a liquid manure handling system; or _</p> <p>m. 5,000 ducks, if the AFO uses a liquid manure handling system._</p> <p>_</p> <p>"Medium Concentrated Animal Feeding Operation" (Medium CAFO)- includes any AFO with the type and number of animals that fall within any of the ranges listed in this definition and that has been defined or designated as a CAFO. An AFO is a Medium CAFO if: _</p> <p>a. the type and number of animals that it stables or confines falls within any of the following ranges: _</p> <p>i. 200 to 699 mature dairy cows, whether milked or dry;_</p> <p>ii. 300 to 999 veal calves; _</p> <p>iii. 300 to 999 cattle other than mature dairy cows or veal calves (Cattle includes but is not limited to heifers, steers, bulls, and cow/calf pairs.);</p> <p>_</p> <p>iv. 750 to 2,499 swine, each weighing 55 pounds or more; _</p> <p>v. 3,000 to 9,999 swine, each weighing less than 55 pounds; _</p> <p>vi. 150 to 499 horses; _</p> <p>vii. 3,000 to 9,999 sheep or lambs; _</p> <p>viii. 16,500 to 54,999 turkeys; _</p> <p>ix. 9,000 to 29,999 laying hens or broilers, if the AFO uses a liquid manure handling system; _</p> <p>x. 37,500 to 124,999 chickens (other than laying hens), if the AFO uses other than a liquid manure handling system; _</p> <p>xi. 25,000 to 81,999 laying hens, if the AFO uses other than a liquid manure handling system; _</p> <p>xii. 10,000 to 29,999 ducks, if the AFO uses other than a liquid manure handling system; or _</p> <p>xiii. 1,500 to 4,999 ducks, if the AFO uses a liquid manure handling system; and _</p> <p>b. either one of the following conditions are met: _</p> <p>i. pollutants are discharged into waters of the state through a manmade ditch, flushing system, or other similar manmade device; or</p> <p>_</p> <p>ii. pollutants are discharged directly into waters of the state that originate outside of and pass over, across, or through the facility or otherwise come into direct contact with the animals confined in the operation.</p>
How animal units are defined (if used):	Not used
NPDES permitting or other permitting requirements:	The owner or operator of a CAFO must seek coverage under an LPDES permit if the CAFO discharges or proposes to discharge a regulated wastewater. A CAFO proposes to discharge if it is designed, constructed, operated, or maintained such that a discharge of regulated wastewater will occur. Specifically, the CAFO owner or

	<p>operator must either apply for an individual LPDES permit or submit a notice of intent for coverage under an LPDES general permit. If the state administrative authority has not made a general permit available to the CAFO, the CAFO owner or operator must submit an application for an individual permit to the state administrative authority._</p> <p>–</p> <p>Land application discharges from a CAFO are subject to LPDES requirements. The discharge of manure, litter, or process wastewater to waters of the state from a CAFO as a result of the application of that manure, litter, or process wastewater by the CAFO to land areas under its control is a discharge from that CAFO subject to LPDES permit requirements, except where it is an agricultural storm water discharge as provided in 33 U.S.C. 1362(14). For purposes of this Subsection, where the manure, litter, or process wastewater has been applied in accordance with site-specific nutrient management practices that ensure appropriate agricultural utilization of the nutrients in the manure, litter, or process wastewater, as specified under LAC 33:IX.2703.E.1.f-i, a precipitation-related discharge of manure, litter, or process wastewater from land areas under the control of a CAFO is an agricultural storm water discharge. _</p> <p>1. For unpermitted Large CAFOs, a precipitation related discharge of manure, litter, or process wastewater from land areas under the control of a CAFO shall be considered an agricultural storm water discharge only where the manure, litter, or process wastewater has been land applied in accordance with site-specific nutrient management practices that ensure appropriate agricultural utilization of the nutrients in the manure, litter, or process wastewater, as specified in LAC 33:IX.2703.E.1.f-i. _</p> <p>2. Unpermitted Large CAFOs must maintain documentation specified in LAC 33:IX.2703.E.1.i either on site or at a nearby office, or otherwise make such documentation readily available to the state administrative authority upon request.</p>
Does the state require an NPDES permit for all Large CAFOs?	No
Does the state issue individual or general CAFO permits?	Individual
Are any other permits required for CAFOs or other large farms?	No
Other definitions needed to understand these regulations:	No other information
Regulatory Details	
Setbacks: <i>State regulations that</i>	Refer to 40 CFR

<i>indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some geographical feature</i>	
Are setbacks more restrictive than CFR?	No
Timing, weather, or conditional application restrictions: <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather, seasons, or land characteristics (like slope)</i>	None
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to saturated soils?	No
Is there a restriction for land application of manure within floodplains?	No
Is there a restriction for land application of manure related to future rainfall?	No
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to frozen or snow-covered ground?	No
Are there restrictions to manure applications based on time of year or time of day?	No
Are there restrictions to manure application based on slope?	No
Are there any other seasonal, timing, weather, or physical restrictions to manure applications not captured above?	No
Transfer of manure off-site: <i>Requirements related to</i>	Refer to CFR

<i>the transfer of manures to other persons</i>	
Are receivers of manure transfers from CAFOs required to follow the same regulations?	No
Nutrient or manure management plans: <i>Additional details on the NMP requirement. Note that some of this information may overlap with other sections</i>	Any permit issued to a CAFO must include a requirement to implement a nutrient management plan that, at a minimum, contains best management practices necessary to meet the requirements of this Paragraph and applicable effluent limitations and standards, including those specified in 40 CFR Part 412. CAFOs can use a linear or narrative approach.
Do your NMP/MMPS follow, comply with, or based on NRCS Technical Standard 590?	Yes
Application rates: <i>State regulations that restrict the rates at which manures are applied and methods needed to determine appropriate rates.</i>	<p>Linear Approach: The terms must include maximum application rates from manure, litter, and process wastewater for each year of permit coverage, for each crop identified in the nutrient management plan, in chemical forms determined to be acceptable to the state administrative authority, in pounds per acre, per year, for each field to be used for land application, and certain factors necessary to determine such rates. At a minimum, the factors used in the terms must include: the outcome of the field-specific assessment of the potential for nitrogen and phosphorus transport from each field; the crops to be planted in each field or any other uses of a field, such as a pasture or fallow field; the realistic yield goal for each crop or use identified for each field; the nitrogen and phosphorus recommendations from sources specified by the state administrative authority for each crop or use identified for each field; credits for all nitrogen in the field that will be plant-available; consideration of multi-year phosphorus application; and accounting for all other additions of plant-available nitrogen and phosphorus to the field. In addition, the terms must include the form and source of manure, litter, and process wastewater to be land applied; the timing and method of land application; and the methodology by which the nutrient management plan accounts for the amount of nitrogen and phosphorus in the manure, litter, and process wastewater to be applied._</p> <p>– Narrative Approach: _</p> <p>i. The terms must include maximum amounts of nitrogen and phosphorus derived from all sources of nutrients, for each crop identified in the nutrient management plan, in chemical forms determined to be acceptable to the state administrative authority, in pounds per acre, for each field, and certain factors necessary to determine such amounts. At a minimum, the factors used in the terms must include: the outcome of the field-specific assessment of the</p>

potential for nitrogen and phosphorus transport from each field; the crops to be planted in each field or any other uses, such as pasture or fallow fields (including alternative crops identified in accordance with Clause E.5.b.ii of this Section); the realistic yield goal for each crop or use identified for each field; and the nitrogen and phosphorus recommendations from sources specified by the state administrative authority for each crop or use identified for each field. In addition, the terms must include the methodology by which the nutrient management plan accounts for the following factors when calculating the amounts of manure, litter, and process wastewater to be land applied: results of soil tests conducted in accordance with protocols identified in the nutrient management plan, as required by Subparagraph E.1.g of this Section; credits for all nitrogen in the field that will be plant-available; the amount of nitrogen and phosphorus in the manure, litter, and process wastewater to be applied; consideration of multiyear phosphorus application; accounting for all other additions of plant-available nitrogen and phosphorus to the field; the form and source of manure, litter, and process wastewater; the timing and method of land application; and volatilization of nitrogen and mineralization of organic nitrogen._

ii. The terms of the nutrient management plan may include alternative crops identified in the CAFO's nutrient management plan that are not in the planned crop rotation. Where a CAFO includes alternative crops in its nutrient management plan, the crops must be listed by field, in addition to the crops identified in the planned crop rotation for that field, and the nutrient management plan must include realistic crop yield goals and the nitrogen and phosphorus recommendations from sources specified by the state administrative authority for each crop. Maximum amounts of nitrogen and phosphorus from all sources of nutrients and the amounts of manure, litter, and process wastewater to be applied must be determined in accordance with the methodology described in Clause E.5.b.i of this Section. _

iii. For CAFOs using this approach, the following projections must be included in the nutrient management plan submitted to the state administrative authority, but are not terms of the nutrient management plan: the CAFO's planned crop rotations for each field for the period of permit coverage; the projected amount of manure, litter, or process wastewater to be applied; projected credits for all nitrogen in the field that will be plant-available; consideration of multiyear phosphorus application; accounting for all other additions of plant-available nitrogen and phosphorus to the field; and the predicted form, source, and method of application of manure, litter, and process wastewater for each crop. Timing of application for each field, insofar as it concerns the calculation of rates of application, is not a term of the nutrient management plan._

iv. CAFOs that use this approach must calculate maximum amounts of manure, litter, and process wastewater to be land applied at least once each year using the methodology required in Clause E.5.b.i of this

	Section before land applying manure, litter, and process wastewater, and must rely on the following data: (a). a field-specific determination of soil levels of nitrogen and phosphorus, including, for nitrogen, a concurrent determination of nitrogen that will be plant available consistent with the methodology required by Clause E.5.b.i of this Section, and for phosphorus, the results of the most recent soil test conducted in accordance with soil testing requirements approved by the state administrative authority; and (b). the results of most recent representative manure, litter, and process wastewater tests for nitrogen and phosphorus taken within 12 months of the date of land application, in order to determine the amount of nitrogen and phosphorus in the manure, litter, and process wastewater to be applied.
Manure application rates for phosphorus are based on: 1) <i>Phosphorus Index Only</i> 2) <i>Soil Test Phosphorus Only</i> 3) <i>Either PIO or STPO</i> 4) <i>Other</i>	Soil test phosphorus only
Are there any nutrient “caps” to manure application?	No
Composition testing: <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on manures before application</i>	In both the linear and narrative approach, CAFOs ach must calculate the maximum amount of manure, litter, and process wastewater to be land applied at least once each year using the results of the most recent representative manure, litter, and process wastewater tests for nitrogen and phosphorus taken within 12 months of the date of land application.
Does your state require testing of manure for anything beyond nutrients, such as metals, pathogens, antibiotics, etc.?	Yes
Other land application highlights: <i>Additional restrictions for land application of manures</i>	No other information
Other regulatory details: <i>Additional information on the regulation of land application of manures</i>	No other information
General Assessment Questions	

<p>Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change:</p>	<p>Undetermined</p>
<p>Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of manures that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links:</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of manures beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so:</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.</p>	<p>No other information</p>

Maine Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2019
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Maine Department of Environmental Protection (MEDEP)_ Maine Department of Agriculture, Conservation, and Forestry (DACF)_
Links to regulations	Code of Maine Rules (CMR), 06-096, Chapter 521:_ https://www.maine.gov/sos/cec/rules/06/chaps06.htm _ _ CMR 01-001 Chapter 565, Nutrient Management Rules_ https://www.maine.gov/dacf/php/nutrient_management/index.shtml _ Maine Nutrient Management Law, 7:4201 et seq _ _ Application for Maine Pollutant Discharge Elimination System Permit/Maine Waste Discharge License And Livestock Operating Permit_ Concentrated Animal Feeding Operation (CAFO)_ www.maine.gov/dep/water/wd/municipal_industrial/appcafo.doc
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	More than one agency
Other regulator info	The NM Rules were updated in 2018. However, the DEP rules have to be made consistent with the current EPA CAFO Rules. Some DEP rules are on the books, but are not used.
Definitions	
How CAFOs are defined or categorized:	Large CAFOs An AFO is defined as an operation that stables or_ confines and feeds or maintains (for a total of 45 days or more in any 12-month period) equivalent to the numbers of animals presented below. _ Medium CAFOs are AFOs discharge pollutants into waters of the state_ either through a man-made ditch, flushing system, or other similar man-made device, or directly into waters of the state that originates outside of and passes over, across, or through the facility or otherwise comes into direct contact with animals confined in the operation and with the number of animals shown._ Case-by-case designation of concentrated Animal Feeding Operations. _ The Department may designate any Animal Feeding Operation as a concentrated Animal Feeding Operation upon determining that it is a significant contributor of pollution to the waters of the State. In making this designation the Department shall consider the following factors:_ (i) The size of the Animal Feeding Operation and the amount of

	<p>wastes reaching waters of the State;_</p> <p>(ii) The location of the Animal Feeding Operation relative to waters of the State;_</p> <p>(iii) The means of conveyance of animal wastes and process wastewaters into waters of the State;_</p> <p>(iv) The slope, vegetation, rainfall, and other factors affecting the likelihood or frequency of discharge of animal wastes and process waste waters into waters of the State; and_</p> <p>(v) Other relevant factors._</p> <p>No Animal Feeding Operation with less than the numbers of animals set forth in appendix B shall be designated as a concentrated Animal Feeding Operation unless:_</p> <p>(i) Pollutants are discharged into waters of the State through a manmade ditch, flushing system, or other similar manmade device; or_</p> <p>(ii) Pollutants are discharged directly into waters of the State which originate outside of the facility and pass over, across, or through the facility or otherwise come into direct contact with the animals confined in the operation._</p> <p>Large CAFO:_</p> <p>(a) More than the numbers of animals specified in any of the following categories are confined:_</p> <p>(1) 1,000 slaughter and feeder cattle,_</p> <p>(2) 700 mature dairy cattle (whether milked or dry cows),_</p> <p>(3) 2,500 swine each weighing over 25 kilograms (approximately 55 pounds),_</p> <p>(4) 500 horses,_</p> <p>(5) 10,000 sheep or lambs,_</p> <p>(6) 55,000 turkeys,_</p> <p>(8) 30,000 laying hens or broilers (if the facility has a liquid manure system),_</p> <p>(9) 5,000 ducks, or_</p> <p>Medium CAFO:_</p> <p>(b) More than the following number and types of animals are confined:_</p> <p>(1) 300 slaughter or feeder cattle,_</p> <p>(2) 200 mature dairy cattle (whether milked or dry cows),_</p> <p>(3) 750 swine each weighing over 25 kilograms (approximately 55 pounds),_</p> <p>(4) 150 horses,_</p> <p>(5) 3,000 sheep or lambs,_</p> <p>(6) 16,500 turkeys,_</p> <p>overflow watering),_</p> <p>(8) 9,000 laying hens or broilers (if the facility has a liquid manure handling system),_</p> <p>(9) 1,500 ducks</p>
<p>How animal units are defined (if used):</p>	<p>The term "animal unit" means: One animal unit = 1000 lb. of live animal. The term manmade means constructed by man and used for</p>

	the purpose of transporting wastes.
NPDES permitting or other permitting requirements:	<p>The MEDEP administers the MEPDES program that contains many CAFO requirements and issues MEPDES permits._</p> <p>A permit application shall not be required from a concentrated Animal Feeding Operation designated under this paragraph until the Department has conducted an on-site inspection of the operation and determined that the operation should and could be regulated under the permit program. Large CAFOs determined not to have a discharge are not required to have a MEPDES permit._</p> <p>–</p> <p>Farms with 300 or more animal units, and CAFOs, are required to have a Livestock Operations Permit. However, farms that had 300 or more animal units on April 15, 1998 are not required to get an LOP unless the operation is a CAFO.</p>
Does the state require an NPDES permit for all Large CAFOs?	No
Does the state issue individual or general CAFO permits?	Individual
Are any other permits required for CAFOs or other large farms?	Yes
Other definitions needed to understand these regulations:	No other information
Regulatory Details	
<p>Setbacks:</p> <p><i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some geographical feature</i></p>	<p>Site-specific setbacks and siting standards for spreading manure, and for long-term and temporary storage of manure in the farm production area and on field stacking facilities, that will minimize nuisance complaints and threats to surface and ground water; Site-specific setbacks must be prescribed by a qualified professional. Qualified professionals include qualified NRCS, SWCD, or Department employees, Maine certified nutrient management planning specialists, or Maine certified professional soil scientists, who have expertise for making these determinations. Justification for the site specific setbacks utilized must be provided if the setback recommendations are less stringent than those recommended in the Department's Manure Utilization Guidelines. Temporary manure storage sites where manure is stacked on the natural soil surface for less than two weeks must meet setbacks in the Department's Manure Utilization Guidelines and separation distances in the table Minimum Separation Distances from Ground Features for Manure Stacking Sites. Setbacks for manure application sites to drinking water wells must be a minimum of 100 feet for private wells and 300 feet for public wells; Setbacks for manure storage and stacking sites</p>

	is determined by whether the sensitive feature is upslope or downslope from the storage site (see the attached Manure Stacking Guidelines document). These setbacks may be modified by a qualified individual if conditions warrant an alternative setback.
Are setbacks more restrictive than CFR?	Yes
Timing, weather, or conditional application restrictions: <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather, seasons, or land characteristics (like slope)</i>	<p>Winter Manure Spreading Ban:_ In accordance with 7 M.R.S. §4207, a person may not spread manure on agricultural fields from December 1 of a calendar year through March 15 of the following calendar year._ The Commissioner may grant a variance on the Winter Manure Spreading Ban or in case of emergency. An emergency request may be made verbally to the Commissioner (or designee), followed by a written request application to the Commissioner within 10 days of the verbal request._ Designated Shoreland Zones have restrictions on land application of manure in floodplains._ 38:417A. Manure spreading. Says no manure spreading on fields with frozen ground within a great pond watershed unless it is in accordance with a conservation plan for that land on, and is on file with a state soil and water conservation district. However, a variance may override this requirement.</p>
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to saturated soils?	No
Is there a restriction for land application of manure within floodplains?	Yes
Is there a restriction for land application of manure related to future rainfall?	No
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to frozen or snow-covered ground?	Yes
Are there restrictions to manure applications based on time of year or time of day?	Yes
Are there restrictions to manure application based on slope?	No
Are there any other seasonal, timing, weather, or physical restrictions to manure applications not	No

captured above?	
<p>Transfer of manure off-site: <i>Requirements related to the transfer of manures to other persons</i></p>	<p>Manure Transfer and Ownership._ Manure that is produced by a farm or farming operation that is transferred to another farm or farming operation by the entity that produced the manure is the responsibility and ownership of the recipient upon unloading of the manure._ Manure that is produced by a farm or farming operation that is transferred to another farm or farming operation by a third party, e. g., a contractor hired by the entity that produced the manure, is the responsibility of the contractor until delivered and unloaded to the recipient, unless an alternative, written agreement has been established between the contractor and the recipient. Any recipient self-hauling manure from the farm of origin assumes responsibility and ownership for that manure after the manure has been loaded on the recipient's vehicle or trailer._ Manure that is produced by a farm or farming operation that is transferred to a temporary storage site that is not owned by the entity that produced the manure, and the ultimate utilization of the manure will accrue to the producer of the manure, is the responsibility of the entity that produced the manure while the manure is in temporary storage._ – If a farming operation (CAFO or not) receives more than 100 tons of solid manure or 25,000 gallons of liquid manure annually, that operation is required to develop and implement a nutrient management plan. Therefore, the basic setbacks and other requirements apply. If no NMP is required, they must implement BMPs consistent with our Manure Utilization Guidelines-2.</p>
<p>Are receivers of manure transfers from CAFOs required to follow the same regulations?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Nutrient or manure management plans: <i>Additional details on the NMP requirement. Note that some of this information may overlap with other sections</i></p>	<p>Farm operations that meet certain conditions are required to develop a Plan, specifically if:_ * The farm confines and feeds 50 or more animal units at any one time (one animal unit = 1000 pounds of live animal weight);_ * The farm stores or utilizes more than 100 tons of solid manure or 25,000 gallons of liquid manure per year not generated on that farm;_ * The farm is the subject of a verified complaint of improper manure handling; or _ * The farm stores or utilizes regulated residuals_ Interested individuals are trained to be certified as nutrient management planners and are licensed by the Program, who then may develop and approve Nutrient Management Plans. A list of certified planners is available from the Nutrient Management Office. The Nutrient Management Office oversees nutrient management planning, coordinates enforcement actions as needed, and responds to municipalities and others regarding Right-to-Farm matters. The</p>

	<p>Department developed a Loan Program administered by the Finance Authority of Maine, to help farmers comply with the Law._</p> <p>– The NMP must be consistent with NRCS 590 specs, and manure storages must be consistent with NRCS Code 313.</p>
<p>Do your NMP/MMPS follow, comply with, or based on NRCS Technical Standard 590?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Application rates: <i>State regulations that restrict the rates at which manures are applied and methods needed to determine appropriate rates.</i></p>	<p>Calculation of crop nutrient needs. The calculation of nutrients to be applied must be based on soil tests, manure tests, crop to be grown, and realistic yield goals. A realistic yield goal must be no more than 130% of the state average for the crop in question as determined by the Commissioner, unless the producer can demonstrate that in at least 2 out of 5 years yields have been greater than 130% of the state average, in which case nutrients may be recalculated to meet the higher yields actually experienced. Each field must have its own calculation. The calculation of nutrient needs must take into account the mineralization of organic nitrogen in the soil and in the nutrient material to be applied as well as inorganic nitrogen, following procedures approved by the Commissioner. New farms and farming operations that are developing an initial NMP, which do not have a crop or livestock production history, may estimate crop nutrient requirements and the nutrient values to be derived from manure by utilizing data from current editions of the New England Vegetable Management Guide-² or the publication Nutrient Recommendations for Field Crops in Vermont-²;</p> <p>Soil tests for each field where manure or other crop nutrients will be applied. Soil testing must be repeated for each field at least every 5 years. More frequent testing is recommended for fields with soil phosphorus levels above 40 lb./ac. Soil tests must be conducted by an appropriately accredited laboratory;_</p> <p>– Phosphorus application rates based on soil test values and either the Maine N & P Manure Priority Matrix, or an approved phosphorus index for Maine (which we developed several years ago based on a Pennsylvania model).</p>
<p>Manure application rates for phosphorus are based on: 1) <i>Phosphorus Index Only</i> 2) <i>Soil Test Phosphorus Only</i> 3) <i>Either PIO or STPO</i> 4) <i>Other</i></p>	<p>Phosphorus Index Only</p>
<p>Are there any nutrient “caps” to manure application?</p>	<p>Yes</p>

<p>Composition testing: <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on manures before application</i></p>	<p>Manure testing at least every 5 years or when a significant management change will affect manure nutrient values (for example, changing from a solid manure handling system to a liquid manure handling system, or changing the type of bedding used from sawdust to shredded paper, or changing the source of manure that is used). The Department may, when appropriate, require more frequent manure testing than every 5 years in certain cases. Manure must, at a minimum, be analyzed for total nitrogen, ammonium nitrogen, total phosphorus, total potassium, and moisture content according to the national methods manual Recommended Methods of Manure Analysis, 2003-², University of Wisconsin Publication A3769, http://learningstore.uwex.edu/assets/pdfs/A3769.pdf</p>
<p>Does your state require testing of manure for anything beyond nutrients, such as metals, pathogens, antibiotics, etc.?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Other land application highlights: <i>Additional restrictions for land application of manures</i></p>	<p>No other information</p>
<p>Other regulatory details: <i>Additional information on the regulation of land application of manures</i></p>	<p>No other information</p>
General Assessment Questions	
<p>Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change:</p>	<p>Undetermined</p>
<p>Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of manures that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links:</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of</p>	<p>No</p>

<p>manures beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so:</p>	
<p>Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.</p>	<p>No other information</p>

Maryland Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2019
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Maryland Department of the Environment (MDE)_ Maryland Department of Agriculture (MDA)_
Links to regulations	Water pollution chapter 1-10:_ https://19january2021snapshot.epa.gov/sites/static/files/2014-12/documents/mdwqs_chapters.pdf _ COMAR 26.08.03.09_ https://www.law.cornell.edu/regulations/maryland/COMAR-26-08-03-09 _ _ COMAR 26.08.04- General Discharge Permits (NPDES) for AFOs: https://mde.maryland.gov/programs/land/RecyclingandOperationsprogram/Documents/Notice_of_Final_Action.pdf _ _ Agricultural Operation Nutrient Management Plan Requirements COMAR 15.20.07: http://mdrules.elaws.us/comar/15.20.07
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	More than one agency
Other regulator info	No other information
Definitions	
How CAFOs are defined or categorized:	Concentrated Animal Feeding Operation (CAFO) means: (a) A medium AFO or large AFO, based upon the size categories established in Table 1 of COMAR 26.08.03.09A (below), that discharges or proposes to discharge, as defined by the Federal Act, to surface waters of this State; (b) A small AFO designated a CAFO by the Department in accordance with COMAR 26.08.03.09B; or (c) An AFO designated as a CAFO by the Regional Administrator (RA) of the EPA in accordance with the Federal Act._ Large CAFO_ Dairy Cattle > 700 _ Veal Calves > 1,000 _ Cattle (includes heifers) > 1,000 _ Swine (> 55 pounds) > 2,500 _ Swine (< 55 pounds) > 10,000 _ Turkeys > 55,000 _

	<p>Chickens (liquid manure handling system) > 30,000 _</p> <p>Laying Hens (dry manure handling system) > 82,000 _</p> <p>Chickens (dry manure handling systems and other than laying hens)_</p> <p>> 125,000 animals_</p> <p>or_</p> <p>> 100,000 ft2 in_</p> <p>confinement house_</p> <p>_</p> <p>Medium CAFO_</p> <p>Dairy Cattle 200 - 699_</p> <p>Veal Calves 300 - 999_</p> <p>Cattle (includes heifers) 300 -“ 999_</p> <p>Swine (> 55 pounds) 750 -“ 2,499_</p> <p>Swine (< 55 pounds) 3,000 -“ 9,999_</p> <p>Turkeys 16,500 -“ 54,999_</p> <p>Chickens (liquid manure handling system) 9,000 -“ 29,999_</p> <p>Laying Hens (dry manure handling system) 25,000 -“ 81,999_</p> <p>Chickens (dry manure handling systems and other than laying hens) 37,500 -“ 124,999_</p> <p>animals and <100,000 ft2 in confinement house</p>
How animal units are defined (if used):	Not used
NPDES permitting or other permitting requirements:	<p>MDE has been delegated regulatory authority by the U. S. Environmental Protection Agency (USEPA) over discharges of pollutants to Maryland surface waters. With this authority, MDE administers the National Pollutant Discharge Elimination System (NPDES) program._</p> <p>_</p> <p>MDA has authority to administer the state's nutrient management requirements_</p>
Does the state require an NPDES permit for all Large CAFOs?	Yes
Does the state issue	General

individual or general CAFO permits?	
Are any other permits required for CAFOs or other large farms?	Yes
Other definitions needed to understand these regulations:	No other information
Regulatory Details	
Setbacks: <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some geographical feature</i>	Maryland setbacks at the same as federal regulations, but also includes MDE-approved alternative setbacks. These alternatives are published in, Maryland Setback Standards and Approved Alternatives Consistent with CAFO/MAFO Requirements. http://mde.maryland.gov/programs/LAND/RecyclingandOperationsprogram
Are setbacks more restrictive than CFR?	Undetermined
Timing, weather, or conditional application	Weather related regulations are the same as federal regulations, but they are also published in the separate document, Maryland Setback Standards and Approved Alternatives Consistent with CAFO/MAFO Requirements. http://mde.maryland.gov/programs/LAND/RecyclingandOperationsprogram

<p>n restriction s: <i>State regulation s that restrict land applicatio n under certain weather, seasons, or land characteri stics (like slope)</i></p>	
<p>Is there a restriction for land applicatio n of manure to saturated soils?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Is there a restriction for land application of manure within floodplains ?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Is there a restriction for land application of manure related to future rainfall?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Is there a restriction for land application of manure to frozen or snow-</p>	<p>Yes</p>

covered ground?	
Are there restrictions to manure applications based on time of year or time of day?	Yes
Are there restrictions to manure application based on slope?	Yes
Are there any other seasonal, timing, weather, or physical restrictions to manure applications not captured above?	Yes
Transfer of manure off-site: <i>Requirements related to the transfer of manures to other persons</i>	15.20.05.01: This chapter describes the Department's voluntary Manure Transportation Project required by the Maryland Water Quality Improvement Act of 1998. The project is intended to facilitate the transport of poultry litter and livestock manure from farms in all areas of the State that are subject to phosphorus over enrichment. This project is intended to encourage voluntary participation to remove or redirect at least 20 percent of the poultry litter produced in Dorchester, Somerset, Wicomico, and Worcester counties.
Are receivers of manure transfers from CAFOs required to follow the	Yes

<p>same regulations ?</p>	
<p>Nutrient or manure management plans: <i>Additional details on the NMP requirement. Note that some of this information may overlap with other sections</i></p>	<p>AFOs must develop a CNMP, prepared by either a certified farm operator, or a certified nutrient management consultant, and adhere to COMAR 15.20.07-.08 for land application and sampling testing procedures. National standards used such as the Natural Resources Conservation Service (NRCS) National Planning Procedures Handbook (Part 600.5, Amendment 4, March 2003)</p>
<p>Do your NMP/MMP S follow, comply with, or based on NRCS Technical Standard 590?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Application rates: <i>State regulations that restrict the rates at which manures are applied and methods needed to determine appropriate rates.</i></p>	<p>Sec. 15.20.08.05. Nutrient Management - Required Plan Recommendations_ http://mdrules.elaws.us/comar/15.20.08.05 _ - B. Nutrient Rates._ (1) Nutrient rates of the primary nutrients shall be calculated for plant growth requirements of the crop._ (2) Plant growth requirements shall be based on one of the following:_ (a) University of Maryland Plant or Crop Nutrient Recommendations, as provided in the Maryland Nutrient Management Manual, Section I-B; or_ (b) Alternative standards, as provided in scientifically validated data for the development of a nutrient management plan acceptable to the Department._ (3) A consultant or certified farm operator may recommend the use of lime, secondary nutrients, or micronutrients needed for optimal plant growth._ (4) A consultant or certified farm operator may recommend nutrient rates that deviate from University of Maryland Plant or Crop Nutrient Recommendations and alternative standards provided in the Maryland Nutrient Management Manual, Section I-B, for application on farm test plots with prior approval from the Department._ (5) A consultant or certified farm operator may recommend nutrient rates based on a single variety tissue sample when used in conjunction with a soil sample._</p>

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C. Expected Crop Yield or Production Goal. _
(1) The calculation of expected crop yield shall be based upon one of the following: _
(a) An average of the 3 highest-yielding years for the crop out of the latest consecutive 5-year cropping sequence; or _
(b) If yield information exists for more than 5 years for a given field or management unit, crop yield calculations may be based on the average of 60 percent of the highest-yielding years for all consecutive years that crop yield information is available. _
(2) If field or management unit-specific yield or plant production goal information is unavailable or unrepresentative due to the inclusion of new seed varieties, irrigation, or new technologies, a consultant or certified farm operator shall use one of the following: _
(a) Any soil productivity information; _
(b) The average yield based upon an average of the 3 highest-yielding years for the crop out of the latest consecutive 5-year cropping sequence from nearby fields or management units with similar soil type and management conditions; or _
(c) Any data acceptable to the Department. _
–
(3) A consultant shall document what information was used as the basis for determining expected yield goal as part of the consultant's record-keeping requirements. _
–
(4) Phosphorus Criteria for Tier A Operations. _
(a) Except for nutrient management plans developed in accordance with §E(4)(e) of this regulation, the certified consultant shall: _
(i) Provide the operator information outlining the changes in the management of the operation that will be required when the Phosphorus Management Tool becomes effective; _
(ii) Calculate the Average Soil Phosphorus Fertility Index Value for the operation; and _
(iii) Report the Average Soil Phosphorus Fertility Index Value for the operation to the Department on a form provided by the Department not later than September 1, 2016. _
–
(b) Nutrient management plans implemented before July 1, 2019 shall: _
(i) Be developed using both the Phosphorus Site Index and the Phosphorus Management Tool, as provided in the Maryland Nutrient Management Manual, Section II-C; and _
(ii) Use the Phosphorus Site Index set forth in Regulation .06 of this chapter to determine phosphorus applications. _
–
(c) Nutrient management plans implemented between July 1, 2019 and June 30, 2020 shall use the Phosphorus Transition Management Phase I set forth in Regulation .07 of this chapter to determine phosphorus applications. _
–
(d) Unless the transition schedule is adjusted as provided under this paragraph, nutrient management plans implemented between July 1, 2020 and June 30, 2021 shall use the Phosphorus Transition Management Phase II set forth in Regulation .08 of this chapter to determine phosphorus applications. Before January 1, 2020, the

Department, in consultation with the Phosphorus Management Tool Transition Advisory Committee, shall conduct an evaluation of the existing markets for animal manures, participation in and additional capacity of the Manure Transport Program, the capacity of existing infrastructure for manure transportation, handling and land application, the availability of public and private sector resources, and the status and capacity of alternative uses to utilize animal manures. The evaluation shall be comprehensive in scope, considering all available, relevant information to address current major animal agriculture sectors in the State with the objective of advancing implementation of the next level of management to the maximum extent practicable. If the results of this evaluation indicate insufficient capacity to support the additional volume of animal manure expected to be created when operations are required to determine phosphorus applications under Transition Management Phase II:—

- (i) Transition Management Phase I shall continue to be used to determine phosphorus applications for 1 additional year, through June 30, 2021;—
- (ii) The transition to Transition Management Phase II, as provided in this section, shall be implemented 1 year later, beginning July 1, 2021; and—
- (iii) The subsequent schedule to transition to the Phosphorus Management Tool, as provided in §E(4)(e) of this regulation, likewise shall be implemented 1 year later, beginning July 1, 2022.—

—

(e) Unless the transition schedule is adjusted as provided under either §E(4)(d) of this regulation or this paragraph, nutrient management plans implemented after July 1, 2021 shall use the Phosphorus Management Tool set forth in Regulation .09 of this chapter to determine phosphorus applications. Before January 1, 2021 or, alternatively, January 1, 2022, if the transition schedule has been adjusted under §E(4)(d) of this regulation, the Department, in consultation with the Phosphorus Management Tool Transition Advisory Committee, shall conduct an evaluation of the existing markets for animal manures, participation in and additional capacity of the Manure Transport Program, the capacity of existing infrastructure for manure transportation, handling and land application, the availability of public and private sector resources, and the status and capacity of alternative uses to utilize animal manures. The evaluation shall be comprehensive in scope, considering all available, relevant information to address current major animal agriculture sectors in the State with the objective of advancing implementation of the next level of management to the maximum extent practicable. If the results of this evaluation indicate insufficient capacity to support the additional volume of animal manure expected to be created when operations are required to determine phosphorus applications under the Phosphorus Management Tool:—

- (i) Transition Management Phase II shall continue to be used to determine phosphorus applications for 1 additional year, through June 30, 2022 or, alternatively, June 30, 2023, if the schedule has also been adjusted under §E(4)(d) of this regulation;—
- (ii) The Phosphorus Management Tool shall be used to determine phosphorus applications after June 30, 2022 or, alternatively, after June 30, 2023, if the schedule has also been adjusted under §E(4)(d) of this regulation.—

—

(5) Phosphorus Criteria for Tier B Operations.—

- (a) Except for nutrient management plans developed in accordance with §E(5)(e) of

this regulation, the certified consultant shall:—

(i) Provide the operator information outlining the changes in the management of the operation that shall be required when the Phosphorus Management Tool becomes effective;—

(ii) Calculate the Average Soil Phosphorus Fertility Index Value for the operation; and—

(iii) Report the Average Soil Phosphorus Fertility Index Value for the operation to the Department on a form provided by the Department not later than September 1, 2016.—

(b) Nutrient management plans developed for implementation before July 1, 2018 shall:—

—

(i) Be developed using both the Phosphorus Site Index and the Phosphorus Management Tool, as provided in the Maryland Nutrient Management Manual, Section II-C; and—

(ii) Use the Phosphorus Site Index set forth in Regulation .06 of this chapter to determine phosphorus applications.—

(c) Nutrient management plans implemented between July 1, 2018 and June 30, 2019 shall use the Phosphorus Transition Management Phase I set forth in Regulation .07 of this chapter to determine phosphorus applications.—

(d) Unless the schedule is adjusted as provided under this paragraph, nutrient management plans implemented between July 1, 2019 and June 30, 2021 shall use the Phosphorus Transition Management Phase II set forth in Regulation .08 of this chapter to determine phosphorus applications. Before January 1, 2019, the Department, in consultation with the Phosphorus Management Tool Transition Advisory Committee, shall conduct an evaluation of the existing markets for animal manures, participation in and additional capacity of the Manure Transport Program, the capacity of existing infrastructure for manure transportation, handling and land application, the availability of public and private sector resources, and the status and capacity of alternative uses to utilize animal manures. The evaluation shall be comprehensive in scope, considering all available, relevant information to address current major animal agriculture sectors in the State with the objective of advancing implementation of the next level of management to the maximum extent practicable. If the results of this evaluation indicate insufficient capacity to support the additional volume of animal manure expected to be created when operations are required to determine phosphorus applications under Transition Management Phase II:—

(i) Transition Management Phase I shall continue to be used to determine phosphorus applications for 1 additional year, through June 30, 2020;—

(ii) The transition to Transition Management Phase II, as provided in this section, shall be implemented 1 year later, beginning July 1, 2020; and—

(iii) The subsequent schedule to transition to the Phosphorus Management Tool, as provided in §E(5)(d) of this regulation, shall be implemented 2 years later, beginning July 1, 2022.—

(e) Unless the transition schedule is adjusted as provided under either §E(5)(d) of this regulation or this paragraph, nutrient management plans implemented after July 1, 2021 shall use the Phosphorus Management Tool set forth in Regulation .09 of this chapter to determine phosphorus applications. Before January 1, 2021 or, alternatively, January 1, 2022, if the transition schedule has been adjusted under §E(5)(d) of this regulation, the Department, in consultation with the Phosphorus Management Tool Transition Advisory Committee, shall conduct an evaluation of the

existing markets for animal manures, participation in and additional capacity of the Manure Transport Program, the capacity of existing infrastructure for manure transportation, handling and land application, the availability of public and private sector resources, and the status and capacity of alternative uses to utilize animal manures. The evaluation shall be comprehensive in scope, considering all available, relevant information to address current major animal agriculture sectors in the State with the objective of advancing implementation of the next level of management to the maximum extent practicable. If the results of this evaluation indicate insufficient capacity to support the additional volume of animal manure expected to be created when operations are required to determine phosphorus applications under the Phosphorus Management Tool:—

(i) Transition Management Phase II shall continue to be used to determine phosphorus applications for 1 additional year, through June 30, 2022 or, alternatively, June 30, 2023, if the schedule has also been adjusted under §E(5)(d) of this regulation; and—

(ii) The Phosphorus Management Tool shall be used to determine phosphorus applications after June 30, 2022 or, alternatively, after June 30, 2023, if the schedule has also been adjusted under §E(5)(d) of this regulation.—

—
(6) Phosphorus Criteria for Tier C Operations.—

(a) Except for nutrient management plans developed in accordance with §E(6)(e) of this regulation, the certified consultant shall:—

(i) Provide the operator information outlining the changes in the management of the operation that will be required when the Phosphorus Management Tool becomes effective;—

(ii) Calculate the Average Soil Phosphorus Fertility Index Value for the operation; and—

(iii) Report the Average Soil Phosphorus Fertility Index Value for the operation to the Department on a form provided by the Department not later than September 1, 2016.—

(b) Nutrient management plans implemented prior to July 1, 2017 shall:—

(i) Be developed using both the Phosphorus Site Index and the Phosphorus Management Tool, as provided in the Maryland Nutrient Management Manual, Section II-C; and—

(ii) Use the Phosphorus Site Index set forth in Regulation .06 of this chapter to determine phosphorus applications.—

(c) Nutrient management plans implemented between July 1, 2017 and June 30, 2019 shall use the Phosphorus Transition Management Phase 1 set forth in Regulation .07 of this chapter to determine phosphorus applications.—

(d) Unless the schedule is adjusted as provided under this paragraph, nutrient management plans implemented between July 1, 2019 and June 30, 2021 shall use the Phosphorus Transition Management Phase II set forth in Regulation .08 of this chapter to determine phosphorus applications. Before January 1, 2019, the Department, in consultation with the Phosphorus Management Tool Transition Advisory Committee, shall conduct an evaluation of the existing markets for animal manures, participation in and additional capacity of the Manure Transport Program, the capacity of existing infrastructure for manure transportation, handling and land application, the availability of public and private sector resources, and the status and capacity of alternative uses to utilize animal manures. The evaluation shall be comprehensive in scope, considering all available, relevant information to address

	<p>current major animal agriculture sectors in the State with the objective of advancing implementation of the next level of management to the maximum extent practicable. If the results of this evaluation indicate insufficient capacity to support the additional volume of animal manure expected to be created when operations are required to determine phosphorus applications under Transition Management Phase II: _</p> <p>(i) Transition Management Phase I shall continue to be used to determine phosphorus applications for 1 additional year, through June 30, 2020; _</p> <p>(ii) The transition to Transition Management Phase II, as provided in this section, shall be implemented 1 year later, beginning July 1, 2020; and _</p> <p>(iii) The subsequent schedule to transition to the Phosphorus Management Tool, as provided in §E(6)(e) of this regulation, shall be implemented 2 years later, beginning July 1, 2022. _</p> <p>(e) Unless the transition schedule is adjusted, as provided under either §E(6)(d) of this regulation or this paragraph, nutrient management plans implemented after July 1, 2021 shall use the Phosphorus Management Tool set forth in Regulation .09 of this chapter to determine phosphorus applications. Before January 1, 2021 or, alternatively, January 1, 2022, if the transition schedule has been adjusted under §E(6)(d) of this regulation, the Department, in consultation with the Phosphorus Management Tool Transition Advisory Committee, shall conduct an evaluation of the existing markets for animal manures, participation in and additional capacity of the Manure Transport Program, the capacity of existing infrastructure for manure transportation, handling and land application, the availability of public and private sector resources, and the status and capacity of alternative uses to utilize animal manures. The evaluation shall be comprehensive in scope, considering all available, relevant information to address current major animal agriculture sectors in the State with the objective of advancing implementation of the next level of management to the maximum extent practicable. If the results of this evaluation indicate insufficient capacity to support the additional volume of animal manure expected to be created when operations are required to determine phosphorus applications under the Phosphorus Management Tool: _</p> <p>_</p> <p>(i) Transition Management Phase II shall continue to be used to determine phosphorus applications for 1 additional year, through June 30, 2022 or, alternatively, June 30, 2023, if the schedule has also been adjusted under §E(6)(d), of this regulation; _</p> <p>_</p> <p>(ii) The Phosphorus Management Tool shall be used to determine phosphorus applications after June 30, 2022 or, alternatively, after June 30, 2023, if the schedule has also been adjusted under §E(6)(d) of this regulation.</p>
<p>Manure application rates for phosphorus are based on: 1) <i>Phosphorus Index</i></p>	<p>Undetermined</p>

<p><i>Only</i> 2) <i>Soil Test Phosphorus Only</i> 3) <i>Either PIO or STPO</i> 4) <i>Other</i></p>	
<p>Are there any nutrient “caps” to manure application?</p>	<p>Undetermined</p>
<p>Composition testing: <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on manures before application</i></p>	<p>Undetermined</p>
<p>Does your state require testing of manure for anything beyond nutrients, such as metals, pathogens, antibiotics, etc.?</p>	<p>Undetermined</p>
<p>Other land application highlights:</p>	<p>No other information</p>

<i>Additional restrictions for land application of manures</i>	
Other regulatory details: <i>Additional information on the regulation of land application of manures</i>	No other information
General Assessment Questions	
Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change:	Undetermined
Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of manures that we haven't captured? If yes, please	No

describe or provide links:	
Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of manures beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so:	No
Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.	No other information

Massachusetts	
Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2019
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	US Environmental Protection Agency (US EPA)_ Massachusetts Department of Environmental Protection (MassDEP)_
Links to regulations	Mass website on Surface Water Discharge Permitting (NPDES):_ https://www.mass.gov/service-details/surface-water-discharge-permitting-npdes?_ga=2.34598113.1966478204.1534693388-1936516720.1531924264
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	More than one agency
Other regulator info	Currently only 1 CAFO in Massachusetts based on 2017 numbers
Definitions	
How CAFOs are defined or categorized:	Refer to 40 CFR
How animal units are defined (if used):	Not used
NPDES permitting or other permitting requirements:	MassDEP and US EPA administer the National Pollutant Discharge Elimination System (NPDES) permit program in Massachusetts.
Does the state require an NPDES permit for all Large CAFOs?	No
Does the state issue individual or general CAFO permits?	Undetermined
Are any other permits required for CAFOs or other large farms?	Undetermined
Other definitions needed to understand these regulations:	No other information
Regulatory Details	
Setbacks: <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some geographical feature</i>	Refer to 40 CFR
Are setbacks more restrictive than CFR?	No
Timing, weather, or	None

conditional application restrictions: <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather, seasons, or land characteristics (like slope)</i>	
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to saturated soils?	No
Is there a restriction for land application of manure within floodplains?	No
Is there a restriction for land application of manure related to future rainfall?	No
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to frozen or snow-covered ground?	No
Are there restrictions to manure applications based on time of year or time of day?	No
Are there restrictions to manure application based on slope?	No
Are there any other seasonal, timing, weather, or physical restrictions to manure applications not captured above?	Not Applicable
Transfer of manure off-site: <i>Requirements related to the transfer of manures to other persons</i>	Refer to CFR
Are receivers of manure transfers from CAFOs required to follow the same regulations?	No
Nutrient or manure management plans: <i>Additional details on the NMP requirement. Note that some of this</i>	Refer to CFR

<i>information may overlap with other sections</i>	
Do your NMP/MMPS follow, comply with, or based on NRCS Technical Standard 590?	Not Applicable
Application rates: <i>State regulations that restrict the rates at which manures are applied and methods needed to determine appropriate rates.</i>	Refer to CFR
Manure application rates for phosphorus are based on: 1) <i>Phosphorus Index Only</i> 2) <i>Soil Test Phosphorus Only</i> 3) <i>Either PIO or STPO</i> 4) <i>Other</i>	No method
Are there any nutrient “caps” to manure application?	No
Composition testing: <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on manures before application</i>	Refer to CFR
Does your state require testing of manure for anything beyond nutrients, such as metals, pathogens, antibiotics, etc.?	Not Applicable
Other land application highlights: <i>Additional restrictions for land application of manures</i>	No other information
Other regulatory details: <i>Additional information on the regulation of land application of manures</i>	No other information
General Assessment Questions	
Do you anticipate	

changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change:	Undetermined
Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of manures that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links:	No
Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of manures beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so:	No
Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.	No other information

Michigan Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2025
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Michigan Department of Environmental Quality (MDEQ)_
Links to regulations	Links to regulations, permit applications, etc._ https://www.michigan.gov/egle/about/organization/water-resources/cafo _ – Department of Environmental Quality Water Bureau Water Resources Protection Part 21. Wastewater Discharge Permits_ http://dmbinternet.state.mi.us/DMB/ORRDocs/AdminCode/309_10287_AdminCode.pdf
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Environmental
Other regulator info	No other information
Definitions	
How CAFOs are defined or categorized:	<p>"Animal feeding operation (AFO)" means a lot or facility, other than an aquatic animal production facility, where the animals, other than aquatic animals, have been, are, or will be stabled or confined and fed or maintained for a total of 45 days or more in any 12-month period, and crops, vegetation, forage growth, or post-harvest residues are not sustained in the normal growing season over any portion of the lot or facility._</p> <p>–</p> <p>"Concentrated Animal Feeding Operation (CAFO)" means an AFO that is defined as a large CAFO or a medium CAFO, or that is designated by the department under R 323.2196(3) as a medium CAFO or a small CAFO. Two or more AFOs under common ownership are considered to be a single AFO for the purposes of determining the number of animals at an operation, if they adjoin each other or if they use a common area or system for the disposal of wastes._</p> <p>–</p> <p>"Large CAFO" is an AFO that stables or confines as many as or more than the numbers of animals specified in any of the following categories: (i) 700 mature dairy cows, whether milked or dry. (ii) 1,000 veal calves. (iii) 1,000 cattle other than mature dairy cows or veal calves. Cattle includes heifers, steers, bulls, and cow/calf pairs. (iv) 2,500 swine each weighing 55 pounds or more. (v) 10,000 swine each weighing less than 55 pounds. (vi) 500 horses. (vii) 10,000 sheep or lambs. (viii) 55,000 turkeys. (ix) 30,000 laying hens or broilers, if the AFO uses a liquid manure handling system. (x) 125,000 chickens (other than laying hens), if the AFO uses other than a liquid manure handling system. (xi) 82,000 laying hens, if the AFO</p>

	<p>uses other than a liquid manure handling system. (xii) 30,000 ducks, if the AFO uses other than a liquid manure handling system. (xiii) 5,000 ducks, if the AFO uses a liquid manure handling system._</p> <p>–</p> <p>"Medium CAFO" is defined as the following: (i) Is an AFO that stables or confines the numbers of animals specified in any of the categories listed in subdivision (ii) of this subrule, and any of the following are met: (A) Has been designated by the department as a CAFO under R 323.2196(3). (B) Pollutants are discharged from the production area into waters of the state through a manmade ditch, pipe, tile, swale, flushing system, or other similar manmade conveyance. (C) Pollutants are discharged directly into waters of the state from the production area which originate outside of and pass over, across, or through the facility or that otherwise come into direct contact with the animals confined in the operation. (ii) Includes the following number and type of animals: (A) 200 to 699 mature dairy cows, whether milked or dry. (B) 300 to 999 veal calves. (C) 300 to 999 cattle other than mature dairy cows or veal calves. Cattle includes heifers, steers, bulls, and cow/calf pairs. (D) 750 to 2,499 swine each weighing 55 pounds or more. (E) 3,000 to 9,999 swine each weighing less than 55 pounds. (F) 150 to 499 horses. (G) 3,000 to 9,999 sheep or lambs. (H) 16,500 to 54,999 turkeys. (I) 9,000 to 29,999 laying hens or broilers, if the AFO uses a liquid manure handling system. (J) 37,500 to 124,999 chickens (other than laying hens), if the AFO uses other than a liquid manure handling system. (K) 25,000 to 81,999 laying hens, if the AFO uses other than a liquid manure handling system. (L) 10,000 to 29,999 ducks, if the AFO uses other than a liquid manure handling system. (M) 1,500 to 4,999 ducks, if the AFO uses a liquid manure handling system.</p>
How animal units are defined (if used):	Not used
NPDES permitting or other permitting requirements :	<p>CAFOs are point sources that require NPDES permits for discharges or potential discharges. Potentially a Groundwater Permit are required._</p> <p>–</p> <p>The discharge to waters of the state from land application areas is a discharge from the CAFO subject to NPDES permit requirements._</p> <p>–</p> <p>All CAFO owners or operators shall apply either for an individual NPDES permit, or a certificate of coverage under an NPDES general permit, unless the owner or operator has received a determination from the department, made after providing notice and opportunity for public comment, that the CAFO has "no potential to discharge" _</p>
Does the state require an NPDES permit for all Large CAFOs?	Yes
Does the state issue	Both

individual or general CAFO permits?	
Are any other permits required for CAFOs or other large farms?	Yes
Other definitions needed to understand these regulations:	No other information
Regulatory Details	
Setbacks: <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some geographical feature</i>	<p>* CAFO waste will not be applied closer than 100 feet to any ditches that are conduits to surface waters, surface waters except for up-gradient surface waters, open tile line intake structures, sinkholes, or agricultural well heads._</p> <p>* The 100-foot setback required above may be reduced with a 35-foot wide vegetated buffer. CAFO waste shall not be applied within the 35-foot buffer. _</p> <p>* CAFO waste shall not be applied within grassed waterways and swales that are conduits to surface waters._</p> <p>* Setbacks are measured from the ordinary high water mark, where applicable, or from the upper edge of the bank if the ordinary high water mark cannot be determined.</p>
Are setbacks more restrictive than CFR?	No
Timing, weather, or conditional application restrictions: <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather, seasons, or land</i>	<p>* Production area waste and CAFO process wastewater shall not be land-applied on ground that is flooded, saturated with water, frozen, or snow-covered where the production area waste and CAFO process wastewater may enter waters of the state._</p> <p>* Production area waste and CAFO process wastewater shall not be applied to frozen or snow-covered ground unless it is subsurface injected and there is substantial soil coverage of the applied production area waste and CAFO process wastewater, or it is surface-applied and incorporated within 24 hours._</p> <p>* Production area waste and CAFO process wastewater may be surface-applied to frozen or snow-covered ground and not incorporated within 24 hours only if there is a field-by-field demonstration in the CNMP showing that such land application will not result in a situation where production area waste and CAFO process wastewater may enter waters of the state_</p> <p>* Production area waste and CAFO process wastewater shall not be applied when</p>

<p><i>characteristics (like slope)</i></p>	<p>precipitation exceeding ½ inch is forecast within 24 hours or if precipitation is forecast that may cause the production area waste and CAFO process wastewater to enter waters of the state._ * On ground that is not frozen or snow-covered, production area waste and CAFO process wastewater, if not subsurface-injected, shall be incorporated into the soil within 24 hours of application except on no-till fields._ * CAFO waste may be surface applied and not incorporated within 24 hours only if there is a field-by-field demonstration, in accordance with the Department 2005 Technical Standard for the Surface Application of CAFO Waste on Frozen or Snow-Covered Ground Without Incorporation or Injection, showing that the land application will not result in a situation where CAFO waste may enter waters of the state</p>
<p>Is there a restriction for land application of manure to saturated soils?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Is there a restriction for land application of manure within floodplains?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Is there a restriction for land application of manure related to future rainfall?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Is there a restriction for land application of manure to frozen or snow-covered ground?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Are there restrictions to manure applications based on time of year or time</p>	<p>No</p>

of day?	
Are there restrictions to manure application based on slope?	No
Are there any other seasonal, timing, weather, or physical restrictions to manure applications not captured above?	Undetermined
<p>Transfer of manure off-site:</p> <p><i>Requirements related to the transfer of manures to other persons</i></p>	<p>Unless the department determines otherwise, in cases where production area waste or CAFO process wastewater is sold, given away, or otherwise transferred to other persons (recipient) and the land application of that production area waste or CAFO process wastewater is not under the operational control of the CAFO owner or operator that generates the production area waste or CAFO process wastewater (generator), a manifest shall be used to track the transfer and use of the production area waste or CAFO process wastewater. _</p> <p>(i) The CAFO owner or operator shall do all of the following: _</p> <p>(A) Prepare a manifest for tracking the production area waste or CAFO process wastewater before transferring the production area waste or CAFO process wastewater. _</p> <p>(B) Designate on the manifest the recipient of the production area waste or CAFO process wastewater. _</p> <p>(ii) The generator shall use a manifest form which is approved by the department and which has locations for recording all of the following information: _</p> <p>(A) A manifest document number. _</p> <p>(B) The generator's name, mailing address, and telephone number._</p> <p>(C) The name and address of the recipient of the production area waste or CAFO process wastewater._</p> <p>(D) The nutrient content of the production area waste or CAFO process wastewater to be used in determining the appropriate land application rates._</p> <p>(E) The total quantity of production area waste or CAFO process wastewater by units of weight or volume and the number and size of the loads or containers used to transfer that quantity of production area waste or CAFO process wastewater._</p> <p>(F) A statement that informs the recipient of his or her responsibility to properly manage the land application of the manure and/or wastewater to minimize the discharge of pollutants to waters of the state._</p> <p>(G) The following certification: "I hereby declare that the production area waste or CAFO process wastewater is accurately described above and is suitable for land application."_</p>

	<p>(H) Other certification statements as may be required by the department._</p> <p>(I) Address or other description for the final destination of the production area waste or CAFO process wastewater._</p> <p>(J) Locations for dates and signatures. _</p> <p>(iii) The generator shall do all of the following with respect to the manifest:_</p> <p>(A) Sign the manifest certification by hand. _</p> <p>(B) Obtain the handwritten signature of the recipient and the date of acceptance on the manifest._</p> <p>(C) Retain 1 copy of the manifest._</p> <p>(D) Give the remaining copies to the recipient._</p> <p>(E) Advise the recipient of his or her responsibilities to complete the manifest and return a copy to the generator within 30 days after completion of the land application or other disposal or use of the production area waste or CAFO process wastewater._</p> <p>(iv) One manifest may be used for multiple loads or containers of the same production area waste or CAFO process wastewater transferred to the same recipient. _</p> <p>(v) The generator shall not sell, give away, or otherwise transfer production area waste or CAFO process wastewater to a recipient if any of the following occurs:_</p> <p>(A) The recipient has previously not returned a copy of the completed manifest to the generator._</p> <p>(B) The returned manifest indicates improper land application, use, or disposal._</p> <p>(C) The generator has been advised by the department that the department or a court of appropriate jurisdiction has determined that the recipient has improperly land-applied, used, or disposed of a manifested production area waste or CAFO process wastewater._</p> <p>(D) The recipient fails or refuses to provide accurate information on the manifest in a timely manner. _</p> <p>(vi) If the generator has been prohibited from selling, giving, or otherwise transferring large CAFO waste to a particular recipient under paragraph _ (v), above, and the generator wishes to resume selling, giving, or otherwise transferring large CAFO waste to that particular recipient, then the one of the following shall be accomplished: _</p> <p>(A) For improper paperwork only, such as incomplete or inaccurate information on the manifest, the recipient must provide the correct, complete information._</p> <p>(B) For improper land application, use, or disposal of the large CAFO waste by the recipient, the generator must demonstrate, in writing, to the department that the improper land application, use, or disposal has been corrected, and the department has provided approval of the demonstration. _</p> <p>(vii) All copies of manifests shall be kept with the CAFO owner or operator's CNMP for a minimum of 5 years. _</p> <p>(viii) The requirements of this rule do not apply to quantities of production area waste or CAFO process wastewater less than 1 pick-up truck load, 1 cubic yard, or 1 ton per recipient per day.</p>
<p>Are receivers of manure transfers from CAFOs</p>	<p>Undetermined</p>

<p>required to follow the same regulations?</p>	
<p>Nutrient or manure management plans: <i>Additional details on the NMP requirement. Note that some of this information may overlap with other sections</i></p>	<p>Unless the department determines otherwise, in cases where production area waste or CAFO process wastewater is sold, given away, or otherwise transferred to other persons (recipient) and the land application of that production area waste or CAFO process wastewater is not under the operational control of the CAFO owner or operator that generates the production area waste or CAFO process wastewater (generator), a manifest shall be used to track the transfer and use of the production area waste or CAFO process wastewater. _</p> <p>(i) The CAFO owner or operator shall do all of the following: _</p> <p>(A) Prepare a manifest for tracking the production area waste or CAFO process wastewater before transferring the production area waste or CAFO process wastewater. _</p> <p>(B) Designate on the manifest the recipient of the production area waste or CAFO process wastewater. _</p> <p>(ii) The generator shall use a manifest form which is approved by the department and which has locations for recording all of the following information: _</p> <p>(A) A manifest document number. _</p> <p>(B) The generator's name, mailing address, and telephone number._</p> <p>(C) The name and address of the recipient of the production area waste or CAFO process wastewater._</p> <p>(D) The nutrient content of the production area waste or CAFO process wastewater to be used in determining the appropriate land application rates._</p> <p>(E) The total quantity of production area waste or CAFO process wastewater by units of weight or volume and the number and size of the loads or containers used to transfer that quantity of production area waste or CAFO process wastewater._</p> <p>(F) A statement that informs the recipient of his or her responsibility to properly manage the land application of the manure and/or wastewater to minimize the discharge of pollutants to waters of the state._</p> <p>(G) The following certification: "I hereby declare that the production area waste or CAFO process wastewater is accurately described above and is suitable for land application." _</p> <p>(H) Other certification statements as may be required by the department._</p> <p>(I) Address or other description for the final destination of the production area waste or CAFO process wastewater._</p> <p>(J) Locations for dates and signatures. _</p> <p>(iii) The generator shall do all of the following with respect to the manifest:_</p> <p>(A) Sign the manifest certification by hand. _</p> <p>(B) Obtain the handwritten signature of the recipient and the date of acceptance on the manifest._</p> <p>(C) Retain 1 copy of the manifest._</p> <p>(D) Give the remaining copies to the recipient._</p> <p>(E) Advise the recipient of his or her responsibilities to complete the manifest and return a copy to the generator within 30 days after completion of the land application or other disposal or use of the production area waste or CAFO process wastewater._</p>

	<p>(iv) One manifest may be used for multiple loads or containers of the same production area waste or CAFO process wastewater transferred to the same recipient. _</p> <p>(v) The generator shall not sell, give away, or otherwise transfer production area waste or CAFO process wastewater to a recipient if any of the following occurs:_</p> <p>(A) The recipient has previously not returned a copy of the completed manifest to the generator._</p> <p>(B) The returned manifest indicates improper land application, use, or disposal._</p> <p>(C) The generator has been advised by the department that the department or a court of appropriate jurisdiction has determined that the recipient has improperly land-applied, used, or disposed of a manifested production area waste or CAFO process wastewater._</p> <p>(D) The recipient fails or refuses to provide accurate information on the manifest in a timely manner. _</p> <p>(vi) If the generator has been prohibited from selling, giving, or otherwise transferring large CAFO waste to a particular recipient under paragraph _ (v), above, and the generator wishes to resume selling, giving, or otherwise transferring large CAFO waste to that particular recipient, then the one of the following shall be accomplished: _</p> <p>(A) For improper paperwork only, such as incomplete or inaccurate information on the manifest, the recipient must provide the correct, complete information._</p> <p>(B) For improper land application, use, or disposal of the large CAFO waste by the recipient, the generator must demonstrate, in writing, to the department that the improper land application, use, or disposal has been corrected, and the department has provided approval of the demonstration. _</p> <p>(vii) All copies of manifests shall be kept with the CAFO owner or operator's CNMP for a minimum of 5 years. _</p> <p>(viii) The requirements of this rule do not apply to quantities of production area waste or CAFO process wastewater less than 1 pick-up truck load, 1 cubic yard, or 1 ton per recipient per day._</p> <p>_</p> <p>While manure receivers are not required by law to follow the same regulations, a condition of the manifest that the recipient follow the requirements outlined in the permit. I.e. proper agronomic rate, weather conditions, soil conditions, etc.</p>
<p>Do your NMP/MMPS follow, comply with, or based on NRCS Technical Standard 590?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Application rates: <i>State regulations that restrict</i></p>	<p>* Soils at land application sites sampled and analyzed for phosphorus levels (Bray P1). The results will be used to determine land application rates. Tests must be done every 3 years. Samples should be done using an 8-inch core, and 20 or more cores should be taken in a random pattern evenly over a uniform field area. Bray P1 should be analysis method._</p>

<p><i>the rates at which manures are applied and methods needed to determine appropriate rates.</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * CAFOs can either use Bray P1 numerical limits, or the Michigan Phosphorus Risk Assessment Tool (MRPA) to determine application rates. The permittee MUST use only one system for life of permit for all land application areas._ * Application guidance is based on soil phosphorus tests:_ * Bray P1 = 0-74 ppm of P: Annual CAFO waste application shall not exceed the lesser of these:_ * 1 year N recommendation for next cropping year (MSU Extension Bulletin E2904) or 1 year N removal rate for legumes._ * 4 year phosphorus removal rates as calculated using the Table on Pages 11 & 12 of Permit No. MIG01000. This must be calculated using the removal rate for the planned crop rotation specific to each field._ * Bray P1 = 75-149 ppm of P: Annual CAFO waste application shall not exceed the lesser of these:_ * 1 year phosphorus removal rates as calculated using the Table on Pages 11 & 12 of Permit No. MIG01000 OR 2 year phosphorus removal rates as calculated using the Table on Pages 11 & 12 of Permit No. MIG010000. If the 2 year rate is utilized, the land application log will specify the 2nd year crop to be grown, and the reason why the 1 year rate is impractical._ * 1 year N recommendation for next cropping year (MSU Extension Bulletin E2904) or 1 year N removal rate for legumes._ * Bray P1 > 150 ppm of P: No land applications of CAFO waste will occur (even if MPRA is used)._ * Fields where MPRA is HIGH, CAFO waste cannot be applied._ * The application rate shall not exceed the nitrogen (N) fertilizer recommendation (removal value for legumes) for the first crop year grown after the CAFO waste is applied _ * The application rate shall not exceed four years of P for each of the four crops planned for the next four years_ <p>No manure applications to fields testing above 150ppm of P in the soil.</p>
<p>Manure application rates for phosphorus are based on:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) <i>Phosphorus Index Only</i> 2) <i>Soil Test Phosphorus Only</i> 3) <i>Either PIO or STPO</i> 4) <i>Other</i> 	<p>Phosphorus index or soil test</p>
<p>Are there any nutrient “caps” to manure application?</p>	<p>Yes</p>

<p>Composition testing: <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on manures before application</i></p>	<p>CAFO waste sampled and analyzed for: TKN, ammonium, total phosphorus. The results will be used to determine land application rates. These need to be determined annually.</p>
<p>Does your state require testing of manure for anything beyond nutrients, such as metals, pathogens, antibiotics, etc.?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Other land application highlights: <i>Additional restrictions for land application of manures</i></p>	<p>Undetermined</p>
<p>Other regulatory details: <i>Additional information on the regulation of land application of manures</i></p>	<p>If a CAFO has more than 5,000 animal units, they must apply for a groundwater permit with the DEQ. Link: https://www.michigan.gov/-/media/Project/Websites/egle/Documents/Programs/WRD/CAFO/MIG010000-General-Permit-2025.pdf?rev=0082fe38fb7d41d995e7de1dfad12</p>
<p>General Assessment Questions</p>	
<p>Do you anticipate changes in</p>	<p>Yes. A recent Michigan Supreme Court ruling will likely impact the CAFO program and land application permit requirements.</p>

<p>these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change:</p>	
<p>Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of manures that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links:</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of manures beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so:</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or</p>	<p>No other information</p>

other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.

Minnesota	
Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2019
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Minnesota Pollution Control Agency (MPCA)
Links to regulations	Minnesota Pollution Control Agency_ CHAPTER 7020, ANIMAL FEEDLOTS _ https://www.revisor.mn.gov/rules/7020/ _ _ 7020.2225 LAND APPLICATION OF MANURE_ https://www.revisor.mn.gov/rules/7020.2225/
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Environmental
Other regulator info	No other information
Definitions	
How CAFOs are defined or categorized:	"Concentrated Animal Feeding Operation" or "CAFO" means an animal feedlot meeting the definition of a large, medium, or small CAFO under Code of Federal Regulations, title 40, section 122.23
How animal units are defined (if used):	"Animal unit" means a unit of measure used to compare differences in the production of animal manure that employs as a standard the amount of manure produced on a regular basis by a slaughter steer or heifer for an animal feedlot or a manure storage area, calculated by multiplying the number of animals of each type in items A to I by the respective multiplication factor and summing the resulting values for the total number of animal units. For purposes of this chapter, the following multiplication factors shall apply:_ A. dairy cattle:_ (1) one mature cow (whether milked or dry):_ (a) over 1,000 pounds, 1.4 animal unit; or_ (b) under 1,000 pounds, 1.0 animal unit;_ (2) one heifer, 0.7 animal unit; and_ (3) one calf, 0.2 animal unit;_ B. beef cattle:_ (1) one slaughter steer or stock cow, 1.0 animal unit;_ (2) one feeder cattle (stocker or backgrounding) or heifer, 0.7 animal unit;_ (3) one cow and calf pair, 1.2 animal unit; and_ (4) one calf, 0.2 animal unit;_ C. one head of swine:_ (1) over 300 pounds, 0.4 animal unit;_ (2) between 55 pounds and 300 pounds, 0.3 animal unit; and_ (3) under 55 pounds, 0.05 animal unit;_ D. one horse, 1.0 animal unit;_ E. one sheep or lamb, 0.1 animal unit;_ F. chickens:_

	<p>(1) one laying hen or broiler, if the facility has a liquid manure system, 0.033 animal unit; or_</p> <p>(2) one chicken if the facility has a dry manure system:_</p> <p>(a) over five pounds, 0.005 animal unit; or_</p> <p>(b) under five pounds, 0.003 animal unit;_</p> <p>G. one turkey:_</p> <p>(1) over five pounds, 0.018 animal unit; or_</p> <p>(2) under five pounds, 0.005 animal unit;_</p> <p>H. one duck, 0.01 animal unit; and_</p> <p>I. for animals not listed in items A to H, the number of animal units is the average weight of the animal in pounds divided by 1,000 pounds.</p>
NPDES permitting or other permitting requirements:	<p>Either an NPDES permit or an SDS permit is required for animal feedlots capable of holding 1,000 or more animal units. An NPDES permit is required for the construction, expansion, modification, or operation of a CAFO as required by federal law. A State Disposal (SDS) permit is required for the construction, expansion, modification, or operation of an animal feedlot (similar definition as an AFO) or manure storage area that is capable of holding 1,000 or more animal units. Obtention of an NPDES satisfies the requirement to obtain an SDS permit._</p> <p>More than 90% of the NPDES permit issuances are general permit coverages.</p>
Does the state require an NPDES permit for all Large CAFOs?	No
Does the state issue individual or general CAFO permits?	Both
Are any other permits required for CAFOs or other large farms?	Yes
Other definitions needed to understand these regulations:	<p>Yes. Animal Feedlot- "Animal Feedlot" means a lot or building or combination of lots and buildings intended for the confined feeding, breeding, raising, or holding of animals and specifically designed as a confinement area in which manure may accumulate, or where the concentration of animals is such that a vegetative cover cannot be maintained within the enclosure. For purposes of these parts, open lots used for the feeding and rearing of poultry (poultry ranges) shall be considered to be animal feedlots. Pastures shall not be considered animal feedlots under these parts</p>
Regulatory Details	
Setbacks: <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land</i>	<p>Minn. R. 7020.2225, subps. 6 -8._</p> <p>Subp. 6._</p> <p>Manure and process wastewater application requirements in special protection areas._</p> <p>_</p>

<p><i>application and some geographical feature</i></p>	<p>A. Manure or process wastewater must not be applied to frozen or snow-covered soils in special protection areas._</p> <p>–</p> <p>B. Manure or process wastewater applied to unfrozen soils in special protection areas must comply with subitem (1), (2), or (3)._</p> <p>–</p> <p>(1) A vegetative buffer must be maintained that:_</p> <p>–</p> <p>(a) consists of perennial grasses or forages;_</p> <p>–</p> <p>(b) is a minimum of 100 feet wide along lakes and perennial streams and 50 feet wide in other special protection areas; and_</p> <p>–</p> <p>(c) does not receive manure applications from any animal feedlot or manure storage area._</p> <p>–</p> <p>(2) The following practices must be complied with:_</p> <p>–</p> <p>(a) no application within 25 feet of the protected water, protected wetland, intermittent stream, or drainage ditch in the special protection area;_</p> <p>–</p> <p>(b) inject or incorporate within 24 hours and prior to rainfall; and_</p> <p>–</p> <p>(c) apply at a rate and/or frequency which will not allow soil phosphorus levels to increase over any six-year period with the following exception: soil phosphorus may be increased to 21 ppm (Bray P1) or 16 ppm (Olsen) when soil testing indicates soil phosphorus test concentrations are less than these values._</p> <p>–</p> <p>(3) Other agency-approved practices must be implemented that have been demonstrated through research by a land grant college to provide an equal degree of water quality protection as the measures in subitems (1) and (2)._</p> <p>–</p> <p>C. Manure and process wastewater application by a traveling gun, center pivot, or other irrigation equipment that allows liquid application of manure to travel more than 50 feet in the air is prohibited in special protection areas._</p> <p>–</p> <p>Subp. 7. Manure and process wastewater application for land within 300 feet of open tile intakes. _</p> <p>Manure and process wastewater applied within 300 feet of open tile intakes, and where manure-contaminated runoff may flow into the open tile intake, must be injected or incorporated within 24 hours of application according to the schedule in items A and B unless other agency-approved water quality protection management practices are implemented in accordance with item C._</p>
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	<p>– A. All liquid manure and process wastewater applied within 300 feet of open tile intakes must be injected or incorporated within 24 hours of application beginning October 23, 2000._</p> <p>– B. All manure and process wastewater applied within 300 feet of open tile intakes must be injected or incorporated within 24 hours of application when applied after October 1, 2005._</p> <p>– C. Other agency-approved practices must be implemented that have been demonstrated through research by a land grant college to provide an equal degree of water quality protection as injection or incorporation within 24 hours._</p> <p>– Subp. 8._ Manure and process wastewater application near sinkholes, mines, quarries, and wells._</p> <p>– A. Manure and process wastewater must not be applied to land within 50 feet of an active or inactive water supply well, sinkhole, mine, or quarry._</p> <p>– B. Manure and process wastewater must be incorporated within 24 hours of surface application when applied to land that slopes toward a sinkhole and is less than 300 feet from the sinkhole except that no setback incorporation is necessary where diversions prevent manure-contaminated runoff from entering the sinkhole.</p>
<p>Are setbacks more restrictive than CFR?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Timing, weather, or conditional application restrictions: <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather, seasons, or land characteristics (like slope)</i></p>	<p>Minn. R. 7020.2225, subp. 6, A-B. Manure and process wastewater application requirements in special protection areas._</p> <p>A. Manure or process wastewater must not be applied to frozen or snow-covered soils in special protection areas._</p> <p>B. Manure or process wastewater applied to unfrozen soils in special protection areas must comply with subitem (1), (2), or (3)._</p> <p>(1) A vegetative buffer must be maintained that:_</p> <p>(a) consists of perennial grasses or forages;_</p> <p>b) is a minimum of 100 feet wide along lakes and perennial streams and 50 feet wide in other special protection areas; and_</p> <p>(c) does not receive manure applications from any animal feedlot or manure storage area._</p> <p>(2) The following practices must be complied with:_</p> <p>(a) no application within 25 feet of the protected water, protected wetland, intermittent stream, or drainage ditch in the special protection area;_</p> <p>(b) inject or incorporate within 24 hours and prior to rainfall; and_</p> <p>(c) apply at a rate and/or frequency which will not allow soil phosphorus levels to increase over any six-year period with the</p>

	<p>following exception: soil phosphorus may be increased to 21 ppm (Bray P1) or 16 ppm (Olsen) when soil testing indicates soil phosphorus test concentrations are less than these values._</p> <p>Minn. R. 7020.2225, subp. 4, D(10) a manure management plan requires a plan for protective measures on steep slopes on frozen soil: For application onto frozen or snow-covered soil, the following information about the fields that may receive the manure or process wastewater: field location; land slopes; proximity of fields to surface waters; expected months of application for each field; and tillage and other conservation measures used to minimize risk of manure-contaminated runoff;_</p> <p>–</p> <p>Minn. R. 7020.2225, subp. 1, A., Application on Saturated Soil:_</p> <p>Manure and process wastewater must not be applied to land in a manner that will:_</p> <p>result in a discharge to waters of the state during the application process, except that manure and process wastewater application is allowed onto seasonally saturated soils that are seeded to annual farm crops or crop rotations of perennial grasses or legumes; or cause pollution of waters of the state due to manure-contaminated runoff._</p> <p>–</p> <p>Minn. R. 7020.2225, subp. 4, D(13) , a manure management plan requires a plan to have a cover crop for application during June, July, or August._</p> <p>–</p> <p>Minn. R. 7020.2225, subp. 4, D(10) a manure management plan requires a plan for protective measures on steep slopes on frozen soil. _</p> <p>for application onto frozen or snow-covered soil, the following information about the fields that may receive the manure or process wastewater:_</p> <p>field location; land slopes; proximity of fields to surface waters; expected months of application for each field; and tillage and other conservation measures used to minimize risk of manure-contaminated runoff;_</p> <p>–</p> <p>–</p> <p>In the MN General Permit, there is a prohibition on hydrologic overloading in part 4.5.2_</p> <p>–</p> <p>In the MN General Permit, a permittee shall immediately incorporate surface broadcast manure into the soil surface if a high probability (over 50%) of rainfall exceeding one-half inch is predicted within 24hours of the end of the application period.</p>
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to saturated	Yes

soils?	
Is there a restriction for land application of manure within floodplains?	No
Is there a restriction for land application of manure related to future rainfall?	Yes
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to frozen or snow-covered ground?	Yes
Are there restrictions to manure applications based on time of year or time of day?	Yes
Are there restrictions to manure application based on slope?	Yes
Are there any other seasonal, timing, weather, or physical restrictions to manure applications not captured above?	No
Transfer of manure off-site: <i>Requirements related to the transfer of manures to other persons</i>	Minn. R. 7020.2225, subp 1, 4, and 5, outline regulations and reporting requirements for manure transfers from an animal feedlot with capacity of 300 or more animal units or a manure storage area capable of holding the manure produced by 300 or more animal units.
Are receivers of manure transfers from CAFOs required to follow the same regulations?	Yes
Nutrient or manure management plans: <i>Additional details on the NMP requirement. Note that some of this information may overlap with other sections</i>	Minn. R. 7020.2225, subp. 4: Manure management plan requirements. Item A indicates who must prepare a manure management plan and when the plan must be prepared. Item B lists when manure management plans must be submitted to the agency or delegated county for review. Item C describes when the manure management plan must be reviewed and revised. Item D lists the required elements of a manure management plan. Item E describes exceptions to manure management plans when manure ownership is transferred._ A. An owner or operator of an animal feedlot shall prepare and retain on file a manure management plan that complies with item D according to the following schedule:_ (1) upon application for an NPDES, SDS, interim, or construction short-form permit for a facility capable of holding 100 or more animal units;_

(2) an owner of an animal feedlot capable of holding 300 or more animal units that is not required to obtain an NPDES, SDS, interim, or construction short-form permit shall prepare or update a manure management plan prior to January 1, 2005, when a manure management plan does not meet the requirements of this part or reflect current operations and the manure is applied by someone other than a commercial animal waste technician or a certified private manure applicator; and_

(3) once a manure management plan is required for a facility, a plan that meets the requirements under this subpart must be retained on file at the animal feedlot or manure storage area._

B. A manure management plan that complies with the requirements of item D must be submitted to the commissioner or delegated county when any one of the following conditions applies:_

(1) when an owner submits a permit application to the commissioner for an NPDES, SDS, or interim permit under part 7020.0405, subpart 1, item C, subitem (3); or_

(2) the manure management plan is requested by the commissioner or county feedlot pollution control officer._

C. The manure management plan must be reviewed by the owner each year and adjusted for any changes in the amount of manure production, manure nutrient test results, fields available for receiving manure, crop rotations, or other practices which affect the available nutrient amounts or crop nutrient needs on fields receiving manure._

D. Except as provided in item E, the manure management plan must contain:_

(1) a description of the manure storage/handling system and the expected annual amount of manure and nutrients which will need to be land applied;_

(2) application methods, equipment, and calibration procedures;_

(3) acreage available for manure and process wastewater application including maps or aerial photos showing field locations and areas within the fields that are suitable for manure or process wastewater application;_

(4) a description of nutrient testing methods and frequency and the expected nutrient content of the manure to be applied;_

(5) planned manure application rates and assumptions used to determine these rates, including assumptions of crop nitrogen and phosphorus needs and nitrogen and phosphorus supplied from all manure and nonmanure sources;_

(6) total nitrogen and phosphorus amounts from manure and nonmanure sources to be applied per acre on each field and for each crop in the rotation when applied in accordance with the planned manure or process wastewater application rates established under subitem (5);_

(7) expected first and second year plant available nutrients from the manure and process wastewater;_

	<p>(8) expected months of application;_</p> <p>(9) a description of protective measures to minimize the risk of surface water and groundwater contamination when applying manure or process wastewater in a floodplain, special protection area, soils with less than three feet above limestone bedrock, drinking water supply management areas where the aquifer is designated vulnerable under chapter 4720, and land within 300 feet of all surface tile intakes, sinkholes without constructed diversions, and uncultivated wetlands. Protective measures include, but are not limited to, soil and water conservation measures, timing of application, methods of application, manure application rates, and frequency of application;_</p> <p>(10) for application onto frozen or snow-covered soil, the following information about the fields that may receive the manure or process wastewater:_</p> <p>(a) field location;_</p> <p>(b) land slopes;_</p> <p>(c) proximity of fields to surface waters;_</p> <p>(d) expected months of application for each field; and_</p> <p>(e) tillage and other conservation measures used to minimize risk of manure-contaminated runoff;_</p> <p>(11) a description of how phosphorus from manure is to be managed to minimize phosphorus transport to surface waters resulting from soil phosphorus build-up to levels described in subpart 3, item C;_</p> <p>(12) plans for soil nitrate testing in accordance with University of Minnesota Extension Service recommendations; and_</p> <p>(13) type of cover crop to be planted when manure is to be applied in June, July, or August to fields that have been harvested and would otherwise not have active growing crops for the remainder of the growing season._</p> <p>E. When ownership of manure from an animal feedlot capable of holding 300 or more animal units or a manure storage area capable of holding the manure produced by 300 or more animal units is to be transferred for application to fields not owned or leased by the owner of the animal feedlot or manure storage area, the owner of the animal feedlot where the manure was produced need not include the requirements in item D, subitems (3), (5) to (7), and (10) in the owner's manure management plan. Any person receiving the manure shall comply with subpart 1, item C.</p>
<p>Do your NMP/MMPS follow, comply with, or based on NRCS Technical Standard 590?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Application rates: <i>State regulations that restrict the rates at which manures are applied and</i></p>	<p>Minn. R. 7020.2225, subp. 3: Nutrient application rate standards. Items A and B apply to all manure and process wastewater application sites. Item C applies only to animal feedlots with a capacity of 300 or more animal units and manure storage areas</p>

<p><i>methods needed to determine appropriate rates.</i></p>	<p>capable of holding the manure produced by 300 or more animal units._</p> <p>A. Manure and process wastewater application rates must be limited as described in subitems (1) to (3) so that the estimated plant available nitrogen from all nitrogen sources does not exceed expected crop nitrogen needs for nonlegume crops and expected nitrogen removal for legumes._</p> <p>(1) Expected crop nitrogen needs, crop nitrogen removal rates, and estimated plant available nitrogen from manure and legumes must be based on the most recent published recommendations of the University of Minnesota Extension Service or of another land grant college in a contiguous state._</p> <p>(2) Estimated plant available nitrogen from organic nitrogen sources, including manure, may deviate up to 20 percent from University of Minnesota Extension Service, or of another land grant college in a contiguous state, estimates where site nutrient management history, soil conditions, or cool weather warrant additional nitrogen application. When crop nitrogen deficiencies are visible or measured, remedial nitrogen applications above the 20 percent deviation can be made._</p> <p>(3) Nitrogen sources include commercial fertilizer nitrogen, soil organic matter, irrigation water, legumes grown during previous years, biosolids, process wastewater, and manure applied for the current year and previous years._</p> <p>C. For land receiving manure or process wastewater from animal feedlots capable of holding 300 or more animal units or manure storage areas capable of holding the manure produced by 300 or more animal units, soil samples from the upper six inches must be collected at a minimum frequency of once every four years and analyzed for phosphorus using the Bray P1 or Olsen test. If soil phosphorus levels exceed the levels in subitems (1) and (2), then the owner must complete a manure management plan in accordance with subpart 4, item D, and submit it with a permit application to the agency or delegated county for review in accordance with subpart 4, item B, subitem (1)._</p> <p>(1) Fields in special protection areas or within 300 feet of open tile intakes that have an average soil phosphorus test level exceeding 75 ppm using the Bray P1 test or 60 ppm using the Olsen test._</p> <p>(2) Fields outside the special protection areas and more than 300 feet from open tile intakes that have an average soil phosphorus test level exceeding 150 ppm using the Bray P1 test or 120 ppm using the Olsen test._</p> <p>—</p> <p>Minn. R. 7020.2225, Subp. 6., B, (2), (c) Nutrient caps are required for manure application in special protection areas.</p>
<p>Manure application rates for phosphorus are based on:</p>	<p>Soil test phosphorus only</p>

<p>1) <i>Phosphorus Index Only</i> 2) <i>Soil Test Phosphorus Only</i> 3) <i>Either PIO or STPO</i> 4) <i>Other</i></p>	
<p>Are there any nutrient “caps” to manure application?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Composition testing: <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on manures before application</i></p>	<p>Manure nutrient testing requirements. Manure from all manure storage areas storing manure produced from more than 100 animal units must be tested by the owner of the animal feedlot for nitrogen and phosphorus content in accordance with items A to E, except that item A is not required for manure storage areas storing manure produced by fewer than 300 animal units._ — A. For manure storage areas storing manure from 300 or more animal units, the manure must initially be tested once per year for at least three years._ B. Manure must be retested following changes in conditions affecting manure nutrient content including unusual climatic conditions, or changes in manure storage and handling, livestock types, or livestock feed._ C. Ongoing testing must continue at least once every four years unless more frequent testing is required under item B or in a permit._ D. The nutrient analysis must be conducted using a laboratory certified by the Minnesota Department of Agriculture or commissioner-approved on-farm sampling and analysis._ E. Sampling must be conducted so that a representative sample is obtained in accordance with University of Minnesota Extension Service recommendations.</p>
<p>Does your state require testing of manure for anything beyond nutrients, such as metals, pathogens, antibiotics, etc.?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Other land application highlights: <i>Additional restrictions for land application of manures</i></p>	<p>No other information</p>
<p>Other regulatory details: <i>Additional information on the regulation of land application of manures</i></p>	<p>No other information</p>
<p>General Assessment Questions</p>	

<p>Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change:</p>	<p>Undetermined</p>
<p>Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of manures that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links:</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of manures beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so:</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.</p>	<p>No other information</p>

Mississippi Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2025
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Mississippi Department of Environmental Quality (MDEQ)
Links to regulations	General Pollution Control Permit to Manage Manure/Litter And/or to Construct/Operate Air Emissions Equipment in Accordance with the NPDES and MS Ambient Air Quality Standards_ https://www.mdeq.ms.gov/wp-content/uploads/2017/06/Final-CAFO-GP-Permit.pdf
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Environmental
Other regulator info	No other information
Definitions	
How CAFOs are defined or categorized:	<p>"Animal Feeding Operation (AFO) means a lot or facility (other than an aquatic animal production facility) where the following conditions are met: (1) Animals (other than aquatic animals) have been, are, or will be stabled or confined and fed or maintained for a total of 45 days or more in any 12-month period, and (2) Crops, vegetation, forage growth, or post-harvest residues are not sustained in the normal growing season over any portion of the lot or facility. [40 CFR Part 122.23(b)(1)]_</p> <p>_</p> <p>CONCENTRATED ANIMAL FEEDING OPERATION (CAFO) means an AFO that is defined as a Large CAFO or as a Medium CAFO by the terms of this paragraph, or that is designated as a CAFO in accordance with 40 CFR Part 122.23(c). Two or more AFOs under common ownership are considered to be a single AFO for the purposes of determining the number of animals at an operation, if they adjoin each other or if they use a common area or system for the disposal of wastes. [40 CFR Part 122.23(b)(2)]_</p> <p>_</p> <p>LARGE CONCENTRATED ANIMAL FEEDING OPERATION (Large CAFO) An AFO is defined as a Large CAFO if it stables or confines as many as or more than the numbers of animals specified in any of the following categories: _</p> <p>(1) 700 mature dairy cows, whether milked or dry; _</p> <p>(2) 1,000 veal calves; _</p> <p>(3) 1,000 cattle other than mature dairy cows or veal calves. Cattle includes but is not limited to heifers, steers, bulls and cow/calf pairs; _</p> <p>(4) 2,500 swine each weighing 55 pounds or more; _</p> <p>(5) 10,000 swine each weighing less than 55 pounds; _</p> <p>(6) 500 horses; _</p> <p>(7) 10,000 sheep or lambs; _</p>

- (8) 55,000 turkeys; _
 - (9) 30,000 laying hens or broilers, if the AFO uses a liquid manure handling system; _
 - (10) 125,000 chickens (other than laying hens), if the AFO uses other than a liquid manure handling system; _
 - (11) 82,000 laying hens, if the AFO uses other than a liquid manure handling system; _
 - (12) 30,000 ducks (if the AFO uses other than a liquid manure handling system); or _
 - (13) 5,000 ducks (if the AFO uses a liquid manure handling system).
- [40 CFR Part 122.23(b)(4)]_

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MEDIUM CONCENTRATED ANIMAL FEEDING OPERATION ('Medium CAFO) includes any AFO with the type and number of animals that fall within any of the ranges listed below and which has been defined or designated as a CAFO. An AFO is defined as a Medium CAFO if: _

- (1) The type and number of animals that it stables or confines falls within any of the following ranges: _
 - (i) 200 to 699 mature dairy cows, whether milked or dry; (ii) 300 to 999 veal calves;_
 - (iii) 300 to 999 cattle other than mature dairy cows or veal calves. Cattle includes but is not limited to heifers, steers, bulls and cow/calf pairs;_
 - (iv) 750 to 2,499 swine each weighing 55 pounds or more;_
 - (v) 3,000 to 9,999 swine each weighing less than 55 pounds;_
 - (vi) 150 to 499 horses;_
 - (vii) 3,000 to 9,999 sheep or lambs;_
 - (viii) 16,500 to 54,999 turkeys;_
 - (ix) 9,000 to 29,999 laying hens or broilers, if the AFO uses a liquid manure handling system;_
 - (x) 37,500 to 124,999 chickens (other than laying hens), if the AFO uses other than a liquid manure handling system; _
 - (xi) 25,000 to 81,999 laying hens, if the AFO uses other than a liquid manure handling system;_
 - (xii) 10,000 to 29,999 ducks (if the AFO uses other than a liquid manure handling system); or_
 - (xiii) 1,500 to 4,999 ducks (if the AFO uses a liquid manure handling system); and _
- (2) Either one of the following conditions are met:_
 - (i) Pollutants are discharged into waters of the United States through a man-made ditch, flushing system, or other similar man-made device; or_
 - (ii) Pollutants are discharged directly into waters of the United States which originate outside of and pass over, across, or through the facility or otherwise come into direct contact with the animals confined in the operation. [40 CFR Part 122.23(b)(6)]

How animal units are defined (if used):	Not used
NPDES permitting or other permitting requirements:	<p>The CAFO General permit may provide coverage for all new and existing farms classified as a CAFO that fall under Standard Industrial Classifications (SIC) 0211 (beef cattle feedlots), 0213 (swine), 0214 (sheep and goats), 0241 (dairy), 0251 (broiler, fryer, and roaster chickens), 0252 (chicken eggs), 0253 (turkeys and turkey eggs), 0254 (poultry hatcheries), 0259 (poultry and eggs not else where classified), or 0272 (horses), and seeking to obtain permit coverage under paragraph(s) (1), (2), and/or (3) below: _</p> <p>(1) NPDES permit coverage for farming identified by the SIC Codes above and associated with the operation of: _</p> <p>(i) a Large Concentrated Animal Feeding Operation (Large CAFO-²) as defined in ACT9 Condition T-9, of this permit, or _</p> <p>(ii) a Medium Concentrated Animal Feeding Operation (Medium CAFO-²) as defined in ACT9 Condition T-12 of this permit, and _</p> <p>(iii) generates no process wastewater discharge, and _</p> <p>(iv) has no waste or raw material exposed to storm water rainfall or runoff._</p> <p>Construction Stormwater might be required for a new or expanding sites during construction.</p>
Does the state require an NPDES permit for all Large CAFOs?	Yes
Does the state issue individual or general CAFO permits?	General
Are any other permits required for CAFOs or other large farms?	Yes
Other definitions needed to understand these regulations:	No other information
Regulatory Details	
<p>Setbacks:</p> <p><i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some geographical feature</i></p>	<p>Land application of animal waste (excluding dry litter waste) must be at least 50 feet from the nearest adjoining property line and at least 300 feet from the nearest non-owned (by the applicant) occupied dwelling. [11 Miss. Admin. Code Pt. 6, R. 1.1.1.C(2)(D).]_</p> <p>_</p> <p>Unless the CAFO exercises one of the compliance alternatives provided for in paragraph (1) or (2) below, manure, litter, and process wastewater may not be applied closer than 100 feet to any down-gradient surface waters, open tile line intake structures, sinkholes, agricultural well heads, or other conduits to surface waters. _</p> <p>(1) Vegetated buffer compliance alternative. As a compliance alternative, the CAFO may substitute the 100-foot setback with a</p>

	35-foot wide vegetated buffer where applications of manure, litter, or process wastewater are prohibited. _ (2) Alternative practices compliance alternative. As a compliance alternative, the CAFO may demonstrate that a setback or buffer is not necessary because implementation of alternative conservation practices or field-specific conditions will provide pollutant reductions equivalent or better than the reductions that would be achieved by the 100-foot setback. [40 CFR Part 412.4(c)(5), 40 CFR Part 412.31(b)(1), 40 CFR 412.43(b)]
Are setbacks more restrictive than CFR?	No
Timing, weather, or conditional application restrictions: <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather, seasons, or land characteristics (like slope)</i>	Wastewater shall not be applied when the ground is frozen, saturated, or during rainfall events. [11 Miss. Admin. Code Pt. 6.]. Waste application shall occur only between 30 minutes after sunrise and 30 minutes before sunset unless authorized by MDEQ. Waste application on weekends should be minimized. Facility personnel must remain on site during this application.
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to saturated soils?	Yes
Is there a restriction for land application of manure within floodplains?	No
Is there a restriction for land application of manure related to future rainfall?	Yes
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to frozen or snow-covered ground?	Yes
Are there restrictions to manure applications based on time of year or time of day?	Yes
Are there restrictions to manure application based on slope?	No
Are there any other seasonal, timing, weather, or physical restrictions to manure applications not captured above?	Undetermined
Transfer of manure off-site:	Prior to transferring manure, litter or process wastewater to other

<p><i>Requirements related to the transfer of manures to other persons</i></p>	<p>persons, CAFOs must provide the recipient of the manure, litter or process wastewater with the most current nutrient analysis. The analysis provided must be consistent with the requirements of 40 CFR Part 412. CAFOs must retain for five years records of the date, recipient name and address, and approximate amount of manure, litter or process wastewater transferred to another person. These records must be documented on Appendix G of the CAFO Forms Package. [40 CFR Part 122.42(e)(3)]</p>
<p>Are receivers of manure transfers from CAFOs required to follow the same regulations?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Nutrient or manure management plans: <i>Additional details on the NMP requirement. Note that some of this information may overlap with other sections</i></p>	<p>Each CAFO must develop, implement, maintain on site or locally available for a period of five years from the development date, and upon request make available to the Permit Board an approved Nutrient Management Plan (NMP) that at a minimum includes best management practices and procedures necessary to meet the requirements of this paragraph and applicable effluent limitations and standards, including those specified in 40 CFR part 412.</p>
<p>Do your NMP/MMPS follow, comply with, or based on NRCS Technical Standard 590?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Application rates: <i>State regulations that restrict the rates at which manures are applied and methods needed to determine appropriate rates.</i></p>	<p>Soil Testing. Soil from the land application area analyzed a minimum of once every five years for phosphorus content. The results of these analyses are to be used in determining application rates for manure, litter, and other process wastewater. Application rates for manure, litter, and other process wastewater applied to land under the ownership or operational control of the CAFO must minimize phosphorus and nitrogen transport from the field to surface waters in compliance with the technical standards for nutrient management established by the Director. Such technical standards for nutrient management shall: _</p> <p>(1) Include a field-specific assessment of the potential for nitrogen and phosphorus transport from the field to surface waters, and address the form, source, amount, timing, and method of application of nutrients on each field to achieve realistic production goals, while minimizing nitrogen and phosphorus movement to surface waters; and _</p> <p>(2) Include appropriate flexibilities for any CAFO to implement nutrient management practices to comply with the technical standards, including consideration of multi-year phosphorus application on fields that do not have a high potential for phosphorus runoff to surface water, phased implementation of phosphorus-based nutrient management, and other components, as determined appropriate by the Director. [40 CFR Part 412.4(c)(2), 40 CFR Part 412.31(b)(1), 40 CFR 412.43(b)]</p>

Manure application rates for phosphorus are based on: 1) <i>Phosphorus Index Only</i> 2) <i>Soil Test Phosphorus Only</i> 3) <i>Either PIO or STPO</i> 4) <i>Other</i>	Soil test phosphorus only
Are there any nutrient “caps” to manure application?	No
Composition testing: <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on manures before application</i>	Manure must be analyzed a minimum of once annually for nitrogen and phosphorus content, and soil from the land application area analyzed a minimum of once every five years for phosphorus content. The results of these analyses are to be used in determining application rates for manure, litter, and other process wastewater. The analyses must be maintained on site or locally available for a period of five years from the date they are created, and upon request make available to the Permit Board. [40 CFR Part 412.4(c)(3), 40 CFR Part 412.31(b)(1), 40 CFR 412.43(b)].
Does your state require testing of manure for anything beyond nutrients, such as metals, pathogens, antibiotics, etc.?	No
Other land application highlights: <i>Additional restrictions for land application of manures</i>	Waste application shall occur only between 30 minutes after sunrise and 30 minutes before sunset unless authorized by MDEQ._ – Waste application on weekends should be minimized. Facility personnel must remain on site during this application._ – Operators
Other regulatory details: <i>Additional information on the regulation of land application of manures</i>	No other information
General Assessment Questions	
Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change:	Undetermined
Are there any other regulations in your state	No

<p>that may affect land application of manures that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links:</p>	
<p>Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of manures beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so:</p>	No
<p>Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.</p>	No other information

Missouri Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2019
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Missouri Department of Natural Resources (MDNR)_ Missouri Clean Water Commission (MCWC)_
Links to regulations	Links to regulations, permits, guidance, etc._ https://www.sos.mo.gov/adrules/csr/current/10csr/10csr#10-20 _ _ MDNR Missouri CAFO Nutrient Management Technical Standard_ https://nmplanner.missouri.edu/wp-content/plugins/nm-planner-functionality/public/assets/pdfs/Nutrient_Management_Tech_Standard-FINAL_3-4-09_Marked_NM-A.pdf
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	More than one agency
Other regulator info	No other information
Definitions	
How CAFOs are defined or categorized:	<p>An operation is defined as an Animal Feeding Operation, or AFO, if the facility confines, stables, or feeds animals for 45 days or more in a 12-month period and a ground cover of vegetation is not sustained over at least 50 percent of the confinement area._</p> <p>_</p> <p>An operation is defined as a concentrated Animal Feeding Operation, or CAFO, if it meets the definition of an Animal Feeding Operation (above) and also confines more than 1,000 animal units (1,000 animal units is equal to 2,500 swine; 100,000 broilers; 700 dairy cows; or 1,000 beef steers)._</p> <p>_</p> <p>An operation's "class size" is a category that is based upon the total number of animal units confined at an operation. The Class IC, IB and IA are categories that start at 1,000, 3,000 and 7,000 animal units respectively, and are required by state regulation to obtain a permit._</p> <p>_</p> <p>Class II operations confine less than 1,000 animal units and, by definition, are only an Animal Feeding Operation. Class II operations are not required to have a permit, although many voluntarily obtain one anyway. The department can also require a Class II operation to obtain a permit when an unauthorized discharge has occurred or when a discharge results in a violation of water quality standards. The class II operations that appear on these maps include only those that are currently permitted and do not represent the total state-wide count of all Class II operations in Missouri. The department does not track nor have records of non-permitted Class II operations.</p>
How animal units are defined (if used):	Animal unit (AU) classifications can be calculated by dividing the number of animals by the conversion factor for that animal category

	<p>from_</p> <p>Beef cow, feeder, veal calf, cow/calf pair, and dairy heifer = 1 AU_</p> <p>Horses = 0.5 AU_</p> <p>Mature Dairy cows = 0.7 AU_</p> <p>Swine weighing over 55 lbs. = 2.5 AU_</p> <p>Swine weighing under 55 lbs. = 10 AU_</p> <p>Ducks with a wet handling system = 5 AU_</p> <p>Ducks without a wet handling system = 300 AU_</p> <p>Sheep, lambs and meat and dairy goats = 10 AU_</p> <p>Chicken laying hens, pullets, and broilers with a wet handling system = 30 AU_</p> <p>Turkeys in grow out phase = 55 AU_</p> <p>Chicken laying hens without a wet handling system = 82 AU_</p> <p>Chicken broilers and pullets, and turkey poults in brood phase, all without a wet handling system = 125 AU_</p> <p>–</p> <p>Class size category can also be determined by using numbers below:_</p> <p>Class IA = 7000 AUs_</p> <p>Class IB = 3000-6999 AUs_</p> <p>Class IC = 1000-2999 AUs_</p> <p>Class II = 300-999 AUs</p>
<p>NPDES permitting or other permitting requirements:</p>	<p>State regulations require all Class I CAFOs to obtain coverage under a NPDES or State No-discharge operating permit. Class II AFOs that are defined or designated as a CAFO due to discharging, must obtain a NPDES operating permit also. State regulations also require a construction permit for certain construction activities for new or expanding Class I CAFOs. To determine if either of these permits are required for a specific operation, the class size must be determined, and if the operation is an AFO or CAFO._</p> <p>–</p> <p>Operating permit coverage must be obtained prior to the operation of a waste management system at a CAFO and before any animals can be placed in confinement. There are two different general operating permits available:_</p> <p>(1)NPDES - This permit allows for a discharge from an uncovered liquid storage structure due to a catastrophic storm or chronic weather event. A discharge for any other reason is not allowed._</p> <p>(2)State No-discharge - Discharges are not allowed for any reason._</p> <p>Each type of general operating permit issued contains the same monitoring and reporting requirements. Some of the requirements may not be applicable to certain operations due to the type of waste management system used by the operation. Permits are effective for fixed five year period. Both general permits can be viewed on the department's CAFO web page at dnr.mo.gov/env/wpp/cafo/._</p> <p>–</p> <p>Class IA CAFO's are excluded from obtaining general permit coverage and must obtain a site specific operating permit. A site specific permit NPDES operating permit is written with monitoring and reporting</p>

	requirements that are specific to that operation.
Does the state require an NPDES permit for all Large CAFOs?	No
Does the state issue individual or general CAFO permits?	Undetermined
Are any other permits required for CAFOs or other large farms?	Undetermined
Other definitions needed to understand these regulations:	No other information
Regulatory Details	
<p>Setbacks: <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some geographical feature</i></p>	<p>Here are required minimum setback distances for confinement buildings, open lots, manure storage structures, and mortality composters in the production area from certain features. Additionally, there are setbacks for the land application of manure, litter and process wastewater at land application areas. These setbacks are meant to ensure the protection of surface waters and wells. Land application setbacks are:_</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Public or private drinking water well or impoundment, or drinking water intake structure, all application methods, 300 ft_ * Classified waters of the state not used as a water supply, with permanent vegetated buffer, 35 ft_ * Classified waters of the state not used as a water supply, with no or insufficient vegetated buffer, 100 ft_ * Public or private impoundments not used as a water supply with permanent vegetated buffer, 35 ft_ * Public or private impoundments not used as a water supply with up-gradient, or no or insufficient vegetated buffer, 100 ft_ * Public or private impoundments not used as a water supply with down-gradient, or no or insufficient vegetated buffer, 35 ft_ * Perennial or intermittent stream, wetland with permanent vegetated buffer, 35 ft_ * Perennial or intermittent stream, wetland with up-gradient, or no or insufficient vegetated buffer, 100 ft_ * Perennial or intermittent stream, wetland with down-gradient, or no or insufficient vegetated buffer, 35 ft_ * Tile line inlet, (if left unplugged during application) up-gradient with permanent vegetated buffer, 35 ft_ * Tile line inlet, (if left unplugged during application) up-gradient with no or insufficient vegetated buffer, 100 ft_ * Tile line inlet, (if left unplugged during application) down-gradient, 0 ft_ * Losing stream cave, spring, or sinkhole, all application methods, 300 ft_ * Perennial or intermittent losing stream or sinkhole, all application

	<p>methods, 300 ft_</p> <p>* Public use area, non-owned residence or business, spray irrigation only, 150_</p> <p>* Public road or property boundary, all application methods, 50 ft</p>
Are setbacks more restrictive than CFR?	Yes
<p>Timing, weather, or conditional application restrictions:</p> <p><i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather, seasons, or land characteristics (like slope)</i></p>	<p>* no land application on slopes greater than 20 percent,_</p> <p>* no surface application when soil is frozen, snow covered, or saturated,_</p> <p>* no surface application if a precipitation event that is likely to create runoff is forecasted within 24 hours of the planned application.</p>
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to saturated soils?	Yes
Is there a restriction for land application of manure within floodplains?	No
Is there a restriction for land application of manure related to future rainfall?	Yes
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to frozen or snow-covered ground?	Yes
Are there restrictions to manure applications based on time of year or time of day?	No
Are there restrictions to manure application based on slope?	Yes
Are there any other seasonal, timing, weather, or physical restrictions to manure applications not captured above?	Undetermined
<p>Transfer of manure off-site:</p> <p><i>Requirements related to</i></p>	* No surface application of manure is allowed if precipitation, likely to create runoff, is forecasted to occur within 24 hours of the planned application;_

<p><i>the transfer of manures to other persons</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Manure will not be applied on land with a slope greater than 20 percent; _ * Manure will not be surface applied to frozen, snow-covered or saturated soils; _ * Manure applications must be monitored such that target application rates are met and any malfunction in the operation of the equipment is detected and corrected before any overapplication of manure occurs on the land-application site; _ * Wastewater and liquid manure applications must be conducted so as to prevent surface runoff of wastewater and liquid manure beyond the edge of the field during land application. Steps to insure no runoff of manure during land application include: 1. Adjusting surface application rates to meet infiltration rate and water holding capacity of the soil; 2. Irrigation systems must have automatic shut-off devices in case of pressure loss and/or an operator on-site at all times during operation to monitor application equipment.
<p>Are receivers of manure transfers from CAFOs required to follow the same regulations?</p>	<p>Undetermined</p>
<p>Nutrient or manure management plans: <i>Additional details on the NMP requirement. Note that some of this information may overlap with other sections</i></p>	<p>Manure, litter, and process wastewater applied to the land application area must minimize phosphorus and nitrogen transport from the field to surface waters in compliance with the Missouri Concentrated Animal Feeding Operation Nutrient Management Technical Standard (NMTS) approved by the Clean Water Commission on March 4, 2009, in accordance with 40 CFR 123.36, as published by the Missouri Department of Natural Resources, Division of Environmental Quality, Water Protection Program, PO Box 176, Jefferson City, MO 65102-0176, which is hereby incorporated by reference into this rule without any later amendments or additions, or an alternative but equally protective standard subsequently approved by the department. https://nmplanner.missouri.edu/wp-content/plugins/nm-planner-functionality/public/assets/pdfs/Nutrient_Management_Tech_Standard-FINAL_3-4-09_Marked_NM-A.pdf</p>
<p>Do your NMP/MMPS follow, comply with, or based on NRCS Technical Standard 590?</p>	<p>Undetermined</p>
<p>Application rates: <i>State regulations that restrict the rates at which manures are applied and methods needed to determine appropriate rates.</i></p>	<p>Soil Testing_ Soil sampling protocols to determine soil test phosphorus, cation exchange capacity (CEC) and soil organic matter should be based on the following criteria: _</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. MU Guides G9215 (for pastures) and G9217 (for row and hay crops); _ b. The average field area represented by a soil sample should be approximately 20 acres or less; _ c. Each soil sample should be comprised of a well-mixed subsample derived from at least 15 representative cores from the sampled field

area; more cores are recommended on pastures or where phosphorus has been band applied; d. As an alternative to the conventional soil sampling approach in A1(1)c., operations may elect to use a geo-referenced grid soil sampling method instead. Grid size should be less than three acres and at least 10 cores should be obtained from within 15 feet of the central grid point; _

e. Soil sampling depth should be six to eight inches; _

f. Fields should be re-sampled before manure application when: _

i. The soil test is greater than five years old; or _

ii. Phosphate surplus (actual applied phosphate minus actual removed phosphate) for the field has exceeded 500 lbs./acre since the last soil test; g. Soil samples should be analyzed at soil testing laboratories accredited by the Missouri Soil Testing Association (see a current list of accredited labs at <https://extension.missouri.edu/programs/soil-and-plant-testing-laboratory/spl-missouri-soil-accreditation-program> using procedures recommended by the University of Missouri Soil Testing Laboratory._

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Fertilizer recommendations should be based on the following: _

a. Justified field-specific yield goals. Yield goals should be based on crop yield records from multiple years for the field. Good judgment should be used to adjust yield goals to counteract unusually low or high yields. When a field's yield history is not available another referenced source may be used to estimate yield goal; _

b. Current soil test results; _

c. University of Missouri fertilizer recommendations should be utilized. University of Missouri recommendations can be obtained on-line using current soil sample results at <https://extension.missouri.edu/programs/soil-and-plant-testing-laboratory/spl-soil-analysis/spl-online-results> ; _

d. When necessary, nutrient removal rates should be based on MU Guide G9120 or alternatively can be based on measured plant analysis records from the farm. If nutrient removal rates are based on plant analysis records, document how the crop is sampled and how plant analysis records are used to estimate nutrient removal for a crop; _

e. Published nutrient removal estimates from other land grant universities in adjoining states are also acceptable. _

f. Field-Level Fertilizer Applications -“ Fertilizer recommendations used to develop nutrient budgets shall be based on 20-acre field areas. When fertilizer recommendations are similar (within 10% or 10 pounds per acre, whichever is greater) for adjoining 20-acre field areas, they may be combined for purposes of fertilizer application and nutrient budgeting. Field areas of up to 80 acres may be combined using this guidance. Larger field areas may be combined if justification for this decision is documented in the nutrient management plan._

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All manure applications on land application area(s) shall meet all three of the following criteria: _

(1) Annual nitrogen application from all sources should not exceed the recommended nitrogen application rate for non-legume crops and the nitrogen removal capacity of legume crops by more than 10 pounds per acre or 10 percent, whichever is greater. _

a. The recommended nitrogen application rate for non-legume crops should be based on University of Missouri nitrogen fertilizer recommendations derived from a current soil test result for the field and a realistic yield goal. The nitrogen fertilizer recommendation must be adjusted using nitrogen credits for a preceding legume crop, residual fertilizer nitrogen value of manure applications from the previous year and, when appropriate, excessive residual inorganic nitrogen in the soil profile as quantified by the preplant soil nitrogen test. If University of Missouri does not provide a specific nitrogen recommendation for a non-legume crop, recommendations from other land grant universities should be used. Information on calculating residual fertilizer value of manure applications is available in MU Guide Publication G9186. Information on the appropriate use of the preplant soil nitrogen test is in MU Guide Publication G9177; _

b. The nitrogen removal capacity of legume crops should be based on the estimated nitrogen content of the harvested crop as defined in MU Guide G9120 and a realistic yield goal. The estimated nitrogen content of the crop must be adjusted using nitrogen credits for residual fertilizer nitrogen value of manure applications from the previous year and, when appropriate, excessive residual inorganic nitrogen in the soil profile as quantified by the preplant soil nitrogen test. If MU Guide G9120 does not provide an estimate of the nitrogen content of legume crop, recommendations from other land grant universities should be used. Information on calculating residual fertilizer value of manure applications is available in MU Guide Publication G9186. Information on the appropriate use of the preplant soil nitrogen test is in MU Guide Publication G9177; _

c. The nitrogen contribution of manure should be based on a calculation of plant-available nitrogen (PAN). Plant-available nitrogen is calculated by adjusting the inorganic and organic nitrogen concentrations using procedures outlined in MU Guide Publication G9186, and is available on the Web at <https://extension.missouri.edu/publications/g9184> _

(2) Manure application rates must comply with the results of a field-specific phosphorus loss assessment. _

a. Manure application rates can be based solely on nitrogen criteria (nitrogen-based management) if: _

i. The Missouri soil test phosphorus rating from a current soil test is very low, low, medium or optimum; or _

ii. The Missouri P-Index rating is low or medium. _

b. Manure application rates cannot exceed the annual planned phosphate removal capacity of the crop by more than 10 pounds per acre or 10 percent, whichever is greater (phosphorus-based management) if: _

i. The Missouri P-index rating is high; or _

	<p>ii. The Missouri soil test phosphorus rating from a current soil test is high and the field has not been assessed using the Missouri P-index. _</p> <p>c. Multi-year phosphorus application -“ When phosphorus-based management is necessary, manure applications can exceed the annual planned phosphate removal capacity of the crop. However, application rates must comply with the following conditions: _</p> <p>i. Rates shall not exceed the recommended nitrogen application rate during the year of application, or estimated nitrogen removal capacity in the harvested crop during the year of application when there is no recommended nitrogen application, and_</p> <p>ii. the amount of phosphorus banked in the soil will not exceed four years of crop removal for the planned rotation using the criteria found in section A1.(2) above, and _</p> <p>iii. the actual application rate shall not exceed 10 pounds per acre or 10 percent of the planned multi-year phosphorus application rate, whichever is greater. _</p> <p>d. No manure will be applied on a land application field if:_</p> <p>i. The Missouri P-index rating for the field is very high; or_</p> <p>ii. the University of Missouri soil test phosphorus rating from a current soil test is very high or excess and the field has not been assessed using the Missouri P-index. The Missouri P Index is described in MU Guide Publication G9184.</p>
<p>Manure application rates for phosphorus are based on:</p> <p>1) <i>Phosphorus Index Only</i></p> <p>2) <i>Soil Test Phosphorus Only</i></p> <p>3) <i>Either PIO or STPO</i></p> <p>4) <i>Other</i></p>	<p>Phosphorus index only</p>
<p>Are there any nutrient “caps” to manure application?</p>	<p>Undetermined</p>
<p>Composition testing: <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on manures before application</i></p>	<p>The following protocols describe how and when sources of manure should be sampled and how manure testing results will be used to estimate nutrient concentration in manure. _</p> <p>a. CAFOs are required to sample each unique source of land-applied manure at least once per year; _</p> <p>b. All manure samples should be tested for total nitrogen, ammonium nitrogen, total phosphorus, and total potassium. When lab results are reported on a dry basis manure samples should also be tested for dry matter or total solids (moisture content). Nitrate nitrogen is typically not present in manure samples but should be tested for if an innovative manure handling system is likely to create aerobic conditions where nitrate will persist in manure; _</p> <p>c. Samples should be collected and handled following the guidelines outlined in MU Guide Publications EQ215 and G9340 (for poultry litter); _</p>

	d. When possible, sample and analyze manure just prior to the time for land application of manure so current results are available for calculating manure application rates.
Does your state require testing of manure for anything beyond nutrients, such as metals, pathogens, antibiotics, etc.?	Undetermined
Other land application highlights: <i>Additional restrictions for land application of manures</i>	No other information
Other regulatory details: <i>Additional information on the regulation of land application of manures</i>	No other information
General Assessment Questions	
Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change:	Undetermined
Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of manures that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links:	No
Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of manures beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so:	No
Is the land application	No other information

of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.

Montana Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2025
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Montana Department of Environmental Quality (MDEQ)
Links to regulations	MDEQ General Permit for CAFOs_ https://deq.mt.gov/files/Water/WQInfo/Documents/2023%20Public%20Notices/PN-MT-23-04-MTG010000/FINAL/2023-FPER-MTG010000.pdf _ Montana Code Annotated (MCA):_ https://archive.legmt.gov/bills/mca/title_0750/chapter_0050/part_0080/sections_index.html _ c.f. 75-5-801, 75-5-802, 75-5-803_ Administrative Rules of MT (ARM):_ https://rules.mt.gov/ _ c.f 17.30.1330, 17.30.1334
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Environmental
Other regulator info	No other information
Definitions	
How CAFOs are defined or categorized:	An operation is considered an Animal Feeding Operation (AFO) if the operation meets both of these conditions: 1.) the animals are confined for at least 45 days during a 12-month period, and 2.) crops, forage growth, and other vegetation are not grown in the area where animals are confined. The 45 days of confinement do not have to be consecutive days and the 12 month period can be any 12 consecutive months._ – Concentrated Animal Feeding Operations (CAFOs) are AFOs that meet certain regulatory criteria. An AFO can be considered a CAFO if an AFO is defined as a CAFO or an AFO is designated as CAFO. AFOs are defined as CAFOs if the CAFO has a certain number of animals and it meets other criteria in the regulations. The regulations set thresholds for size categories based on the number of animals confined in the production area for a total of 45 days or more in any 12-month period._ – There are two defined thresholds for CAFOs, which include:_ Large CAFOs_ To be defined as a large CAFO, the operation must: Meet the regulatory definition of an AFO, and Meet the Large CAFO threshold for at least one animal type. Refer to

	<p>the General Permit for Concentrated Animal Feeding Operations (General Permit) for threshold sizes._ Medium CAFOs_ To be defined as a medium CAFO, the operation must: Meet the regulatory definition of an AFO, and Meet the Medium CAFO threshold for at least one animal type. Refer to the General Permit for threshold sizes. Meet at least one of the following two criteria: Pollutants are discharged in waters of the state through a man-made ditch, flushing system, or similar man-made device, or Pollutants are discharged directly into waters of the state which originate outside of and pass over, across, or through the facility or otherwise come in direct contact with the animals confined in the operation._</p> <p>– An AFO may be designated as a CAFO based on the Department of Environmental Quality (Department) determination that the operation is a significant contributor of pollution to state watersIn making this designation, the department considers the following factors:_</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * The size of the AFO and the amount of wastes reaching state waters;_ *The location of the AFO relative to state waters;_ *The means of conveyance of animal wastes and process waste waters into state waters;_ *The slope, vegetation, rainfall, and other factors affecting the likelihood or frequency of discharge of animal wastes and process waste waters into state waters; and_ *Other relevant factors._ <p>See above</p>
<p>How animal units are defined (if used):</p>	<p>Not used</p>
<p>NPDES permitting or other permitting requirements:</p>	<p>Owners or operators of animal feeding operations that meet the definition of a concentrated animal feeding operation (CAFO) as defined by Montana Code Annotated 75-5-801 are eligible for coverage under a general permit. Once an operation is defined as a CAFO, the Montana Discharge Elimination System (MPDES) requirements for CAFOs apply to all animals in confinement at the operation and to all manure, litter and process wastewater generated by those animals or by the production of those animals, regardless of the type of animal. DEQ may require any facility to apply for and obtain individual permit coverage if review of the NOI package finds it necessary (See Section I.C of the CAFO General Permit)._ The following CAFOs are not eligible for coverage under this general permit and must apply for an individual permit:_</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) CAFOs that cannot comply with any applicable effluent standards, effluent limitations, standards of performance for new sources of pollutants, toxic effluent standards and prohibitions, and pretreatment standards, or any additional requirements that DEQ determines are necessary_ (b) CAFOs that do not meet the adequate storage requirements for manure, litter and process wastewater given in Part II.A of the CAFO General Permit (GP)_ (c) CAFOs that do not meet the minimum ground water protection practices

	<p>specified in Part II.C of the CAFO GP_</p> <p>(d) CAFOs that cannot comply with any applicable water quality standards established in Title 17, Chapter 30, Subchapter 6 and Subchapter 10_</p> <p>(e) CAFOs that have discharges to which the regional administrator of the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) has objected in writing;_</p> <p>(f) CAFOs that the Department has notified to apply for an individual permit per Part I.H of the CAFO GP._</p> <p>(g) If an MPDES permit or authorization for the same operation has been previously denied or revoked._</p> <p>(h) Discharge different in degree or nature from the sources or activities described in the General Permit._</p> <p>(i) Point sources in an area of unique ecological or recreational significance as determined by Montana stream classifications, such as impacts on fishery resources, local conditions at proposed discharge sites, designations of wilderness areas, or designations of wild and scenic rivers.</p>
Does the state require an NPDES permit for all Large CAFOs?	Yes
Does the state issue individual or general CAFO permits?	Both
Are any other permits required for CAFOs or other large farms?	Undetermined
Other definitions needed to understand these regulations:	No other information
Regulatory Details	
Setbacks: <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie</i>	<p>Manure, litter, and process wastewater must not be applied or temporarily stored within 100 feet of any down-gradient surface waters, open tile line intake structures, sink holes, agricultural well heads, or any other conduits to surface waters unless the permittee demonstrates in the site-specific NMP that the following compliance alternatives are protective of water quality:_</p> <p>(i) the CAFO may substitute the 100-foot setback with a 35-foot wide vegetated buffer where applications of manure, litter or process wastewater are prohibited;</p>

<p><i>between the site of land application and some geographical feature</i></p>	<p>or_ (ii) the CAFO may demonstrate that a set-back or buffer is not necessary because implementation of alternative conservation practices or field-specific conditions will provide pollutant reductions equivalent to or better than the reductions that would be achieved by the 100-foot setback.</p>
<p>Are setbacks more restrictive than CFR?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Timing, weather, or conditional application restrictions: <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather, seasons, or land characteristics (like slope)</i></p>	<p>Timing of Application_ Manure must be applied to fields at times and under conditions that will hold the nutrients in place for crop growth and protect both surface and ground water by using the best management practices described in the NMP. The intended target spreading dates must be included in the NMP. Manure must not be land applied under the following conditions:_ (a) on land that is flooded or saturated with water;_ (b)) during or within 36 hours of a rainfall event that exceeds four hours in duration or 0.25 inches or more of precipitation; or_ (c) to frozen or snow-covered ground (winter application) except for fields meeting the following criteria:_ (i) the application area must be at least 300 feet from lakes, stream, intermittent streams, irrigation canals and ditches, open intake structures, property lines and road rights-of-way;_ (ii) there must be permanent vegetative cover or standing stubble with crop residue greater than 50%; and_ (iii) land slope of the field must not exceed the following criteria: six percent for application of solid manure (total solids content great than 15%); or three percent for application of slurry or liquid waste (total solids content of 15% or less).</p>
<p>Is there a restriction for land application of manure to saturated soils?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Is there a restriction for land application of manure within floodplains?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Is there a restriction for land application of</p>	<p>Yes</p>

manure related to future rainfall?	
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to frozen or snow-covered ground?	Yes
Are there restrictions to manure applications based on time of year or time of day?	No
Are there restrictions to manure application based on slope?	Yes
Are there any other seasonal, timing, weather, or physical restrictions to manure applications not captured above?	Undetermined
Transfer of manure off-site: <i>Requirements related to the transfer of manures to other persons</i>	Prior to transferring manure, litter, or process wastewater to other persons, the CAFO must provide the recipient of the manure, litter, or process wastewater with the most current nutrient analysis. The analysis must specify the nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P) content of the manure, litter, and process wastewater based on the current calendar year using the testing procedures given in Part II.D.4 of the CAFO GP. CAFOs must retain for five years records of the date, recipient name and address, and the approximate amount of manure, litter, or process wastewater transferred to the recipient.
Are receivers of manure transfers	Undetermined

<p>from CAFOs required to follow the same regulations?</p>	
<p>Nutrient or manure management plans: <i>Additional details on the NMP requirement. Note that some of this information may overlap with other sections</i></p>	<p>CAFO owner or operators seeking coverage under the general permit must submit a nutrient management plan (NMP) with the NOI, as required by Part II.F. of the CAFO GP. The NMP shall specifically identify and describe the practices that will be implemented to assure compliance with the effluent limitations set forth in Part II.A-E of the CAFO GP and other conditions of this permit. The NMP must be developed in accordance with the permit and must be completed on the application form NOI-NMP CAFO (ver. March 2023). NMPs can use a linear or narrative approach for determining application rates.</p>
<p>Do your NMP/MMPS follow, comply with, or based on NRCS Technical Standard 590?</p>	<p>As an alternative to the manure application rates based on the criteria given in Part II.D.3 of the CAFO PG, the CAFO may develop application rates for manure based on NRCS Conservation Practice Standard Code 590, provided that all of the conditions in se</p>
<p>Application rates: <i>State regulations that restrict the rates at which manures are applied and methods needed to determine appropriate rates.</i></p>	<p>Application rates for manure, litter, and process wastewater applied to land under the ownership or operational control of the CAFO must minimize N and P transport from the field into surface water in accordance with technical standards given in ARM 17.30.1334. These standards must be incorporated into the CAFO's site-specific NMP._</p> <p>– Nutrient-based limits_</p> <p>Except as provided in Part II.D.3.10 of the Permit, application rates for each field must be determined based on the following criteria:_</p> <p>(a) The field-specific assessment for CAFOs applying manure on fields that are located in a watershed that is listed as impaired for nutrients (total P or total N) must follow the method listed in (i). The field-specific assessment for CAFOs applying manure on fields that are not located in a watershed that is listed as impaired for nutrients (total P or total N) may follow the procedures in either (i) or (ii)._</p> <p>(i) The field-specific assessment must be based on the P index assessment method described in United States Department of Agriculture (USDA) Natural Resources Conservation Service (NRCS), No. 80.1 Nutrient Management, Agronomy Technical Note MT-77 (revision 4), May 2013. The nutrient application basis is determined as follows: (A) N-based application if the site vulnerability rating is low (total P index</p>

value is less than 11); (B) P-based if the site vulnerability rating is medium (total P index value is between 11 and 21); (C) P-based application up to crop removal if the site vulnerability rating is high (total P index value is between 22 and 43); or (D) no application if the site vulnerability rating is rated as very high (total P index value is greater than 43)._

(ii) The field-specific assessment must be based on a representative soil sample using the Olsen P soil test method. The nutrient application basis is determined as follows: (A) N-based application if the Olsen P soil test is less than 25 mg/L; (B) P-based application if the Olsen P soil test is greater than 25 .1 mg/L and less than 100 mg/L; (C) P-based up to crop removal if the Olsen P soil test is_ greater than 100.1 mg/L and less than 150.0 mg/L; or (D) no application if the Olsen P soil test is greater than 150 mg/L._

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Soil Testing_

Each field where manure, litter, and process wastewater is to be land applied must be sampled at least once every five years and analyzed as follows:_

(a) A minimum of ten individual soil core samples must be composited to formulate a composite sample for the field. Core sampling in fields with significant landscape variation, including soil type, slope, degree of erosion, drainage, historic usage, or other factors, must be collected from each unit in proportion to the relative abundance in terms of total area. Uniform fields may be sampled in a simple random, stratified random, or systematic pattern following the guidance sources listed below. Individual core samples must be composited and thoroughly mixed in a clean plastic container except that core samples collected at different depths must be kept separate. Alternative soil sapling procedures are given in the following:

(i) United States Department of Agriculture (USDA), Natural Resource Conservation Service (NRCS), Sampling Soils for Nutrient Management – Manure Resource Series, MT, April 2007; and

(ii) Montana State University Extension, MontGuide, Interpretation of Soil Test Reports for Agriculture, MT200702AG, Oct. 2013.

(b) The composite soil sample for P analysis must be collected from a depth of zero to six inches below the surface and analyzed for P using the Olsen soil test method. Results must be reported as mg/kg P and pounds per acre;_

(c) The composite soil sample for N analysis must be collected from a depth of zero to six inches below the surface and analyzed for total N and nitrate (as N). A second composite sample must be collected at a depth of six to 24 inches and analyzed for nitrate (as N) only. Samples must be analyzed in accordance with method code 4H2a1-3 in USDA NRCS Soil Survey Methods Manual, Soil Survey Investigations Report No. 42, Version 6.0, 2022. Results must be reported as mg/kg total N and pounds per acre. _

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Analytical laboratories approved for manure and soil testing are given in Montana State University Extension Service Publication 4449-1, Soil Sampling and Laboratory Selection, June 2005._

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Crop Nutrient Requirements_

The CAFO must complete a nutrient needs analysis for each crop to determine the

	<p>acceptable amounts of N and P to be applied to the field based on the appropriate basis (N- or P-based application) as determined above. The nutrient needs must be determined using Montana State University Extension Service Publication 161, Fertilizer Guidelines for Montana Crops. For crops not listed in Bulletin 161, the department may approve a fertilizer application rate provided by the local county extension service or other qualified source. The CAFO must identify the source of the nutrient needs analysis in the NMP. _</p> <p>The CAFO must complete a nutrient budget based on the nutrients needs of the crop as defined above. The nutrient budget must account for all sources of nutrients available to the crop. Other sources that must be addressed where applicable include:_</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (i) N needs determined above must be reduced based on N fixation credits if a legume crop was grown in the field in the previous year;_ (ii) N needs determined above must be reduced based on the N residual from past manure application and N mineralization rates as given in ARM 17.30.1334(3)(c);_ (iii) the N needs determined above must be reduced based on any commercial fertilizer applied, irrigation water, or other sources of nutrients; and_ (iv) N availability may be adjusted to reflect the method of application as given in ARM 17.30.1334(3)(c) Schedule II. For P-based application, the N availability is 1.0._ <p>_</p> <p>A multi-year P application is allowed for fields that require an N-based application based on a site-specific assessment (site vulnerability rating less than 22) as described in ARM 17.30.1334(3). When such application is made, the following conditions apply:_</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) the application may not exceed the recommended N application rate during the years of application. This may include a calculation for fertilizer inefficiencies or the estimated N removal in harvested plant biomass during the year of application when there is no recommended N application;_ (b) conservation practices must be included in the NMP and implemented to minimize the risk of P loss from the field; and_ (c) no additional manure may be applied to the field until the P applied in the single application has been removed through plant harvest._ <p>_</p> <p>As an alternative to the manure application rates based on the criteria given in this part, the CAFO may develop application rates for manure based on United States Department of Agriculture (USDA), Natural Resource Conservation Service (NRCS), Conservation Practice Standard, Code 590 (November 2006), provided the conditions in ARM 17.30.1334(11) are met.</p>
<p>Manure application rates for phosphorus are based on:</p> <p>1) <i>Phosphorus Index Only</i></p>	<p>Phosphorus index or soil test</p>

<p>2) Soil Test Phosphorus Only 3) Either PIO or STPO 4) Other</p>	
<p>Are there any nutrient “caps” to manure application?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Composition testing: <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on manures before application</i></p>	<p>Manure, litter, and process wastewater that is land applied must be sampled at least once per year and analyzed for total N, ammonium (as NH₄-N), total P (as Phosphrous petoxide; P₂₀₅), total potassium (as K₂O), and percent dry matter (solids). Except for percent dry matter, the results of this analysis must be expressed as pounds per 1,000 gallons for liquid wastes or as pounds per ton for solid manure. The sample must be representative of the manure that is to be land-applied to a field and must be collected and analyzed in accordance with ARM 17.30.1334(4)(a) and (b)._ Each field where manure is to be land applied must be sampled at least once every five years for total N, nitrate (as N), and P in accordance with the procedures given in ARM 17.30.1334(5)(a)-(c).</p>
<p>Does your state require testing of manure for anything beyond nutrients, such as metals, pathogens, antibiotics, etc.?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Other land application highlights: <i>Additional restrictions for land application of manures</i></p>	<p>The Department may require the permittee to monitor ground water near the facility if any component of the production area constitutes a potential source of pollution to state ground water. Monitoring may be required in areas having shallow ground water o</p>
<p>Other regulatory details:</p>	<p>The field-specific assessment may be based on either the P index assessment method or a representative soil sample using the Olsen P soil test method, unless the receiving water is impaired for nutrients. In such case, the assessment must be</p>

<p><i>Additional information on the regulation of land application of manures</i></p>	<p>based on the</p>
<p>General Assessment Questions</p>	
<p>Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change:</p>	<p>Undetermined</p>
<p>Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of manures that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links:</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of manures beyond</p>	<p>No. However, CAFOs are subject to any applicable local floodplain regulations.</p>

<p>state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so:</p>	
<p>Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.</p>	<p>No other information</p>

Nebraska Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2019
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Nebraska Department of Environmental Quality (NDEQ)
Links to regulations	Overview including links to regulations, applications, etc._ https://dee.nebraska.gov/land-waste/agriculture/livestock-waste-control-program _ _ Title 130 Livestock Waste Control Regulations_ https://dee.nebraska.gov/sites/default/files/titles/Title%20130%20Effective%2010-04-2011.pdf
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Environmental
Other regulator info	No other information
Definitions	
How CAFOs are defined or categorized:	<p>Animal Feeding Operation - means a location where beef cattle, dairy cattle, horses, swine, sheep, poultry, or other livestock have been, are, or will be stabled or confined and fed or maintained for a total of forty-five days or more in any twelve-month period and crops, vegetation, forage growth, or post-harvest residues are not sustained in the normal growing season over any portion of the location. Two or more Animal Feeding Operations under common ownership are deemed to be a single Animal Feeding Operation if they are adjacent to each other or if they utilize a common area or system for the disposal of livestock waste. Animal feeding operation does not include aquaculture as defined in Neb. Rev. Stat. § 2-3804.01._</p> <p>_</p> <p>Concentrated Animal Feeding Operation -or CAFO- means an Animal Feeding Operation that is:_</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Defined as a large concentrated Animal Feeding Operation because of size;_ * Defined as a medium concentrated Animal Feeding Operation because of size and because animals are in direct contact with waters of the State or waste is discharged to waters of the state through a man-made conduit; or_ * Designated as a medium or small concentrated Animal Feeding Operation by the Director._ <p>_</p> <p>Large CAFO-or Large AFO- means an Animal Feeding Operation that stables or confines as many as or more than the number of animals specified in any of the following categories:_</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * 700 mature dairy cows, whether milked or dry;_

- * 1,000 veal calves;_
- * 1,000 cattle other than mature dairy cows or veal calves and including but not limited to heifers, steers, bulls, and cow/calf pairs;_
- * 2,500 swine each weighing 55 pounds or more;_
- * 10,000 swine each weighing less than 55 pounds;_
- * 500 horses;_
- * 10,000 sheep or lambs;_
- * 55,000 turkeys;_
- * 30,000 laying hens or broilers, if the Animal Feeding Operation uses a liquid manure handling system;_
- * 125,000 chickens, other than laying hens, if the Animal Feeding Operation uses other than a liquid manure handling system;_
- * 82,000 laying hens, if the Animal Feeding Operation uses other than a liquid manure handling system;_
- * 5,000 ducks, if the Animal Feeding Operation uses a liquid manure handling system; or_
- * 30,000 ducks, if the Animal Feeding Operation uses other than a liquid manure handling system._

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 Medium Animal Feeding Operation-² means an Animal Feeding Operation that confines or stables the type and number of animals in any of the following ranges: _

- * 200 to 699 mature dairy cows, whether milked or dry;_
- * 300 to 999 veal calves;_
- * 300 to 999 cattle other than mature dairy cows or veal calves. Cattle include but are not limited to heifers, steers, bulls, and cow/calf pairs;_
- * 750 to 2,499 swine each weighing 55 pounds or more;_
- * 3,000 to 9,999 swine each weighing less than 55 pounds;_
- * 150 to 499 horses;_
- * 3,000 to 9,999 sheep or lambs;_
- * 16,500 to 54,999 turkeys;_
- * 9,000 to 29,999 laying hens or broilers, if the Animal Feeding Operation uses a liquid manure handling system;_
- * 37,500 to 124,999 chickens, other than laying hens, if the Animal Feeding Operation uses other than a liquid manure handling system;_
- * 25,000 to 81,999 laying hens, if the Animal Feeding Operation uses other than a liquid manure handling system;_
- * 1,500 to 4,999 ducks, if the Animal Feeding Operation uses a liquid manure handling system; or _
- * 10,000 to 29,999 ducks, if the Animal Feeding Operation uses other than a liquid manure handling system._

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 Medium concentrated Animal Feeding Operation-² means a medium Animal Feeding Operation, as defined by the type and number of animals that it confines or stables, and which has been defined or designated as a concentrated Animal Feeding Operation. An Animal Feeding Operation is defined as a medium concentrated Animal Feeding Operation if either one of the following conditions is met: _

	<p>* Pollutants are discharged into waters of the state through a man-made ditch, flushing system, or other similar man-made device; or _</p> <p>* Pollutants are discharged directly into waters of the state that originate outside of and pass over, across, or through the Animal Feeding Operation or otherwise come into direct contact with the animals confined in the operation.</p>
How animal units are defined (if used):	Not used
NPDES permitting or other permitting requirements:	<p>An owner or operator of a concentrated Animal Feeding Operation that discharges is required to obtain an NPDES permit._</p> <p>All AFOs that have potential to negatively impact waters of the State (based on an inspection) must submit an application for a Construction and Operating Permit which includes the development of a nutrient management plan._</p> <p>_</p> <p>Both Individual and general NPDES permits are issued to CAFOs._</p> <p>Individual NPDES Permits are issued to operations that have either multiple livestock species or livestock waste control facilities that would be considered alternative technologies, such as vegetative treatment areas._</p> <p>General NPDES Permits are issued to operations that confine cattle only._</p> <p>The state Construction and Operating Permit is considered an individual permit._</p> <p>_</p> <p>Depending on the type of mortality handling an Air Permit (incineration) might be required or Solid Waste Permit (large composting operation) might be required._</p> <p>If more than an acre is disturbed during construction at an operation a Construction Stormwater Permit is required as well._</p>
Does the state require an NPDES permit for all Large CAFOs?	No
Does the state issue individual or general CAFO permits?	Both
Are any other permits required for CAFOs or other large farms?	Yes
Other definitions needed to understand	"Discharge" means the spilling, leaking, pumping, pouring, emitting, emptying, or dumping of pollutants into any waters of the State or in a place which will likely reach waters of the State.

these regulations:	
Regulatory Details	
Setbacks: <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some geographical feature</i>	For large concentrated Animal Feeding Operations, manure, litter, and process wastewater may not be stockpiled or applied closer than 100 feet to any down-gradient surface waters, open tile line intake structures, well heads, or other conduits to surface or ground water, except that one of the following two compliance alternatives may be substituted for the application setback requirement:_ * A 35-foot-wide vegetated buffer where the application of manure, litter, or process wastewater is prohibited. For the purposes of these regulations vegetated buffer means a permanent strip of dense perennial vegetation established parallel to the contours of and perpendicular to the dominant slope of the field for the purposes of slowing water runoff, enhancing water infiltration, and minimizing the risk of any potential nutrients or pollutants from leaving the field and reaching waters of the state; or_ * A satisfactory demonstration that a setback or buffer is not necessary because implementation of alternative conservation practices will provide pollutant reductions equal to or better than reductions that would be achieved by the 100-foot setback._ * The NDEQ will determine if a specific site requires setbacks more restrictive than CFR.
Are setbacks more restrictive than CFR?	Yes
Timing, weather, or conditional application restrictions: <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather, seasons, or land characteristics (like slope)</i>	For a field or field segment with a high or very high phosphorus risk assessment rating, there shall be no application of manure, litter, or process wastewater when the soil is frozen, or snow or ice covered._ _ An application rate of liquid containing manure, litter, or process wastewater that shall not exceed the intake rate of the soil such that runoff of the manure, litter, or process wastewater occurs. Total liquid application shall not exceed the field capacity of the soil;_
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to	No

saturated soils?	
Is there a restriction for land application of manure within floodplains?	No
Is there a restriction for land application of manure related to future rainfall?	No
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to frozen or snow-covered ground?	Yes
Are there restrictions to manure applications based on time of year or time of day?	No
Are there restrictions to manure application based on slope?	No
Are there any other seasonal, timing, weather, or physical restrictions to manure applications not captured above?	0% discharge allowed by Department.
Transfer of	The NPDES permittee or the owner or operator of a large concentrated Animal

<p>manure off-site: <i>Requirements related to the transfer of manures to other persons</i></p>	<p>Feeding Operation with a livestock waste control facility, shall maintain production area and land application area records at the concentrated Animal Feeding Operation for a period of five years from the date they are created. A complete copy of the following information is required (in terms of transfer): For manure, litter, or process wastewater transferred to other persons the nutrient analysis results and the date, recipient name and address, and approximate amount transferred. If slurry or effluent is applied to the same site two consecutive years, the site shall be added to the land application area of the NMP and all application site regulations followed.</p>
<p>Are receivers of manure transfers from CAFOs required to follow the same regulations?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Nutrient or manure management plans: <i>Additional details on the NMP requirement. Note that some of this information may overlap with other sections</i></p>	<p>Nutrient Management Plan is required to ensure meeting 40 CFR standards, using either a linear or narrative approach. NMP's must follow and comply with Nebraska Administrative Code - Title 130 regulations, University of Nebraska recommendations, NRCS 590, or any standard deemed by the Department to fulfill Title 130 requirements.</p>
<p>Do your NMP/MMPS follow, comply with, or based on NRCS Technical Standard 590?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Application rates: <i>State regulations that restrict the rates at which manures are applied and methods</i></p>	<p>A field phosphorus risk assessment conducted prior to initial land application of manure, litter, or process wastewater and then prior to subsequent applications if the risk value of any site category listed in Table 3 of Field Phosphorus Risk Assessment (Appendix E) has changed, but in no case less than once every five years. The assessment evaluates such factors as soil type, slope, crop residue, soil fertility, potential for erosion, and planned cropping practices for each field or field segment used for land application, to determine the potential for phosphorus transport from the field or field segment. The assessment shall be completed for each field or field segment using the form provided in Field Phosphorus Risk</p>

<p><i>needed to determine appropriate rates.</i></p>	<p>Assessment (Appendix E), which is based on a method developed by the United States Department of Agriculture Natural Resources Conservation Service, or by using a comparable field phosphorus risk assessment method and forms approved for use by the Department. The plan shall identify the phosphorus risk assessment used for each field or field segment. The planned application rates for manure, litter, or process wastewater shall be consistent with the risk assessment for each field, or field segment, as follows:_ * For a field or field segment where there is a low or medium risk of phosphorus movement from the field, a single year's application of manure, litter, or process wastewater may be based on the expected annual available nitrogen from the waste and other sources;_ * For a field or field segment where there is a high risk of phosphorus movement from the field, the application of manure, litter, or process wastewater shall be kept at a rate equal to, or less than, the expected phosphorus removal in harvested plant biomass in a single crop year, or for a planned crop sequence of five years or less, that is equal to or less than the expected phosphorus removal in harvested plant biomass for the crop sequence. The application and other sources shall not exceed the expected annual available nitrogen use of the crop; and_ * For a field or field segment with a very high risk of phosphorus movement from the field, manure, litter, or process wastewater shall not be applied.</p>
<p>Manure application rates for phosphorus are based on: 1) <i>Phosphorus Index Only</i> 2) <i>Soil Test Phosphorus Only</i> 3) <i>Either PIO or STPO</i> 4) <i>Other</i></p>	<p>Phosphorus index only</p>
<p>Are there any nutrient “caps” to manure application?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Composition testing: <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on</i></p>	<p>Sampling and laboratory testing as follows:_ * Manure, litter, and process wastewater at least annually for nitrogen and phosphorus content;_ * Application site soils for nitrogen content before the initial application of manure, litter, or process wastewater, and then sample and analyze at least annually thereafter if used for application;_ * Application site soils for phosphorus content before the initial application of manure, litter, or process wastewater and then at least once every five years thereafter if used for application;_</p>

<i>manures before application</i>	* Irrigation water prior to initial use and at least once every five years thereafter for nitrogen; and_ * University of Nebraska guidelines for sampling and analysis may be used. The Department may approve alternate methods as appropriate;_
Does your state require testing of manure for anything beyond nutrients, such as metals, pathogens, antibiotics, etc.?	No
Other land application highlights: <i>Additional restrictions for land application of manures</i>	Zero percent discharge for all facilities, including land application.
Other regulatory details: <i>Additional information on the regulation of land application of manures</i>	Permits are required to attend Manure Land Application Training once every five years.
General Assessment Questions	
Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may	Undetermined

potentially change:	
Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of manures that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links:	No
Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of manures beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so:	Yes
Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.	No other information

Nevada	
Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2019
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Nevada Department of Environmental Protection (NDEP)
Links to regulations	Nevada Administrative Code (NAC) Chapter 445A, Water Controls_ https://www.leg.state.nv.us/NAC/NAC-445A.html
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Environmental
Other regulator info	No other information
Definitions	
How CAFOs are defined or categorized:	<p>Concentrated Animal Feeding Operation-² has the meaning ascribed to it in 40 C.F.R. § 122.23._</p> <p>_</p> <p>Facilities in which crops, vegetation, forage growth or postharvest residues are not sustained in the normal growing season and that confine animals if the facilities contain, or at any time during the previous 12 months contained, for a total of 30 days or more, any of the following types of animals at or in excess of the number listed for each type of animal:_</p> <p>(I)Cattle, veal calves or a pair consisting of a cow and a calf, 1,000;_ (II)Mature dairy cattle (whether milkers or dry cows), 700;_ (III)Swine weighing over 55 pounds, 2,500;_ (IV)Swine weighing 55 pounds or less, 10,000;_ (V)Horses, 500;_ (VI)Sheep or lambs, 10,000;_ (VII)Turkeys, 55,000;_ (VIII)Chickens, if the animal confinement facility has a liquid manure handling system, 30,000;_ (IX)Chickens, other than laying hens, if the animal confinement facility does not have a liquid manure handling system, 125,000;_ (X)Laying hens, if the animal confinement facility does not have a liquid manure handling system, 82,000;_ (XI)Ducks, if the animal confinement facility has a liquid manure handling system, 5,000; or_ (XII)Ducks, if the animal confinement facility does not have a liquid manure handling system, 30,000.</p>
How animal units are defined (if used):	Not used

<p>NPDES permitting or other permitting requirements:</p>	<p>The NDEP Bureau of Water Pollution Control (BWPC) administers the state's Nevada's National Pollutant Discharge Elimination System (NPDES) program, as well as a State groundwater permit to CAFOs that do not discharge to a water of the United States. The state CAFO permits are required under certain activities by US EPA 40 CFR 412 and applied to CAFOs as defined under NRS 445A and NAC445A. The main difference between the two permits is the discharge point - facilities that are issued a NPDES permit either discharge, or have the potential to discharge, to a water of the United States. _</p> <p>_</p> <p>https://ndep.nv.gov/uploads/water-wpc-permitting-individual-npdes-docs/discharge-permit-overview-2017.pdf _</p> <p>_</p> <p>https://ndep.nv.gov/water/water-pollution-control/permitting/concentrated-animal-feeding-operations-cafo-program _</p> <p>Outline on NV CAFOs:_</p> <p>http://agri.nv.gov/uploadedFiles/agrinvgov/Content/Resources/FAQs/cafo_faq.pdf</p>
<p>Does the state require an NPDES permit for all Large CAFOs?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Does the state issue individual or general CAFO permits?</p>	<p>Individual</p>
<p>Are any other permits required for CAFOs or other large farms?</p>	<p>Undetermined</p>
<p>Other definitions needed to understand these regulations:</p>	<p>Point source-² means any discernible, confined and discrete conveyance, including but not limited to any pipe, ditch, channel, tunnel, conduit, well, discrete fissure, container, rolling stock, concentrated Animal Feeding Operation, or vessel or other floating craft, from which pollutants are or may be discharged. The term does not include return flows from irrigated agriculture.</p>
<p>Regulatory Details</p>	
<p>Setbacks: <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between</i></p>	<p>Nevada water quality-based setback requirements are the same as federal requirements. Land application should not be closer than 100 feet of any down gradient surface waters, sinkholes, agricultural well heads, or other conduits to surface waters unless the CAFO substitutes the 100-foot setback with a 35-foot wide vegetated buffer where applications of manure, litter, or process wastewater are prohibited. The CAFO owner or operator may demonstrate to NDEP that a setback or vegetated buffer is unnecessary because of site-specific conditions or</p>

<i>the site of land application and some geographical feature</i>	BMPs (NAC, 2008).
Are setbacks more restrictive than CFR?	No
Timing, weather, or conditional application restrictions: <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather, seasons, or land characteristics (like slope)</i>	None
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to saturated soils?	No
Is there a restriction for land application of manure within floodplains?	No
Is there a restriction for land application of manure related to future rainfall?	No
Is there a restriction for	No

land application of manure to frozen or snow-covered ground?	
Are there restrictions to manure applications based on time of year or time of day?	No
Are there restrictions to manure application based on slope?	No
Are there any other seasonal, timing, weather, or physical restrictions to manure applications not captured above?	Dry weather discharges of manure to surface waters of the State are prohibited from production and land application areas.
Transfer of manure off-site: <i>Requirements related to the transfer of manures to other persons</i>	Refer to 40 CFR
Are receivers of manure transfers from CAFOs required to follow the same regulations?	No
Nutrient or manure management	All Nevada large CAFOs must have a Division-approved Comprehensive Nutrient Management Plan (CNMP). The CNMP should be prepared in accordance with the most recent Natural Resources Conservation Service (NRCS) Conservation

<p>plans: <i>Additional details on the NMP requirement. Note that some of this information may overlap with other sections</i></p>	<p>Practice Standard Code.</p>
<p>Do your NMP/MMPS follow, comply with, or based on NRCS Technical Standard 590?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Application rates: <i>State regulations that restrict the rates at which manures are applied and methods needed to determine appropriate rates.</i></p>	<p>Refer to 40 CFR</p>
<p>Manure application rates for phosphorus are based on: <i>1) Phosphorus Index Only 2) Soil Test Phosphorus Only 3) Either PIO or STPO 4) Other</i></p>	<p>No method</p>
<p>Are there any nutrient “caps” to manure</p>	<p>No</p>

application?	
Composition testing: <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on manures before application</i>	Refer to 40 CFR
Does your state require testing of manure for anything beyond nutrients, such as metals, pathogens, antibiotics, etc.?	No
Other land application highlights: <i>Additional restrictions for land application of manures</i>	No other information
Other regulatory details: <i>Additional information on the regulation of land application of manures</i>	No other information
General Assessment Questions	
Do you anticipate changes in these	Undetermined

<p>regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change:</p>	
<p>Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of manures that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links:</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of manures beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so:</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not</p>	<p>No other information</p>

biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.

New Hampshire	
Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2019
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	US Environmental Protection Agency (US EPA)_ New Hampshire Department of Environmental Services (DES)_ New Hampshire Department of Agriculture (NHDA)_ _ (The DES is notified of improper manure handling practices that cannot be remedied by the Department o
Links to regulations	Env-Wq 301 State Surface Water Discharge Permits. Specifically state that do not apply to CAFOs._ https://www.des.nh.gov/sites/g/files/ehbemt341/files/documents/env-wq-300.pdf _ RSA Title 40 431:33-36 statutes address BMP, manure handling and the Agriculture Nutrient Management Program. Not specifically CAFOs._ http://www.gencourt.state.nh.us/rsa/html/NHTOC/NHTOC-XL-431.htm
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	More than one agency
Other regulator info	There is one permit being drafted by EPA for the first CAFO regulated in NH. Most other AFOs are dairy farms.
Definitions	
How CAFOs are defined or categorized:	Refer to 40 CFR
How animal units are defined (if used):	Refer to 40 CFR
NPDES permitting or other permitting requirements:	New Hampshire NPDES permits are issued by US EPA - the state is not delegated authority to administer the NPDES program. _ https://www.epa.gov/npdes-permits/new-hampshire-npdes-permits _ A dam permit may be required if manure storage lagoon dimensions meet the definition of a dam.
Does the state require an NPDES permit for all Large CAFOs?	No
Does the state issue individual or general CAFO permits?	Individual
Are any other permits required for CAFOs or other large farms?	Yes
Other definitions needed to understand these regulations:	No other information
Regulatory Details	
Setbacks:	Refer to 40 CFR

<i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some geographical feature</i>	
Are setbacks more restrictive than CFR?	No
Timing, weather, or conditional application restrictions: <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather, seasons, or land characteristics (like slope)</i>	Refer to 40 CFR
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to saturated soils?	No
Is there a restriction for land application of manure within floodplains?	No
Is there a restriction for land application of manure related to future rainfall?	No
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to frozen or snow-covered ground?	No
Are there restrictions to manure applications based on time of year or time of day?	No
Are there restrictions to manure application based on slope?	No
Are there any other seasonal, timing, weather, or physical restrictions to manure applications not captured above?	Refer to 40 CFR
Transfer of manure off-site:	Refer to 40 CFR

<i>Requirements related to the transfer of manures to other persons</i>	
Are receivers of manure transfers from CAFOs required to follow the same regulations?	No
Nutrient or manure management plans: <i>Additional details on the NMP requirement. Note that some of this information may overlap with other sections</i>	Refer to 40 CFR
Do your NMP/MMPS follow, comply with, or based on NRCS Technical Standard 590?	Yes
Application rates: <i>State regulations that restrict the rates at which manures are applied and methods needed to determine appropriate rates.</i>	Refer to 40 CFR
Manure application rates for phosphorus are based on: 1) <i>Phosphorus Index Only</i> 2) <i>Soil Test Phosphorus Only</i> 3) <i>Either PIO or STPO</i> 4) <i>Other</i>	Undetermined
Are there any nutrient “caps” to manure application?	Undetermined
Composition testing: <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on manures before application</i>	Refer to 40 CFR
Does your state require testing of manure for anything beyond nutrients, such as	Undetermined

metals, pathogens, antibiotics, etc.?	
Other land application highlights: <i>Additional restrictions for land application of manures</i>	No other information
Other regulatory details: <i>Additional information on the regulation of land application of manures</i>	No other information
General Assessment Questions	
Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change:	Undetermined
Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of manures that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links:	No
Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of manures beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so:	No
Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.	No other information

New Jersey	
Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2019
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	New Jersey Department of Environmental Protection (NJDEP)
Links to regulations	<p>NJPDES Rules N.J.A.C. 7:14A _ https://www.state.nj.us/dep/dwq/714a.htm _</p> <p>– Animal Waste Management Rule NJAC 2:91._ https://www.nj.gov/agriculture/divisions/anr/pdf/2016%20AWM%20Rules.pdf</p> <p>– – BMP Manual:_ https://www.nj.gov/agriculture/divisions/anr/pdf/BMPManual.pdf</p>
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Environmental
Other regulator info	Only 2 CAFOs in state
Definitions	
How CAFOs are defined or categorized:	<p>(a) Except for indirect discharges, a permit shall be obtained for any discharge from an Animal Feeding Operation if the Animal Feeding Operation meets the criteria for a concentrated Animal Feeding Operation under (b) or (d) below._</p> <p>(b) An Animal Feeding Operation shall be considered concentrated if either (b)1 or 2 are met:_</p> <p>1. More than the numbers of animals specified in any of the following categories are confined:_</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. 1,000 slaughter and feeder cattle;_ ii. 700 mature dairy cattle (whether milked or dry cows);_ iii. 2,500 swine each weighing over 25 kilograms (approximately 55 pounds);_ iv. 500 horses;_ v. 10,000 sheep or lambs;_ vi. 55,000 turkeys;_ vii. 100,000 laying hens or broilers (if the facility has continuous overflow watering);_ viii. 30,000 laying hens or broilers (if the facility has a liquid manure handling system);_ ix. 5,000 ducks; or_ x. 1,000 animal units; or_ <p>2. More than the number and types of animal set forth in (b)2i through x below are confined, and pollutants are discharged into waters of the State, or directly into waters of the State which originate outside of and pass over,</p>

	<p>across, or through the facility or otherwise come in contact with the animals confined in the operation._</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. 300 slaughter or feeder cattle;_ ii. 200 mature dairy cattle (either milked or dry cows);_ iii. 750 swine each weighing over 25 kilograms (approximately 55 pounds);_ iv. 150 horses;_ v. 3,000 sheep or lambs;_ vi. 16,500 turkeys;_ vii. 30,000 laying hens or broilers (if the facility has continuous overflow watering);_ viii. 9,000 laying hens or broilers (if the facility has a liquid manure handling system);_ ix. 1,500 ducks; or_ x. 300 animal units._ <p>3. An Animal Feeding Operation shall not be considered a concentrated Animal Feeding Operation as defined above if such Animal Feeding Operation discharges only in the event of a 25 year, 24-hour storm event._</p> <p>(c) Any Animal Feeding Operation shall, upon the Department's written request, submit the following information:_</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The number and type of animals confined;_ 2. A description of the means of discharge; and_ 3. The name and address of the owner or operator._ <p>(d) On a case-by-case basis and after conducting an on-site inspection, the Department shall designate, as a concentrated Animal Feeding Operation, any Animal Feeding Operation which does not meet the criteria in (b) above if (d)1 and 2 below are met:_</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The Department determines that the operation is a significant contributor of pollution to the waters of the State. In making this determination the Department shall consider the following factors:_ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. The size of the Animal Feeding Operation and the amount of wastes reaching waters of the State;_ ii. The location of the Animal Feeding Operation relative to waters of the State;_ iii. The means of conveyance of animal wastes and process waste waters into waters of the State;_ iv. The slope, vegetation, rainfall, and other factors affecting the likelihood or frequency of discharge of animal wastes and process wastewaters into waters of the State; and_ v. Other relevant factors; and_ 2. The Department determines that:_ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. Pollutants are discharged into waters of the State through a manmade ditch, flushing system, or other similar manmade device; or_ ii. Pollutants are discharged directly into waters of the State which originate outside of the facility and pass over, across, or through the facility or otherwise come into direct contact with the animals confined in the operation.
How animal units are defined (if	"Animal units" means the unit of measurement for any Animal Feeding Operation calculated as follows: the number of slaughter and feeder cattle

used):	multiplied by 1.0, plus the number of mature dairy cattle multiplied by 1.4, plus the number of swine weighing over 25 kilograms (approximately 55 pounds) multiplied by 0.4, plus the number of sheep multiplied by 0.1, plus the number of horses multiplied by 2.0.
NPDES permitting or other permitting requirements:	NJPDES regulates CAFOs. Also, NJAC 2:91 requires all farms to develop an AWMP that is consistent with the NJDA BMP Manual -whether they have a NJPDES permit or not.
Does the state require an NPDES permit for all Large CAFOs?	Undetermined
Does the state issue individual or general CAFO permits?	Undetermined
Are any other permits required for CAFOs or other large farms?	Undetermined
Other definitions needed to understand these regulations:	No other information
Regulatory Details	
Setbacks: <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some geographical feature</i>	Refer to 40 CFR
Are setbacks more restrictive than CFR?	No
Timing, weather, or conditional application restrictions: <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather, seasons, or land</i>	Not to be applied on frozen ground, and should be incorporated immediately. Application under rainy conditions or when soil is saturated should be avoided.

<i>characteristics (like slope)</i>	
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to saturated soils?	Yes
Is there a restriction for land application of manure within floodplains?	No
Is there a restriction for land application of manure related to future rainfall?	Yes
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to frozen or snow-covered ground?	Yes
Are there restrictions to manure applications based on time of year or time of day?	No
Are there restrictions to manure application based on slope?	No
Are there any other seasonal, timing, weather, or physical restrictions to manure applications not captured above?	Undetermined
Transfer of manure off-site: <i>Requirements related to the transfer of manures to other</i>	Refer to 40 CFR

<i>persons</i>	
Are receivers of manure transfers from CAFOs required to follow the same regulations?	No
Nutrient or manure management plans: <i>Additional details on the NMP requirement. Note that some of this information may overlap with other sections</i>	Animal Waste Management Rule NJAC 2:91 requires all farms to develop a Animal Waste Management Plan and incorporate NJDA Best Management Practices. Farms that have 300 or more AUs must develop and implement a Comprehensive Nutrient Management Plan (CNMP) that has been approved by NJDA. Manual:_ https://www.nj.gov/agriculture/divisions/anr/pdf/BMPManual.pdf _ _ Management practices include: _ * Farm and field maps showing acreage, soils, crops, and water bodies_ * Yield Expectations_ * Summary of the nutrient management planning resources available to the farmer: soil test, nutrient analysis of manures and composts, nitrogen contribution to the soil from legumes, other sig nutrient sources_ * Evaluation of field limitations based on environmental conditions_ * Establishing mix of nutrient sources and requirements_ * Timing and application methods_ * Equipment operation and calibration
Do your NMP/MMPS follow, comply with, or based on NRCS Technical Standard 590?	Undetermined
Application rates: <i>State regulations that restrict the rates at which manures are applied and methods needed to determine appropriate rates.</i>	Immediately prior to side or top-dressing with nitrogen fertilizer, soil test required from nitrate-nitrogen concentrations._ _ Manage nutrient applications to match realistic yield expectations. _ _ Apply for desired crop yield requires at least one solid sample for each field and crop type: phosphorus, potassium, calcium, magnesium, pH.
Manure application rates for phosphorus are based on: 1) <i>Phosphorus Index Only</i> 2) <i>Soil Test Phosphorus Only</i>	Soil test phosphorus only

3) <i>Either PIO or STPO</i> 4) <i>Other</i>	
Are there any nutrient “caps” to manure application?	Not Applicable
Composition testing: <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on manures before application</i>	Refer to 40 CFR
Does your state require testing of manure for anything beyond nutrients, such as metals, pathogens, antibiotics, etc.?	Not Applicable
Other land application highlights: <i>Additional restrictions for land application of manures</i>	§ 2:91-3.7 Farms receiving or applying less than 142 tons of animal waste per year_ (a) Farms receiving or applying less than 142 tons of animal waste per year are required to implement the general requirements at N.J.A.C. 2:91-3.1 by March 16, 2010._ (b)
Other regulatory details: <i>Additional information on the regulation of land application of manures</i>	The New Jersey Department of Agriculture maintains Animal Waste Management regulations. All Livestock Farms, which includes equine operations, are required to follow the 5 General Requirements: _ 1. Animals in confinement areas shall only have controlled
General Assessment Questions	
Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may	Undetermined

<p>potentially change:</p>	
<p>Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of manures that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links:</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of manures beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so:</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.</p>	<p>No other information</p>

New Mexico	
Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2019
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	US Environmental Protection Agency (US EPA)_ _ New Mexico Environment Department (NMED)_
Links to regulations	* Clean Water Act (CWA) _ * National Pollutant Discharge Elimination Systems (NPDES) Program _ * Code of Federal Regulations (CFR) _ * New Mexico National Pollutant Discharge Elimination System (NPDES) General Permit for Discharges from Concentrated Animal Feeding Operations(CAFOs)_ https://www.env.nm.gov/wp-content/uploads/sites/25/2017/07/NMG010000-CAFO-NM-20160901.pdf
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	More than one agency
Other regulator info	Nutrient Management Plan practices may come from US Department of Agriculture (USDA) Natural Resources Conservation Service (NRCS) _ _ New Mexico's Dairy Rule may have some ground water regulatory impacts on CAFOs in New Mexico_
Definitions	
How CAFOs are defined or categorized:	Concentrated Animal Feeding Operation (CAFO) means an AFO which is defined as a Large CAFO or Medium CAFO by 40 CFR 122.23(b)(4) and (6), or that is designated as a CAFO._ _ Large CAFO means an AFO that stables or confines as many as or more than the numbers of animals specified in any of the following categories: (i) 700 mature dairy cattle, whether milked or dry; (ii) 1,000 veal calves; (iii) 1,000 cattle other than mature dairy cows or veal calves. Cattle includes but is not limited to heifers, steers, bulls and cow/calf pairs; (iv) 2,500 swine each weighing 55 pounds or more; (v) 10,000 swine each weighing less than 55 pounds; (vi) 500 horses; (vii) 10,000 sheep or lambs; (viii) 55,000 turkeys; (ix) 30,000 laying hens or broilers, if the AFO uses a liquid manure handling system; (x) 125,000 chickens (other than laying hens), if the AFO uses other than a liquid manure handling system; (xi) 82,000 laying hens, if the AFO uses other than a liquid manure handling system; (xii) 30,000 ducks (if the AFO uses other than a liquid manure handling system); or (xiii) 5,000 ducks (if the AFO uses a liquid

	<p>manure handling system). _</p> <p>_</p> <p>Medium CAFO means any AFO that stables or confines as many or more than the numbers of animals specified in any of the following categories: (i) 200 to 699 mature dairy cattle, whether milked or dry cows; (ii) 300 to 999 veal calves; (iii) 300 to 999 cattle other than mature dairy cows or veal calves. Cattle includes but is not limited to heifers, steers, bulls and cow/calf pairs; (iv) 750 to 2,499 swine each weighing 55 pounds or more; (v) 3,000 to 9,999 swine each weighing less than 55 pounds; (vi) 150 to 499 horses, (vii) 3,000 to 9,999 sheep or lambs, (viii) 16,500 to 54,999 turkeys, (ix) 9,000 to 29,999 laying hens or broilers, if the AFO uses a liquid manure handling system; (x) 37,500 to 124,999 chickens (other than laying hens), if the AFO uses other than a liquid manure handling system; (xi) 25,000 to 81,999 laying hens, if the AFO uses other than a liquid manure handling system; (xii) 10,000 to 29,999 ducks (if the AFO uses other than a liquid manure handling system); or (xiii) 1,500 to 4,999 ducks (if the AFO uses a liquid manure handling system) and either one of the following conditions are met (a) pollutants are discharged into waters of the United States through a man-made ditch, flushing system, or other similar man-made device; or (b) pollutants are discharged directly into waters of the United States which originate outside of and pass over, across, or through the facility or otherwise come into direct contact with the animals confined in the operation._</p> <p>_</p> <p>Small CAFO means an AFO that is designated as a CAFO and is not a Medium CAFO. EPA's Regulatory Definitions of Large CAFOs, Medium CAFOs, and Small CAFOs: https://www3.epa.gov/npdes/pubs/sector_table.pdf</p>
<p>How animal units are defined (if used):</p>	<p>Not used</p>
<p>NPDES permitting or other permitting requirements:</p>	<p>U. S. Environmental Protection Agency (USEPA) Region 6 regulates the National Pollutant Discharge Elimination System (NPDES) permitting in New Mexico only CAFOs that discharge or propose to discharge are required to have NPDES permit coverage in New Mexico. Some CAFOs are not eligible for coverage under this NPDES general permit, but must apply for an individual permit._</p> <p>There shall be no discharge of manure, litter, or process wastewater to a water of the United States from a CAFO as a result of the application of manure, litter or process wastewater to land application areas under the control of the CAFO, except where it is an agricultural storm water discharge. Where manure, litter, or process wastewater has been applied in accordance with the CAFO's site specific NMP, a precipitation related discharge of manure, litter, or process wastewater from land areas under the control of the CAFO is considered to be an agricultural storm water discharge.</p>

Does the state require an NPDES permit for all Large CAFOs?	No
Does the state issue individual or general CAFO permits?	Individual
Are any other permits required for CAFOs or other large farms?	No
Other definitions needed to understand these regulations:	No other information
Regulatory Details	
Setbacks: <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some geographical feature</i>	Manure, litter, or process wastewater must not be applied closer than one-hundred (100) feet to any down-gradient water of the United States, open tile line intake structures, sinkholes, agricultural well heads, or other conduits to waters of the United States. The permittee may elect to use a 35-foot vegetated buffer where applications of manure, litter, or process wastewater are prohibited as an alternative to the 100-foot setback to meet this requirement. As a compliance alternative, the permittee may demonstrate that a set-back or buffer is not necessary because implementation of alternative conservation practices or field-specific conditions will provide pollutant reductions equivalent or better than the reductions that would be achieved by the 100-foot setback.
Are setbacks more restrictive than CFR?	No
Timing, weather, or conditional application restrictions: <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather, seasons, or land characteristics (like slope)</i>	Waste shall not be applied to land when the ground is frozen, snow-covered ground, saturated with water, or during rainfall events. The permittee shall not land apply if precipitation capable of producing runoff and erosion is forecast by the National Weather Service or other reputable weather service organizations to occur within 24 hours of the time of the planned application._ Water Quality-Based Effluent Limitations. There shall be no dry weather discharges from land application sites._ Land application areas shall be identified that, due to topography, activities or other factors, have a high potential for significant soil erosion. Where land application areas have the potential to contribute pollutants to waters of the United States, measures used to limit erosion and pollutant runoff shall be identified._ Irrigation Control: Irrigation systems shall be managed so as to minimize_ (a) ponding or puddling of wastewater on land application fields, (b) contamination of ground and surface water and (c) the occurrence of nuisance conditions such as odors and flies.
Is there a restriction for	Yes

land application of manure to saturated soils?	
Is there a restriction for land application of manure within floodplains?	No
Is there a restriction for land application of manure related to future rainfall?	Yes
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to frozen or snow-covered ground?	Yes
Are there restrictions to manure applications based on time of year or time of day?	No
Are there restrictions to manure application based on slope?	No
Are there any other seasonal, timing, weather, or physical restrictions to manure applications not captured above?	Yes, The Phosphorous Index numbers or Nutrient transport risk assessments may limit manure application rates to a particular land application field.
Transfer of manure off-site: <i>Requirements related to the transfer of manures to other persons</i>	In cases where CAFO-generated manure, litter, or process wastewater is sold or given away the permittee must comply with the following conditions (amounts less than 10 tons per year given or sold to a single recipient need not be recorded.): _ a. Maintain records showing the date and amount of manure, litter, and/or process wastewater that leaves the permitted operation;_ b. Record the name, telephone number, and address of the recipient of transferred manure, litter or process wastewater;_ c. Provide the recipient(s) with representative information on the nutrient content of the manure, litter, and/or process wastewater; and_ d. Retain all records on-site, for a period of five (5) years, and submit to the Permitting Authority any requested records.
Are receivers of manure transfers from CAFOs required to follow the same regulations?	No
Nutrient or manure management plans: <i>Additional details on the NMP requirement. Note that some of this</i>	CAFOs that apply for NPDES coverage must have a NMP designed by a certified NMP planner. _ _ The permittee shall develop, submit, and implement a site specific NMP. The NMP shall specifically identify and describe practices that

<p><i>information may overlap with other sections</i></p>	<p>will be implemented to assure compliance with the effluent limitations and special conditions of this permit (Parts II.A and III.A). The NMP must be developed in accordance with the New Mexico NRCS Conservation Practice Standard Code 590 (Nutrient Management) (see Part II.A and Appendix D)._</p> <p>– The site specific NMP at a minimum must include practices and procedures necessary to implement the applicable effluent limitations and standards.</p>
<p>Do your NMP/MMPS follow, comply with, or based on NRCS Technical Standard 590?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Application rates: <i>State regulations that restrict the rates at which manures are applied and methods needed to determine appropriate rates.</i></p>	<p>Soil must be analyzed at least once every five years. The results of these analyses must be used in determining application rates for manure, litter, and process wastewater._</p> <p>Application rates for manure, litter, or process wastewater must minimize phosphorus and nitrogen transport from the field to surface waters in compliance with the most current New Mexico NRCS Conservation Practice Standard Code 590 (Nutrient Management),(see Appendix D), including the New Mexico Phosphorus Index (New Mexico NRCS Agronomy Technical Note 57)_</p> <p>– Application rates shall be expressed in the NMP consistent with either the Linear Approach or Narrative Rate Approach. _</p> <p>– The Linear Approach expresses rates of application as pounds of nitrogen and phosphorus. Permittees selecting the linear approach to address rates of application must include in the NMP submitted to the Director the following information for each crop, field, and year covered by the NMP, which will be used by the Director to establish site specific permit terms_</p> <p>– The Narrative Rate Approach expresses a narrative rate of application that results in the amount, in tons or gallons, of manure, litter, and process wastewater to be land applied. Permittees selecting the narrative rate approach to address rates of application must include in the NMP submitted to the Director the following information for each crop, field, and year covered by the NMP, which will be used by the Director to establish site specific permit terms._</p> <p>For fields receiving manure, where phosphorus risk assessment results equate to:_</p> <p>* LOW risk, additional phosphorus and potassium can be applied at rates greater than crop removal not to exceed the nitrogen requirement for the succeeding crop. *MODERATE risk, additional phosphorus and potassium may be applied at a phosphorus crop</p>

	<p>removal rate for the planned crops in the rotation. *HIGH risk, additional phosphorus and potassium may be applied at phosphorus crop removal rates if the following requirements are met:_</p> <p>* a soil phosphorus drawdown strategy has been implemented, and</p> <p>* a site assessment for nutrients and soil loss has been conducted to determine if mitigation practices are required to protect water quality, any deviation from these high risk requirements must have the approval of the Chief of the NRCS. The Phosphorous Index, (PI) for NM is described Agronomy Technical Note 57. Download Worksheet under Agronomy Tech note 57.</p> <p>http://www.nm.nrcs.usda.gov/technical/technotes/agro.html</p>
<p>Manure application rates for phosphorus are based on:</p> <p>1) <i>Phosphorus Index Only</i></p> <p>2) <i>Soil Test Phosphorus Only</i></p> <p>3) <i>Either PIO or STPO</i></p> <p>4) <i>Other</i></p>	Phosphorus index only
<p>Are there any nutrient “caps” to manure application?</p>	No
<p>Composition testing: <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on manures before application</i></p>	<p>Manure must be analyzed at least once annually for nitrogen and phosphorus content and the total quantities of manure, litter and process wastewater that was land applied._</p> <p>Manure, wastewater and soil sampling must be conducted in accordance with the requirements of Parts III.A.7.d and e._</p> <p>Total Nitrogen _</p> <p>Nitrate Nitrogen _</p> <p>Ammonia Nitrogen _</p> <p>Total Phosphorus_</p> <p>E. coli -“ bacteria_</p> <p>5-day BOD_</p> <p>Total Suspended Solids _</p> <p>pH_</p> <p>Temperature</p>
<p>Does your state require testing of manure for anything beyond nutrients, such as metals, pathogens, antibiotics, etc.?</p>	Yes
<p>Other land application highlights: <i>Additional restrictions for land application of</i></p>	No other information

<i>manures</i>	
Other regulatory details: <i>Additional information on the regulation of land application of manures</i>	In New Mexico, all CAFOs in the counties of Bernalillo, Chavez, Eddy, Sandoval, San Juan and Valencia must develop and implement soil sampling of land application sites once every five (5) years for the metals selenium, copper and zinc. The sampling may b
General Assessment Questions	
Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change:	Undetermined
Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of manures that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links:	No
Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of manures beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so:	No
Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.	No other information

New York Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2025
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	New York State Department of Environmental Conservation (NYSDEC)
Links to regulations	NYSDEC webpage, Concentrated Animal Feeding Operations: https://www.dec.ny.gov/permits/6285.html GP-0-19-001: https://extapps.dec.ny.gov/docs/water_pdf/cafogp019001permit.pdf 6 CRR-NY 750: https://govt.westlaw.com/nycrr/Browse/Home/NewYork/
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Environmental
Other regulator info	No other information
Definitions	
How CAFOs are defined or categorized:	<p>Concentrated Animal Feeding Operation. (CAFO) means an AFO that meets the criteria of either a large, medium or small CAFO. A large CAFO means an AFO that stables or confines as many as or more than the numbers of animals in any of the following categories: (a) 700 mature dairy cows, whether milked or dry; (b) 1,000 veal calves; (c) 1,000 cattle other than mature dairy cows or veal calves. Cattle includes but is not limited to heifers, steers, bulls and cow/calf pairs; (d) 2,500 swine each weighing 55 pounds or more; (e) 10,000 swine each weighing less than 55 pounds; (f) 500 horses; (g) 10,000 sheep or lambs; (h) 55,000 turkeys; (i) 30,000 laying hens or broilers, if the AFO uses a liquid manure handling system; (j) 125,000 chickens (other than laying hens), if the AFO uses other than a liquid manure handling system; (k) 82,000 laying hens, if the AFO uses other than a liquid manure handling system; (l) 30,000 ducks (if the AFO uses other than a liquid manure handling system); or (m) 5,000 ducks (if the AFO uses a liquid manure handling system). A medium CAFO means an AFO that stables or confines as many as or more than the numbers of animals in any of the following categories: (a) 200 to 699 mature dairy cows, whether milked or dry, except that an AFO that stables or confines 200-299 mature dairy cows, whether</p>

	<p> milked or dry that does not cause a discharge would not be considered a medium CAFO;_ (b) 300 to 999 veal calves;_ (c) 300 to 999 cattle other than mature dairy cows or veal calves. Cattle includes but is not limited to heifers, steers, bulls and cow/calf pairs;_ (d) 750 to 2,499 swine each weighing 55 pounds or more;_ (e) 3,000 to 9,999 swine each weighing less than 55 pounds;_ (f) 150 to 499 horses;_ (g) 3,000 to 9,999 sheep or lambs;_ (h) 16,500 to 54,999 turkeys;_ (i) 9,000 to 29,999 laying hens or broilers, if the AFO uses a liquid manure handling system;_ (j) 37,500 to 124,999 chickens (other than laying hens), if the AFO uses other than a liquid manure handling system;_ (k) 25,000 to 81,999 laying hens, if the AFO uses other than a liquid manure handling system;_ (l) 10,000 to 29,999 ducks (if the AFO uses other than a liquid manure handling system); or_ (m) 1,500 to 4,999 ducks (if the AFO uses a liquid manure handling system)._ – A small CAFO means an AFO that is designated by the department as a CAFO or requests CAFO SPDES permit coverage and is not a medium or large CAFO._ While not required, an AFO with 200-299 mature dairy cows may request CAFO SPDES permit coverage and, if permit coverage is granted, the AFO would be considered a small CAFO throughout permit coverage. </p>
How animal units are defined (if used):	Not used
NPDES permitting or other permitting requirements:	<p> Large and medium CAFOs that do not discharge are regulated under the GP-00-22-001 SPDES General Permit for Concentrated Animal Feeding Operations_ CAFOs that discharge process wastewater to waters of the state are required to obtain an individual State Pollutant Discharge Elimination System (SPDES) permit that reflects Clean Water Act (CWA) requirements . _ Among other potential permits ranging from wetland/stream corridor impacts to air quality, CAFOs may be subject to the NYS Department of Environmental Conservation SPDES General Permit for Stormwater Discharges from Construction Activity (GP-0-20-001) and/or Solid Waste Registrations/Permits through 6 NYCRR Part 361 depending on how the facility operates. </p>
Does the state require an NPDES permit for all Large CAFOs?	Yes

Does the state issue individual or general CAFO permits?	Both
Are any other permits required for CAFOs or other large farms?	Yes
Other definitions needed to understand these regulations:	No other information
Regulatory Details	
Setbacks: <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some geographical feature</i>	<p>One of the following minimum flow path distances must be maintained between manure applications and surface waters, surface inlets or down-gradient sinkholes or other direct conduits to surface or groundwater: _</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * a 100-foot setback; or _ * a 35-foot setback, where the entire setback width is a vegetated buffer; or _ * a 15-foot setback with incorporation within 24 hours of application. <p>_</p> <p>_</p> <p>The minimum spreading setback requirement for wells and down-gradient springs is: _</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * a 100-foot setback. _ <p>_</p> <p>There are additional setback requirements for manure applications in areas with at-risk --groundwater (e.g. Carbonate shallow bedrock; Thin soils over shallow bedrock; any soils with rapid drainage; karst features; or areas with historical well contamination problems). Applications must be made in accordance with 2021 Cornell recommendations in "Groundwater Protection Guidelines for Agriculture".</p> <p>_</p> <p>If operating near a public water supply (surface water or wellhead), employ additional setbacks as required by state and local rules.</p>
Are setbacks more restrictive than CFR?	Yes
Timing, weather, or conditional application restrictions: <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather, seasons, or land characteristics (like slope)</i>	<p>Manure application is prohibited on saturated soils (fluid -saturated or frozen-saturated). _</p> <p>_</p> <p>Nutrients must not be mechanically surface-applied if a high probability of offsite nutrient loss is identified. Except as specifically defined in this section, this precludes spreading when the following field conditions are present: _</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * frozen and/or snow-covered soils or _ * when soils are saturated from rainfall or snow melt, as indicated by visible water on the soil _ <p>surface with the potential to runoff (isolated areas of saturation not</p>

	<p>prone to runoff must be avoided, but do not prohibit spreading on a given field). _</p> <p>If nutrient applications are made according to the criteria and conservation measures in one or more of the scenarios in this section to safeguard against offsite delivery, then such applications may be made to frozen and/or snow covered soil. _</p> <p>Scenario 1: Commercial fertilizers may be applied during frozen, but not snow-covered, soil conditions to fields in close-grown crops, such as hay or small grains, and in accordance with the Cornell University Nutrient Guidelines, NY P Index, NY NLI, and RUSLE2. _</p> <p>Scenario 2: When conditions allow, manure may be frost-injected or immediately incorporated upon application when soils are frozen and/or snow-covered and in accordance with the general setback requirements, Cornell University Nutrient Guidelines, NY P Index, NY NLI, and RUSLE2. _</p> <p>Scenario 3: In instances where mechanical surface applications of manure, litter, or process wastewater to frozen and/or snow-covered soils are necessary, the applications will: _</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * be in accordance with the Cornell University Nutrient Guidelines, NY P Index, NY NLI, and RUSLE2; _ * be based on a check of the 48-hour weather forecast to assess if rainfall and/or temperatures are predicted to cause snowmelt and/or runoff conditions; _ * not be applied to soils designated by the soil survey as frequently flooded; _ * be in accordance with Section 1 (Limestone areas-) in Groundwater Protection Guidelines for Agriculture and Supporting Guidelines -for fields with soils less than 40 inches deep over carbonate bedrock._ * not be within a 100-foot flow path distance from surface waters, surface inlets, springs, sinkholes, and swallets; _ * not be within 100 feet of wells; and _ * not be applied in concentrated flow areas (i.e., well-defined channels within fields)._ <p>_</p> <p>Applications during winter spreading conditions (i.e. soil is frozen 4+ inches, snow-covered 4+ inches, or encumbered by significant surface icing) must be made in accordance with 2015 Cornell Guide Revised winter and wet weather manure spreading guidelines to reduce water contamination risk-2.</p>
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to saturated soils?	Yes
Is there a restriction for land application of manure within floodplains?	No
Is there a restriction for land application of manure	Yes

related to future rainfall?	
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to frozen or snow-covered ground?	Yes
Are there restrictions to manure applications based on time of year or time of day?	No
Are there restrictions to manure application based on slope?	No
Are there any other seasonal, timing, weather, or physical restrictions to manure applications not captured above?	Yes, Single manure, food processing waste, and digestate application rates shall not exceed 20,000 gallons per acre cumulatively within any 7-day period._ Single process wastewater application rates shall not exceed 27,000 gallons per acre cumulatively wi
Transfer of manure off-site: <i>Requirements related to the transfer of manures to other persons</i>	CAFO's who export manure must maintain records showing the date and amount of the transferred material; record the name and address of the recipient; provide the recipient with representative information on nutrient content; and retain records on-site. _ _ If CAFO is in control of the application acreage, rate, timing and/or transfer rate and time, application must be made in accordance with the CAFOs nutrient management plan. _
Are receivers of manure transfers from CAFOs required to follow the same regulations?	No
Nutrient or manure management plans: <i>Additional details on the NMP requirement. Note that some of this information may overlap with other sections</i>	All CAFOs are required to develop a nutrient management plan, written by a certified planner and developed in accordance with site specific nutrient management practices that ensure appropriate agricultural utilization of the nutrients in the manure, litter or process waste water. As a result, any precipitation related discharge from land areas under control of the CAFO would be an agricultural stormwater discharge-☐ that falls within the exemption in ECL §17-0105(16). _ CAFOs that are permitted under GP-0-22-001 are required to develop a NMP (termed CNMP in that version of the permit), and fully implement it prior to becoming operational, but they are not required to submit for approval prior to implementation. The New York State Department of Agriculture and Markets oversees planner certification and the quality assurance program for that certification. Each farm-specific NMP or CNMP identifies the environmental sensitivities of the farm and utilizes the technical standards set by the United States Department of Agriculture - Natural Resources Conservation Service (USDA - NRCS) to mitigate those environmental impact.

Do your NMP/MMPS follow, comply with, or based on NRCS Technical Standard 590?	Yes
Application rates: <i>State regulations that restrict the rates at which manures are applied and methods needed to determine appropriate rates.</i>	Each farm-specific NMP/CNMP identifies the environmental sensitivities of the farm and utilizes the technical standards set by the United States Department of Agriculture - Natural Resources Conservation Service (USDA - NRCS) to mitigate those environmental impacts (available at: https://www.nrcs.usda.gov/sites/default/files/2022-09/Nutrient_Management_590_NHCP_CPS_2017.pdf). These technical standards are the effluent limitations to be included in each farm-specific nutrient management plan. For example, NRCS Standard NY 590 describes the protocol that must be followed when sampling fields to receive waste applications. The results of those samples, which are used to calculate the Nitrogen Leaching Index Rating and Phosphorus Runoff Index Rating for each field, are included in the NMP/CNMPs. These results are used to calculate the application rates for each field, which are also made available in the NMP/CNMPs. N based limits on all fields, 100+ Phosphorus rating according to the PIND = no P application permitted.
Manure application rates for phosphorus are based on: 1) <i>Phosphorus Index Only</i> 2) <i>Soil Test Phosphorus Only</i> 3) <i>Either PIO or STPO</i> 4) <i>Other</i>	Phosphorus index only
Are there any nutrient “caps” to manure application?	Yes
Composition testing: <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on manures before application</i>	CAFO Rule requires owners/operators of CAFOs to indicate in their NMP/CNMP which nutrient application methodology they are following in order to provide reasonable assurance that there will be appropriate agricultural utilization of nutrients in the manure, litter or process wastewater applied to their land base. Specifically, the CAFO Rule requires adherence to either a Linear Method or a Narrative Method as described in 40 CFR 122.42(e)(5) for CAFOs which have a discharge. In NY, these methods are combined to form the NRCS Standard NY 590 which incorporates Cornell’s Nutrient Guidelines, including the NY Nitrate Leaching Index and the NY Phosphorus Runoff Index, and ensures appropriate agriculture utilization of nutrients. The farm-specific field-by-field requirements set by NY590 are required to be followed by all permitted CAFOs in NY.
Does your state require	No

testing of manure for anything beyond nutrients, such as metals, pathogens, antibiotics, etc.?	
Other land application highlights: <i>Additional restrictions for land application of manures</i>	No other information
Other regulatory details: <i>Additional information on the regulation of land application of manures</i>	No other information
General Assessment Questions	
Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change:	No
Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of manures that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links:	No
Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of manures beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so:	No
Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.	Yes. 6 NYCRR Part 361.

North Carolina	
Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2019
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	North Carolina Department of Natural Resources (NCDNR)
Links to regulations	<p>Title 15A of the North Carolina Administrative Code (NCAC), Chapter 2, Subchapter H_</p> <p>http://reports.oah.state.nc.us/ncac/title%2015a%20-%20environmental%20quality/chapter%2002%20-%20environmental%20management/subchapter%20h/subchapter%20h%20rules.pdf _</p> <p>_</p> <p>Title 15A, NCAC, Chapter 2, Subchapter T, Section 1300 - Animal Waste Management Systems_</p> <p>15A NCAC 02T .1305 NPDES PERMITTING REQUIREMENTS (a) This Rule applies to animal waste management systems subject to regulation under 40 CFR § 122.23 and G.S. 143- 215.10C._</p> <p>http://reports.oah.state.nc.us/ncac/title%2015a%20-%20environmental%20quality/chapter%2002%20-%20environmental%20management/subchapter%20t/subchapter%20t%20rules.pdf</p>
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Natural Resources
Other regulator info	No other information
Definitions	
How CAFOs are defined or categorized:	<p>Large Concentrated Feeding Operations are AFOs that stable or confine and feed or maintain animals for a total of 45 days or more in any 12-month period where crops are not sustained over any portion of the_</p> <p>lot or facility in normal growing season, and have animal number below._</p> <p>Large CAFO:_</p> <p>Mature Dairy Cows (milked or dry) > 700 Veal Calves > 1,000 _</p> <p>Cattle (other than mature dairy cows or veal calves)> 1,000_</p> <p>Swine (> 55 pounds) > 2,500 > 250 1_</p> <p>Swine (< 55 pounds) > 10,000 _</p> <p>Turkeys > 55,000 _</p> <p>Laying Hens or Broilers (liquid manure handling systems) > 30,000_</p> <p>Chickens (other than laying hens and other than liquid manure handling systems) > 125,000 _</p> <p>Laying Hens (other than liquid manure handling systems) > 82,000</p>

How animal units are defined (if used):	Not used
NPDES permitting or other permitting requirements:	NC DNR Division of Water Quality administers the NPDES program that contains many CAFO requirements
Does the state require an NPDES permit for all Large CAFOs?	Undetermined
Does the state issue individual or general CAFO permits?	Undetermined
Are any other permits required for CAFOs or other large farms?	Undetermined
Other definitions needed to understand these regulations:	No other information
Regulatory Details	
Setbacks: <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some geographical feature</i>	<p>The land application and siting setbacks must meet the applicable conditions established in G.S. 106-803, NRCS standards and 40 CFR Part 412 at the time of construction. _</p> <p>_</p> <p>New and expanded animal waste treatment systems such as lagoons and waste storage structures shall be located at least 100 feet from a perennial stream or perennial waterbody. For new and expanding systems, this setback requirement shall also apply to areas in feedlots where an established vegetative cover will not be maintained because of the concentration of animals, with the exception of stock trails and stream crossings._</p> <p>_</p> <p>Exemptions from the minimum buffer requirements for animal waste storage and treatment facilities and animal concentration areas shall be approved if no other siting options are available and the BMP installed as an equivalent control is designed to prevent the discharge of pollutants except during a storm event more</p>

	severe than a 25-year, 24-hour storm event.
Are setbacks more restrictive than CFR?	No
Timing, weather, or conditional application restrictions: <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather, seasons, or land characteristics (like slope)</i>	None
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to saturated soils?	No
Is there a restriction for land application of manure within floodplains?	No
Is there a restriction for land application of manure related to future rainfall?	No
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to frozen or	No

snow-covered ground?	
Are there restrictions to manure applications based on time of year or time of day?	No
Are there restrictions to manure application based on slope?	No
Are there any other seasonal, timing, weather, or physical restrictions to manure applications not captured above?	Undetermined
Transfer of manure off-site: <i>Requirements related to the transfer of manures to other persons</i>	Refer to 40 CFR
Are receivers of manure transfers from CAFOs required to follow the same regulations?	No
Nutrient or manure management plans: <i>Additional</i>	All permitted animal operations are required to have a Certified Animal Waste Management Plan (CAWMP) that has been developed by a Certified Technical Specialist. The CAWMP is incorporated into the permit by reference and defines the fields to which the waste is applied, the crops to be grown and other details of the operation. The CAWMP must meet the minimum specifications of the NRCS

<p><i>details on the NMP requirement. Note that some of this information may overlap with other sections</i></p>	<p>(contained in the agency's Field Office Technical Guide) standard of practices adopted by the Soil and Water Conservation Commission or other standards for any combination of water quality protection-practices, as approved by NRCS or the Soil and Water Conservation Commission. _</p> <p>_</p> <p>BMPs designed and installed for an animal waste management plan at the time of certification shall either: (1) meet the standards and specifications of the US Department of Agriculture Natural Resources Conservation Service (NRCS) Technical Guide, Section IV, Raleigh, North Carolina, incorporated by reference with subsequent amendments and additions, or standards and specifications otherwise determined by the Commission; or (2) meet the Swine Waste System Performance Standards pursuant to 15A NCAC 02T .1307 and follow the approval process described in 15A NCAC 02T .1308._</p> <p>_</p> <p>Land application BMPs that follow the nutrient management standard contained in the Section IV of the NRCS Technical Guide or as recommended by the Agronomic Division of the North Carolina Department of Agriculture and Consumer Services (predictive Soil Test Report and predictive Waste Analysis Report) shall be deemed approved. _</p> <p>_</p> <p>In cases where NC agronomic rates are not established for a specific crop or vegetative type, application rates may be determined by the NC Interagency Nutrient Management Committee. With concurrence from a NCDA&CS Regional Agronomist, a voting member of the NC Agricultural Consultants Association (NCACA), or a Certified Crop Advisor (CCA), a technical specialist may use plant and tissue analysis to justify additional nitrogen and extend the application period.</p>
<p>Do your NMP/MMPS follow, comply with, or based on NRCS Technical Standard 590?</p>	<p>Undetermined</p>
<p>Application rates: <i>State regulations that restrict the rates at which manures are applied and methods needed to determine appropriate rates.</i></p>	<p>All waste must be applied at no greater than agronomic rates -an amount that can be used productively by the crops planted.</p>

<p>Manure application rates for phosphorus are based on:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) <i>Phosphorus Index Only</i> 2) <i>Soil Test Phosphorus Only</i> 3) <i>Either PIO or STPO</i> 4) <i>Other</i> 	<p>Soil test phosphorus only</p>
<p>Are there any nutrient “caps” to manure application?</p>	<p>Undetermined</p>
<p>Composition testing: <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on manures before application</i></p>	<p>Refer to 40 CFR</p>
<p>Does your state require testing of manure for anything beyond nutrients, such as metals, pathogens, antibiotics, etc.?</p>	<p>Not Applicable</p>
<p>Other land application highlights: <i>Additional restrictions for</i></p>	<p>No other information</p>

<i>land application of manures</i>	
Other regulatory details: <i>Additional information on the regulation of land application of manures</i>	No other information
General Assessment Questions	
Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change:	Undetermined
Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of manures that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links:	No
Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties,	No

<p>watersheds) that regulate land application of manures beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so:</p>	
<p>Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.</p>	<p>No other information</p>

North Dakota	
Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2019
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	North Dakota Department of Health (NDDoH)
Links to regulations	33-16-03.1-01 -13 Control of pollution from Animal Feeding Operations. _ https://www.legis.nd.gov/information/acdata/pdf/33-16-03.1.pdf _ 33-16-01 NDPDES_ https://www.legis.nd.gov/information/acdata/pdf/33-16-01.pdf
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Environmental
Other regulator info	No other information
Definitions	
How CAFOs are defined or categorized:	<p>Concentrated Animal Feeding Operation means an Animal Feeding Operation that is defined as a large concentrated Animal Feeding Operation, as a medium concentrated Animal Feeding Operation, or is a small or other type of Animal Feeding Operation designated as a concentrated Animal Feeding Operation in accordance with section 33-16-03.1-04. For purposes of determining animal numbers, two or more feeding operations under common ownership are considered to be a single Animal Feeding Operation if they adjoin each other or if they use a common area or system for the disposal of wastes. All discharging concentrated Animal Feeding Operations are required to obtain a North Dakota pollutant discharge elimination system permit pursuant to chapter 33-16-01._</p> <p>Large Animal Feeding Operation means any Animal Feeding Operation that stables or confines as many as or more than the numbers of animals specified in any of the following categories: Seven hundred mature dairy cows, whether milked or dry; One thousand veal calves; One thousand cattle other than mature dairy cows or veal calves. For purposes of this subdivision, "cattle" includes heifers, steers, bulls, and cow-calf pairs; Two thousand five hundred swine, each weighing fifty-five pounds [24.95 kilograms] or more; Ten thousand swine, each weighing less than fifty-five pounds [24.95 kilograms]; Five hundred horses; Ten thousand sheep or lambs; Fifty-five thousand turkeys Thirty thousand laying hens or broilers, if the Animal Feeding Operation uses a liquid manure handling system; One hundred twenty-five thousand chickens, other than laying hens, if the Animal Feeding Operation uses other than a liquid manure handling system; Eighty-two thousand laying hens, if the Animal Feeding Operation uses other than a liquid manure handling system; Thirty thousand ducks, if the Animal Feeding Operation uses other than a liquid manure handling system; or Five thousand ducks, if the Animal Feeding</p>

	<p>Operation uses a liquid manure handling system_</p> <p>Medium concentrated Animal Feeding Operation are AFOs where manure, litter, or process waste water is causing or is likely to cause pollution by discharging pollutants into waters of the state either through a man-made ditch, flushing system, or_</p> <p>other similar man-made device, or directly into waters of the state that_</p> <p>originates outside of and passes over, across, or through the facility or otherwise comes into direct contact with animals confined in the operation and, any Animal Feeding Operation that stables or confines the numbers of animals specified within any of the following ranges: Two hundred to six hundred ninety-nine mature dairy cows, whether milked or dry; Three hundred to nine hundred ninety-nine veal calves; Three hundred to nine hundred ninety-nine cattle other than mature dairy cows or veal calves. For purposes of this subdivision, "cattle" includes heifers, steers, bulls, and cow-calf pairs; Seven hundred fifty to two thousand four hundred ninety-nine swine, each weighing fifty-five pounds [24.95 kilograms] or more; Three thousand to nine thousand nine hundred ninety-nine swine, each weighing less than fifty-five pounds [24.95 kilograms]; One hundred fifty to four hundred ninety-nine horses; Three thousand to nine thousand nine hundred ninety-nine sheep or lambs; Sixteen thousand five hundred to fifty-four thousand nine hundred ninety-nine turkeys; Nine thousand to twenty-nine thousand nine hundred ninety-nine laying hens or broilers, if the Animal Feeding Operation uses a liquid manure handling system; Thirty-seven thousand five hundred to one hundred twenty-four thousand nine hundred ninety-nine chickens, other than laying hens, if the Animal Feeding Operation uses other than a liquid manure handling system; Twenty-five thousand to eighty-one thousand nine hundred ninety-nine laying hens, if the Animal Feeding Operation uses other than a liquid manure handling system; Ten thousand to twenty-nine thousand nine hundred ninety-nine ducks, if the Animal Feeding Operation uses other than a liquid manure handling system; or One thousand five hundred to four thousand nine hundred ninety-nine ducks, if the Animal Feeding Operation uses a liquid manure handling system._</p> <p>Small Animal Feeding Operation means any Animal Feeding Operation that stables or confines less than the numbers of animals specified for a medium Animal Feeding Operation and is designated as a concentrated Animal Feeding Operation in accordance with section 33-16-03.1-04.</p>
<p>How animal units are defined (if used):</p>	<p>Not used</p>
<p>NPDES permitting or other permitting requirements:</p>	<p>NDDoH, Division of Water Quality oversees the North Dakota Pollutant Discharge Elimination System (NDPDES) permit program._</p> <p>North Dakota medium and small AFOs that require a permit are covered under state permits instead of NDPDES permits, and they</p>

	are considered permitted AFOs.- A State Permit, not a NPDES permit, is required for all Large CAFOs. State Stormwater Construction permits may also be required.
Does the state require an NPDES permit for all Large CAFOs?	No
Does the state issue individual or general CAFO permits?	Individual
Are any other permits required for CAFOs or other large farms?	Yes
Other definitions needed to understand these regulations:	No other information
Regulatory Details	
Setbacks: <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some geographical feature</i>	<p>New and expanding livestock facilities and manure storage areas shall be located a minimum horizontal distance of 100 feet from a public water supply well, 50 feet from a private water supply well, and 500 feet from any water supply well not owned by the facility where the topography is in a down-slope or down-gradient direction from the livestock facility._</p> <p>– Land controlled by the operator, manure shall not be applied closer than 100 feet to any down-gradient surface waters, open tile line intake structures, sinkholes, agricultural well heads or other conduits to surface waters, unless: A 35-foot wide vegetated buffer on which there are no applications of manure is used; The facility's owner/operator demonstrates that a setback or buffer is not necessary because implementation of alternative conservation practices or field-specific conditions will provide pollutant reductions equal to or greater than the reductions achieved by the 100-foot setback. (same as 40 CFR).</p>
Are setbacks more restrictive than CFR?	No
Timing, weather, or conditional application restrictions: <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather, seasons, or land characteristics (like slope)</i>	<p>Land application shall not occur during rainfall events, except to prevent the catastrophic failure of a storage structure._</p> <p>– Manure shall not be applied to frozen, snow-covered or saturated soils if there is a likelihood of runoff. However, manure can be land applied during frozen conditions provided it is applied on land where runoff is contained and does not drain off during spring runoff. The department recommends operators consider land with slopes of less than 6 percent, where there is stubble or vegetative cover and less than 8 inches of snow on the ground surface. Conservation measures such as terraces, contour strips and reduced tillage effective at reducing runoff. Livestock facilities planning to apply</p>

	<p>manure on frozen ground must submit a copy of their current nutrient management plans to the department along with their application or design, or both._</p> <p>– When irrigating with manure or process wastewater, the application rate shall not exceed the estimated soil infiltration rate, or the nutrient requirements of the crop. Irrigation application rates shall be adjusted to avoid significant ponding of manure or process waste water in surface depressions or seasonal drainage ways._</p> <p>– Manure shall be injected or incorporated within eight hours if applied within 1/2 mile of an occupied residence (other than the owner's residence), building or public area where people may be present. The operator shall be required to inject or incorporate the manure into the soil if manure is applied in a manner such that it causes an odor reading, for two or more days within a 10-day period, (as measured with a scentometer) of 7 or greater within 100 feet of an occupied residence, building or public area. A plan to minimize excess odors will be required before future application of manure in this area.</p>
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to saturated soils?	Yes
Is there a restriction for land application of manure within floodplains?	No
Is there a restriction for land application of manure related to future rainfall?	Yes
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to frozen or snow-covered ground?	Yes
Are there restrictions to manure applications based on time of year or time of day?	No
Are there restrictions to manure application based on slope?	Yes
Are there any other seasonal, timing, weather, or physical restrictions to manure applications not captured above?	Yes
Transfer of manure off-site:	Manure shall be transported in a manner where it will not leak or

<p><i>Requirements related to the transfer of manures to other persons</i></p>	<p>spill on to public roads or into areas where it could enter surface or ground water.</p>
<p>Are receivers of manure transfers from CAFOs required to follow the same regulations?</p>	<p>Undetermined</p>
<p>Nutrient or manure management plans: <i>Additional details on the NMP requirement. Note that some of this information may overlap with other sections</i></p>	<p>Nutrient Management Plans required. _ NMP must include amount of land available for land application of manure, type of crops or vegetation grown on this land, typical manure application rate for each of the crops to be grown, method and timing of application, precautions used to prevent manure from reaching waters of the state and precautions used to minimize odors to residences or public areas where people are present during transport and land application of manure, and information specified in the North Dakota Program Design Manual. _</p>
<p>Do your NMP/MMPS follow, comply with, or based on NRCS Technical Standard 590?</p>	<p>Undetermined</p>
<p>Application rates: <i>State regulations that restrict the rates at which manures are applied and methods needed to determine appropriate rates.</i></p>	<p>Application Rates to Meet Nutrient Requirements:_ 1. The manure application rate shall not exceed the recommendations for nitrogen and phosphorous based on either the North Dakota Phosphorous Index (PI), as developed by the NRCS, or NDSU Extension Service recommendations based on soil testing._ 2. The PI allows manure and other sources of nutrients to be applied at rates to meet the nitrogen needs of a crop if the PI rating is low or medium. If the PI is high, it allows manure and other sources of nutrients to be applied at rates to meet the phosphorous removal in the crop biomass. If the PI is very high, it requires that no manure be applied to that field. Manure shall not be applied to fields where the soil test phosphorous exceeds 125 parts per million (ppm) (250 lbs. per acre)._ 3. Manure and other sources of nitrogen must not be applied at rates that exceed:_ a. The recommended nitrogen application rate during the year of application; or_ b. The estimated nitrogen removal in harvested plant biomass for legumes during the year of application._ 4. Nutrient Management Plans shall contain a field-specific assessment of the potential for nitrogen and phosphorous transport from the field. The assessment for phosphorous can be done using the phosphorous screening tool and soil tests, or the PI assessment._ Soil Testing:_ Soil samples shall be collected and prepared according to NDSU</p>

	<p>Extension Service guidance. Laboratories shall use testing procedures accepted by NDSU to perform soil sample analyses. Soil testing shall include analyses for soil organic matter, nitrogen, and phosphorous. If there is concern about heavy metals or salts, the department may require testing of the soil for these materials. Livestock facilities identified by the department as needing nutrient management plans shall have their manure and the soil where manure is being applied tested in accordance with items 1-5 once every three years. CAFOs shall have their manure and the soil where manure is being applied tested in accordance with items 1-5 each year. Operations require more detailed subsurface soil information on large CAFOs or existing operations expanding to large CAFO.</p>
<p>Manure application rates for phosphorus are based on: 1) <i>Phosphorus Index Only</i> 2) <i>Soil Test Phosphorus Only</i> 3) <i>Either PIO or STPO</i> 4) <i>Other</i></p>	<p>Phosphorus index only</p>
<p>Are there any nutrient “caps” to manure application?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Composition testing: <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on manures before application</i></p>	<p>Manure samples shall be collected and prepared according to NDSU Extension Service guidance or industry standard methods, as approved by the department. Manure testing shall include analyses for nitrogen, ammonia, and phosphorous.</p> <p>– If the operator uses feed or feed additives with high concentrations of salts or heavy metals, the department may require the manure be tested for these materials. The same is true if there is a reasonable expectation that the manure might contain elevated salts, metals or other potentially harmful materials.</p> <p>– Manure to be land applied shall be sampled from each manure storage structure that holds manure from separate types of livestock or from similar types of livestock in different phases of growth.</p> <p>– Livestock facilities identified by the department as needing nutrient management plans shall have their manure and the soil where manure is being applied tested in accordance with items 1-5 once every three years. CAFOs shall have their manure and the soil where manure is being applied tested in accordance with items 1-5 each year.</p>
<p>Does your state require testing of manure for</p>	<p>No</p>

anything beyond nutrients, such as metals, pathogens, antibiotics, etc.?	
Other land application highlights: <i>Additional restrictions for land application of manures</i>	No other information
Other regulatory details: <i>Additional information on the regulation of land application of manures</i>	Manure is generally prohibited from being disposed of in a landfill; however, in certain circumstances, the department can allow for such disposal if the landfill owner agrees.
General Assessment Questions	
Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change:	Undetermined
Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of manures that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links:	No
Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of manures beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so:	No
Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.	No other information

Ohio	
Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2025
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Ohio Environmental Protection Agency (OEPA)_ Ohio Department of Agriculture (ODA)_ Division of Livestock Environmental Permitting (DLEP) - regulates large CAFF's and Certified Livestock Managers (CLM)_ Division of Soil and Water Conservation (DSWC) _
Links to regulations	OAC, Chapter 3745-33 -This rule contains NPDES permit requirements for all point source discharges, including CAFOs_ https://dam.assets.ohio.gov/image/upload/epa.ohio.gov/Portals/35/rules/33_all.pdf _ OAC Chapter 901 (Livestock Environmental Permitting): 10-1, 10-2, 10-3, 10-4, 13-1_ https://agri.ohio.gov/divisions/livestock-environmental-permitting/laws-and-rules _ https://agri.ohio.gov/divisions/soil-and-water-conservation/laws-and-rules _ PART VII -“ Production Area Monitoring and Inspections and Land Application Requirements _ https://dam.assets.ohio.gov/image/upload/epa.ohio.gov/Portals/35/cafo/CAFO_NPDES_PARTVII.pdf
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	More than one agency
Other regulator info	Ohio Environmental Protection Agency (Ohio EPA) has been delegated_ by the U.S. EPA to implement the NPDES permit. Ohio Department of Agriculture has regulatory authority to issue permits to operate and permits to install to all large CAFOs and smaller facilities based on discretion.
Definitions	
How CAFOs are defined or categorized:	"Concentrated Animal Feeding Facility" means an animal feeding facility with a total design capacity equal to or more than the number of animals specified in any of the categories in division (M) of this section. (below) _ _ "Concentrated Animal Feeding Operation" means an animal feeding facility that complies with one of the following: (1) Has a total design capacity equal to or more than the number of animals specified in any of the categories in division (M) of this section; (2)Satisfies the criteria in division (M), (Q), or (EE) of this section;_ _ M. Large Concentrated Animal Feeding Operation" means an animal feeding facility that stables or confines at least the number of animals specified in any of the following categories: (1) Seven hundred mature dairy cattle whether milked or dry; (2) One thousand veal calves; (3) One thousand cattle other than mature dairy cattle or veal calves; (4) Two thousand five hundred swine that each weigh fifty-five pounds

	<p>or more; (5) Ten thousand swine that each weigh less than fifty-five pounds; (6) Five hundred horses; (7) Ten thousand sheep or lambs; (8) Fifty-five thousand turkeys; (9) Thirty thousand laying hens or broilers if the animal feeding facility uses a liquid manure handling system; (10) One hundred twenty-five thousand chickens, other than laying hens, if the animal feeding facility uses a manure handling system that is not a liquid manure handling system; (11) Eighty-two thousand laying hens if the animal feeding facility uses a manure handling system that is not a liquid manure handling system; (12) Thirty thousand ducks if the animal feeding facility uses a manure handling system that is not a liquid manure handling system; (13) Five thousand ducks if the animal feeding facility uses a liquid manure handling system._</p> <p>—</p> <p>"Medium Concentrated Animal Feeding Operation" means an animal feeding facility that satisfies both of the following:—</p> <p>(1) The facility stables or confines the number of animals specified in any of the following categories: (a) Two hundred to six hundred ninety-nine mature dairy cattle whether milked or dry; (b) Three hundred to nine hundred ninety-nine veal calves; (c) Three hundred to nine hundred ninety-nine cattle other than mature dairy cattle or veal calves; (d) Seven hundred fifty to two thousand four hundred ninety-nine swine that each weigh fifty-five pounds or more; (e) Three thousand to nine thousand nine hundred ninety-nine swine that each weigh less than fifty-five pounds; (f) One hundred fifty to four hundred ninety-nine horses; (g) Three thousand to nine thousand nine hundred ninety-nine sheep or lambs; (h) Sixteen thousand five hundred to fifty-four thousand nine hundred ninety-nine turkeys; (i) Nine thousand to twenty-nine thousand nine hundred ninety-nine laying hens or broilers if the animal feeding facility uses a liquid manure handling system; (j) Thirty-seven thousand five hundred to one hundred twenty-four thousand nine hundred ninety-nine chickens, other than laying hens, if the animal feeding facility uses a manure handling system that is not a liquid manure handling system; (k) Twenty-five thousand to eighty-one thousand nine hundred ninety-nine laying hens if the animal feeding facility uses a manure handling system that is not a liquid manure handling system; (l) Ten thousand to twenty-nine thousand nine hundred ninety-nine ducks if the animal feeding facility uses a manure handling system that is not a liquid manure handling system; (m) One thousand five hundred to four thousand nine hundred ninety-nine ducks if the animal feeding facility uses a liquid manure handling system.</p>
How animal units are defined (if used):	Not used
NPDES permitting or other permitting requirements:	A large or medium CAFO that discharges or proposes to discharge needs a CAFO NPDES permit. Land application field discharges may trigger NPDES requirements, though agricultural stormwater discharges are not subject to NPDES permit requirements. Also, ODA-DLEP issues state Permits to Install (PTI) and Permits to Operate (PTO). Facilities that disturb more than 1 acre during construction are required to have a NPDES Construction SW permit thru Ohio EPA.
Does the state require an	No

NPDES permit for all Large CAFOs?	
Does the state issue individual or general CAFO permits?	Individual
Are any other permits required for CAFOs or other large farms?	Yes
Other definitions needed to understand these regulations:	No other information
Regulatory Details	
Setbacks: <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some geographical feature</i>	Streams, Lakes, Ponds, Watercourses, Other Surface Water, Waterways, Open Tile Line Intake Structures, or Other Conduits to Surface Waters: Manure shall not be applied closer than 100 feet, unless a 35-foot vegetated buffer has been established where manure application is prohibited. _ Public Drinking Water Surface Water Intakes: Land Application shall not take place within the emergency management zone of a public water system using surface water. Otherwise, manure shall not be applied closer than 300 feet from the edge of the field._ _ Seasonal Salmonid and Cold Water Habitats: Manure shall not be applied closer than 100 feet, unless a 35-foot vegetated buffer has been established where manure application is prohibited._ _ Public Drinking Water Wells: Land application shall not take place within a highly susceptible drinking water source protection area (as defined by Ohio EPA) for a community public water system using ground water and not within the inner management zone for all other community public water systems using ground water._ Private Drinking Water Wells: For injection application and surface application followed by incorporation within 24 hours, manure shall not be applied closer than 100 feet. For surface application not followed by incorporation within 24 hours, manure shall not be applied closer than 300 feet._ Class V Agricultural Drainage Wells, Agricultural Wellheads, or Sinkholes: For

	<p>injection application and surface application followed by incorporation within 24 hours, manure shall not be applied closer than 100 feet. For surface application not followed by incorporation within 24 hours, manure shall not be applied closer than 300 feet. _</p> <p>Springs: Manure shall not be applied closer than 300 feet. _</p> <p>Slope: For fields with a slope less than 15%, surface application can be used when yearly average soil loss is less than five tons per acre or T-2, whichever is less. Manure shall not be applied to cropland over 15% slope or to pasture/hay land over 20% slope unless one of the following precautions are taken: _</p> <p>a. Immediate incorporation or injection with operations done on the contour, unless the field has 80% ground cover (residue or canopy); b. Applications are timed during periods of lower runoff and/or rainfall (May 20 to October 15); _</p> <p>c. Split applications are made (separated by rainfall events) with single applications not exceeding 5000 gallons per acre for liquid manure or 10 wet tons per acre for solid manure; d. The field is established and managed in contour strips with alternated strips in grass or legume.</p>
<p>Are setbacks more restrictive than CFR?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Timing, weather, or conditional application restrictions: <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather, seasons, or land characteristics (like slope)</i></p>	<p>Refer to Water Capacity Chart and OAC 901:10-2-14, specifically paragraph (C)(1)(d) and (e) and (C)(6). _</p> <p>– Dry weather discharges of manure are prohibited from production and land application areas. Storm water associated with industrial activity can be discharged in accordance with this permit as long as good housekeeping practices are conducted to ensure that the storm water is not contaminated by manure. _</p> <p>– For fields that are prone to flooding, floodplains, or floodways, manure must be injected or incorporated within 24 hours of application. No manure application shall occur during periods of expected flooding. _</p> <p>– Land application shall not occur on saturated soils or during rain or runoff events, and shall not occur if the forecast contains a greater than fifty per cent chance of precipitation as determined in Managing Manure Nutrients at Concentrated Animal Feeding Operations, Appendix M, United States Environmental Protection Agency, EPA-821-B-04-006, August 2004, -2 exceeding an amount of one-quarter inch for hydrologic soil group D soils and one-half inch for hydrologic soil group A, B, and C soils, for a period extending twenty-four hours after the start of land application. Record weather conditions in the operating record for conditions at the time of application and for twenty-four hours prior to and following application. For determining hydrologic soil groups, refer to USDA-NRCS Engineering Field Manual, Chapter 2 -“ Ohio Supplement (1989), Table 2.1, pages 2-42 through 2-83. _</p> <p>– Manure shall be managed in such a manner to prevent land application on frozen or snow covered ground. Every attempt shall be made by the permittee to avoid land application during the frozen or snow covered ground conditions because of lack of</p>

	<p>agronomic benefit and high risk of pollution of surface waters. As stated in Part II, failure to take appropriate action to avoid land application on frozen and/or snow covered ground is a violation of this permit and subject to enforcement. The nutrients in the manure applied on frozen and/or snow covered ground shall be included in the manure application rate calculations for the next crop. _</p> <p>_</p> <p>See also Ohio S.B.1 from 2015for additional restrictions: https://www.legislature.ohio.gov/legislation/legislation-summary?id=GA131-SB-1</p>
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to saturated soils?	Yes
Is there a restriction for land application of manure within floodplains?	Yes
Is there a restriction for land application of manure related to future rainfall?	Yes
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to frozen or snow-covered ground?	Yes
Are there restrictions to manure applications based on time of year or time of day?	Yes

<p>Are there restrictions to manure application based on slope?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Are there any other seasonal, timing, weather, or physical restrictions to manure applications not captured above?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Transfer of manure off-site: <i>Requirements related to the transfer of manures to other persons</i></p>	<p>DLEP facilities do transfer manure (mostly solid) offsite thru what is known as Distribution and Utilization (D&U) agreements. The requirement for the permitted facility is to only distribute this manure to someone that will land apply as a CLM (regulated by DLEP) or someone that is certified as an Agriculture Fertilizer Certification (reference ORC 903.40). Details of what is required for D&U manure can be found in OAC 901:10-2-11.</p>
<p>Are receivers of manure transfers from CAFOs required to follow the same regulations?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Nutrient or manure management plans: <i>Additional details on the NMP requirement . Note that some of this information may overlap with other sections</i></p>	<p>DLEP requires a MMP for all facilities as part of the PTO's. All land under their control has to be included in the MMP and they provide a total nutrient budget for the acres available vs nutrients generated. Once operating, they are required to maintain Operating records to demonstrate compliance with permit/rules and DLEP inspects most facilities 2x per year to ensure compliance. _ _</p> <p>The MMP must address the following aspects of the production area to ensure compliance with the discharge prohibition in the permit: _</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Specific practices to ensure adequate storage capacity to protect water quality, including provisions to ensure proper operation and maintenance of the storage facilities. _ * Practices for proper disposal of dead animals to prevent disposal in the wastewater treatment system and to prevent discharges of pollutants to surface water. _

	<p>* Practices to divert clean storm water away from production areas. _</p> <p>* Practices to make sure that animals and manure in the production area do not come into direct contact with waters of the State. _</p> <p>* Practices to ensure that unused and waste chemicals and other contaminants do not enter waste storage structures or storm water storage or treatment systems, unless the system is designed to treat the chemicals and other contaminants. _</p> <p>* Provisions to conduct inspections and monitoring. _</p> <p>The MMP must also include a land application plan to comply with the land application requirements of the permit, including:_</p> <p>* A total nutrient budget, _</p> <p>* Manure and soil characterizations, _</p> <p>* Application methods and timing that will minimize nutrient transport to waters of the state, and _</p> <p>* Specific agronomic application rates._</p> <p>_</p> <p>For DLEP, use 2 different P Risk Assessments. Most widely used is a Soil Test P assessment, and a P-Index Assessment is used occasionally. These are reference in 901:10-2-14 and each of these Risk Assessments is provided as appendices to this rule.</p>
<p>Do your NMP/MMPS follow, comply with, or based on NRCS Technical Standard 590?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Application rates: <i>State regulations that restrict the rates at which manures are applied and methods needed to determine appropriate rates.</i></p>	<p>Nutrient Budget: The manure management plan shall include a total nutrient budget for the operation, based on 1) targeted crop yields based on actual crop yields, 2) soil productivity information, 3) historical yield data, 4) realistic potential yield, or 5) combinations of yield data. The plan shall consider all potential sources of nutrients including quantity of manure and manure nutrients, organic by- products, wastewater, commercial fertilizer, crop residues, legume credits, and irrigation water and a summary of the total acres of land to be used for land application. _</p> <p>_</p> <p>Manure Application Rates:_</p> <p>Ohio manure land application needs to meet crop yield but not to exceed crop needs. Using P index for monitoring._</p> <p>a. Determine if the land application site has soils that are prone to flooding and when the expected flooding seasons are according to Table 3. For timing restrictions, see Part VII, B, 2, c._</p> <p>b. The manure application rate shall be based on the land application site's soil tests that are no older than three years. See Part VII, A, 3, above._</p> <p>c. The manure application rate shall be based on the most current manure test results. The manure test results expressed as a nutrient percentage shall be converted into either pounds per ton of dry manure or pounds per one thousand</p>

gallons of liquid manure._

d. Determine if a solid or liquid manure application will be performed. The manure application rate shall be based on the most limiting factor (i.e., most restrictive factor for the purpose of protecting surface water quality) of the following:_

(1)For liquid manure (less than 20% solids):_

i. The crop nitrogen requirements or removal expressed in thousands of gallons of manure per acre, as determined in accordance with g., below;_

ii. The crop phosphorus requirements or removal expressed in thousands of gallons of manure per acre, as determined in accordance with h., below;_

iii. The restrictions on the volume of liquid manure application, in accordance with Part VII, B and Part VII, C, Tables 21 and 22, with volume expressed as a measure of gallons per acre or inches per acre, with twenty seven thousand two hundred gallons equal to one acre/inch;_

iv. The application rate shall not exceed the available water capacity in the upper eight inches of the soil for both subsurface and no subsurface drained sites in accordance with Part VII, C, Table 4; and_

v. The application rate shall be adjusted to preclude surface ponding and/or runoff from a land application site. See Part VII, B, 2._

(2)For solid manure (greater than or equal to 20% solids):_

i. Either the crop nitrogen requirements or removal of nitrogen expressed in pounds per ton of dry manure per acre, as determined in accordance with g., below;_

ii. The crop phosphorus requirements or removal expressed in pounds per ton of dry manure per acre, as determined in accordance with h., below; or_

iii. The restrictions on the volume of solid manure applied, taken from Part VII, B and Part VII, C, Tables 21 and 22, with volume expressed as a measure of tons/acre._

e. Determine if solid manure will be stockpiled at the land application site.

Stockpiles shall meet the setbacks in Part VII, B, Table 2._

f. For liquid manure applications, determine restrictions based on Part VII, C, Table 4 Available Water Capacity and Tables 21 and 22 Most Limiting Manure Application Rates (for Tiled Fields and Non-Tiled Fields). For solid manures, determine restrictions based on Part VII, C, Tables 21 and 22 Most Limiting Manure Application Rates Charts (for Tiled Fields and Non-Tiled Fields)._

g. The manure application rate for nitrogen shall be the most restrictive value (i.e., most restrictive factor for the purpose of protecting surface water quality) determined after considering the following:_

(1)The application rate for nitrogen shall be based on utilization of crops at the recommended agronomic rates (using the Ohio Agronomy Guide, OSU Bulletin 472) and based on minimum runoff and leaching to waters of the state, as determined in accordance with (3) below._

(2)In determining the agronomic rate for nitrogen, the owner or operator shall do the following:_

i. Determine the nitrogen requirements (based on Part VII, C, Tables 6, 7, and 8) or removal rates (based on Part VII, C, Table 5) for a realistic yield goal of planned crops; Determine the nutrient removal for the expected cropping sequence using Part VII, C, Table 5 Nutrient removed in Harvested Portions of Crops. Determine residual nitrogen credits for the expected cropping sequence using Part VII, C, Table 8 Residual Nitrogen Credits Based on Previous Crops._

ii. Subtract the nitrogen credit to be given to the next crop in accordance with values

for previous crops, subtract credits for crop residues and legumes grown in previous years, and subtract nitrogen that will be added in other forms including commercial fertilizer and organic by-products (see Part VII, C, Table 8); and_

iii. When applying nitrogen to a grass or legume cover crop that is growing or being established immediately after manure application, manure can be applied at the recommended nitrogen rate (using the Ohio Agronomy Guide, OSU Bulletin 472) for the next non-legume crop or the nitrogen removal rate for the next legume crop._

(3)In determining how to minimize nitrogen leaching to waters of the state, the owner or operator shall do the following:_

i. Assess each land application site with the Ohio nitrogen leaching risk assessment procedure in Part VII, C; and_

ii. If the nitrogen leaching risk assessment procedure completed in accordance with i above, demonstrates that the land application site has a high nitrogen leaching potential and no growing cover crop, then application of manure shall be limited to fifty pounds per acre as applied nitrogen calculated at the time of application (by adding ammonia-nitrogen to one third of organic nitrogen) from June to October first._

(4)Use the current manure analysis and the relevant sections of the following tables in Part VII, C to determine the amount of manure nutrient available for crop production: Table 10 Calculating Available Nitrogen of Manure, Table 11 Nitrogen Sufficiency ranges for Corn, Soybeans, Alfalfa and Wheat, and Table 12 Side dress N Fertilizer Rates for Corn._

(5)When using legumes as a nitrogen removal source, the maximum legume nitrogen removal must be less than or equal to one hundred and fifty pounds per acre._

h. The manure application rate for phosphorus shall be the most restrictive value (i.e., most restrictive factor for the purpose of protecting surface water quality) determined after considering the following:_

(1)The application rate for phosphate applications shall be based on the following:_

i. Estimated plant uptake by crops at the recommended agronomic rates (using the Ohio Agronomy Guide, OSU Bulletin 472);_

ii. Soil test analysis;_

iii. Subsequent phosphorus removal in plant biomass (see Part VII, C, Table 5); and_

iv. Minimum runoff to waters of the State._

(2)In determining the agronomic rate for phosphate application, the owner or operator shall do the following:_

i. Determine the phosphorus requirements for a realistic yield goal of planned crops and/or crop rotations (see Part VII, C, Tables 13, 14, 15, 16, and 17);_

ii. Subtract phosphorus that will be added in other forms including commercial fertilizer and organic by-products; and_

iii. The application rate for phosphorus shall not exceed the removal rates for a realistic yield goal of planned crops, unless following the procedures in h, (3) below._

(3)In determining how to minimize phosphorus runoff to waters of the State, the owner r operator shall do the following:_

i. Prior to the land application of manure, a land application site shall be assessed with either the phosphorus index risk assessment procedure or the phosphorus soil test risk assessment procedure in Part VII, C. This risk assessment shall be used in

the determination of manure application rates and the results shall be documented as required in Part VII, A, 5. Use the phosphorus index risk assessment procedure if the Bray P1 value of the soil test is over one hundred and fifty parts per million. The phosphorus index risk assessment procedure shall only be relied upon for a transitional period of time to allow the owner or operator an opportunity to find other fields or other methods to distribute nutrients from the facility in order to achieve less than one hundred and fifty parts per million Bray P1 soil test method;_

ii. There shall be no multi-year phosphorus applications on fields where either the phosphorus index risk assessment procedure produces a high rating or the phosphorus soil test risk assessment procedure produces a high potential rating. There shall be no phosphorus applications on fields where either the phosphorus index risk assessment procedure produces a very high rating or the phosphorus soil test risk assessment procedure produces a very high potential rating; and_

iii. Phosphate manure application rates above two hundred and fifty pounds per acre are not recommended. However, if phosphate concentrations in liquid manure exceed sixty pounds of phosphate per one thousand gallons or eighty pounds phosphate per ton for solid manure, rates higher than two hundred and fifty pounds per acre may need to be applied due to limitations of the application equipment. In no case shall manure application exceed the rates specified in Part VII, A, 4, g and Part VII, A, 4, h, (3), ii. In no case shall phosphate applications exceed five hundred pounds per acre of phosphate during one year. When phosphate applications exceed two hundred and fifty pounds per acre the following additional criteria applies:_

Phosphate applications exceeding two hundred and fifty pounds per acre in any one year shall not be applied on fields with a phosphorus soil test exceeding 100 ppm Bray P1 or equivalent, results of a phosphorus index risk assessment procedure notwithstanding._

There shall be no further phosphate applications for a minimum of three years on land with a phosphorus soil test level below 40 ppm (80 pounds per acre) Bray P1 or equivalent and no additional phosphate applications for a minimum of five years on land with a phosphorus soil test level above 40 ppm (80 pounds per acre) Bray P1 or equivalent._

Soil Characterization: At a minimum, soil samples shall be taken to a uniform depth and the fertility analysis shall include: pH, phosphorus, potassium, calcium, magnesium and cation exchange capacity._

a. Soil fertility analysis shall be conducted in accordance with Publication 221, "Recommended Chemical Soil Test Procedures for the North Central Region; Published by the North Central Regional Committee on Soil Testing and Plant Analysis (NCR-13), North Dakota Agricultural Experiment Station". See Part VII, A, 3, e, below._

b. Sample shall be representative of a land application site with one composite soil sample representing no more than twenty-five acres or one composite soil sample for each land application site, whichever is less. A sample depth of 8 inches shall be used unless justified otherwise in the plan._

c. The manure management plan shall specify the soil sampling frequency in accordance with the following requirements:_

(1)A site that receives manure shall be soil tested, at a minimum, once every three years._

	<p>(2)For any land application site used by the owner or operator the land application site shall be sampled at least six months following application._ results of the soil sampling events shall be recorded and shall include the location of the soil sample collection site, the depth of the sample collected and the analysis._</p> <p>e. In developing appropriate manure application rates for land application methods, the owner or operator shall use the Bray P1 soil test level or equivalent appropriate phosphorus soil test, (Mehlich III, Olsen, Phosphorus Retention Test). The owner or operator shall choose a phosphorus soil test method and identify the selected method in the manure management plan._</p> <p>_</p> <p>If using the NRCS PSTRAP, no manure applications on fields represented by a soil test P value of 150 ppm Bray P1 or higher. Can use P Index to apply to fields with soil test P values higher than 150 ppm Bray P1.</p>
<p>Manure application rates for phosphorus are based on:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) <i>Phosphorus Index Only</i> 2) <i>Soil Test Phosphorus Only</i> 3) <i>Either PIO or STPO</i> 4) <i>Other</i> 	<p>Phosphorus index or soil test</p>
<p>Are there any nutrient “caps” to manure application?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Composition testing: <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on manures before application</i></p>	<p>MMP Content._ Manure Characterization: At a minimum, manure from each manure storage or treatment facility shall be analyzed annually for the following: total nitrogen, ammonium nitrogen, organic nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium, and percent total solids. Procedures for the collection and analysis of the samples shall be in accordance with Publication A3769, Recommended Methods of Manure Analysis; Published by the Board of Regents of the University of Wisconsin System, University of Wisconsin- Extension-.</p>
<p>Does your</p>	<p>No</p>

<p>state require testing of manure for anything beyond nutrients, such as metals, pathogens, antibiotics, etc.?</p>	
<p>Other land application highlights: <i>Additional restrictions for land application of manures</i></p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Other regulatory details: <i>Additional information on the regulation of land application of manures</i></p>	<p>No other information</p>
<p>General Assessment Questions</p>	
<p>Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change:</p>	<p>Potentially. The Department of Agriculture is working on rule updates that may impact their involvement or lack of involvement in future NPDES permitting, as well as phosphorus application rate determinations.</p>
<p>Are there</p>	<p>No</p>

<p>any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of manures that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links:</p>	
<p>Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of manures beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so:</p>	<p>Yes. Local Soil and Water Conservation Districts.</p>
<p>Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state?</p>	<p>No other information</p>

If so, please
briefly
describe.

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Oklahoma Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2025
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Oklahoma Department of Environmental Quality (ODEQ)_ Oklahoma Department of Agriculture, Food, and Forestry (ODAFF)
Links to regulations	35:17-4 Concentrated Animal Feeding Operations_ Act:_ https://ag.ok.gov/wp-content/uploads/2023/04/Oklahoma-Concentrated-Animal-Feeding-Operations-Act-Nov-24.pdf _ Rules:_ https://ag.ok.gov/wp-content/uploads/2023/04/20240315_OAC_CAF0-rules.pdf _ 35:17-3 Swine _ Act: _ https://ag.ok.gov/wp-content/uploads/2023/04/Oklahoma-Swine-Feeding-Operations-Act-Nov-24.pdf _ Rules:_ https://ag.ok.gov/wp-content/uploads/2023/04/Oklahoma-Swine-Feeding-Operation-Rules-Nov-24.pdf
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	More than one agency
Other regulator info	Oklahoma Water Resources Board (OWRB)
Definitions	
How CAFOs are defined or categorized:	Oklahoma contains different definitions of AFOs, CAFOs, and other size thresholds for regulation when compared to federal NPDES definitions. _ _ Concentrated Animal Feeding Operation means: (a) An Animal Feeding Operation which meets the following criteria: (1)more than the number of animals specified in any of the following categories are confined: (a)1,000 slaughter and feeder cattle, (b)700 mature dairy cattle, whether milk or dry cows, (c)500 horses, (d)10,000 sheep or lambs, (e)55,000 turkeys, (f)100,000 laying hens or broilers, if the facility has continuous overflow watering, (g)30,000 laying hens or broilers, if the facility has a liquid manure system, (h)5,000 ducks, or (i)1,000 animal units, and (2)pollutants are discharged into waters of the state. _ _ Provided, no Animal Feeding Operation pursuant to this subparagraph shall be construed to be a concentrated Animal Feeding Operation if the Animal Feeding Operation discharges only in the event of a twenty-five-year, twenty-four-hour storm event, or (b) an Animal Feeding Operation which meets the following criteria: (1)more than the number of animals specified in any of the following categories are confined: (a)300 slaughter or feeder cattle, (b)200

	<p>mature dairy cattle, whether milk or dry cows, (c)150 horses, (d)3,000 sheep or lambs, (e)16,500 turkeys, (f)30,000 laying hens or broilers, if the facility has continuous overflow watering, (g)9,000 laying hens or broilers, if the facility has a liquid manure system, (h)1,500 ducks, or (i)300 animal units, and (2)either one of the following conditions are met: (a)pollutants are discharged into waters of the state through an artificially constructed ditch, flushing system or other similar artificially constructed device, or (b)pollutants are discharged directly into navigable waters which originate outside of and pass over, across or through the facility or otherwise come into direct contact with the animals confined in the operation._</p> <p>– Provided, however, that no Animal Feeding Operation pursuant to this subparagraph is a Concentrated Animal Feeding Operation if the Animal Feeding Operation discharges only in the event of a twenty-five-year, twenty-four-hour storm event, or (c) the Board determines that the operation is a significant contributor of pollution to waters of the state pursuant to Section 20-44 of this act;_</p> <p>– Concentrated Swine Feeding Operation means: a. a licensed managed feeding operation, b. a swine feeding operation which meets the following criteria: (1) more than the number of swine specified in any of the following categories are confined: (a) 750 swine each weighing over 25 kilograms or approximately 55 pounds, (b) 3,000 weaned swine each weighing under 25 kilograms, or (c) 300 swine animal units, and (2) either one of the following conditions are met: (a) pollutants are discharged into waters of the state through an artificially constructed ditch, flushing system or other similar artificially constructed device; or directly into navigable waters which originate outside of and pass over, across or through the facility or otherwise come into direct contact with the swine confined in the operation. Provided, however, that no swine feeding operation pursuant to this subparagraph is a concentrated swine feeding operation if the swine feeding operation discharges only in the event of a twenty-five-year, twenty-four-hour storm event, (c) the Board determines that the operation is a significant contributor of pollution to waters of the state pursuant to Section 20-6 of this title, or (d) any new swine feeding operation established after November 1, 2011, with more than one hundred (100) animal units;</p>
<p>How animal units are defined (if used):</p>	<p>"Animal Unit" means a unit of measurement for any Animal Feeding Operation calculated by adding the following numbers: The number of slaughter and feeder cattle multiplied by one (1), plus the number of mature dairy cattle multiplied by one and four-tenths (1.4), plus the number of sheep multiplied by one-tenth (0.1), plus the number of horses multiplied by two (2);_</p>

	<p>– Swine Animal Unit: A unit of measurement for any swine feeding operation calculated by adding the following numbers: The number of swine weighing over twentyfive (25) kilograms, approximately fifty-five (55) pounds, multiplied by four-tenths (0.4), Page 3 of 33 ODAFF AEMS Reference: Effective November 1, 2024 plus the number of weaned swine weighing under twenty-five (25) kilograms multiplied by one-tenth (0.1)</p>
<p>NPDES permitting or other permitting requirements:</p>	<p>Concentrated Animal Feeding Operations are point sources subject to the license program established pursuant to the provisions of the Oklahoma Concentrated Animal Feeding Operations Act. The Oklahoma Department of Environmental Quality (ODEQ) was delegated regulatory authority of the National Pollutant Discharge Elimination System (NPDES) program. The lead agency for agricultural point source pollution is delegated to ODAFF. ODAFF issues an Agriculture Pollutant Discharge Elimination System (AgPDES) permit. The state permitting program, administered by ODAFF, requires Concentrated Animal Feeding Operations (CAFOs) Concentrated Swine Feeding Operations (CSFOs) to obtain an AgPDES stormwater construction permit for any soil disturbance over 1 acre and an AgPDES CAFO permit (only if they are or proposing to discharge to a WOTUS). Permit requirements generally reflect the federal CAFO rule, but establish more stringent requirements for swine operations that utilize liquid waste management systems. Those possessing an AgPDES Permit for a swine feeding operation shall also be required to obtain an Oklahoma swine feeding operation (CSFO) license. Required plans within regulations and permits: Pollution Prevention Plan (PPP) PPP for CAFO: Prior to the submission of a state CAFO license application, each facility shall develop a Pollution Prevention Plan (PPP) according to the Oklahoma Concentrated Animal Feeding Operations Act and rules promulgated pursuant to the Act. The Plan shall include provisions for documentation of structural controls, documentation of operating Best Management Practices (BMPs), an Animal Waste Management Plan (AWMP), a carcass disposal plan for normal and emergency disposal of carcasses, and record keeping provisions. The Plan shall identify an individual who is responsible for implementing, maintaining, and revising the PPP. PPP for Swine: Prior to the submission of a CSFO license application, each facility shall develop a Pollution Prevention Plan (PPP) according to the Oklahoma Swine Feeding Operations Act and rules promulgated pursuant to the Act. The Plan shall include provisions for documentation of structural controls, Best Management Practices (BMPs), a Swine Waste Management Plan (SWMP), a carcass disposal plan (CDP) for normal and emergency disposal of carcasses, hydrological connection documentation and</p>

	<p>record keeping provisions. The Plan shall identify an individual who is responsible for implementing, maintaining, and revising the PPP. The PPP for an LMFO shall also include an Odor Abatement Plan (OAP) and a Pest Management Plan (PMP)._</p> <p>NMP: Must ensure: adequate storage of manure, litter and process wastewater; proper management of mortalities; clean water diversions; prevention of direct contact of confined animals with WOTUS; chemicals on site are not disposed of in waste or storm water and have proper handling procedures; protocols for appropriate testing of manure, litter and process wastewater; the NMP is signed by the owner/operator. Other requirements in the NMP include: nutrient transport potential; form, source, amount, timing, and method of application; determination of application rates; conservation practices; manure and soil sampling results; record keeping provisions; setbacks; and annual calculations._</p> <p>Water usage permits are also required.</p>
Does the state require an NPDES permit for all Large CAFOs?	No
Does the state issue individual or general CAFO permits?	Both
Are any other permits required for CAFOs or other large farms?	Yes
Other definitions needed to understand these regulations:	<p>WOTUS – Waters of the United States_</p> <p>AWMP: An AWMP or its equivalent shall be prepared, according to Departmental policy, for each facility prior to the submission of a CAFO license application. An AWMP or its equivalent may include, but is not limited to, a Comprehensive Nutrient Management Plan per NRCS guidance, or a Nutrient Management Plan per EPA guidance._</p> <p>BMP: The owner shall document all Best Management Practices (BMPs) used to comply with the required effluent limitations. Equivalent measures contained in a site-specific AWMP prepared by NRCS may be substituted for the BMPs._</p> <p>SWMP: Swine Waste Management Plan - A swine waste management plan or its equivalent shall be prepared, according to Departmental policy, for each facility prior to the submission of a CAFO license application. A swine waste management plan or its equivalent may include, but is not limited to, a Comprehensive Nutrient Management Plan per NRCS guidance, or a Nutrient Management Plan per EPA guidance</p>
Regulatory Details	
Setbacks: <i>State regulations that indicate how much</i>	There shall be no water quality impairment to public and neighboring private drinking water wells due to waste handling at a facility. Wastewater retention structures or land application of

<p><i>distance must lie between the site of land application and some geographical feature</i></p>	<p>wastewater from both CAFO and CFSO shall not be located within three hundred (300) feet of an existing public or private drinking water well, and must be at least 500 feet from the nearest occupied Residence. Land applications must also not be in areas within 50 feet of an intermittent stream or 100 feet of a perennial stream unless an established buffer strip is present._</p> <p>— , Municipalities, a state park or resort, and the high water mark of a public surface water supply must be 3 miles from CAFOs and CSFOs.</p>
<p>Are setbacks more restrictive than CFR?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Timing, weather, or conditional application restrictions: <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather, seasons, or land characteristics (like slope)</i></p>	<p>Land applications shall not occur on soils over 15% cannot be applied on. There shall also be no applications on frequently flooded soils or on soils that are frozen, snow covered, or water saturated (including periods of heavy rain when water ponding has occurred on the soil surface).</p>
<p>Is there a restriction for land application of manure to saturated soils?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Is there a restriction for land application of manure within floodplains?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Is there a restriction for land application of manure related to future rainfall?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Is there a restriction for land application of manure to frozen or snow-covered ground?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Are there restrictions to manure applications based on time of year or time of day?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Are there restrictions to manure application based on slope?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Are there any other seasonal, timing, weather, or physical restrictions to manure applications not captured above?</p>	<p>No</p>

<p>Transfer of manure off-site: <i>Requirements related to the transfer of manures to other persons</i></p>	<p>Records of manure or wastewater sold or transferred must be documented and maintained on site and available for inspection from the CAFOs state inspector.</p>
<p>Are receivers of manure transfers from CAFOs required to follow the same regulations?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Nutrient or manure management plans: <i>Additional details on the NMP requirement. Note that some of this information may overlap with other sections</i></p>	<p>Nutrient Management Plans are required under the PPP and AWMP.</p>
<p>Do your NMP/MMPS follow, comply with, or based on NRCS Technical Standard 590?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Application rates: <i>State regulations that restrict the rates at which manures are applied and methods needed to determine appropriate rates.</i></p>	<p>Composite soil samples from each land application must be tested for the amount of Nitrogen as Nitrate and total Phosphorous. Soil tests from land application sites shall be performed by an Oklahoma Department of Environmental Quality certified testing laboratory or State operated laboratory at least annually. All testing shall establish a management record, with all costs paid by the owner. _ The AWMP and SWMP have almost identical requirements. They must include all calculations and all factors and assumptions used in determining land application rates, acreage, and crops for both solid and liquid animal wastes. Land application rates shall take into account the plant available nutrient contribution of any land applied animal wastes. The following requirements shall apply to land application of animal waste on land owned or leased by the owner: _ -Runoff from animal waste is prohibited where it results in a discharge to surface or groundwaters of the State. The owner shall provide controls for runoff and erosion as appropriate for site conditions. _ -Land application practices shall be managed so as to reduce or minimize Ponding or puddling of wastewater on the site and adverse conditions that invite pests including flies and rodents. _ -Timing and rate of applications shall be in response to crop needs, assuming usual nutrient losses, expected precipitation, and soil conditions. Timing and rate of land application of animal waste shall be based on published materials approved by the Department. _ -Land application shall not occur in areas defined as do not apply areas in the waste application criteria of the USDA NRCS Waste Utilization Standard Conservation Practice Standard 633 and</p>

	<p>Nutrient Management Conservation Practice Standard Code 590, or their current replacement._</p> <p>-The AWMP shall identify areas which due to topography, activities, or other factors have a high potential for significant soil erosion. Where these areas have the potential to contribute pollutants to surface or groundwaters of the State, the Pollution Prevention Plan shall identify measures used to limit erosion and pollutant runoff. Land subject to excessive erosion shall be avoided._</p> <p>-When a split application is required, it must contain no more than ½ the total phosphorus allowance and be at least 30 days apart.</p>
<p>Manure application rates for phosphorus are based on:</p> <p>1) <i>Phosphorus Index Only</i> 2) <i>Soil Test Phosphorus Only</i> 3) <i>Either PIO or STPO</i> 4) <i>Other</i></p>	Soil test phosphorus only
<p>Are there any nutrient “caps” to manure application?</p>	Yes
<p>Composition testing: <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on manures before application</i></p>	<p>ODAFF does not require fecal coliform testing for manures prior to AgPDES application. Oklahoma Department of Environmental Quality requires annual fecal coliform bacteria level tests for NPDES permits.</p>
<p>Does your state require testing of manure for anything beyond nutrients, such as metals, pathogens, antibiotics, etc.?</p>	No
<p>Other land application highlights: <i>Additional restrictions for land application of manures</i></p>	No other information
<p>Other regulatory details: <i>Additional information on the regulation of land application of manures</i></p>	Slope shall not be more than 15%.
General Assessment Questions	
<p>Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please</p>	No

list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change:	
Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of manures that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links:	No
Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of manures beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so:	No
Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.	Yes. Composting is regulated, and responsibility is shared between ODEQ and ODAFF. ODEQ handles most composting, while ODAFF regulates agricultural composting that has at least 50% or more source material originating from agricultural sources (livestock b

Oregon Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2025
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Oregon Department of Agriculture (ODA)_ Oregon Department of Environmental Quality (DEQ)
Links to regulations	Multiple links including regulations, permits, guidelines, etc._ https://www.oregon.gov/ODA/programs/NaturalResources/Pages/CAFO.aspx
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	State Agriculture
Other regulator info	No other information
Definitions	
How CAFOs are defined or categorized:	<p>(1) (4) "Confined animal feeding operation or CAFO" means:_</p> <p>(a) An operation that engages in the feeding or holding of animals:_</p> <p>(A) In buildings, pens, or lots not sustaining vegetative growth in the normal growing season, for 12 hours or more per day for more than 120 days in a 12-month period, and has animal numbers as referred to in OAR 603-074-0011; or_</p> <p>(B) With a waste water control facility and generates 100 gallons per day or more of liquid manure, process wastewater, or contaminated production area drainage; or_</p> <p>(C) That discharge any wastes into waters of the state._</p> <p>(b) An animal feeding operation that is subject to regulation as a concentrated animal feeding operation pursuant to 40 CFR § 122.23._</p> <p>Concentrated Animal Feeding Operation (CAFO) as defined in Oregon Administrative Rules 603-074-0010(3) and OAR 340-051-0010(2) means: _</p> <p>(a) the concentrated confined feeding or holding of animals or poultry, including but not limited to horse, cattle, sheep, or swine feeding areas, dairy confinement areas, slaughterhouse or shipping terminal holding pens, poultry and egg production facilities and fur farms: _</p> <p>(i) in buildings or in pens or lots where the surface has been prepared with concrete, rock or fibrous material to support animals in wet weather; or _</p> <p>(ii) that have wastewater treatment works; or _</p> <p>(iii) that discharge any wastes to waters of the state; or_</p> <p>(b) an Animal Feeding Operation that is subjected to regulation as a concentrated Animal Feeding Operation pursuant to 40 CFR 122.23._</p> <p>_</p> <p>40 CFR 122.23(b)(4)(i. through xiii.)Large CAFOs: mature dairy cows (>= 700), veal calves (>=1000), cattle (>=1000), swine greater than or equal to 55 lbs. (>=2500), swine less than 55 lbs. (>=10000), horses (>=500), sheep or lambs (>=10000), turkeys (>=55000), chickens, including laying hens or broilers</p>

	<p>w/wet waste system (30000), laying hens w/dry waste system (82000), broiler chickens w/dry waste system (125000), ducks w/other than wet waste system (30000), ducks w/wet waste system (5000). 40 CFR 122.23(c)other animal type (designated by director)._</p> <p>40 CFR 122.23(b)(6)(i)(A through M) Medium CAFOs: mature dairy cows (200-699), veal calves (300-999), cattle (300-999), swine greater than or equal to 55 lbs. (750-2499), swine less than 55 lbs. (3000-9999), horses (150-499), sheep or lambs (3000-9999), turkeys (16500-54999), chickens, including laying hens or broilers w/wet waste system (9000-29999), laying hens w/dry waste system (25000-81999), broiler chickens w/dry waste system (37500-124999), ducks w/other than wet waste system (10000-29999), ducks w/wet waste system (1500-4999), 40 CFR 122.23(c)other animal type (designated by director)._</p> <p>40 CFR 122.23(b)(9)Small CAFOs: mature dairy cows (<200), veal calves (<300), cattle (<300), swine greater than or equal to 55 lbs. (<750), swine less than 55 lbs. (<3000), horses (<150), sheep or lambs (<3000), turkeys (<16500), chickens, including laying hens or broilers w/wet waste system (<9000), laying hens w/dry waste system (<25000), broiler chickens w/dry waste system (<37500), ducks w/other than wet waste system (<10000), ducks w/wet waste system (<1500), 40 CFR 122.23(c)other animal type (designated by director).</p>
<p>How animal units are defined (if used):</p>	<p>“Animal unit” means a unit of measure used to compare animals of different species, equal to 1,000 pounds of live weight.</p>
<p>NPDES permitting or other permitting requirements:</p>	<p>Oregon may issue a NPDES individual permit, NPDES general permit, WPCF individual permit, or WPCF general permit. Information on current permits and permit related materials is available at this Oregon Dept. of Agriculture web page: _</p> <p>https://www.oregon.gov/ODA/programs/NaturalResources/Pages/CAFO.aspx</p> <p>_</p> <p>_</p> <p>NPDES Permit_</p> <p>Any CAFO that discharges to surface waters of the state is required to get an NPDES general permit. This includes concentrated Animal Feeding Operations defined at 40 CFR § 122.23 that discharge to waters of the U.S. _</p> <p>_</p> <p>Water or Waters of the state is defined at Oregon Revised Statutes 468B.005(10). Water- or the waters of the state- include lakes, bays, ponds, impounding reservoirs, springs, wells, rivers, streams, creeks, estuaries, marshes, inlets, canals, the Pacific Ocean within the territorial limits of the State of Oregon and all other bodies of surface or underground waters, natural or artificial, inland or coastal, fresh or salt, public or private (except those private waters which do not combine or effect a junction with natural surface or underground waters), which are wholly or partially within or bordering the state or within its jurisdiction._</p> <p>_</p> <p>Any CAFO designated by the Director is required to get an NPDES general permit. A determination will be made after an on-site visit and consideration is given to: The size of the Animal Feeding Operation and the amount of wastes reaching surface waters; The location of the Animal Feeding Operation relative</p>

	<p>to waters of the United States; The means of conveyance of animal wastes and process wastewaters into waters of the United States; The slope, vegetation, rainfall and other factors affecting the likelihood or frequency of discharge of animal wastes, manure and process wastewaters into waters of the United States; Other relevant factors to determine whether a Animal Feeding Operation is a significant contributor of pollutants per 40 CFR Part 122.23(c)._</p> <p>– Water Pollution Control Facility Permit (WPCF)_ CAFOs that discharge to groundwater and, depending on size, confine animals for more than 120 days and/or have treatment works for wet or dry wastes. _</p> <p>– A CAFO may also require permit coverage as determined at the discretion of the Director. A determination will be made after an on-site visit and consideration is given to the size of the Animal Feeding Operation and the amount of wastes reaching groundwater; the location of the Animal Feeding Operation relative to groundwater and other relevant factors.</p>
Does the state require an NPDES permit for all Large CAFOs?	Yes
Does the state issue individual or general CAFO permits?	Both
Are any other permits required for CAFOs or other large farms?	Yes
Other definitions needed to understand these regulations:	"Compliance" means meeting the requirements of ORS Chapter 468 or 468B and any rule, order, or permit adopted thereunder and relating to the control and prevention of water pollution from a CAFO. A person not subject to regulations of a CAFO are subject to Agricultural Water Quality Management regulations of ORS chapter 568, OAR chapter 603 divisions 90 and 95.
Regulatory Details	
Setbacks: <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some geographical feature</i>	<p>The permit registrant must develop and maintain setbacks or vegetated buffers when manure, litter, or process wastewater application occur adjacent to any surface water, open tile intake structures, sinkholes, well heads, or other conduits to surface water or groundwater. Compliant setbacks, vegetated buffers, or equivalent measures include the following:_</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. 100 ft. setbacks (non-vegetated, non-managed buffers)_ 2. 35 ft. vegetated, managed buffers_ 3. If approved by ODA, variable-width, seasonal setbacks determined by the type of manure, litter, or process wastewater and application method used._ 4. If approved by ODA, a demonstration that a setback or buffer is not necessary or may be reduced in size because implementation of alternative

	<p>conservation practices or field-specific conditions will provide equivalent or better environmental protection than 1-3 above._</p> <p>Set backs may be more restrictive on a case-by-case basis as established in an ODA-approved AWMP.</p>
Are setbacks more restrictive than CFR?	Yes
<p>Timing, weather, or conditional application restrictions:</p> <p><i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather, seasons, or land characteristics (like slope)</i></p>	<p>The permit registrant is allowed to apply manure, litter, or process wastewater to frozen soil when approved procedures are followed and the ODA-approved AWMP addresses such applications. Procedures provide for proper land application that does not result in a discharge to surface or groundwater or cause or contribute to a violation of state water quality standards._</p> <p>–</p> <p>The permit registrant must not apply manure, litter, or process wastewater to saturated soils immediately before or during rainfall events that are expected to result in surface runoff._</p>
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to saturated soils?	Yes
Is there a restriction for land application of manure within floodplains?	No
Is there a restriction for land application of manure related to future rainfall?	Yes
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to frozen or snow-covered ground?	Yes
Are there restrictions to manure applications based on time of year or time of day?	No
Are there restrictions to	No

manure application based on slope?	
Are there any other seasonal, timing, weather, or physical restrictions to manure applications not captured above?	An animal waste management plan may contain other restrictions necessary to be consistent with waste load allocations in an EPA-approved or issued Total Maximum Daily Load for NPDES permit coverage.
Transfer of manure off-site: <i>Requirements related to the transfer of manures to other persons</i>	40 CFR 122.42(e)(4)(iii)The permit holder retains responsibility of the manure, litter, or process wastewater until the transfer or export is completed with the required documentation. A permit holder keeps records on the total amount of manure or wastewater transferred or exported. 40 CFR. 42(e)(3), a permit holder with a large CAFO keeps additional records on recipient of manure, litter, or process wastewater with a nutrient analysis from the previous 12 months prior to the transfer. ODA has full enforcement authority for controlling discharge from agricultural operations. ORS 468B.025 describes the discharge prohibition. ODA CAFO or AGWQ staff would use ORS 468B.025 to regulate environmental issues arising from non-CAFO users of CAFO-generated manure. Also see ORS 568.900 to 568.933 and OAR 603-090-0000 to 603-090-0120.
Are receivers of manure transfers from CAFOs required to follow the same regulations?	Yes
Nutrient or manure management plans: <i>Additional details on the NMP requirement. Note that some of this information may overlap with other sections</i>	To prevent discharges to waters of the state, the permit registrant must apply manure, litter, or process wastewater to land application areas at agronomic rates in accordance with the permit registrant's ODA-approved AWMP. Land application areas include land under the control of the permit registrant, to which manure, litter, or process wastewater from the production area is or may be applied. _ _ An ODA approved animal waste management plan is required for permit coverage. References to the Natural Resources Conservation Service (NRCS) conservation practice standard guidance 590 for Oregon in the NPDES general permit, the applicable requirements of NRCS 590 are stated throughout the permit. ODA accepts and reviews plans from NRCS-certified Comprehensive Nutrient Management Plan (CNMP) writers. AWMPs must demonstrate that a CAFO will achieve an agronomic balance of nutrients land applied with nutrients removed in harvested crops. ODA will typically require an agronomic balance for nitrogen and a phosphorus balance if the NRCS phosphorus index for the soil in land application field(s) indicates that phosphorous is the most limiting nutrient. A phosphorus balance may also be required if a CAFO is within a watershed that is designated by the state as water quality limited for phosphorus.

<p>Do your NMP/MMPS follow, comply with, or based on NRCS Technical Standard 590?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Application rates: <i>State regulations that restrict the rates at which manures are applied and methods needed to determine appropriate rates.</i></p>	<p>Permits require soil tests. Soils from all CAFOs must be tested at least once every 5 years for total nitrogen, nitrate-nitrogen, and total phosphorus. A minimum of 20% of fields that receive manure, litter, or process wastewater applications must be sampled each year. Sampling must be done in accordance to guidance in PNW 570-E, EM 8832-E for post-harvest nitrate-nitrogen._ The NRCS P-Index, USDA/NRCS Oregon Agronomy Technical Note #26, revised October 2008 or equivalent calculation must be completed for all fields or management units that receive manure, litter or process wastewater to determine if N or P is the most limiting nutrient. The maximum nutrient application rate must be calculated for the most limiting nutrient and must account for all other N and P sources. P. index and agronomic rate calculations required by AWMP and Permit. Caps set on a field by field basis. Typical caps may be due to post harvest soil nitrate levels for facilities located in Ground Water Management Areas.</p>
<p>Manure application rates for phosphorus are based on: 1) Phosphorus Index Only 2) Soil Test Phosphorus Only 3) Either PIO or STPO 4) Other</p>	<p>Other</p>
<p>Are there any nutrient “caps” to manure application?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Composition testing: <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on manures before application</i></p>	<p>Manure from Large CAFOs must be sampled for total nitrogen and total phosphorus annually, according to guidance in PNW 0533 and PNW 505. Other CAFOs can use actual data or book values established from reference sources like Oregon Animal Waste Management program.</p>
<p>Does your state require testing of</p>	<p>No</p>

manure for anything beyond nutrients, such as metals, pathogens, antibiotics, etc.?	
Other land application highlights: <i>Additional restrictions for land application of manures</i>	No other information
Other regulatory details: <i>Additional information on the regulation of land application of manures</i>	No other information
General Assessment Questions	
Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change:	Yes, Senate Bill 85 requires the development and implementation of a Nutrient Application Permit for those who are not on a CAFO permit that land apply CAFO nutrients within a designated Ground Water Management Area.
Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of manures that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links:	Yes
Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land	No

<p>application of manures beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so:</p>	
<p>Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.</p>	<p>No other information</p>

Pennsylvania	
Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2025
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Pennsylvania Department of Environmental Protection (PADEP)
Links to regulations	<p>CHAPTER 92a. NATIONAL POLLUTANT_ DISCHARGE ELIMINATION SYSTEM_ PERMITTING, MONITORING AND COMPLIANCE_ https://www.pacode.com/secure/data/025/chapter92a/chap92atoc.html</p> <p>–</p> <p>–</p> <p>TITLE 25 ENVIRONMENTAL PROTECTION_ 25 PA Chapter 83 Subchapter D: NUTRIENT MANAGEMENT_ https://www.pacode.com/secure/data/025/chapter83/subchapDtoc.html</p> <p>–</p> <p>–</p> <p>TITLE 25 ENVIRONMENTAL PROTECTION_ 25 PA Chapter 91.36: POLLUTION CONTROL AND PREVENTION AT AGRICULTURAL OPERTATIONS_ https://www.pacode.com/secure/data/025/chapter91/s91.36.html</p>
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	More than one agency
Other regulator info	No other information
Definitions	
How CAFOs are defined or categorized:	<p>CAO-”Concentrated animal operation-”Agricultural operations with eight or more animal equivalent units where the animal density exceeds two AEUs per acre on an annualized basis. _</p> <p>CAFO-”Concentrated Animal Feeding Operation” - A CAO with greater than 300 AEUs, any agricultural operation with greater than 1,000 AEUs, or any agricultural operation defined as a large CAFO under 40 CFR 122.23(b)(4) (relating to concentrated Animal Feeding Operations (applicable to State NPDES programs, see § 123.25).</p>
How animal units are defined (if used):	<p>AEU-”Animal Equivalent Unit-”One thousand pounds live weight of livestock or poultry animals, regardless of the actual number of individual animals comprising the unit, as defined in 3 Pa.C.S. § 503 (relating to definitions) annualized to account for the times of the year that the animals are on the operation.</p>
NPDES permitting or other permitting requirements:	<p>Agricultural operations meeting the definition of a CAFO in Pennsylvania are required to obtain National Pollutant Discharge Elimination System (NPDES) permit coverage. DEP is delegated to administer the federal NPDES program under an agreement with EPA. Under EPA regulations, the production area of a CAFO (i.e., animal confinement areas, manure storage areas, raw material storage areas, and waste containment areas) is considered a point source. A discharge of pollutants from the</p>

	<p>production area is not authorized except during heavy precipitation events called "design storm events." The magnitude of a design storm event in which a discharge may be authorized depends on the type of animals maintained on a CAFO, and ranges from the 25-year/24-hour to the 100-year/24-hour storm._</p> <p>A permittee may qualify for coverage under a general permit depending on the protection status of the receiving waters and other applicable state conditions._</p> <p>PA Water Quality Management Permit is required for manure storage construction where the manure storage has a capacity equal to or greater than 2.5 million gallons, or the manure storage has a capacity between 1 and 2.5 million gallons and the nearest downgradient stream is Special Protection or determined to be impaired due to nutrients coming from agricultural activities.</p>
Does the state require an NPDES permit for all Large CAFOs?	Yes
Does the state issue individual or general CAFO permits?	Both
Are any other permits required for CAFOs or other large farms?	Yes
Other definitions needed to understand these regulations:	No other information
Regulatory Details	
<p>Setbacks: <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some geographical feature</i></p>	<p>Setbacks and buffers. Manure may not be mechanically applied in the following situations:_</p> <p>(1) Within 100 feet of the top of the bank of a perennial or intermittent stream with a defined bed and bank, a lake or a pond, unless a permanent vegetated buffer of at least 35 feet in width is used, to prevent manure runoff into the stream, lake or pond._</p> <p>(2) Within 100 feet of an existing open sinkhole unless a permanent vegetated buffer of at least 35 feet in width is used._</p> <p>(3) Within 100 feet of active private drinking water sources such as wells and springs._</p> <p>(4) Within 100 feet of an active public drinking water source, unless other State or Federal laws or regulations require a greater isolation distance.</p>
Are setbacks more restrictive than CFR?	Yes
<p>Timing, weather, or conditional application restrictions: <i>State regulations that restrict land</i></p>	<p>Winter application. For winter application of manure, the following apply:_</p> <p>(1) The application procedures shall be described in the plan._</p> <p>(2) The plan must list the following:_</p> <p>(i) The crop management units where winter application is planned or restricted._</p> <p>(ii) The application procedures that will be utilized at those crop</p>

<p><i>application under certain weather, seasons, or land characteristics (like slope)</i></p>	<p>management units._ (iii) The field conditions that must exist for winter application._ (3) Setbacks listed in the setbacks section above shall be implemented. In addition, during winter manure may not be mechanically applied in the following situations:_ (i) Within 100 feet of an above-ground inlet to an agricultural drainage system, if surface flow is toward the aboveground inlet._ (ii) Within 100 feet of a wetland that is identified on the National Wetlands Inventory Maps, if the following are met:_ (A) The wetland is within the 100-year floodplain of an Exceptional Value stream segment._ (B) Surface flow is toward the wetland._ (4) Fields where manure will be applied in winter must have at least 25% residue, or an established cover crop. The BMPs contained in the Pennsylvania Technical Guide may be used to satisfy this requirement. Other practices shall be approved by the Commission._ (5) For CAOs and CAFOs, if manure from these operations is to be applied in the winter, the PA Winter Manure Application Matrix must be completed on the proposed fields and approved by the reviewing authority, and the winter matrix must indicated that the field is either rated good-<input type="checkbox"/> or fair-<input type="checkbox"/> in order for it to be planned for winter application. _ (6) Manure application limitations based on slope.</p>
<p>Is there a restriction for land application of manure to saturated soils?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Is there a restriction for land application of manure within floodplains?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Is there a restriction for land application of manure related to future rainfall?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Is there a restriction for land application of manure to frozen or snow-covered ground?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Are there restrictions to manure applications based on time of year or time of day?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Are there restrictions to manure application based on slope?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Are there any other seasonal, timing,</p>	<p>No</p>

<p>weather, or physical restrictions to manure applications not captured above?</p>	
<p>Transfer of manure off-site: <i>Requirements related to the transfer of manures to other persons</i></p>	<p>Recordkeeping for manure exports. Recordkeeping requirements apply to manure exported off of the NMP operation- For CAOs and CAFOs, a manure export sheet shall be used for all manure transfers. A Nutrient Balance Sheet or manure management plan is required to be developed for all farms receiving exported manure. Manure receivers have similar manure application rate, timing and setback restrictions imposed on the importing sites as are required on the CAFO operation. The manure application rate calculation process is streamlined for importing operations compared to the planning requirements for manure applied on the CAFO but both N and P are addressed on the importing sites as well as on the CAFO itself._</p>
<p>Are receivers of manure transfers from CAFOs required to follow the same regulations?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Nutrient or manure management plans: <i>Additional details on the NMP requirement. Note that some of this information may overlap with other sections</i></p>	<p>All farms that generate or utilize manure in PA are required to have, and to be implementing, a current and compliant Nutrient Management Plan or Manure Management Plan. This is an obligation pertains to not just CAOs and CAFOs, but all farms generating or using manure. NPDES permits for each CAFO must include, but are not limited to, conditions requiring compliance with the Nutrient Management Plan, the Preparedness, Prevention and Contingency Plan and the Erosion and Sediment Control Plan._ The technical standard for CAOs and CAFOs follows directly along the lines of the 590 standard. For smaller farms that generate and utilize manure, the planning process is streamlined to address nitrogen and phosphorous losses allowing for a more simplified planning process.</p>
<p>Do your NMP/MMPS follow, comply with, or based on NRCS Technical Standard 590?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Application rates: <i>State regulations that restrict the rates at which manures are applied and methods needed to determine appropriate rates.</i></p>	<p>For deterring nutrient application rates on fields receiving manure generated at a CAO or CAFO, the Pa Phosphorus index is required to be used, along with an annual nitrogen balancing limitation based on realistic expected crop yields. _ _ PA Phosphorus Index-_ (i) The field evaluation methodology developed specifically for this Commonwealth and approved by the Commission, which combines indicators of phosphorus sources and phosphorus transport, to identify areas that have a high vulnerability or risk of phosphorus loss to surface</p>

waters. _

(ii) This evaluation methodology provides direction on BMPs to address the land application of phosphorus-containing nutrient sources, to protect water quality. _

The PA P-Index does disallow any phosphorus applications to a field once it is found to have an index level of greater than 100. _

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Results of current soil test analysis are required to be used in the development of the PA Phosphorus index. Soil tests are used to assess the level of soil characteristics such as phosphorus, potassium and pH, analyzed using standard industry methods such as those described in the current Pennsylvania Agronomy Guide. _

When developing the initial plan, soil tests shall be conducted for each crop management unit on the operation, to determine the level of phosphorus (as P), potassium (as K), and soil pH, as follows: _

The soil test procedures used must provide accurate test results. The procedures recommended by the Pennsylvania State University and published in Recommended Soil Testing Procedures for the Northeastern United States, Bulletin #493, published by the University of Delaware, may be used to meet this requirement. Other procedures shall be approved by the Commission. _

Soil tests conducted within the previous 3 years prior to submitting the initial plan are acceptable. _

The plan must include a summary of the results of the soil test analyses for each crop management unit showing the following: (i) Soil test levels for phosphorus and potassium as reported by the laboratory (ii) Soil test levels for phosphorus (as P) in parts-per-million (PPM) and potassium (as K) in PPM, after conversion from the test results from the laboratory, as needed. (iii) Soil test levels for pH. (iv) The date of the soil tests and the name of the lab performing the tests. _

After the approval of the initial plan, soil tests are required for each crop management unit at least every 3 years from the date of the last test. Based on the soil tests taken for plan development, the plan must include recommendations for the amount of nitrogen (as total N), phosphorus (as P₂O₅) and potassium (as K₂O) necessary for realistic expected crop yields. _

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For determining nitrogen and phosphorus need of crops, a realistic crop yield is used for the basis of that determination. When determining expected crop yields, expected crop yields shall be based on documented yield levels achieved for the operation. Expected crop yields higher than historically achieved may be used if sufficient justification is approved by the Commission or delegated conservation district for the use of the higher yields. _

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For non-CAO/non-CAFO farms using manure that did not come from a CAO or CAFO, their manure management planning requirements are the

	<p>same as describe above for addressing nitrogen, but their phosphorus considerations for plan development are streamlined to allow for an easier process for considering phosphorus risk and therefore phosphorus application rates on these farms. Phosphorus risk is assessed using either the PA P-Index as is used for the CAO or CAFO plans, or a simplified method using a soil test threshold can be used to assess farms for the risk of phosphorus loss which is used for determining manure application rates. For those using the soil test threshold process, if the soil test P level is over 200 ppm using the Mehlich-3 testing procedure, then the farm cannot apply more Phosphorus than what that year's crop will remove. For these smaller farms, if a soil test is not used, the farm is assumed to have a high soil test level for phosphorus and manure and fertilizer application rates are limited to phosphorus removal rates for the given crop. _</p> <p>_</p> <p>PIND for CAO and CAFO operations._</p> <p>EITH for nonCAO/non-CAFO farms using manure not coming from a CAO or CAFO the farm can either use the PA P-Index or it can limit P applications based on the soil test threshold process described above.</p>
<p>Manure application rates for phosphorus are based on:</p> <p>1) <i>Phosphorus Index Only</i></p> <p>2) <i>Soil Test Phosphorus Only</i></p> <p>3) <i>Either PIO or STPO</i></p> <p>4) <i>Other</i></p>	<p>Other</p>
<p>Are there any nutrient “caps” to manure application?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Composition testing: <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on manures before application</i></p>	<p>For CAO and CAFO operations, they must test the nutrient content of manure annually as follows: (i) Analytical manure testing results shall be used in the development of the plan. These manure tests must include an analysis of the percent solids, total nitrogen (as N), ammonium nitrogen (as NH₄-N), total phosphate (as P₂O₅) and total potash (as K₂O), for each manure group generated on the operation, and these analytical results shall be recorded in the plan. (ii) These manure analyses shall be performed using manure sampling and chemical analysis methods which accurately represent the contents of the manure. Methods described in the Pennsylvania Agronomy Guide may be used to meet this requirement. Other methods shall be approved by the Commission._</p> <p>Samples and chemical analysis of the manure generated on the operation shall be obtained within 1 year of implementation of the approved plan, and the requirements of § 83.371 (relating to plan amendments) shall be followed as applicable._</p> <p>Testing of manure groups may be consolidated when two or more manure groups on the same operation are produced by the same animal type and</p>

	are managed in a similar manner.
Does your state require testing of manure for anything beyond nutrients, such as metals, pathogens, antibiotics, etc.?	Yes
Other land application highlights: <i>Additional restrictions for land application of manures</i>	Manure may not be applied at rates higher than 9,000 gallons per acre for any individual application event. For winter, that limitation is reduced to 5,000 gallons per acre.
Other regulatory details: <i>Additional information on the regulation of land application of manures</i>	Yes. PA has the PA Commercial Manure Hauler and Broker Certification Law which requires anyone who hauls or applies manure, to take the required training and pass the relevant test to be certified to haul or apply manure commercially in PA. These certifi
General Assessment Questions	
Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change:	No
Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of manures that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links:	No
Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of manures beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so:	No

<p>Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.</p>	<p>No other information</p>
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Rhode Island	
Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2025
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Rhode Island Department of Environmental Management (DEM) Bureau of Environmental
Links to regulations	DEM RIPDES: http://www.dem.ri.gov/programs/water/permits/ripdes/ http://sos.ri.gov/documents/archives/regdocs/released/pdf/DEM/DEM_2435.pdf
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Environmental
Other regulator info	Currently no CAFOs in this state as of 2017. CAFOs are only regulated in Rule 27.
Definitions	
How CAFOs are defined or categorized:	<p>"Concentrated Animal Feeding Operation" means an Animal Feeding Operation which meets the criteria in Appendix B, or which the Department designates under Rule 27. _</p> <p>Rule 27. CONCENTRATED ANIMAL FEEDING OPERATIONS _</p> <p>(a) Permit requirement. "Concentrated Animal Feeding Operations" (as defined in Rule 3) are point sources subject to the RIPDES permit program. _</p> <p>(b) Case-by-case designation of concentrated Animal Feeding Operations. _</p> <p>(1) The Department may designate any Animal Feeding Operation as a concentrated Animal Feeding Operation upon determining that it is a significant contributor of pollution to the waters of the State. In making this designation the Department shall consider the following factors: _</p> <p>(i) The size of the Animal Feeding Operation and the amount of wastes reaching the waters of the State; _</p> <p>(ii) The location of the Animal Feeding Operation relative to waters of the State; _</p> <p>(iii) The means of conveyance of animal wastes and process wastewaters into waters of the State; _</p> <p>(iv) The slope, vegetation, rainfall, and other factors affecting the likelihood or frequency of discharge of animal waste and process wastewaters into waters of the State; and _</p> <p>(v) Other relevant factors. _</p> <p>(2) No Animal Feeding Operation with less than the numbers of animals set forth in Appendix B shall be designated as a concentrated Animal Feeding Operation unless: _</p> <p>(i) Pollutants are discharged into waters of the State through a manmade ditch, flushing system, or other similar manmade device; or _</p> <p>(ii) Pollutants are discharged directly into waters of the State which originate outside of the facility and pass over, across, or through the facility or otherwise come into direct contact with the animals confined in the operation. _</p>

	<p>(3) A permit application shall not be required from a concentrated Animal Feeding Operation designated under this paragraph until the Department has conducted an on-site inspection of the operation and determined that the operation should and could be regulated under the permit program. _</p> <p>APPENDIX B CRITERIA FOR DETERMINING A CONCENTRATED ANIMAL FEEDING OPERATION _</p> <p>An Animal Feeding Operation is a concentrated Animal Feeding Operation for purposes of Rule 27 if either of the following criteria are met. _</p> <p>a) More than the numbers of animals specified in any of the following categories are confined: _</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) 1,000 slaughter and feeder cattle; _ 2) 700 mature dairy cattle (whether milked or dry cows); _ 3) 2,500 swine each weighing over 25 kilograms (approximately 55 pounds); _ 4) 500 horses; _ 5) 10,000 sheep or lambs; _ 6) 55,000 turkeys; _ 7) 100,000 laying hens or broilers (if the facility has continuous overflow watering); _ 8) 30,000 laying hens or broilers (if the facility has a liquid manure handling system); _ 9) 5,000 ducks; or _ 10) 1,000 animal units; or _ <p>b) More than the following number and types of animals are confined: _</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) 300 slaughter or feeder cattle; _ 2) 200 mature dairy cattle (whether milked or dry cows); _ 3) 750 swine each weighing over 25 kilograms (approximately 55 pounds); _ 4) 150 horses; _ 5) 3,000 sheep or lambs; _ 6) 14,500 turkeys; _ 7) 30,000 laying hens or broilers (if the facility has continuous overflow watering); _ 8) 9,000 laying hens or broilers (if the facility has a liquid manure handling system); _ 9) 1,500 ducks; or _ 10) 300 animal units; _ <p>and either one of the following conditions are met: pollutants are discharged into navigable waters through a manmade ditch, flushing system or other similar manmade device; or pollutants are discharged directly into waters of the United States which originate outside of and pass-over, across, or through the facility or otherwise come into direct contact with the animals confined in the operation. Provided, however, that no Animal Feeding Operation is a concentrated Animal Feeding Operation as defined above if such Animal Feeding Operation discharges only in the event of a 25-year, 24-hour storm event.</p>
<p>How animal units are defined (if used):</p>	<p>The term "animal unit" means a unit of measurement for any Animal Feeding Operation calculated by adding the following numbers: the number of slaughter and feeder cattle multiplied by 1.0, plus the number of mature dairy cattle multiplied by 1.4, plus the number of swine weighing over 25 kilograms (approximately 55 pounds) multiplied by 0.4, plus the number of sheep</p>

	multiplied by 0.1, plus the number of horses multiplied by 2.0." means a unit of measurement for any Animal Feeding Operation calculated by adding the following numbers: the number of slaughter and feeder cattle multiplied by 1.0, plus the number of mature dairy cattle multiplied by 1.4, plus the number of swine weighing over 25 kilograms (approximately 55 pounds) multiplied by 0.4, plus the number of sheep multiplied by 0.1, plus the number of horses multiplied by 2.0.
NPDES permitting or other permitting requirements:	Refer to 40 CFR
Does the state require an NPDES permit for all Large CAFOs?	Undetermined
Does the state issue individual or general CAFO permits?	Undetermined
Are any other permits required for CAFOs or other large farms?	Undetermined
Other definitions needed to understand these regulations:	No other information
Regulatory Details	
Setbacks: <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some geographical feature</i>	Refer to 40 CFR
Are setbacks more	No

restrictive than CFR?	
Timing, weather, or conditional application restrictions: <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather, seasons, or land characteristics (like slope)</i>	None
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to saturated soils?	No
Is there a restriction for land application of manure within floodplains?	No
Is there a restriction for land application of manure related to future rainfall?	No
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to frozen or snow-covered ground?	No
Are there restrictions to manure	No

applications based on time of year or time of day?	
Are there restrictions to manure application based on slope?	No
Are there any other seasonal, timing, weather, or physical restrictions to manure applications not captured above?	No
Transfer of manure off-site: <i>Requirements related to the transfer of manures to other persons</i>	Refer to 40 CFR
Are receivers of manure transfers from CAFOs required to follow the same regulations?	No
Nutrient or manure management plans: <i>Additional details on the NMP requirement. Note that some of this information may overlap with other sections</i>	Refer to 40 CFR

<p>Do your NMP/MMPS follow, comply with, or based on NRCS Technical Standard 590?</p>	<p>Not Applicable</p>
<p>Application rates: <i>State regulations that restrict the rates at which manures are applied and methods needed to determine appropriate rates.</i></p>	<p>Refer to 40 CFR</p>
<p>Manure application rates for phosphorus are based on: 1) <i>Phosphorus Index Only</i> 2) <i>Soil Test Phosphorus Only</i> 3) <i>Either PIO or STPO</i> 4) <i>Other</i></p>	<p>No method</p>
<p>Are there any nutrient “caps” to manure application?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Composition testing: <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on manures before application</i></p>	<p>Refer to 40 CFR</p>

<p>Does your state require testing of manure for anything beyond nutrients, such as metals, pathogens, antibiotics, etc.?</p>	<p>Not Applicable</p>
<p>Other land application highlights: <i>Additional restrictions for land application of manures</i></p>	<p>No other information</p>
<p>Other regulatory details: <i>Additional information on the regulation of land application of manures</i></p>	<p>No other information</p>
<p>General Assessment Questions</p>	
<p>Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change:</p>	<p>Undetermined</p>
<p>Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of</p>	<p>No</p>

<p>manures that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links:</p>	
<p>Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of manures beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so:</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.</p>	<p>No other information</p>

South Carolina	
Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2019
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	The South Carolina Department of Health and Environmental Control (SC DHEC)
Links to regulations	<p>SC Reg. 61-9 Water Pollution Control Permits. 61-9.122. The National Pollutant Discharge Elimination System_ https://www.scstatehouse.gov/coderegs/Chapter%2061-1%20through%2061-17.pdf _</p> <p>– SC Reg. 61-43 Part 50 contains definitions, Part 100 contains regulations for swine facilities, and Part 200 deals with regulations for all other animal facilities._ https://www.scstatehouse.gov/coderegs/Chapter%2061-18%20through%2061-58.17.pdf _</p> <p>– DHEC state summary on CAFOs:_ https://www.scdhec.gov/environment/WaterQuality/Agriculture/Permits/ConcentratedAnimalFeedOperations/ _</p> <p>– DHEC summary on New Compliance Requirements for SC DHEC Stormwater Permits for Confined Agricultural Animal Facilities:_ https://www.scdhec.gov/Environment/docs/agswPermits.pdf _ https://www.scdhec.gov/sites/default/files/media/document/R.61-43.pdf</p>
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Environmental
Other regulator info	South Carolina only has Animal Facility Operations (AFO) and all require a permit under R.61-43. South Carolina does not have any CAFOs according to the definition because they do not allow any animal facility to discharge.
Definitions	
How CAFOs are defined or categorized:	"Animal facility" means an agricultural facility where animals are confined and fed or maintained for a total of forty-five days or more in a twelve-month period and crops, vegetative, forage growth, or post harvest residues are not sustained in the normal growing season over any portion of the lot or facility. Structures used for the storage of animal manure and other animal by-products from animals in the operation also are part of the animal facility. Two or more animal facilities under common ownership or management are considered to be a single animal facility if they are

	<p>adjacent or utilize a common system for animal manure storage. _</p> <p>"Commercial Facility" means an animal facility that produces animals or animal by-products for commercial sale, boards animals, rents animals, or provides a service utilizing the animals for a fee. The facility is considered commercial if the owner earned at least one thousand dollars gross farm income in at least three of the first five years. _</p> <p>"Large Animal Facility" means an animal facility (excluding swine facilities) that has a capacity for more than 500,000 pounds of normal production animal live weight at any one time. _</p> <p>"Small Animal Facility" means an animal facility (other than swine) that has a capacity for 500,000 pounds of normal production animal live weight or less at any one time._</p> <p>Small Swine Facilities (500,000 pounds or less of normal production live weight). _</p> <p>Large Swine Facilities (greater than 500,000 pounds normal production live weight).</p>
<p>How animal units are defined (if used):</p>	<p>Not used</p>
<p>NPDES permitting or other permitting requirements:</p>	<p>South Carolina offers a National Pollutant Discharge Elimination System (NPDES) permit but South Carolina only has Animal Facility Operations (AFO) and all require a permit under R.61-43. South Carolina does not have any CAFOs according to the definition because they do not allow any animal facility to discharge. _</p> <p>* Under Regulation 61-43 all Agricultural permits are No Discharge Permits, they will not be allowed to discharge as long as this regulation is written this way._</p> <p>* 100.20 Permits and Compliance Period. C. Permits issued under this regulation are no-discharge permits._</p> <p>* 200.20 Permits and Compliance Period. B. Permits issued under this regulation are no-discharge permits</p>
<p>Does the state require an NPDES permit for all Large CAFOs?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Does the state issue individual or general CAFO permits?</p>	<p>Not Applicable</p>
<p>Are any other permits required for CAFOs</p>	<p>Not Applicable</p>

or other large farms?	
Other definitions needed to understand these regulations :	No other information
Regulatory Details	
Setbacks: <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some geographic al feature</i>	<p>Siting Requirements applicable to all manure utilization areas_</p> <p>Non-Swine:_</p> <p>Wells (Human and Animal Drinking Water) 100 ft_</p> <p>Ditches located down-slope 50 ft_</p> <p>Property lines (unless waived with consent of property owner) 300 ft_</p> <p>Water of the State with application method - Spray irrigation 100 ft_</p> <p>Water of the State with application method -“ Incorporation 75 ft_</p> <p>Water of the State with application method -“ Injection 50 ft_</p> <p>Small swine facilities (500,000 pounds or less normal production live weight):_</p> <p>a. The minimum separation distance in feet required between a manure utilization area and a residence is 300 feet. If there are no residences within 300 feet of the manure utilization area, manure can be applied up to the property line. The 300-foot setback may be waived with the consent of the owner of the residence. If the application method is injection or immediate incorporation, manure may be applied up to the property line. The setbacks are imposed at the time of application. The Department may impose these setbacks on previously approved sites to address problems on a case-by-case basis._</p> <p>b. The minimum separation distance in feet required between a manure utilization area and waters of the State (not including ephemeral and intermittent streams), ditches, and swales that drain directly into waters of the State (not including ephemeral and intermittent streams) is 100 feet._</p> <p>c. The minimum separation distance in feet required between a manure utilization area and ephemeral and intermittent streams is 100 feet when spray application is the application method, 75 feet when incorporation is the application method, and 50 feet when injection is the application method. When incorporation is accomplished within twenty-four hours of the initial application, the distance can be reduced to 50 feet._</p> <p>d. The minimum separation distance in feet required between a manure utilization area and ditches and swales, that drain directly into ephemeral and intermittent streams is 50 feet._</p> <p>e. The minimum separation distance in feet required between a manure utilization area and a public and private drinking water well is 200 feet._</p> <p>Large swine facilities with less than 1,000,000 pounds normal production live weight:_</p> <p>a. The minimum separation distance in feet required between a manure utilization area and a residence is 300 feet. If there are no residences within 300 feet of the manure utilization area, manure can be applied up to the property line. The 300-foot</p>

setback may be waived with the consent of the owner of the residence. If the application method is injection or immediate incorporation, manure may be applied up to the property line. The setbacks are imposed at the time of application. The Department may impose these setbacks on previously approved sites to address problems on a case-by-case basis._

b. The minimum separation distance in feet required between a manure utilization area and waters of the State (not including ephemeral and intermittent streams), ditches, and swales that drain directly into waters of the State (not including ephemeral and intermittent streams) is 100 feet._

c. The minimum separation distance in feet required between a manure utilization area and ephemeral and intermittent streams is 100 feet when spray application is the application method, 75 feet when incorporation is the application method, and 50 feet when injection is the application method. When incorporation is accomplished within twenty-four hours of the initial application, the distance can be reduced to 50 feet._

d. The minimum separation distance in feet required between a manure utilization area and ditches and swales that drain directly into ephemeral and intermittent streams is 50 feet._

e. The minimum separation distance in feet required between a manure utilization area and a public and private drinking water well is 200 feet._

Large swine facilities with 1,000,000 pounds or more normal production live weight:_

a. The minimum separation distance in feet required between a manure utilization area and real property owned by another person is 200 feet from the property lines._

b. The minimum separation distance in feet required between a manure utilization area and an occupied residence is 750 feet (excluding the applicant's residence). _

c. The minimum separation distance in feet required between a manure utilization area and waters of the State (not including ephemeral and intermittent streams), ditches, and swales is 150 feet._

d. The minimum separation distance in feet required between a manure utilization area and a public and private drinking water well is 200 feet._

e. The minimum separation distance in feet required between a manure utilization area and ephemeral and intermittent streams is 100 feet._

Water (pond) that is completely surrounded by land owned by the applicant and has no connection to surface water is excluded from the setback requirements outlined above._

Additional application buffer setbacks:_

H. Setback limits given in this part are minimum siting requirements (with exception to those that are not labeled as minimum requirements, which are absolutes). On a case-by-case basis the Department may require additional separation distances applicable to swine facilities. The Department shall evaluate the proposed site including, but not limited to, the following factors when determining if additional distances are necessary:_

1. Proximity to 100-year floodplain;_

2. Geography and soil types on the site;_

3. Location in a watershed;_

4. Classification or impairment of adjacent waters;_

5. Proximity to a State Designated Focus Area; Outstanding Resource Water; Heritage Corridor; Historic Preservation District; State Approved Source Water Protection

	<p>Area; state or national park or forest; state or federal research area; and privately-owned wildlife refuge, park, or trust property;_</p> <p>6. Proximity to other known point source discharges and potential nonpoint sources_</p> <p>7. Slope of the land;_</p> <p>8. Swine manure application method and aerosols;_</p> <p>9. Runoff prevention;_</p> <p>10. Adjacent groundwater usage_</p> <p>11. Down-wind receptors; and_</p> <p>12. Aquifer vulnerability._</p> <p>_</p> <p>Bill H. 3929 was recently passed in the legislature. This bill has eliminated the requirements of the Department to evaluate for additional distances as long as the setback requirements are met.</p>
<p>Are setbacks more restrictive than CFR?</p>	<p>Undetermined</p>
<p>Timing, weather, or conditional application restrictions :</p> <p><i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather, seasons, or land characteristics (like slope)</i></p>	<p>* Swine manure and other swine by-products shall not be applied to land that is saturated from recent precipitation, flooded, frozen, or snow-covered. _</p> <p>* Swine manure and other swine by-products shall not be applied during inclement weather or when a significant rain event is forecasted to occur within 48 hours, unless approved by the Department in an emergency situation_</p> <p>* Manure (solid or liquid) shall only be applied when weather and soil conditions are favorable and when prevailing winds are blowing away from nearby dwellings. Animal manure should not be applied to land when the soil is saturated, flooded, during rain events, or when a significant rain event is forecasted to occur within 48 hours, unless otherwise approved by the Department in an emergency situation._</p> <p>* Manure shall not be spread in the floodplain if there is danger of a major runoff event, unless the manure is incorporated during application or immediately after application._</p> <p>* Animal manure and other animal by-products shall not be applied to land that is saturated from recent precipitation, flooded, frozen, or snow-covered. _</p> <p>* Animal manure and other animal byproducts shall not be applied during inclement weather or when a significant rain event is forecasted to occur within 48 hours.</p>
<p>Is there a restriction for land application of manure to saturated soils?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Is there a restriction</p>	<p>Yes</p>

for land application of manure within floodplains ?	
Is there a restriction for land application of manure related to future rainfall?	Yes
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to frozen or snow-covered ground?	Yes
Are there restrictions to manure applications based on time of year or time of day?	Yes
Are there restrictions to manure application based on slope?	Yes
Are there any other seasonal, timing, weather, or physical restrictions to manure applications not	Yes, regulations on wind.

<p>captured above?</p>	
<p>Transfer of manure off-site: <i>Requirements related to the transfer of manures to other persons</i></p>	<p>A producer who supplies swine manure and other swine by-products to another person for land application shall provide the person who will land apply the manure and other swine byproducts with the concentration of plant available nitrogen and the concentration of all other constituents listed in the permit. The producer shall also supply the person who will land apply the manure with a copy of the crop management plan included in their Animal Facility Management Plan or a copy of the Land Application brochure approved by the Department which outlines the land application requirements and responsibility for proper management of animal manure._</p> <p>All persons who accept manure from a producer, regardless of whether the land is included in the waste management plan, are responsible for land applying the manure in accordance with these requirements. The Department may require the person(s) land applying the manure to correct any problems that result from the application of manure._</p> <p>Producers who contract to transfer the swine manure and other swine by-products produced at their facility to a manure broker shall modify their existing Animal Facility Management Plan if they discontinue using the designated broker or if the manure broker goes out of the manure brokering business.</p>
<p>Are receivers of manure transfers from CAFOs required to follow the same regulations ?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Nutrient or manure management plans: <i>Additional details on the NMP requirement. Note that some of this information may overlap with other sections</i></p>	<p>One of the requirements of the CAFO permitting process in South Carolina is to submit an Animal Facility Management Plan (AFMP). The plan must be prepared by qualified NRCS personnel or a South Carolina registered professional engineer. The land application component of the plan must at a minimum include the amount of animal manure and other animal by-products generated per year as well as a description of the storage and storage capacity of the lagoon, treatment system, or storage pond that will be used to hold the manure. It must also include the concentration of constituents in the manure. Additionally, a description of the facility and manure utilization area maps should include topography and drainage characteristics, adjacent land usage, all known water supply wells and surface water bodies. Facilities with 10,000 pounds of normal production animal live weight or less that do not have a lagoon, storage pond, or other treatment system must have and implement an AFMP, however, it does not need to be submitted to DHEC. Facilities with greater production are required to submit the plan to DHEC._</p> <p>–</p> <p>A crop management plan should also be included and should include the time of year of the animal manure application and how it relates to crop type, crop planting, and harvesting schedule for all manure utilization areas. Additionally, a Comprehensive</p>

	<p>Nutrient Management Plan is required for manure spreading and should establish an application rate for each manure utilization area based on the agronomic rate of the specific crops being grown, and the manure and other animal by-products impact on the environment. Soil sampling protocols state that sampling should be conducted for each field prior to manure application. The state requires that an evaluation be completed in accordance with the NRCS-Cropping Practices Surveys (CPS) to determine the suitability for application and the limiting nutrient (nitrogen or phosphorus)._</p> <p>–</p> <p>Part 50. "Animal Facility Management Plan" means a plan prepared by the United States Department of Agriculture's Natural Resources Conservation Service or a professional engineer detailing the management, handling, treatment, storage, or utilization of manure generated in an animal facility. This plan shall include facility management details and a detailed map of each manure utilization area showing all buffer zones and setbacks, a description of the land use, the crops grown on the site, the timing for application of swine manure to the land and a land use agreement if the site is not owned by the permittee.</p>
<p>Do your NMP/MMP S follow, comply with, or based on NRCS Technical Standard 590?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Application rates: <i>State regulations that restrict the rates at which manures are applied and methods needed to determine appropriate rates.</i></p>	<p>A soil monitoring plan shall be developed for all manure utilization areas, see Section 100.100 (Manure Utilization Area Requirements) for more detailed information._</p> <p>–</p> <p>Soil sampling shall be conducted for each field prior to manure application to determine the appropriate application rate. Each field should be sampled at least once per year. If manure application frequency shall be less than once per year, then at least one soil sample shall be taken prior to returning to that field for land application. All new manure utilization areas shall be evaluated using the NRCS-CPS to determine the suitability for application and the limiting nutrient(nitrogen or phosphorus). However, fields that are high in phosphorus may also be required to incorporate additional runoff control or soil conservation features as directed by the Department._</p> <p>–</p> <p>Additional soil sampling to greater depths may be required by the Department on a case-by-case basis to ensure there is no potential for groundwater contamination. The permit shall give the appropriate depth and frequency for all soil sampling._</p> <p>–</p> <p>Application Rates. The Department shall approve an Animal Facility Management Plan that establishes an application rate for each manure utilization area based on the agronomic application rate of the specific crop(s) being grown. Other factors considered are the manure and other swine byproducts impact on the environment,</p>

animals, and people living in the vicinity. The application rate shall also be based on the limiting constituent (either a nutrient or other constituent as given in item 100.100.B). In developing annual constituent loading rates and cumulative constituent loading rates, the Department shall consider:

1. Soil type;
2. Type of vegetation growing in land-applied area;
3. Proximity to 100-year floodplain;
4. Location in watershed;
5. Nutrient sensitivity of receiving land and waters;
6. Soil nutrient testing in conjunction with soil productivity information;
7. Nutrient, copper, zinc, and constituent content of the manure and other swine by-products being applied;
8. Proximity to a State Designated Focus Area; Outstanding Resource Water; Heritage Corridor; Historic Preservation District; State Approved Source Water Protection Area; state or national park or forest; state or federal research area; and privately-owned wildlife refuge, park, or trust property;
9. Proximity to other point and nonpoint sources;
10. Slope of land;
11. Distance to water table or groundwater aquifer;
12. Timing of manure application to coincide with vegetative cover growth cycle;
13. Timing of harvest of vegetative cover;
14. Hydraulic loading limitations;
15. Soil assimilative capacity;
16. Type of vegetative cover and its nutrient uptake ability;
17. Method of land application; and
18. Aquifer vulnerability.

Manure Utilization Area Requirements.

A. Application Rates. The Department shall approve an Animal Facility Management Plan that establishes an application rate for each manure utilization area based on the agronomic application rate of the specific crop(s) being grown, and the manure and other animal by-products impact on the environment. The application rate shall be based on the limiting constituent (a nutrient or other constituent as given in item 200.100.B).

B. Constituent Limits for Land Application of Liquid and Dry Animal manure and other animal byproducts and Operational Practices for Land Application.

1. Liquid and dry animal manure and other animal by-products. Animal manure and other animal by-products containing only the standard constituents at normal concentrations as given by commonly accepted reference sources, such as Clemson University, American Society of Agricultural Engineers, Midwest Planning Service Document, or NRCS, can be land applied at or below agronomic rates without any specific constituent limits in a permit. When the animal manure analysis indicates there are levels of arsenic, copper, zinc, or other constituents of concern, the Department shall establish constituent limits in permits for each constituent of concern to ensure the

water quality standards of Regulation 61-68 are maintained. For these cases the producer shall comply with the following criteria:

a. Constituent Limits. If animal manure and other animal by-products subject to a

	<p>constituent limit is applied to land, either: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. The cumulative loading rate for each constituent shall not exceed the cumulative constituent loading rate for the constituent in Table 1 of Section 200.100; or ii. The concentration of each constituent in the animal manure and other animal byproducts shall not exceed the concentration for the constituent in Table 2 of Section 200.100. </p> <p>b. Constituent concentrations and loading rates - animal manure and other animal byproducts.</p> <p>TABLE 1 OF SECTION 200.100 - CUMULATIVE CONSTITUENT LOADING RATES</p> <p>—</p> <p>—</p> <p>9. Soil sampling (usually 6-“8 inch depth) shall be conducted for each field prior to manure application to determine the appropriate application rate. Each field should be sampled at least once per year. If manure application frequency shall be less than once per year, then at least one soil sample shall be taken prior to returning to that field for land application. All new manure utilization areas shall be evaluated using the NRCS-CPS to determine the suitability for application and the limiting nutrient (nitrogen or phosphorus). However, fields that are high in phosphorus may also be required to incorporate additional runoff control or soil conservation features as directed by the Department.</p> <p>10. Soil sampling to a depth of eighteen inches shall be performed within 45 days after each application of animal manure, but no more than two times per year if the application frequency is more than twice per year. This sampling shall be performed for at least three years after the initial application on at least one representative manure utilization area for each crop grown to verify the estimated calculated manure application rates for the utilization areas. The date of manure application and the date of sampling shall be carefully recorded. The sampling shall be conducted at depths of zero to six inches, six to twelve inches, and twelve to eighteen inches with nitrates and phosphorus being analyzed.</p> <p>11. The results of the pre-application and post-application sampling shall be used by the producer to adjust as necessary, the amount of animal manure to be applied to a manure utilization area to meet the agronomic application rate for the crop(s) to be grown. These results shall be submitted to the Department at the time of application for permit renewal.</p> <p>12. Additional soil sampling to greater depths may be required by the Department on a case-by-case basis to ensure there is no potential for groundwater contamination. The permit shall give the appropriate depth and frequency for all soil sampling.</p>
<p>Manure application rates for phosphorus are based on:</p> <p>1) <i>Phosphorus Index</i></p>	<p>Soil test phosphorus only</p>

<p>Only 2) Soil Test Phosphorus Only 3) Either PIO or STPO 4) Other</p>	
<p>Are there any nutrient “caps” to manure application ?</p>	<p>Undetermined</p>
<p>Composition testing: State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on manures before application</p>	<p>The Animal Facility Management Plan shall at a minimum contain: _ f. Concentration of constituents in swine manure including but not limited to the constituents given below:_ i. Nutrients._ (a) Nitrate. (Only needed for aerobic treatment systems)_ (b) Ammonium-Nitrogen._ (c) Total Kjeldahl Nitrogen (TKN)._ (d) Organic Nitrogen (Organic Nitrogen = TKN - Ammonium Nitrogen)_ (e) P2 O5._ (f) K2O (potash)._ ii. Constituents._ (a) Copper._ (b) Zinc._ For new swine facilities, swine manure analysis information does not have to be initially submitted as the Department shall use swine manure analysis from similar sites or published data (such as: Clemson University, American Society of Agricultural Engineers, Midwest Planning Service Document, NRCS Technical Guide or equivalent) in the review of the application. Analysis of the actual swine manure generated shall be submitted to the Department six months after a new swine facility starts operation or prior to the first application of swine manure to a manure utilization area, whichever occurs first. If this analysis is significantly different from the estimated analysis used in the permitting decision, the Department may require a permit modification as necessary to address the situation. Analysis shall be conducted by a laboratory certified by the Department. This laboratory shall have and maintain certification for the constituents to be analyzed._ 200.50_ f. Concentration of constituents in liquid animal manure including but not limited to the_ constituents given below:_ i. Nutrients._ (a) Nitrate (only needed for aerobic systems)._ (b) Ammonium-Nitrogen._ (c) Total Kjeldahl Nitrogen (TKN)._</p>

	<p>(d) Organic-Nitrogen (TKN - Ammonium-Nitrogen)._ (e) P2O5._ (f) K2O (potash)._ ii. Constituents._ (a) Arsenic._ (b) Copper._ (c) Zinc._ g. Concentration of constituents in dry animal manure including but not limited to the_ following:_ i. Nutrients (on a dry weight basis)._ (a) Total Kjeldahl Nitrogen (mg/kg)._ (b) Total inorganic nitrogen (mg/kg)._ (c) Total ammonia nitrogen (mg/kg) and Total nitrate, nitrogen (mg/kg)._ (d) P2O5 (mg/kg)._ (e) K2O (mg/kg)._ (f) Calcium Carbonate equivalency (if animal manure is alkaline stabilized)._ ii. Constituents (on a dry weight basis)._ (a) Arsenic (mg/kg)._ (b) Copper (mg/kg)._ (c) Zinc (mg/kg).</p>
<p>Does your state require testing of manure for anything beyond nutrients, such as metals, pathogens, antibiotics, etc.?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Other land application highlights: <i>Additional restrictions for land application of manures</i></p>	<p>No other information</p>
<p>Other regulatory details: <i>Additional information on the</i></p>	<p>No other information</p>

<p><i>regulation of land application of manures</i></p>	
General Assessment Questions	
<p>Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change:</p>	<p>Undetermined</p>
<p>Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of manures that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links:</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land</p>	<p>No</p>

<p>application of manures beyond state-level regulations ? Please provide names of these entities if so:</p>	
<p>Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.</p>	<p>No other information</p>

South Dakota Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2019
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	South Dakota Department of Agriculture and Natural Resources (DANR)
Links to regulations	South Dakota Codified Laws (SDCL) Chapter 34A-2 Section 36.2 Permit for CAFOs requirements (statement below) http://sdlegislature.gov/Statutes/Codified_Laws/DisplayStatute.aspx _ Administrative Rules of South Dakota (ARSD) Article 74:52:_ http://sdlegislature.gov/rules/DisplayRule.aspx?Rule=74:52 _ South Dakota's General Permit, 2017_ https://danr.sd.gov/Agriculture/Livestock/FeedlotPermit/FormsPermits/GeneralPermit-2017.aspx
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Environmental
Other regulator info	In some cases manure is manipulated and converted to a commercial fertilizer regulated by the South Dakota Department of Agriculture (SDDA)
Definitions	
How CAFOs are defined or categorized:	The definition of CAFO is contained in both South Dakota's General Permit and the Administrative Rules of South Dakota (ARSD)._ A Concentrated Animal Feeding Operation- ² (CAFO) is an Animal Feeding Operation that meets the following criteria for a large, medium, or small concentrated Animal Feeding Operation: 1) A large concentrated Animal Feeding Operation as described in Table 1 (link below); 2) A medium concentrated Animal Feeding Operation as described in Table 1 (link below) and meets one of the following conditions: 1) Pollutants are discharged into waters of the state through a man-made ditch, flushing system, or other similar man-made device; or 2) Pollutants are discharged directly into waters of the state which originate outside of and pass over, across, or through the facility or otherwise come into direct contact with the animals confined in the operation; 3) A small concentrated Animal Feeding Operation as described in Table 1 (link below) and designated as a concentrated Animal Feeding Operation by the Secretary considering the following factors: 1. The size of the Animal Feeding Operation and the amount of manure or process wastewater reaching waters of the state; 2. The location of the Animal Feeding Operation in relation to waters of the state; 3. The means of conveyance of manure and process wastewater into waters of the state; and 4. The slope, vegetation, precipitation, and other factors affecting the likelihood or frequency of discharge of manure and process wastewater into waters of the state. _ _ Number of Animals to Define Large, Medium and Small Concentrated Animal

	<p>Feeding Operations:_ Type of Animal - Numbers of Large, Medium, Small_ Dairy cows (mature - milked or dry) 700, 200-699, 200_ Veal calves 1,000, 300-999, 300_ Cattle other than mature dairy cows or veal calves 1,000, 300-999, 300_ Swine (weighing 55 pounds or more) 2,500, 750-2,499, 750_ Swine (weighing less than 55 pounds) 10,000, 3000-9,999, 3,000_ Horses 500, 150-499, 150_ Sheep or Lambs 10,000, 3,000-9,999, 3,000_ Turkeys 55,000, 16500-54,999, 16,500_ Laying hens or broilers 30,000, 9000-29,999, 9000_ Chickens, other than laying hens 125,000 37,500-124,999, 9000_ Laying hens 82,000, 25,000-81,999, 25,000_ Ducks 5,000, 1,500-4999, 1500_ Geese 30,000, 10,000-29,999, 10,000</p>
How animal units are defined (if used):	Not used
NPDES permitting or other permitting requirements :	<p>SDCL 34A-2-36.2. Permit for concentrated Animal Feeding Operations. Each concentrated Animal Feeding Operation, as defined by Title 40 Codified Federal Regulations Part 122.23 dated January 1, 2007, shall operate under a general or individual water pollution control permit issued pursuant to § 34A-2-36._ ARSD 74:52:01:05. Point sources that require SWD permits. The following point sources require SWD permits: (1) Concentrated Animal Feeding Operations as defined in 40 C.F.R. § 122.23 (January 1, 2007) _ ARSD 74:52:01:05.01. State only surface water discharge permits. The secretary may issue surface water discharge permits outside of the National Pollutant Discharge Elimination System authority granted the State of South Dakota by the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency on December 30, 1993, to concentrated Animal Feeding Operations not required by Federal Regulations to have a National Pollutant Discharge Elimination System Permit. Concentrated Animal Feeding Operations issued coverage under this permit shall meet all requirements of Article 74:52 except the requirements of 40 C.F.R. §§ 122.23(h) and 122.42(e)(4) in § 74:52:02:22 shall be those of February 12, 2003._ ARSD 74:52:01:09. Technical regulations. Technical regulations for the SWD permit program used by the state to determine what requirements are to be placed in the permit are contained in 40 C.F.R. Part 125, criteria and standards for the national pollutant discharge elimination system (July 1, 2016); 40 C.F.R. Part 129 (July 1, 2016), toxic pollutant effluent standards and prohibitions; 40 C.F.R. Subchapter N, effluent guidelines and standards (July 1, 2016); and 40 C.F.R. Part 403, general pretreatment regulations, for existing and new sources of pollution (July 1, 2016). These regulations apply to chapters 74:52:07 to 74:52:11, inclusive._ ARSD 74:52:02:22. Additional requirements for concentrated Animal Feeding Operations. In addition to the requirements in chapters 74:52:01 to 74:52:11, inclusive, requirements for concentrated Animal Feeding Operations are contained in 40 C.F.R. §§ 122.23, 122.28(b)(2)(vii), and 122.42(e) (July 30, 2012)._ On April 15, 2017, the revised General Water Pollution Control Permit for</p>

	<p>Concentrated Animal Feeding Operations became effective. Operations with coverage under the existing general permit are required to obtain coverage under the reissued permit. The revised permit allows applicants to apply for coverage under a state permit or an NPDES permit. The department has put together a checklist and flow chart of requirements for applying for coverage under the reissued permit._</p> <p>Summary of Significant Differences Between State and NPDES Permit can be found here as well: http://denr.sd.gov/des/fp/2017permit.aspx _</p> <p>_</p> <p>SDCL 34A-2-36.2 requires all CAFOs to operate under a general or individual water pollution control permit. Under the 2017 general permit the producer has the option of applying for NPDES permit coverage or state permit coverage. On 11/6/18 - 439 operations had general permit coverage, and 2 operations had individual permits._</p> <p>Other permits and requirements are listed in Section 1.4.8. (page 40) of the 2017 general permit (https://denr.sd.gov/des/fp/documents/2017GeneralPermit.pdf)</p>
Does the state require an NPDES permit for all Large CAFOs?	No
Does the state issue individual or general CAFO permits?	Both
Are any other permits required for CAFOs or other large farms?	Yes
Other definitions needed to understand these regulations:	No other information
Regulatory Details	
Setbacks: <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie</i>	<p>The producer shall maintain at least a 100-foot buffer zone or 35-foot vegetated buffer between: _</p> <p>1) Any manure land application areas and any downslope surface waters, open tile line intake structures, sinkholes, or other conduits to surface waters of the state; and _</p> <p>2) Any irrigation of process wastewater and any downslope surface waters, open tile line intake structures, sinkholes, or other conduits to Depending on the results</p>

<p><i>between the site of land application and some geographical feature</i></p>	<p>of a producer's soil phosphorus test and estimated field erosion, a 100-foot vegetated buffer zone shall be required if the producer wants to apply manure based on the nitrogen needs of the crop and not crop removal of phosphorus (see Table 2 on page 34). _</p> <p>Manure management systems, manure disposal sites, and process wastewater disposal sites shall not be located closer than 250 feet from an existing private water well not owned by the producer or 1,000 feet from an existing public water well, constructed to supply water to water distribution systems as defined by SDCL 46-1-6(17) or surface waters of the state classified by the South Dakota Surface Water Quality Standards, ARSD 74:51:02 and 74:51:03, for a domestic water supply beneficial use. Manure management systems, manure disposal sites, and process wastewater disposal sites shall not be located closer than 150 feet from a water well owned or proposed to be drilled by the producer supplied by an aquifer where the top of the aquifer is less than 100 feet below the land surface or 100 feet from a water well owned or proposed to be drilled by the producer supplied by an aquifer whose top is 100 or more feet below the land surface. These setback requirements do not apply to manure management systems constructed prior to August 13, 1996. (Section 1.4.3.3.v. on page 22 of the general permit)_</p> <p>Fields should be diked or terraced to prevent the release of applied wastewater. _</p> <p>Land to be irrigated or receive manure should have a slope less than 6 percent. _</p> <p>Highly erodible soils due to water erosion should be avoided. _</p> <p>Manure and process wastewater land application practices should be managed to prevent ponding of wastewater on the land application site and shall be managed to prevent runoff of manure or process wastewater beyond the edge of the field. _</p> <p>_</p> <p>Section 1.4.4.1.t. of the general permit contains requirements for application on saturated, snow covered, and frozen soil. Application in this situation requires the producer maintain at least a 300-foot buffer zone between any manure land application areas and any down-gradient surface waters, open tile line intake structures, sinkholes, or other conduits to surface waters of the state and a set back a minimum of 300 feet from surface waters or water conveyances and a minimum of 1,000 feet from National Hydrography Dataset named lakes, rivers, and perennial stream_</p> <p>40CFR122.42(e)(5)(i)(A) requires the nutrient management plan include the outcome of the field-specific assessment of the potential for nitrogen and phosphorus transport from each field and the crops to be planted in each field. South Dakota does this through Table 2 on page 34 of the general permit and other requirements from the SD NRCS 590 Standard._</p> <p>_</p> <p>The requirements for setbacks to wells come from South Dakota's Well Construction Standards, ARSD 74:02:04._</p> <p>_</p> <p>The requirements for application on saturated, snow covered, and frozen soil are more restrictive as EPA does not have additional setbacks for these conditions.</p>
<p>Are setbacks more restrictive than CFR?</p>	<p>Yes</p>

<p>Timing, weather, or conditional application restrictions: <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather, seasons, or land characteristics (like slope)</i></p>	<p>Field Maps for Application to Saturated, Snow Covered, or Frozen Soil - See Section 1.4.4.1.t.11. on page 32 of the 2017 general permit. A tool to determine National Hydrography Dataset (NHD) named lakes, rivers, or perennial streams can be found at http://denr.sd.gov/des/fp/nutrientmanagementtools.aspx _</p> <p>– Manure Application on Saturated, Snow Covered, or Frozen Soil. Manure and process wastewater shall not be surface applied to saturated soil where the top two inches of soil are so wet or water-logged that farm equipment cannot travel over the area effectively, soil covered by one-inch or more of snow or covered by more than one-half inch of ice, or frozen soil that is impermeable to liquid manure applied to the ground surface due to frozen soil moisture unless planned for in the initial nutrient management plan. The producer shall follow all other applicable requirements of their approved initial nutrient management plan and this permit. _</p> <p>1) If the producer has properly designed, constructed, operated and maintained the manure management system in accordance with this permit and the permit application and the wastewater level in the manure containment system is above the maximum operating level, process wastewater can be land applied to saturated, snow covered, or frozen soil to prevent catastrophic equipment or structural failure or a discharge to waters of the state as long as the following conditions 4) through 12) below are met; _</p> <p>2) If the producer has properly designed, constructed, operated and maintained the manure management system in accordance with this permit and the permit application, solid manure can be land applied to saturated, snow covered, or frozen soils if conditions 5) through 12) below are met._</p> <p>3) If the producer has properly designed, constructed, operated and maintained the manure management system in accordance with this permit, incidental amounts of manure collected during feedlot snow removal or cleaning of feed bunks to facilitate livestock feeding and handling may be land applied if conditions 6) through 12) below are met;_</p> <p>4) Process wastewater or manure shall not be spray irrigated on saturated, snow covered, or frozen soil;_</p> <p>5) The producer should notify DENR prior to application so DENR may review buffer zone requirements with the producer and respond to inquiries from the public;_</p> <p>6) Manure application should occur in the upper 50% of the topography of an application field;_</p> <p>7) Application rates shall be determined based on a soil test and a manure or process wastewater test that are no more than one year old. No application shall occur on flood plain soils classified as frequently or occasionally flooded on the National Cooperative Soil Survey (http://websoilsurvey.nrcs.usda.gov). When using the survey, click on soil data explorer, then soil properties and quality, then water features to find this information;_</p> <p>8) The producer shall maintain at least a 300-foot buffer zone between any manure land application areas and any down-gradient surface waters, open tile line intake structures, sinkholes, or other conduits to surface waters of the state;_</p> <p>9) Winter applications of nutrients must be set back a minimum of 300 feet from surface waters or water conveyances and a minimum of 1,000 feet from National Hydrography Dataset named lakes, rivers, and perennial streams._</p>
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	<p>10) The producer shall only apply manure on land with slopes less than 4 percent. Fields with the lowest predicted water erosion soil loss should have the highest priority for winter application;_</p> <p>11) Field maps showing the items in 6) through 8) above and in Sections 1.4.3.3.v shall be included in the initial nutrient management plan for fields where land application under these conditions may occur;_</p> <p>12) Liquid manure containment structures shall only be pumped down one foot below the maximum operating level or the amount necessary to prevent structural failure; and_</p> <p>13) Manure or process wastewater shall be spread as uniformly as possible._</p> <p>_</p> <p>The producer shall inject, or incorporate any liquid manure or process wastewater within 24 hours of application to non-vegetated cropland. If the process wastewater/liquid manure is surface applied, sprinkled, or spray irrigated to cropped fields, grass, alfalfa, pasture land, or no till cropland, incorporation is not required. _</p> <p>>The producer shall incorporate any solid or semi-solid manure within five days of application to non-vegetated cropland. If the application area is a cropped field, alfalfa, grass, pasture land, or no-till cropland, incorporation is not required. _</p> <p>>To reduce nutrient discharges from pattern tile, producers should apply nutrients with the right placement, in the right amount, at the right time and from the right source. The producer should consider the following nutrient use efficiency strategies: slow and controlled release fertilizers; nitrification and urease inhibitors; enhanced efficiency fertilizers; timing and the number of applications; coordinate nutrient applications with optimum crop nutrient uptake; Corn Stalk Nitrate Test, Pre-Side dress Nitrate Test, and Pre-Plant Soil Nitrate Test; tissue testing, chlorophyll meters, and spectral analysis technologies, and other SDSU or NRCS recommendation technologies that improve nutrient use efficiency. Producers should also consider the use of drainage water management, bioreactors, buffers at tile inlets, treatment wetlands, plugging tile outlets during land application, the use of cover crops, and other BMPs to reduce nutrient discharges from tile drainage systems. Additional management considerations can be found in Cornell University Cooperative Extension's Fact Sheet 58 Subsurface (Tile) Drainage Best Management Practices and the University of Minnesota Extension's fact sheet Nitrates in Drainage Water in Minnesota._</p> <p>_</p> <p>Winter Application Buffers: Buffer Zone Determination Map for Winter Application of Nutrients Winter application maps including proper setbacks must be submitted to the department for winter application. Winter applications of nutrients must be set back a minimum of 300 feet from surface waters or water conveyances and a minimum of 1,000 feet from any National Hydrography Dataset (NHD) named lakes, rivers, or perennial streams which are identified in red on the map above.</p>
<p>Is there a restriction for land application of manure to</p>	<p>Yes</p>

saturated soils?	
Is there a restriction for land application of manure within floodplains?	No
Is there a restriction for land application of manure related to future rainfall?	No
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to frozen or snow-covered ground?	Yes
Are there restrictions to manure applications based on time of year or time of day?	Yes
Are there restrictions to manure application based on slope?	No
Are there any other seasonal, timing, weather, or physical restrictions to manure applications not captured above?	No

<p>Transfer of manure off-site: <i>Requirements related to the transfer of manures to other persons</i></p>	<p>Elements required in an initial nutrient management plan: _ * A copy of each written agreement for a minimum of one year executed with the legal land owner where manure will be applied. The written agreement shall indicate the acres that manure from the Animal Feeding Operation may be applied and the length of the agreement. The producer shall ensure that there is enough land to apply manure consistent with the approved initial nutrient management plan. (1.4.4.2.J p.33)_ * A producer can sell or give away up to 100 cubic yards of solid manure per year without including that manure in their annual nutrient management plan. The producer shall provide each landowner with the manure sample results for total nitrogen, inorganic nitrogen, and total phosphorus. The producer shall also let each landowner know that they cannot place or cause to be placed any manure in a location where it is likely to cause pollution of any waters of the state. Once the producer has completed the requirements of this section, the producer is no longer responsible for how the manure is stored or applied. The person who receives the manure assumes responsibility for storing the manure and land applying the manure so it does not cause pollution of waters of the state. This manure may be subject to the South Dakota Department of Agriculture commercial fertilizer law, SDCL 38-19. (1.4.4.2.v. p 35)_ * The general permit allows a producer to sell or give away up to 100 cubic yards of solid manure per year without including that manure in their annual nutrient management plan. The person who receives the manure assumes responsibility for storing the manure and land applying the manure so it does not cause pollution of waters of the state. This manure may be subject to the South Dakota Department of Agriculture commercial fertilizer law, SDCL 38-19. Operations wanting to transfer more than 100 cubic yards of manure need an individual permit.</p>
<p>Are receivers of manure transfers from CAFOs required to follow the same regulations?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Nutrient or manure management plans: <i>Additional details on the NMP requirement. Note that some of this information may overlap with other</i></p>	<p>A nutrient management plan must be developed and submitted as part of the permit application for producers seeking permit coverage for their operation. _ Information Required for 2017 General Permit Nutrient Management Plans _ http://denr.sd.gov/des/fp/documents/2017NMPRequirements.pdf _ _ DENR staff participated in the development of the current 590 standard, and NRCS staff participated in the development of the general permit. The requirements in the general permit meet all the 590 standards requirements except for the standard's requirements for feed management. The current NRCS planning tools can be used in preparing the initial and annual nutrient management plans (https://denr.sd.gov/des/fp/nutrientmanagementtools.aspx). Some additions in the general permit will be considered to be added to the 590 standard when it is next revised.</p>

sections	
Do your NMP/MMPS follow, comply with, or based on NRCS Technical Standard 590?	Yes
Application rates: <i>State regulations that restrict the rates at which manures are applied and methods needed to determine appropriate rates.</i>	<p>Land application rates of nitrogen must be calculated based on soil tests, manure tests, type of crop, expected yield, legume credits, and sampling dates. Land application rates for phosphorus are based on the table provided in the permit.</p> <p>>Analyses of manure must be performed at least once annually for nitrogen and phosphorus, and soil must be sampled prior to each application.</p> <p>> Equipment and sites used for land application must be inspected daily for leaks or runoff.)</p> <p>a. Upon receiving permit coverage and prior to land applying manure, the producer shall use the following procedure to determine the appropriate application rates of manure and process wastewater based on nitrogen or phosphorus (see Table 2). Upon determining the application rate, the producer shall apply the manure and process wastewater according to the calculated rate. Applying manure above the calculated rate is a violation of this permit. The following is the procedure for calculating the application rate:</p> <p>1) Before manure application, each field where manure or process wastewater will be land applied shall be sampled for phosphorus from a depth of 0 to 6 inches and for nitrate- nitrogen from 0 to 2 feet. If manure application sites are located over shallow aquifers, prior to application of nitrogen above starter application rates, the producer shall also either:</p> <p>a) Take soil samples for nitrate-nitrogen from both 0 to 2 and 2 to 4 feet prior to manure application, or</p> <p>b) Take soil samples for nitrate-nitrogen to a depth of 2 feet both prior to manure application and within four weeks after harvesting the crop. This shall apply to all fields in the nutrient management plan located over a shallow aquifer. Once the producer takes the post-harvest soil samples, in lieu of the 2 to 4 foot samples, it shall become a condition of this permit to continue taking post-harvest samples for the fields located over shallow aquifers. If a producer does not take the required 2 to 4 foot samples prior to land application of manure, the post-harvest sampling shall then be required. In either case, the producer shall no longer have the option of taking the deep soil samples.</p> <p>2) If the post-harvest soil sample results indicate the residual nitrate-nitrogen in the soil is above 100 pounds per acre, this field shall not be available for manure application until one full growing season has passed. After one full growing season has passed another soil test shall be taken and if it shows nitrate-nitrogen levels have dropped below 100 pounds per acre then manure application may commence based on the producer's annual nutrient management plan calculations. A minimum of 15 soil sample cores shall be taken from each field or</p>

landscape position in the field. Soil sample cores that represent similar soil and landscape position may be composited into one sample. Soil sampling shall be done in accordance with the NRCS Guidance, Sampling Soils for Nutrient Management SD- NRCS-FS-50 (June 2012)

(<http://denr.sd.gov/des/fp/documents/NRCSSoilSampling.pdf>) or SDSU's Recommended Soil Sampling Methods for South Dakota FS935 (May 2006) (<http://denr.sd.gov/des/fp/documents/SDSUSoilSampling.pdf>). The laboratory analyzing the soil samples shall participate in the North American Proficiency Testing Program (NAPT) Proficiency Assessment Program (PAP) (<https://www.naptprogram.org/>). _

3) The producer shall take a representative sample each year of the manure or process wastewater that will be land applied and have each sample tested for total nitrogen, inorganic nitrogen, and phosphorus. Organic nitrogen is equal to the total nitrogen minus the inorganic nitrogen. Sampling shall be done in accordance with the NRCS guidance Sampling Manure for Nutrient Management SD-NRCS-FS-36 (November 2002)

(<http://denr.sd.gov/des/fp/documents/NRCSSamplingManure.pdf>). The laboratory analyzing the manure samples shall be certified by the Manure Testing Laboratory Certification Program

(<http://www2.mda.state.mn.us/webapp/lis/manurelabs.jsp>). _

4) Nitrogen-based application. Based on a soil test, a manure test, type of crop to be grown, expected crop yield, legume credits, and sampling date, the producer shall determine the total nitrogen that can be applied to each field. When determining the nitrogen application rate, the producer does not have to use the yield goal listed in the initial nutrient management plan. The producer may use a yield goal that is reasonably expected for that field. The total nitrogen that can be applied shall be determined as follows: _

a) The total nitrogen necessary to meet the expected yield goal in pounds of nitrogen per acre shall be determined using the South Dakota State University Cooperative _

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Extension Service publication EC750, Fertilizer Recommendations Guide. This value is determined by the crop to be grown and the expected yield. In addition to the manure nitrogen allowed in the nutrient management plan, other nitrogen necessary to obtain the realistic yield goal, as indicated by soil nitrogen test results, may be applied to the field. _

b) Nitrogen credits shall be subtracted from the total nitrogen value determined in item a) above. The following credits shall be subtracted from this value. _

The results from the 0 to 2 foot nitrate soil test conducted in accordance with item 1) on page 36. If a 2 to 4 foot deep nitrate test is required and the result of the test is greater than 30 pounds of nitrogen, then reduce the nitrogen recommendation an additional four pounds of nitrogen for each five pound increment above 30 pounds (for example, if there are 50 pounds of nitrate nitrogen in the 2 to 4 foot depth, 16 pounds of nitrogen in addition to the 0 to 2 foot deep test shall be subtracted). _

Any legume credits. To determine legume credits, please see the SDSU Cooperative Extension Service publication EC750, Fertilizer Recommendations Guide. _

Sampling date adjustment. Breakdown of organic material continues to release nitrates until soils cool in the fall. Therefore, the nitrogen requirement shall be adjusted if the soil samples are taken between July 1st and September 15th. To make this adjustment, reduce the nitrogen requirement by 0.5 pounds of nitrogen per day prior to September 15th. The maximum adjustment is 23 pounds. Soil samples from fallow fields do not need to be adjusted for time of sampling because most of the residue from the previous crop should have mineralized during the fallow period. _

Any other sources of nitrogen used. _

The resulting value in pounds of nitrogen per acre is the maximum amount of additional nitrogen that may be applied to the field. _

5) Based on the results of the manure testing required in item 3) on page 36, the producer shall apply manure to each field at a rate not to exceed the rate calculated in item 4) above. NOTE: If the yields that are used to calculate the application rate are not consistently attained, residual nitrogen will increase in subsequent years and will decrease the amount of manure that can be applied to that field during future applications. This nitrogen carry-over will be evident in future soil sampling. _

6) Phosphorus Based Application. If the manure application is required to be based on phosphorus crop removal as determined by using Table 2 on page 34, the application rate shall be based on phosphorus removed in the harvested portion of the crop as listed in the most current version of SDSU Extension Publication EXEX 8009, Quantities of Plant Nutrients Contained in Crops. Application can be based on a five-year or one-year phosphorus crop removal (see Table 2) but cannot exceed the one year nitrogen crop need, and no manure may be applied to that field again until the applied phosphorus has been removed from the field via harvest and crop removal. In addition to all other nutrient management planning requirements of this permit, the producer shall submit an amendment to their initial nutrient management plan that includes a soil phosphorous drawdown strategy implementation plan, and a site assessment for nutrients and soil loss to determine mitigation practices that are required to protect water quality. _

7) Manure or process wastewater shall be spread as uniformly as possible. _

8) Precision/Variable Rate Nutrient Management Planning. The following additional components shall be included in a precision/variable rate nutrient management plan: _

a) Document the geo-referenced field boundary and data collected that was processed and analyzed as a Geographic Information Systems (GIS) layer or layers to generate nutrient or soil amendment recommendation; _

b) Document the nutrient recommendation guidance and recommendation equations used to convert the GIS base data layer or layers to a nutrient source material recommendation GIS layer or layers; _

c) Document if a variable rate nutrient or soil amendment application was made; and _

d) Provide application records per management zone or as applied map within individual field boundaries (or electronic records) documenting source, timing, method, and rate of all applications that resulted from use of the precision agriculture process for nutrient applications. _

Phosphorous Soil Test Result - The results of a representative 0 to 6 inch soil phosphorus test from each field included in the nutrient management plan no older than two years from when the application was submitted (Olson or Bray 1 test). To obtain a representative sample, a minimum of 15 soil sample cores shall be taken from each field or landscape position to determine the soil test phosphorus in the field. Sampling Soils for Nutrient Management SDNRCS- FS-50 (June 2012) or SDSU's Recommended Soil Sampling Methods for South Dakota FS935 (May 2006). The laboratory analyzing the soil samples shall participate in the North American Proficiency Testing Program (NAPT) Proficiency Assessment Program (PAP). _

(The requirements for the field specific phosphorus assessment are (DENR, 2003):_

> a representative phosphorus soil test (before land application if any of the_ information from the initial NMP has changed);_

> a soil loss value (can be obtained from a local Natural Resources_ Conservation Service [NRCS] office); and_

> whether or not the field has a 100-foot vegetated buffer to any waterway or wetland.)_

Nitrogen-based application. Based on a soil test, a manure test, type of crop to be grown, expected crop yield, legume credits, and sampling date, the producer shall determine the total nitrogen that can be applied to each field. When determining the nitrogen application rate, the producer does not have to use the yield goal listed in the initial nutrient management plan. The producer may use a yield goal that is reasonably expected for that field. The total nitrogen that can be applied shall be determined as follows: _

a) The total nitrogen necessary to meet the expected yield goal in pounds of nitrogen per acre shall be determined using the South Dakota State University Cooperative _

Extension Service publication EC750, Fertilizer Recommendations Guide. This value is determined by the crop to be grown and the expected yield. In addition to the manure nitrogen allowed in the nutrient management plan, other nitrogen necessary to obtain the realistic yield goal, as indicated by soil nitrogen test results, may be applied to the field. _

5) Based on the results of the manure testing required in item 3) on page 36, the producer shall apply manure to each field at a rate not to exceed the rate calculated in item 4) above. NOTE: If the yields that are used to calculate the application rate are not consistently attained, residual nitrogen will increase in subsequent years and will decrease the amount of manure that can be applied to that field during future applications. This nitrogen carry-over will be evident in future soil sampling._

Tools for calculating application rates for annual nutrient management plans can be found at https://denr.sd.gov/des/fp/nutrientmanagementtools.aspx ._

_ Table 2 on page 34 of the general permit determines if application is based on nitrogen need, one or five year phosphorous crop removal or if no application is allowed._

Both phosphorous soil tests and Table 2 on page 34, our phosphorous index, are

	used each time an application rate is calculated.
Manure application rates for phosphorus are based on: 1) <i>Phosphorus Index Only</i> 2) <i>Soil Test Phosphorus Only</i> 3) <i>Either PIO or STPO</i> 4) <i>Other</i>	Other
Are there any nutrient “caps” to manure application?	No
Composition testing: <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on manures before application</i>	The producer shall take a representative sample each year of the manure or process wastewater that will be land applied and have each sample tested for total nitrogen, inorganic nitrogen, and phosphorus. Organic nitrogen is equal to the total nitrogen minus the inorganic nitrogen. Sampling shall be done in accordance with the NRCS guidance Sampling Manure for Nutrient Management SD-NRCS-FS-36 (November 2002) (http://denr.sd.gov/des/fp/documents/NRCSSamplingManure.pdf). The laboratory analyzing the manure samples shall be certified by the Manure Testing Laboratory Certification Program (http://www2.mda.state.mn.us/webapp/lis/manurelabs.jsp).
Does your state require testing of manure for anything beyond nutrients, such as metals, pathogens, antibiotics, etc.?	No
Other land application	No other information

highlights: <i>Additional restrictions for land application of manures</i>	
Other regulatory details: <i>Additional information on the regulation of land application of manures</i>	No other information
General Assessment Questions	
Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change:	Yes. The department has started the process of reissuing DANR's General Water Pollution Control permits for CAFOs.
Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of manures that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links:	No
Within your state, are there any	Yes

<p>jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of manures beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so:</p>	
<p>Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.</p>	<p>No other information</p>

Tennessee	
Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2019
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Tennessee Department of Environment and Conservation (TDEC)
Links to regulations	0400-40-05-.14 ANIMAL FEEDING OPERATIONS _ https://publications.tnsosfiles.com/rules/0400/0400-40/0400-40-05.20140218.pdf
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Environmental
Other regulator info	No other information
Definitions	
How CAFOs are defined or categorized:	A "concentrated Animal Feeding Operation" (CAFO) is an AFO that either meets the large (Class I) CAFO size criteria of paragraph (2) of Rule 0400-40-05-.14, the medium (Class II) criteria of paragraph (3) of Rule 0400-40-05-.14, or has otherwise been designated as a CAFO by the Director._ _ (43) A "large CAFO" (Class I CAFO) is an AFO that confines greater than or equal to the number of animals specified in TABLE 0400-40-05-.14.1._ _ (48) A "medium CAFO" (Class II CAFO) is an AFO that falls within the size threshold for the animals specified in column 3 of TABLE 0400-40-05-.14.1 and also meets the criteria of paragraph (3) of Rule 0400-40-05-.14.
How animal units are defined (if used):	Not used
NPDES permitting or other permitting requirements:	Any individual who operates a concentrated Animal Feeding Operation (CAFO) must have a Division of Water Resources issued CAFO Permit. Individuals who operate a Class I CAFO may need to apply for an individual NPDES permit.
Does the state require an NPDES permit for all Large CAFOs?	No
Does the state issue individual or general CAFO permits?	Undetermined
Are any other permits required for CAFOs or other large farms?	Undetermined
Other definitions needed to understand these regulations:	No other information
Regulatory Details	

<p>Setbacks: <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some geographical feature</i></p>	<p>CAFO Nutrient Management Plan (NMP) Requirements_</p> <p>7. Identifies appropriate site specific conservation practices to be implemented, including, as appropriate, buffers or equivalent practices, to control runoff of pollutants to waters of the state (these practices shall meet minimum standards set in the USDA-NRCS Field Office Practice Standard and/or the USDA-NRCS Animal Waste Handbook), as follows:_ (i) Manure, litter, and process wastewater shall be applied no closer than 100 feet to any down-gradient surface waters, open tile line intake structures, sinkholes, agricultural well heads, or other conduits to surface waters unless:_ (I) The CAFO substitutes the 100-foot setback with a 35-foot wide vegetated buffer or by leaving in place a 60-foot natural riparian buffer, where applications of manure, litter, or process wastewater are prohibited; or_ (II) The CAFO demonstrates that a setback or buffer is not necessary because implementation of alternative conservation practices or field-specific conditions will provide pollutant reductions equivalent to or better than the reductions that would be achieved by the 100-foot setback;_ (ii) Manure, litter, and process wastewater shall be applied no closer than 100 feet for any potable well, public or private, or as recommended by the_ University of Tennessee Extension; and_ (iii) For new CAFOs that are located adjacent to exceptional Tennessee waters and outstanding national resource waters (as identified by the Department), leave in place a minimum 60-foot natural riparian buffer between the stream and the land application area;</p>
<p>Are setbacks more restrictive than CFR?</p>	<p>Undetermined</p>
<p>Timing, weather, or conditional application restrictions: <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather, seasons, or land characteristics (like slope)</i></p>	<p>None</p>
<p>Is there a restriction for land application of manure to saturated soils?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Is there a restriction for land application of manure within floodplains?</p>	<p>No</p>

Is there a restriction for land application of manure related to future rainfall?	No
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to frozen or snow-covered ground?	No
Are there restrictions to manure applications based on time of year or time of day?	No
Are there restrictions to manure application based on slope?	No
Are there any other seasonal, timing, weather, or physical restrictions to manure applications not captured above?	Undetermined
<p>Transfer of manure off-site: <i>Requirements related to the transfer of manures to other persons</i></p>	<p>Recordkeeping for third-party waste transfers_ A requirement that prior to transferring manure, litter, or process wastewater to a 3rd party, all CAFOs shall provide the recipient of the manure, litter, or process wastewater with the most current nutrient analysis (consistent with 40 CFR Part 412 and approved by the University of Tennessee Extension). Large CAFOs shall ensure that the 3rd party signs an agreement for the removal of manure, litter, or process wastewater for_ all transfers of manure, litter, or process wastewater. All other CAFOs shall ensure that the 3rd party signs an agreement for the removal of manure, litter, or process wastewater only if the CAFO transfers more than 100 tons of manure, litter, or process wastewater. The agreement for the removal of manure, litter, or process wastewater shall be retained for 5 years and shall include the following information, at a minimum:_ 1. The name and location of the facility that is exporting manure, litter, or process wastewater;_ 2. The type and amount of material that is removed from the CAFO;_ 3. The date the material was removed from the CAFO;_ 4. The following best management practice recommendations:_ (i) The manure, litter, or process wastewater shall be managed to ensure there is no discharge of manure, litter, or process wastewater to surface or groundwater._ (ii) When removed from the facility, manure, litter, or process wastewater_ should be applied directly to the field or stockpiled and covered with plastic_ or stored in a building._</p>

	<p>(iii) Manure, litter, or process wastewater shall not be stockpiled near streams, sinkholes, wetlands, or wells._</p> <p>(iv) Fields receiving manure, litter, or process wastewater should be soil tested at least every 5 years._</p> <p>(v) A manure, litter, or process wastewater nutrient analysis should be used to determine application rates for various crops._</p> <p>(vi) Calibrate spreading equipment and apply manure, litter or process wastewater uniformly._</p> <p>(vii) Apply no more nitrogen or phosphorus than can be used by the crop._</p> <p>(viii) A buffer zone is recommended between the application sites and adjacent streams, lakes, ponds, sinkholes, and wells. The following non-application buffer widths, based on the USDA-NRCS Conservation Practice Standard 590 (January 2013 version, or most recent version), should be used when applicable:_</p> <p>(I) 150 ft. from wells located upslope of the application site;_</p> <p>(II) 300 ft. from wells located downslope of the application site, if conditions warrant application;_</p> <p>(III) 30-100 ft. from waterbodies, depending on the amount and quality of vegetation and slope;_</p> <p>(IV) 300 ft. from all public use areas; and_</p> <p>(V) 300 ft. from all residences other than the producer's._</p> <p>(ix) Do not apply manure, litter, or process wastewater when the ground is frozen, flooded, saturated, or on steep slopes subject to flooding, erosion, or rapid runoff._</p> <p>(x) Cover vehicles hauling manure, litter, or process wastewater on public roads._</p> <p>(xi) Keep records of locations where manure, litter, or process wastewater will be land applied or used as a fertilizer._</p> <p>5. A signed certification statement from the recipient of the material from the CAFO, including the recipient's name, address, and phone number.</p>
<p>Are receivers of manure transfers from CAFOs required to follow the same regulations?</p>	<p>Undetermined</p>
<p>Nutrient or manure management plans: <i>Additional details on the NMP requirement. Note that some of this information may overlap with other sections</i></p>	<p>CAFO Nutrient Management Plan (NMP) Requirements_</p> <p>(a) Any permit issued to a CAFO shall include a requirement to develop, submit for state approval, implement, and keep on site a site-specific nutrient management plan that:_</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Includes best management practices and procedures necessary to implement applicable effluent limitations and standards;_ 2. Ensures adequate storage of manure, litter, and process wastewater including procedures to ensure proper operation and maintenance of the storage facilities;_ 3. Ensures proper management of mortalities (i.e., dead animals) so

	<p>that they are not disposed of in a liquid manure, stormwater, or process wastewater storage or treatment system that is not specifically designed to treat animal mortalities as outlined in USDA-NRCS Conservation Practice Standard 316, October 2002 (or most recent) and/or the USDA-NRCS Animal Waste Handbook, and/or University of Tennessee Extension publications;_</p> <p>4. Ensures that clean water is diverted, as appropriate, from the production area;_</p> <p>5. Prevents direct contact of confined animals with waters of the state;_</p> <p>6. Ensures that chemicals and other contaminants handled on-site are not disposed of in any manure, litter, process wastewater, or stormwater storage or treatment system unless specifically designed to treat such chemicals and other contaminants;</p>
<p>Do your NMP/MMPS follow, comply with, or based on NRCS Technical Standard 590?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Application rates: <i>State regulations that restrict the rates at which manures are applied and methods needed to determine appropriate rates.</i></p>	<p>"Multi-year phosphorus application" means phosphorus applied to a field in excess of crop needs and/or crop removal rates when there is no soil test recommendation for phosphorus and the Tennessee Phosphorus Index indicates manure, litter or process wastewater should be applied at the crop phosphorus removal rate. Subsequent phosphorus application is prohibited until the applied phosphorus has been removed via harvest and/or crop removal or a subsequent soil test indicates phosphorus is required. _</p> <p>_</p> <p>Crop phosphorus removal rates are set by University of Tennessee Extension technical guidance documents for nutrient management._</p> <p>_</p> <p>9. Establishes protocols to land apply manure, litter, or process wastewater in accordance with site specific nutrient management practices that ensure_</p> <p>appropriate agricultural utilization of the nutrients in the manure, litter, or process wastewater. Application rates for manure, litter, and other process wastewater applied to land under the ownership or operational control of the CAFO shall minimize phosphorus and nitrogen transport from the field to surface waters in compliance with technical standards for nutrient management that:_</p> <p>(i) Include a field-specific assessment of the potential for nitrogen and_</p> <p>phosphorus transport from the field to surface waters, and address the_</p> <p>form, source, amount, timing, and method of application of nutrients on_</p> <p>each field to achieve realistic production goals, while minimizing nitrogen_</p>

	<p>and phosphorus movement to surface waters, that employs the Tennessee_ Phosphorus Index (a tool developed by the University of Tennessee_ Extension Service and the USDA-NRCS to assess the risk of phosphorus_ movement from the application area to waters of the state); and_ (ii) Include appropriate flexibilities for any CAFO to implement nutrient_ management practices to comply with the technical standards, including consideration of multi-year phosphorus application on fields that do not_ have a high potential for phosphorus runoff to surface water, phased_ implementation of phosphorus-based nutrient management, and other components, in consideration of recommendations from the University of Tennessee Extension and as determined appropriate by the Director;</p>
<p>Manure application rates for phosphorus are based on: 1) <i>Phosphorus Index Only</i> 2) <i>Soil Test Phosphorus Only</i> 3) <i>Either PIO or STPO</i> 4) <i>Other</i></p>	<p>Phosphorus index only</p>
<p>Are there any nutrient “caps” to manure application?</p>	<p>Undetermined</p>
<p>Composition testing: <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on manures before application</i></p>	<p>Provides for annual manure analysis for nitrogen and phosphorus content,_ following University of Tennessee Extension guidelines, and soil analysis at a_ minimum of once every 5 years for phosphorus content (the results of these_ analyses are to be used in determining application rates for manure, litter, and other process wastewater);</p>
<p>Does your state require testing of manure for anything beyond nutrients, such as metals, pathogens, antibiotics, etc.?</p>	<p>Undetermined</p>
<p>Other land application highlights: <i>Additional restrictions for land application of manures</i></p>	<p>No other information</p>

<p>Other regulatory details: <i>Additional information on the regulation of land application of manures</i></p>	<p>No other information</p>
<p>General Assessment Questions</p>	
<p>Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change:</p>	<p>Undetermined</p>
<p>Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of manures that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links:</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of manures beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so:</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.</p>	<p>No other information</p>

Texas	
Regulator	
When was this last updated ?	2025
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Texas Commission on Environmental Quality (TCEQ)
Links to regulations	Title 30 TAC 321.31 to 321.47 Concentrated Animal Feeding Operations_ https://texreg.sos.state.tx.us/public/readtac\$ext.TacPage?sl=R&app=9&p_dir=&p_rloc=&p_tloc=&p_ploc=&pg=1&p_tac=&ti=30&pt=1&ch=321&rl=47
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Environmental
Other regulator info	No other information
Definitions	
How CAFOs are defined or categorized:	Large CAFO--Any AFO that stables or confines and feeds or maintains for a total of 45 days or more in any 12-month period equal to or more than the numbers of animals specified in any of the following categories:_ 1,000 cattle other than mature dairy cattle or veal calves. Cattle includes, but is not limited to, heifers, steers, bulls, and cow/calf pairs;_ 1,000 veal calves;_ 700 mature dairy cattle (whether milkers or dry cows);_ 2,500 swine, each weighing 55 pounds or more; 10,000 swine, each weighing less than 55 pounds;_ 500 horses;_ 10,000 sheep or lambs;_ 55,000 turkeys;_ 125,000 chickens (other than laying hens, if the operation does not use a liquid manure handling system);_ 30,000 laying hens or broilers (if the operation uses a liquid manure handling system), or 82,000 laying hens (if the operation does not use a liquid manure handling system); or_ 5,000 ducks (if the operation uses a liquid manure handling system), or 30,000 ducks (if

	<p>the operation does not use a liquid manure handling system). – Medium CAFO--Any AFO that discharges pollutants into water in the state either through a man-made ditch, flushing system, or other similar man-made device, or directly into water in the state with the following number of animals: 300 to 999 cattle other than mature dairy cattle or veal calves. Cattle includes, but is not limited to, heifers, steers, bulls, and cow/calf pairs; 200 to 699 mature dairy cattle (whether milking or dry cows); 300 to 999 veal calves; 750 to 2,499 swine each weighing 55 pounds or more, or 3,000 to 9,999 swine each weighing less than 55 pounds; 150 to 499 horses; 3,000 to 9,999 sheep or lambs; 16,500 to 54,999 turkeys; 37,500 to 124,999 chickens (other than laying hens if the operation does not use a liquid manure handling system); 9,000 to 29,999 laying hens or broilers (if the operation uses a liquid manure handling system), or 25,000 to 81,999 laying hens (if the operation does not use a liquid manure handling system); or 1,500 to 4,999 ducks (if the operation uses a liquid manure handling system), or 10,000 to 29,999 ducks (if the operation does not use a liquid manure handling system).</p>
How animal units are defined (if used):	Not used
NPDES permitting or other permitting requirements:	<p>The TCEQ administers permitting requirements under the Texas Pollutant Discharge Elimination System (TPDES) program, which has additional requirements beyond those outlined in federal rules. – While most operations that meet Texas CAFO definitions must apply for a general or individual TPDES permit, dry litter poultry facilities that are given the designation of no potential to discharge can instead obtain a certified Water Quality Management Plan (WQMP) from the Texas State Soil and Water Conservation Board (TSSWCB). The WQMP (which includes a nutrient management plan) contains many of the same provisions as Texas' comprehensive Pollution Prevention Plans. _</p>
Does the state require an NPDES permit for all Large CAFOs?	Undetermined
Does the state	Both

issue individual or general CAFO permits ?	
Are any other permits required for CAFOs or other large farms?	Undetermined
Other definitions needed to understand these regulations:	Agronomic rates-The land application of animal manure, sludge, or wastewater at rates of application in accordance with a plan for nutrient management which will enhance soil productivity and provide the crop or forage growth with needed nutrients for optimum health and growth based upon a realistic yield goal._ LMU = Land Management Unit_
Regulatory Details	
Setbacks: <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some geographical feature</i>	<p>(e) Buffers for LMUs. A sinkhole shall be protected with a 100-foot buffer from manure, sludge, and wastewater application. Alternatively, the CAFO may substitute a 35-foot wide vegetative buffer around a sinkhole where alternative conservation practices or field-specific conditions will provide pollutant reductions equivalent to or better than the reductions that would be achieved by the 100-foot buffer._</p> <p>–</p> <p>(g) The CAFO operator shall not locate a new LMU within the required well buffer zones identified in §321.38(b) of this title (relating to Control Facility Design Requirements Applicable to Concentrated Animal Feeding Operations (CAFOs)), unless additional wellhead protective measures are implemented that will prevent pollutants from entering the well and contaminating groundwater. An exception to the full well buffer zone for a private drinking water well or a water well used exclusively for agricultural irrigation may be approved by the executive director if a licensed Texas professional engineer or licensed Texas professional geoscientist provides accurate documentation showing that additional wellhead protective measures will be or have been implemented that will prevent pollutants from entering the well and contaminating groundwater. Additional protective measures may include a sanitary seal, annular seal, a steel sleeve, or surface slab. _</p> <p>(h) Vegetative buffer strips shall be maintained in accordance with Natural Resources Conservation Service (NRCS) Practice Standard Code 393. The minimum buffer shall be no less than 100 feet of vegetation to be maintained between manure, sludge, or</p>

	<p>wastewater application areas and water in the state. A buffer is not required for wastewater irrigation when applied by low-pressure, low-profile center pivot irrigation systems in areas of the state where the annual average rainfall is less than 25 inches per year. Land application of manure, sludge, and wastewater into surface water in the state is an unauthorized discharge and is prohibited. _</p> <p>(i) CAFOs introducing wastewater or chemicals to water wellheads for the purpose of irrigation shall install backflow prevention devices in accordance with requirements contained in 16 TAC Chapter 76 (relating to Water Well Drillers and Water Well Pump Installers) and Chapter 290 of this title (relating to Public Drinking Water), as appropriate.</p>
<p>Are setbacks more restrictive than CFR?</p>	<p>Undetermined</p>
<p>Timing, weather, or conditional application restrictions: <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather, seasons, or land characteristics (like slope)</i></p>	<p>Land application shall not occur when the ground is frozen or saturated or during rainfall events unless in accordance with §321.39(b)(3) of this title (relating to Operational Requirements Applicable to Concentrated Animal Feeding Operations (CAFOs)) or as approved by the commission._</p> <p>– Manure, sludge, or wastewater may be applied to the areas in the 100-year flood plain at agronomic rates not to exceed the hydrologic needs of the crop. _</p> <p>– Discharge of manure, sludge, or wastewater from a land management unit (LMU) is prohibited and shall not cause or contribute to a violation of surface water quality standards, contaminate groundwater, or create a nuisance condition. _</p> <p>– Irrigation practices shall be managed so as to minimize ponding or puddling of wastewater on the site, prevent tailwater discharges to waters in the state, and prevent the occurrence of nuisance conditions._</p> <p>– Nighttime application of manure, sludge, or wastewater by a CAFO shall be allowed only in areas with no occupied residence(s) within 1/4 mile from the outer boundary of the actual area receiving manure, sludge, or wastewater application. In areas with an occupied residence within 1/4 mile from the outer boundary of the actual area receiving manure, sludge, or wastewater application, application shall only be allowed from one hour after sunrise until one hour before sunset, unless the current resident owner or lessee of such residences have agreed in writing to specified nighttime applications.</p>
<p>Is there a restriction for land application of</p>	<p>Yes</p>

manure to saturated soils?	
Is there a restriction for land application of manure within floodplains?	Yes
Is there a restriction for land application of manure related to future rainfall?	Yes
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to frozen or snow-covered ground?	Yes
Are there restrictions to manure applications based on time of year or time of day?	No

<p>Are there restrictions to manure application based on slope?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Are there any other seasonal, timing, weather, or physical restrictions to manure applications not captured above?</p>	<p>Undetermined</p>
<p>Transfer of manure off-site: <i>Requirements related to the transfer of manures to other persons</i></p>	<p>Permits for existing dairy CAFOs in the major sole-source impairment zone in accordance with subsection (i) of this section may allow the operator to provide manure, litter, and wastewater to operators of third-party fields, i.e., areas of land not owned, operated, controlled, rented, or leased by an AFO owner or operator, that have been identified in the PPP. The dairy operator will be subject to enforcement action for violations of the land application requirements on any third-party field under contract. The permit provision must, at a minimum, include the following requirements: _</p> <p>(1) there must be a written contract between the dairy operator and the recipient that requires all transferred manure, litter, and wastewater to be beneficially applied to third-party fields identified in the PPP in accordance with the applicable requirements in §321.36 of this title (relating to Texas Pollutant Discharge Elimination System Requirements for Concentrated Animal Feeding Operations (CAFOs) and §321.40 of this title at an agronomic rate based on soil test phosphorus; _</p> <p>(2) the permit must prohibit the dairy operator from delivering manure, litter, or wastewater to an operator of a third-party field once the soil test phosphorus analysis shows a level equal to or greater than 200 ppm or after becoming aware that the third-party operator is not following §321.36 of this title and §321.40 of this title and the contract; _</p> <p>(3) third-party fields identified in the PPP on which manure, litter, or wastewater have been applied during the preceding year must be sampled annually by a nutrient management specialist and the samples analyzed in accordance with §321.36(g) of this title; and _</p> <p>(4) the dairy operator shall submit records to the appropriate regional office quarterly</p>

	that contain the name, locations, and amounts of manure, litter, or wastewater transferred to operators of third-party fields.
Are receivers of manure transfers from CAFOs required to follow the same regulations?	Undetermined
Nutrient or manure management plans: <i>Additional details on the NMP requirement. Note that some of this information may overlap with other sections</i>	<p>Nutrient management plan (NMP). _</p> <p>(1) The operator of a large CAFO shall develop and implement an NMP certified by a person or entity identified in §321.32(10) of this title (relating to Definitions) to be in accordance with the Texas Natural Resources Conservation Service NRCS Practice Standard Code 590. The plan shall include site-specific nutrient management practices that ensure appropriate agricultural utilization of nutrients in the manure, sludge, or wastewater. The NMP shall be updated annually. The operator shall determine the amount, in tons/acre or acre-inches/acre, of manure, sludge, and wastewater for each land management unit (LMU) using the following methodology: _</p> <p>(A) determine the phosphorus index rating using the Agronomy Technical Note No. 15 Phosphorus Assessment Tool of Texas; _</p> <p>(B) determine the maximum annual application rate using Appendix 5 of the NRCS Practice Standard Code 590 for Texas; _</p> <p>(C) determine the crop requirement or the crop removal rate, as appropriate, from the S Crops Table as contained in the Texas NRCS 590-Software Tool, site-specific historic CAFO yield data, or other sources as approved by the executive director; and _</p> <p>(D) account for: _</p> <p>(i) the results of soil tests required by §321.40(m)(1)(B) of this title (relating to Concentrated Animal Feeding Operation (CAFO) Land Application Requirements); _</p> <p>(ii) credits for all nitrogen in the soil that will be available for plant use; _</p> <p>(iii) the amount of nitrogen and phosphorus in the manure and wastewater to be applied; _</p> <p>(iv) consideration of multi-year phosphorus application (for any LMU where nutrients are applied at a rate based on crop phosphorus requirement, the methodology must account for single-year nutrient applications that supply more than the crop's annual phosphorus requirement); and _</p> <p>(v) all other additions of plant available nitrogen and phosphorus to the LMU (i.e., from sources other than manure or wastewater or credits for residual nitrogen). _</p> <p>(2) Terms of the NMP include the following: _</p> <p>(A) animal type and authorized head count; _</p> <p>(B) LMU and application acreage for each LMU; _</p> <p>(C) crops (including alternative crops) identified in the NMP with their yield goals for each LMU; _</p> <p>(D) the maximum application rates for nitrogen and phosphorus for each crop in each</p>

LMU; _

(E) the methodology in paragraph (1) of this subsection (including formulas, sources of data, protocols for making determinations, etc.) and actual data used to calculate application rates; and _

(F) any other factors necessary to determine the amounts of nitrogen and phosphorus to be applied. _

(3) Changes to a NMP. Any changes, except changes resulting from annual recalculation, must be submitted to the executive director. The NMP will be reviewed by the executive director to determine if changes require revisions to the terms of the NMP. Revisions to terms of the NMP can be substantial or non-substantial. _

(4) Substantial and non-substantial changes. Those changes that constitute a substantial change are defined in §321.32(56) of this title. Non-substantial changes include, but are not limited to, changes to the site-specific LMU information in the Phosphorus index Worksheet, changes to the maximum application rate of nitrogen or phosphorus to be land applied or changes in the phosphorus index rating. _

(5) If changes to the terms of the NMP are determined to be substantial, the changes must be incorporated into the permit in accordance with §321.33(g) of this title (relating to Applicability and Required Authorizations). _

(6) If changes to the terms of the NMP are determined to be non-substantial, the executive director will notify the permittee and include the revised permit in the permit record. _

(7) The CAFO operator shall create, maintain for five years, and make available to the executive director, upon request, a copy of the site-specific NMP and records of manure and wastewater application. _

(d) Compliance with the requirements of this section and applicable requirements of this subchapter constitute compliance with the provisions of 40 Code of Federal Regulations (CFR) §122.42(e)(1)(i) - (ix). _

(e) Buffers for LMUs. A sinkhole shall be protected with a 100-foot buffer from manure, sludge, and wastewater application. Alternatively, the CAFO may substitute a 35-foot wide vegetative buffer around a sinkhole where alternative conservation practices or field-specific conditions will provide pollutant reductions equivalent to or better than the reductions that would be achieved by the 100-foot buffer. _

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Cumulative Nutrient Management Plan_

All dairy CAFOs in a major sole-source impairment zone shall develop and operate under a comprehensive nutrient management plan (CNMP) certified by the Texas State Soil and Water Conservation Board. This CNMP shall be implemented not later than December 31, 2006. _

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Nutrient Utilization Plan_

Dairy CAFOs located in a major sole-source impairment zone shall develop a nutrient utilization plan (NUP) when the annual soil analysis for extractable phosphorus in zone 1 (0 - 6-inch incorporated; 0 - 2 or 2 - 6-inch if not incorporated) depth in an LMU is greater than 200 ppm. State-only CAFOs shall develop a NUP when the annual soil analysis for an LMU indicates the critical phosphorus levels in paragraph (2) of this subsection have been exceeded. A nutrient management plan, based on crop removal certified as meeting the NRCS Practice Standard Code 590 is equivalent to the requirements for a NUP. _

	<p>– Water Quality Management Plan_</p> <p>Dry litter poultry operations. A dry litter poultry CAFO shall only be required to obtain authorization by an individual water quality permit or a CAFO general permit in accordance with subsection (a), (b), or (c) of this section if it proposes to discharge or the executive director determines that a permit is necessary due to an unauthorized discharge; the operation's failure to comply with, or timely obtain, a certified water quality management plan approved by the Texas State Soil and Water Conservation Board; or other pertinent factors. Any dry litter poultry CAFO is authorized to be constructed and operated if the operation has a certified water quality management plan approved by the Texas State Soil and Water Conservation Board or is otherwise in compliance with the plan implementation schedule set forth in the notes following codified TWC, §26.302.</p>
<p>Do your NMP/MPS follow, comply with, or based on NRCS Technical Standard 590?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Application rates: <i>State regulations that restrict the rates at which manures are applied and methods needed to determine appropriate rates.</i></p>	<p>Nutrient requirement. _</p> <p>(1) Any land application of manure, sludge, and wastewater shall not exceed the planned crop requirements. Land application rates of manure, sludge, or wastewater shall be based on the total nutrient concentration, on a dry weight basis, where applicable. _</p> <p>(2) Critical phosphorus level. Land application of manure, sludge, or wastewater shall not exceed the crop removal rate when results of the annual soil analysis for extractable phosphorus indicate: _</p> <p>(A) a level greater than 200 parts per million (ppm) for a particular LMU; or _</p> <p>(B) a level greater than 350 ppm for an LMU where the average annual rainfall is 25 inches or less and erosion control is adequate to keep erosion at the soil loss tolerance (T) or less and the closest edge of the field is more than one mile from a named stream; or _</p> <p>(C) if ordered by the executive director to do so in order to protect water in the state. _</p> <p>(3) Dairy CAFOs located in a major sole-source impairment zone shall develop a nutrient utilization plan (NUP) when the annual soil analysis for extractable phosphorus in zone 1 (0 - 6-inch incorporated; 0 - 2 or 2 - 6-inch if not incorporated) depth in an LMU is greater than 200 ppm. State-only CAFOs shall develop a NUP when the annual soil analysis for an LMU indicates the critical phosphorus levels in paragraph (2) of this subsection have been exceeded. A nutrient management plan, based on crop removal certified as meeting the NRCS Practice Standard Code 590 is equivalent to the requirements for a NUP. _</p>

(A) If an operator is required to develop a NUP, the operator shall cease land application of manure, sludge, or wastewater to the affected area and may resume only after a NUP is implemented._

(B) The NUP must be developed and certified by: _

(i) an employee of the NRCS; _

(ii) a nutrient management specialist certified by the NRCS; _

(iii) the Texas State Soil and Water Conservation Board;_

(iv) Texas AgriLife Extension Service; _

(v) an agronomist or soil scientist on full-time staff at an accredited university located in the State of Texas; _

(vi) a Certified Professional Agronomist certified through the certification program of the American Society of Agronomy;_

(vii) a Certified Professional Soil Scientist certified through the certification program of the Soil Science Society of America; or _

(viii) a licensed geoscientist-soil scientist in Texas after approval by the executive director based on a determination by the executive director that another person or entity identified in this subparagraph cannot develop the plan in a timely manner. _

(C) After a NUP is implemented, the operator shall land apply in accordance with the NUP until soil phosphorus is reduced below the critical phosphorus level. Thereafter, the operator of a dairy CAFO located in a major sole-source impairment zone shall implement the requirements of the nutrient management plan certified in accordance with §321.36(c) of this title (relating to Texas Pollutant Discharge Elimination System General Requirements for Concentrated Animal Feeding Operations (CAFOs)) and the operator of other state-only CAFOs must follow the requirements in this section. _

(D) Land application under the terms of the NUP may begin 30 days after the plan is filed with the executive director, unless before that time the executive director has returned the plan for failure to comply with all the requirements of this subsection._

—
Sampling and Testing. _

(1) Initial sampling. Before commencing land application of manure, sludge, or wastewater on LMUs and before resuming land application on LMUs where manure, sludge, or wastewater was not applied during the preceding year, the operator shall: _

(A) collect and analyze at least one representative sample of manure, sludge (if applicable), and wastewater for total nitrogen, total phosphorus, and total potassium; _

(B) collect and analyze at least one representative soil sample from each LMU according to the procedures in paragraphs (4) and (5) of this subsection; and _

(C) utilize the results of these analyses in determining application rates for manure, sludge, and wastewater. _

(2) Annual Sampling. The operator shall: _

(A) collect and analyze at least one representative sample of manure, sludge (if applicable), and wastewater for total nitrogen, total phosphorus, and total potassium; _

(B) collect and analyze at least one representative soil sample from each LMU where manure, sludge, or wastewater was applied during the preceding year according to the procedures in paragraphs (4) and (5) of this subsection; and _

(C) utilize the results of these analyses in determining application rates for manure, sludge, and wastewater. _

(3) The operator shall make the most recent nutrient analysis available to any recipient of manure, sludge, or wastewater._

(4) Sampling procedures. The operator shall employ sampling procedures using accepted techniques of soil science for obtaining representative samples and analytical results. _

(A) Samples shall be collected using approved methods described in the agency's guidance RG-408 entitled "Soil Sampling for Concentrated Animal Feeding Operations." _

(B) Samples shall be collected by the operator or its designee and analyzed by a soil testing laboratory annually, except when crop rotations or inclement weather require a change in the sampling time. The pollution prevention plan shall contain documentation to explain the reasons for adjusting the sampling timeframe. _

(C) Obtain one composite sample for each LMU and per uniform soil type (soils with the same characteristics and texture) within the LMU. _

(D) Composite samples shall be comprised of 10 - 15 randomly sampled cores at a depth of zero to six inches. _

(5) Laboratory analysis. The operator shall have a laboratory analysis of the soil samples performed for physical and chemical parameters to include: nitrate reported as nitrogen in ppm; phosphorus (extractable, ppm, using Mehlich III extractant with Inductively Coupled Plasma analysis); potassium (extractable, ppm); sodium (extractable, ppm); magnesium (extractable, ppm); calcium (extractable, ppm); soluble salts (ppm) or electrical conductivity (deciSiemens/meter (dS/m) or millimhos/cm (mmhos/cm) determined from extract of 2:1 volume to volume (v/v) water/soil mixture); and soil water pH (soil:water, 1:2 ratio). _

(f) Soil sampling and testing procedures for dairy CAFOs, both state-only and Texas Pollutant Discharge Elimination System, located in a major sole-source impairment zone. _

(1) Initial sampling. Before commencing land application of manure, sludge, or wastewater on an LMU, the operator shall collect and analyze at least one representative soil sample from each of the LMUs according to the following procedures. The CAFO operator is not required to collect soil samples or report on LMUs where manure, litter, or wastewater has not been applied during the preceding year. The CAFO operator must comply with the initial sampling requirement before resuming land application to such LMUs. _

(2) Annual sampling. The TCEQ or its designee shall annually collect soil samples, according to the following procedures, for each LMU owned, operated, controlled, rented or leased by the CAFO operator where manure, litter, or wastewater was applied during the preceding year. The results of these analyses shall be used in determining the application rates for manure, sludge and wastewater. _

(3) Sampling procedures. Soil sampling procedures shall employ sampling procedures using accepted techniques of soil science for obtaining representative samples and analytical results. _

(A) Samples shall be collected using approved procedures described in this section and the agency's publication, RG-408 entitled "Soil Sampling for Concentrated Animal Feeding Operations." _

(B) Samples shall be collected by the Texas Commission on Environmental Quality or its designee and analyzed by a soil testing laboratory within the same 45-day time frame each year (from 45 days prior to until 45 days after the date of the previous year's sampling date), except when crop rotations or inclement weather require a change in

	<p>the sampling time frame. _</p> <p>(C) One composite sample shall be obtained for each soil depth zone per uniform soil type (soils with the same characteristics and texture) within each LMU. _</p> <p>(D) Composite samples shall be comprised of 10 - 15 randomly sampled cores obtained from each of the following soil depth zones: _</p> <p>(i) Zone 1: zero to six inches (for an LMU where the manure is incorporated directly into the soil) or zero to two inches (for an LMU where the manure is not incorporated into the soil). Wastewater is considered to be incorporated. If a zero to two-inch sample is required under this subsection, then an additional sample from the two to six-inch soil depth zone shall be obtained in accordance with the provisions of this section; and _</p> <p>(ii) Zone 2: six to 24 inches. _</p> <p>(4) Laboratory analysis. Laboratory analysis of the soil samples shall be performed for physical and chemical parameters to include: nitrate as nitrogen in parts per million (ppm), extractable phosphorus (ppm, using Mehlich III with Inductively Coupled Plasma (ICP)), potassium (extractable, ppm); sodium (extractable, ppm); magnesium (extractable, ppm); calcium (extractable, ppm); soluble salts (ppm) or electrical conductivity (deciSiemens/meter (dS/m) or millimhos/cm (mmhos/cm) - determined from extract of 2:1 volume to volume (v/v) water/soil mixture); and soil water pH.</p>
<p>Manure application rates for phosphorus are based on:</p> <p>1) <i>Phosphorus Index Only</i></p> <p>2) <i>Soil Test Phosphorus Only</i></p> <p>3) <i>Either PIO or STPO</i></p> <p>4) <i>Other</i></p>	<p>Soil test phosphorus only</p>
<p>Are there any nutrient "caps" to manure</p>	<p>Yes</p>

applicati on?	
Composi tion testing: <i>State regulatio ns that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performe d on manures before applicati on</i>	<p>In accordance with NRCS Practice Standard Code 590_ https://www.nrcs.usda.gov/sites/default/files/2022-09/Nutrient_Management_590_NHCP_CPS_2017.pdf _</p> <p>–</p> <p>(m) Sampling and Testing. _</p> <p>(1) Initial sampling. Before commencing land application of manure, sludge, or wastewater on LMUs and before resuming land application on LMUs where manure, sludge, or wastewater was not applied during the preceding year, the operator shall: _</p> <p>(A) collect and analyze at least one representative sample of manure, sludge (if applicable), and wastewater for total nitrogen, total phosphorus, and total potassium; _</p> <p>(B) collect and analyze at least one representative soil sample from each LMU according to the procedures in paragraphs (4) and (5) of this subsection; and _</p> <p>(C) utilize the results of these analyses in determining application rates for manure, sludge, and wastewater. _</p> <p>(2) Annual Sampling. The operator shall: _</p> <p>(A) collect and analyze at least one representative sample of manure, sludge (if applicable), and wastewater for total nitrogen, total phosphorus, and total potassium; _</p> <p>(B) collect and analyze at least one representative soil sample from each LMU where manure, sludge, or wastewater was applied during the preceding year according to the procedures in paragraphs (4) and (5) of this subsection; and _</p> <p>(C) utilize the results of these analyses in determining application rates for manure, sludge, and wastewater. _</p> <p>(3) The operator shall make the most recent nutrient analysis available to any recipient of manure, sludge, or wastewater. _</p> <p>(4) Sampling procedures. The operator shall employ sampling procedures using accepted techniques of soil science for obtaining representative samples and analytical results. _</p> <p>(A) Samples shall be collected using approved methods described in the agency's guidance RG-408 entitled "Soil Sampling for Concentrated Animal Feeding Operations." _</p> <p>–</p> <p>(B) Samples shall be collected by the operator or its designee and analyzed by a soil testing laboratory annually, except when crop rotations or inclement weather require a change in the sampling time. The pollution prevention plan shall contain documentation to explain the reasons for adjusting the sampling timeframe. _</p> <p>(C) Obtain one composite sample for each LMU and per uniform soil type (soils with the same characteristics and texture) within the LMU. _</p> <p>(D) Composite samples shall be comprised of 10 - 15 randomly sampled cores at a depth of zero to six inches. _</p> <p>(5) Laboratory analysis. The operator shall have a laboratory analysis of the soil samples performed for physical and chemical parameters to include: nitrate reported as nitrogen in ppm; phosphorus (extractable, ppm, using Mehlich III extractant with Inductively Coupled Plasma analysis); potassium (extractable, ppm); sodium (extractable, ppm); magnesium (extractable, ppm); calcium (extractable, ppm); soluble salts (ppm) or electrical conductivity (deciSiemens/meter (dS/m) or millimhos/cm (mmhos/cm) determined from extract of 2:1 volume to volume (v/v) water/soil mixture); and soil water pH (soil:water, 1:2 ratio).</p>

<p>Does your state require testing of manure for anything beyond nutrients, such as metals, pathogens, antibiotics, etc.?</p>	<p>Undetermined</p>
<p>Other land application highlights: <i>Additional restrictions for land application of manures</i></p>	<p>No other information</p>
<p>Other regulatory details: <i>Additional information on the regulation of land application of manures</i></p>	<p>Every CAFO covered under the Texas general and individual permit is required to develop a Pollution Prevention Plan (PPP). The elements of the PPP are thoroughly detailed within the General Permit and, in fact, PPP requirements are the majority of content</p>
<p>General Assessment Questions</p>	

<p>Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change:</p>	<p>Undetermined</p>
<p>Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of manures that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links:</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Within your state,</p>	<p>No</p>

<p>are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of manures beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so:</p>	
<p>Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If</p>	<p>No other information</p>

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please
briefly
describe
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Utah	
Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2019
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Utah Department of Environmental Quality (UTDEQ)
Links to regulations	UAC Title R317 Chapter 8 Utah Pollutant Discharge Elimination System_ (UPDES)_ R317-8-10. Animal Feeding Operations (AFOs) and Concentrated Animal Feeding Operations (CAFOs)._ https://rules.utah.gov/publicat/code/r317/r317-008.htm _ _ Utah Natural Resources Conservation Service (Utah NRCS) Practice Standard 590, Nutrient Management_ https://www.nrcs.usda.gov/sites/default/files/2022-09/Nutrient_Management_590_NHCP_CPS_2017.pdf
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Environmental
Other regulator info	No other information
Definitions	
How CAFOs are defined or categorized:	State definitions are not more restrictive than 40 CFR 122.23. State regulations on CAFOs are not more restrictive than 40 CFR. _ _ "Large CAFO" means an AFO that stables, houses, or confines the type and number of animals that fall within any of these ranges:_ (a) Beef, calves, heifers, and/or veal 1,000 or more_ (b) Cows (milking and dry) 700 or more_ (c) Layers, broilers (wet system) 30,000 or more_ (d) Other than layers (dry system) 125,000 or more_ (e) Layers (dry system) 82,000 or more_ (f) Turkeys 55,000 or more_ (g) Swine (55 pounds or more) 2,500 or more_ (h) Swine (less than 55 pounds) 10,000 or more_ (i) Sheep 10,000 or more_ (j) Horses 500 or more_ (k) Ducks (dry system) 30,000 or more_ (l) Ducks (wet system) 5,000 or more_ Medium CAFO_ Designated CAFO
How animal units are defined (if used):	Not used
NPDES permitting or other permitting requirements:	The UTDEQ administers the Utah Pollutant Discharge Elimination System (UPDES) permit program that contains many CAFO requirements. General permit used most often, but individual permits can be issued. Some operations require a state ground

	water permit.
Does the state require an NPDES permit for all Large CAFOs?	No
Does the state issue individual or general CAFO permits?	Both
Are any other permits required for CAFOs or other large farms?	Yes
Other definitions needed to understand these regulations:	No other information
Regulatory Details	
Setbacks: <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some geographical feature</i>	Refer to 40 CFR
Are setbacks more restrictive than CFR?	No
Timing, weather, or conditional application restrictions: <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather, seasons, or land characteristics (like slope)</i>	Refer to 40 CFR
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to saturated soils?	Yes
Is there a restriction for land application of manure within floodplains?	No
Is there a restriction for land application of manure related to future rainfall?	No
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to frozen or snow-covered ground?	Yes
Are there restrictions to	No

manure applications based on time of year or time of day?	
Are there restrictions to manure application based on slope?	Yes
Are there any other seasonal, timing, weather, or physical restrictions to manure applications not captured above?	Yes
Transfer of manure off-site: <i>Requirements related to the transfer of manures to other persons</i>	Permitted facilities only
Are receivers of manure transfers from CAFOs required to follow the same regulations?	No
Nutrient or manure management plans: <i>Additional details on the NMP requirement. Note that some of this information may overlap with other sections</i>	<p>An AFO or CAFO with a UPDES permit, and as provided in R317-8-10.9, shall have a facility- specific nutrient management plan (NMP). On a field-specific basis, NMPs for permitted facilities shall comply with the requirements and standards specified in a) R317-8-10; (b) Applicable federal regulations incorporated by reference in R317-8-1.10 and also specified in R317-8-10.1; (c) The requirements of 40 CFR 122.42(e)(1)(i) through (viii) and the practices and protocols that are required to be identified in those provisions; (d) Technical Standards in R317-8-10.6; and (e) nutrient management plan requirements in the UPDES permit. (2) An NMP for permitted facilities shall be approved by an NRCS certified planner._</p> <p>The requirements of the Utah Natural Resources Conservation Service (Utah NRCS) Practice Standard 590, Nutrient Management, dated January 2013, are hereby incorporated by reference as the Technical Standards, for purposes of this rule and 40 CFR 412.4(c)(2). Implementation of these standards at a facility requires evaluation on a field- specific basis. Detailed at: https://www.nrcs.usda.gov/sites/default/files/2022-09/Nutrient_Management_590_NHCP_CPS_2017.pdf _</p> <p>Permitted CAFOs application rates based on phosphorus index and have a rate cap of 120 ppm of P in soil.</p>
Do your NMP/MMPS follow, comply with, or based on NRCS Technical Standard 590?	Yes
Application rates: <i>State regulations that restrict the rates at which</i>	An AFO or CAFO with a UPDES permit, and as provided in R317-8-10.9, shall have a facility- specific nutrient management plan (NMP). On a field-specific basis, NMPs for permitted facilities shall

<p><i>manures are applied and methods needed to determine appropriate rates.</i></p>	<p>comply with the requirements and standards specified in a) R317-8-10; (b) Applicable federal regulations incorporated by reference in R317-8-1.10 and also specified in R317-8-10.1; (c) The requirements of 40 CFR 122.42(e)(1)(i) through (viii) and the practices and protocols that are required to be identified in those provisions; (d) Technical Standards in R317-8-10.6; and (e) nutrient management plan requirements in the UPDES permit. (2) An NMP for permitted facilities shall be approved by an NRCS certified planner._ The requirements of the Utah Natural Resources Conservation Service (Utah NRCS) Practice Standard 590, Nutrient Management, dated January 2013, are hereby incorporated by reference as the Technical Standards, for purposes of this rule and 40 CFR 412.4(c)(2). Implementation of these standards at a facility requires evaluation on a field- specific basis. Detailed at:_ https://www.nrcs.usda.gov/sites/default/files/2022-09/Nutrient_Management_590_NHCP_CPS_2017.pdf _ Permitted CAFOs application rates based on phosphorus index and have a rate cap of 120 ppm of P in soil.</p>
<p>Manure application rates for phosphorus are based on: 1) <i>Phosphorus Index Only</i> 2) <i>Soil Test Phosphorus Only</i> 3) <i>Either PIO or STPO</i> 4) <i>Other</i></p>	<p>Phosphorus index only</p>
<p>Are there any nutrient “caps” to manure application?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Composition testing: <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on manures before application</i></p>	<p>Manure composition testing of nutrients required for permitted CAFOs.</p>
<p>Does your state require testing of manure for anything beyond nutrients, such as metals, pathogens, antibiotics, etc.?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Other land application highlights: <i>Additional restrictions for land application of manures</i></p>	<p>No other information</p>
<p>Other regulatory details:</p>	<p>No other information</p>

<p><i>Additional information on the regulation of land application of manures</i></p>	
General Assessment Questions	
<p>Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change:</p>	<p>Undetermined</p>
<p>Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of manures that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links:</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of manures beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so:</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.</p>	<p>No other information</p>

Vermont Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2025
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Vermont Agency of Agriculture, Food, and Markets (VAAFM)_ Vermont Department of Environmental Control (VDEC)_ Vermont Agency of Natural Resources (VANR) (NPDES)_
Links to regulations	Vermont Statutes Annotated (VSA), Title 6, Chapter 215, Agricultural Water_ Quality https://law.justia.com/codes/vermont/2016/title-6/chapter-215/
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	More than one agency
Other regulator info	No other information
Definitions	
How CAFOs are defined or categorized:	LFO: means Large Farm Operations_ LFO Facility: means the production area, the barns, the land devoted to waste storage and other agricultural structures, including those created as waste management systems constructed to prevent direct discharges to waters of the state or to prevent groundwater from exceeding state groundwater quality standards, designed, adapted, or used to operate a farm in which the barn or barns are designed to house more than:_ 700 mature dairy animals whether milked or dry; or_ 700 bulls; or_ 1000 cattle, cow/calf pairs, young stock, or heifers; or_ 1000 veal calves; or_ 2500 swine weighing over 55 pounds; or_ 10,000 swine weighing less than 55 pounds; or_ 500 horses; or_ 10,000 sheep or lambs; or_ 55,000 turkeys; or_ 30,000 laying hens with a liquid manure handling system; or_ 82,000 laying hens without a liquid manure handling system;_ 125,000 chickens other than laying hens without a liquid manure handling system; or_ 5000 ducks with a liquid manure handling system; or_ 30,000 ducks without a liquid manure handling system; or_ any other animal type and number that the Secretary may deem to fit this category if:_ 1. Such livestock or domestic fowl are confined:_ for more than 45 days; and_ in an area where vegetation is not sustained during the growing season; and_ 2. Such livestock or domestic fowl are in a barn or adjacent barns owned by the same person; or_

	<p>3. The barns, collectively designed to house the threshold number of livestock or domestic fowl, owned by the same person, share a common border or_</p> <p>4. The barns, owned by the same person, which have the potential to collectively house the threshold number of livestock or domestic fowl, share a common waste disposal system; or,_</p> <p>5. If any barns, owned by any person, where the threshold number of livestock or domestic fowl are collectively housed, share a common waste disposal system or fields._</p> <p>MFO:_</p> <p>Medium Farm Operation (MFO) means an AFO which houses_</p> <p>200 to 699 mature dairy cows, whether milked or dry; 300 to 999 young stock or heifers;_</p> <p>300 to 999 veal calves;_</p> <p>300 to 999 cattle or cow/calf pairs;_</p> <p>750 to 2,499 swine weighing over 55 pounds;_</p> <p>3,000 to 9,999 swine weighing less than 55 pounds;_</p> <p>150 to 499 horses;_</p> <p>3,000 to 9,999 sheep or lambs; 16,500 to 54,999 turkeys;_</p> <p>9,000 to 29,999 laying hens or broilers with a liquid manure system; 25,000 to 81,999 laying hens without a liquid manure handling system; 1,500 to 4,999 ducks with a liquid manure handling system;_</p> <p>10,000 to 29,999 ducks without a liquid manure handling system; or, any other animal type and number that the Secretary may designate.</p>
How animal units are defined (if used):	Not used
NPDES permitting or other permitting requirements:	<p>VAAFM administers AFO permits utilizing the state LFO_ and MFO definitions, which mirror the federal CAFO definition._</p> <p>_</p> <p>The state has a NPDES CAFO general permit. There are currently no permitted CAFOs in Vermont under the NDPEs program._</p> <p>The NPS regulations require that all large farms obtain a Large Farm Operation permit and all medium sized farms obtain a Medium Farm General Permit from the Agency of Agriculture, Food & Markets.</p>
Does the state require an NPDES permit for all Large CAFOs?	No
Does the state issue individual or general CAFO permits?	General
Are any other permits required for CAFOs or other large farms?	Yes
Other definitions needed	No other information

to understand these regulations:	
Regulatory Details	
Setbacks: <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some geographical feature</i>	Non-point-source regulations (which include 3 sets of rules; Required Agricultural Practices and MFO and LFO rules) are 10 feet between adjoining ditches, 25 feet between adjoining surface waters and surface inlets, and well setbacks are variable depending on the status of the well._ CAFO regulations for Medium Farm General Permit : Surface waters and conduits to surface waters, including ditches that are conduits to surface water, that are situated downslope of manure, compost, process wastewater, or fertilizer applications must be buffered from croplands by at least 25 ft. of dense perennial vegetation. Surface waters, ditches, and conduits to surface waters that are situated upslope of manure, compost, process wastewater, or fertilizer applications shall be buffered in accordance with NPS regulations above.
Are setbacks more restrictive than CFR?	Undetermined
Timing, weather, or conditional application restrictions: <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather, seasons, or land characteristics (like slope)</i>	As required by the Vermont Agency of Agriculture, Food & Markets' (VAAF) Required Agricultural Practices (RAPs), between December 15 and April 1, no manure or other agricultural wastes (including: compost and spoiled feed) may be spread on agricultural fields throughout Vermont.
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to saturated soils?	Yes
Is there a restriction for land application of manure within floodplains?	Yes
Is there a restriction for land application of manure related to future rainfall?	Yes
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to frozen or snow-covered ground?	Yes
Are there restrictions to manure applications based on time of year or time of day?	Yes
Are there restrictions to	Yes

manure application based on slope?	
Are there any other seasonal, timing, weather, or physical restrictions to manure applications not captured above?	Undetermined
Transfer of manure off-site: <i>Requirements related to the transfer of manures to other persons</i>	<p>Refer to 40 CFR. When a MFO exports MFO-generated manure, compost, or other wastes from the MFO, the MFO must ensure management of exported manure, compost, or other wastes is in compliance with the Required Agricultural Practices. When a MFO imports manure, compost, or other wastes to the MFO, the MFO must perform nutrient analysis, or use current nutrient analysis from source, of any import of manure, compost, or other wastes and use this information to document and incorporate the materials into the NMP; and ensure management of imported manure, compost, or other wastes is in compliance with the Required Agricultural Practices._</p> <p>MFO farms are not required to be responsible for manure after they export it, however the receiving farm would be regulated by NPS regulations likely under the RAPs. When a MFO or LFO imports manure, compost, or other wastes, it must perform nutrient analysis, or use current nutrient analysis from source, of any import of manure, compost, or other wastes and use this information to document and incorporate the materials into the NMP; and ensure management of imported manure, compost, or other wastes is in compliance with the Required Agricultural Practices.</p>
Are receivers of manure transfers from CAFOs required to follow the same regulations?	Undetermined
Nutrient or manure management plans: <i>Additional details on the NMP requirement. Note that some of this information may overlap with other sections</i>	<p>NMP the system by which nutrient imports and exports and animal waste generation, storage, and use is handled for the purpose of minimizing the entry of sediment and nutrients into waters of the State and groundwater, while planning nutrient applications and field management practices for optimum forage and crop yields including the related management aspects of fertilizer nutrients, conservation practices, animal mortalities, clean water, chemical handling, waste and soil testing, and record keeping. An NMP must include all production areas and land application areas owned, rented, or operated by the farm operating under the MFO GP._</p> <p>It manages the amount, form, placement, and timing of plant nutrient applications to obtain optimum forage and crop yields, minimize the entry of sediment and nutrients into waters of the State and groundwater._</p>
Do your NMP/MMPS	Yes

follow, comply with, or based on NRCS Technical Standard 590?	
Application rates: <i>State regulations that restrict the rates at which manures are applied and methods needed to determine appropriate rates.</i>	VT NRCS 590 Conservation Practice Standard limits application rates on all certified small farm operations (CSFO's), MFO and LFO's. All small farm operations (SFO) must utilize agronomic rates.
Manure application rates for phosphorus are based on: 1) <i>Phosphorus Index Only</i> 2) <i>Soil Test Phosphorus Only</i> 3) <i>Either PIO or STPO</i> 4) <i>Other</i>	Phosphorus index only
Are there any nutrient "caps" to manure application?	Yes
Composition testing: <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on manures before application</i>	CSFO, MFO and LFO : Every waste that is land applied shall have its nutrient value tested using appropriate testing protocols and integrated into the NMP nutrient application recommendations.
Does your state require testing of manure for anything beyond nutrients, such as metals, pathogens, antibiotics, etc.?	Undetermined
Other land application highlights: <i>Additional restrictions for land application of manures</i>	No other information
Other regulatory details: <i>Additional information on the regulation of land application of manures</i>	Caps on application rates are included in the VT 590 NRCS Standard
General Assessment Questions	
Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please	Undetermined

list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change:	
Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of manures that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links:	No
Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of manures beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so:	No
Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.	No other information

Virginia	
Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2019
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Virginia Department of Environmental Quality (VDEQ)
Links to regulations	9VAC25-31-10 et seq, there are several chapters that pertain to CAFOs. 9VAC25-31-130. VPDES Concentrated Animal Feeding Operations._ https://law.lis.virginia.gov/admincode/title9/agency25/chapter31/section130/ _ _ 2015 Virginia Animal Agriculture Program Assessment:_ https://www.epa.gov/sites/production/files/2015-07/documents/virginia_animal_agriculture_program_assessment_final_2.pdf _
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Environmental
Other regulator info	No other information
Definitions	
How CAFOs are defined or categorized:	9VAC25-192-10._ "Animal feeding operation" means a lot or facility where the following conditions are met: _ 1. Animals have been, are, or will be stabled or confined and fed or maintained for a total of 45 days or more in any 12-month period; and _ 2. Crops, vegetation, forage growth or post-harvest residues are not sustained in the normal growing season over any portion of the operation of the lot or facility. _ Two or more Animal Feeding Operations under common ownership are a single Animal Feeding Operation for the purposes of determining the number of animals at an operation, if they adjoin each other, or if they use a common area or system for the disposal of wastes._ "Confined Animal Feeding Operation," for the purposes of this regulation, has the same meaning as an "Animal Feeding Operation." _ 9VAC25-630-10- "Confined poultry feeding operation" means any confined Animal Feeding Operation with 200 or more animal units of poultry. This equates to 20,000 chickens or 11,000 turkeys, regardless of animal age or sex._ Also defined in 9VAC25-31-10
How animal units are defined (if used):	As defined in 9VAC25-32-10 and 9VAC25-192-10 "300 animal units" means 300,000 pounds of live animal weight, or the following numbers and types of animals: _

	<p>a. 300 slaughter and feeder cattle; _</p> <p>b. 200 mature dairy cattle (whether milked or dry cows); _</p> <p>c. 750 swine each weighing over 25 kilograms (approximately 55 pounds); _</p> <p>d. 150 horses; _</p> <p>e. 3,000 sheep or lambs; _</p> <p>f. 16,500 turkeys; _</p> <p>g. 30,000 laying hens or broilers.</p>
<p>NPDES permitting or other permitting requirements:</p>	<p>Concentrated Animal Feeding Operations as defined in 9VAC25-31-10 or designated in accordance with subsection B of this section are point sources that require VPDES permits for discharges. Once an operation is defined as a CAFO, the VPDES requirements for CAFOs apply with respect to all animals in confinement at the operation and all manure, litter and process wastewater generated by those animals or the production of those animals, regardless of the type of animal. Only discharging CAFOs are required to obtain a VPDES CAFO individual permit._</p> <p>Two or more Animal Feeding Operations under common ownership are considered, for the purposes of this chapter, to be a single Animal Feeding Operation if they adjoin each other or if they use a common area or system for the disposal of wastes._</p> <p>_</p> <p>The board may designate any Animal Feeding Operation as a concentrated Animal Feeding Operation upon determining that it is a significant contributor of pollution to surface waters._</p> <p>In order to manage pollutants from an Animal Feeding Operation, the owner shall be required to obtain coverage under the Virginia Pollution Abatement (VPA) general permit or an individual VPA permit provided that the owner has not been required to obtain a Virginia Pollutant Discharge Elimination System (VPDES) permit. The owner shall comply with the requirements of this chapter and the permit._</p> <p>VDEQ covers CAFOs with Individual VPDES CAFO permits._</p> <p>Most poultry and livestock operations are covered by a General VPA permits. There is also the option to cover an operation with an individual VPA permit._</p> <p>Most permitted farms that meet the statute prescribed threshold are covered by a VPA general permit. A farm that meets the prescribed threshold, is only required to be covered by one Animal Waste permit; i.e., if the operation needs to be covered by a VPDES CAFO, then the VPA permit is not required._</p> <p>_</p> <p>9VAC25-192-20. This general permit regulation governs the pollutant management activities at Animal Feeding Operations having 300 or more animal units utilizing a liquid manure collection and storage system not covered by a Virginia Pollutant Discharge Elimination System (VPDES) permit and animal waste utilized or stored by animal waste end-users. These Animal Feeding Operations may operate and maintain treatment works for waste storage, treatment, or recycling and may perform land application of manure, wastewater, compost, or sludges._</p> <p>9VAC25-630-20. Regulations specific to poultry waste at confined poultry feeding operations not covered by a Virginia Pollutant Discharge Elimination System (VPDES) permit and poultry waste utilized or stored by poultry waste</p>

	end-users or poultry waste brokers. It establishes requirements for proper nutrient management, waste storage, and waste tracking and accounting of poultry waste.
Does the state require an NPDES permit for all Large CAFOs?	No
Does the state issue individual or general CAFO permits?	Both
Are any other permits required for CAFOs or other large farms?	Yes
Other definitions needed to understand these regulations:	No other information
Regulatory Details	
Setbacks: <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some geographical feature</i>	Waste shall not be land applied within buffer zones. Buffer zones at waste application sites shall, at a minimum, be maintained as follows: _ a. Distance from occupied dwellings not on the permittee's property: 200 feet (unless the occupant of the dwelling signs a waiver of the buffer zone); _ b. Distance from water supply wells or springs: 100 feet;_ c. Distance from surface water courses: 100 feet (without a permanent vegetated buffer) or 35 feet (if a permanent vegetated buffer exists). Other site-specific conservation practices may be approved by the department that will provide pollutant reductions equivalent or better than the reductions that would be achieved by the 100-foot buffer or 35-foot wide vegetated buffer;_ d. Distance from rock outcropping (except limestone): 25 feet; _ e. Distance from limestone outcroppings: 50 feet; and _ f. Waste shall not be applied in such a manner that it would discharge to sinkholes that may exist in the area.
Are setbacks more restrictive than CFR?	Yes
Timing, weather, or conditional application restrictions: <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather, seasons, or land characteristics</i>	There are prescribed requirements for timing in each NMP based on the crop being grown. The NMP is required to be followed by the permit. _ _ 9VAC630-50. The timing of land application of poultry waste shall be according to the schedule contained in the NMP, except that no waste may be applied to ice covered or snow covered ground or to soils that are saturated. Poultry waste may be applied to frozen ground within the NMP scheduled times only under the following conditions:_ a. Slopes are not greater than 6.0%; b. A minimum of a 200-foot vegetative or adequate crop residue buffer is maintained between the application area and

<i>(like slope)</i>	all surface water courses; c. Only those soils characterized by USDA as "well drained" with good infiltration are used; and d. At least 60% uniform cover by vegetation or crop residue is present in order to reduce surface runoff and the potential for leaching of nutrients to ground water.
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to saturated soils?	Yes
Is there a restriction for land application of manure within floodplains?	Yes
Is there a restriction for land application of manure related to future rainfall?	No
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to frozen or snow-covered ground?	Yes
Are there restrictions to manure applications based on time of year or time of day?	Yes
Are there restrictions to manure application based on slope?	Yes
Are there any other seasonal, timing, weather, or physical restrictions to manure applications not captured above?	Yes, See 4VAC50-85-10- et seq. for more details of requirements of what must be included in an NMP.
Transfer of manure off-site: <i>Requirements related to the</i>	Animal Waste transfers: see requirements in 9VAC25-192-10 et seq. to include section 70, 80 & 90._ Poultry Waste transfers: see requirements in 9VAC25-630-10 et seq. to include section 50, 60, 70 & 80._

<p><i>transfer of manures to other persons</i></p>	<p>– Animal waste generated by this facility may be transferred from the permittee to another person if one or more of the following conditions are met: _</p> <p>a. Animal waste generated by this facility may be transferred off-site for land application or another acceptable use approved by the department, if: _</p> <p>(1) The sites where the animal waste will be utilized are included in this permitted facility's approved nutrient management plan; or _</p> <p>(2) The sites where the animal waste will be utilized are included in another permitted facility's approved nutrient management plan. _</p> <p>b. Animal waste generated by this facility may be transferred off-site without identifying in the permittee's approved nutrient management plan the fields where such waste will be utilized, if one of the following conditions are met: _</p> <p>(1) The animal waste is registered with the Virginia Department of Agriculture and Consumer Services in accordance with regulations adopted pursuant to subdivision A 2 of § 3.2-3607 of the Code of Virginia; or _</p> <p>(2) When the permittee transfers to another person more than 10 tons of solid or semi-solid animal waste (solid or semi-solid animal waste contains less than 85% moisture) or more than 6,000 gallons of liquid animal waste (liquid animal waste contains 85% or more moisture) in any 365-day period, the permittee shall maintain records in accordance with Part I B 16. _</p> <p>Animal waste may be transferred from a permittee to another person without identifying the fields where such waste will be utilized in the permittee's approved nutrient management plan if the following conditions are met: _</p> <p>a. When a permittee transfers to another person more than 10 tons of solid or semi-solid animal waste (solid or semi-solid animal waste contains less than 85% moisture) or more than 6,000 gallons of liquid animal waste (liquid animal waste contains 85% or more moisture) in any 365-day period, the permittee shall provide that person with: _</p> <p>(1) Permittee's name, address, and permit number; _</p> <p>(2) A copy of the most recent nutrient analysis of the animal waste; and _</p> <p>(3) An animal waste fact sheet. _</p> <p>b. When a permittee transfers to another person more than 10 tons of solid or semi-solid animal waste (solid or semi-solid animal waste contains less than 85% moisture) or more than 6,000 gallons of liquid animal waste (liquid animal waste contains 85% or more moisture) in any 365-day period, the permittee shall keep a record of the following: _</p> <p>(1) The recipient name and address; _</p> <p>(2) The amount of animal waste received by the person; _</p> <p>(3) The date of the transaction; _</p> <p>(4) The nutrient analysis of the animal waste; _</p> <p>(5) The locality in which the recipient intends to utilize the animal waste (i.e., nearest town or city and zip code); _</p> <p>(6) The name of the stream or waterbody, if known, to the recipient that is nearest to the animal waste utilization or storage site; and _</p> <p>(7) The signed waste transfer records form acknowledging the receipt of the following: _</p> <p>(a) The animal waste; _</p> <p>(b) The nutrient analysis of the animal waste; and _</p>
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	<p>(c) An animal waste fact sheet. _</p> <p>c. Permittees shall maintain the records required by Part I B 16 a and b for at least three years after the date of the transaction and shall make them available to department personnel upon request.</p>
Are receivers of manure transfers from CAFOs required to follow the same regulations?	No
<p>Nutrient or manure management plans:</p> <p><i>Additional details on the NMP requirement. Note that some of this information may overlap with other sections</i></p>	<p>4VAC50-85-10- et seq: NMP plan developed or approved by the Department of Conservation and Recreation that requires proper storage, treatment, and management of animal waste and limits accumulation of excess nutrients in soils and leaching or discharge of nutrients into state waters; except that for an animal waste end-user who is not covered under the general permit, the requirements of 9VAC25-192-90 constitute the NMP._</p> <p>The owner shall obtain Department of Conservation and Recreation approval of a nutrient management plan for the Animal Feeding Operation prior to the submittal of the registration statement. The owner shall attach to the registration statement a copy of the approved nutrient management plan and a copy of the letter from the Department of Conservation and Recreation certifying approval of the nutrient management plan that was developed by a certified nutrient management planner in accordance with § 10.1-104.2 of the Code of Virginia. The owner shall implement the approved nutrient management plan._</p> <p>The permittee shall implement a nutrient management plan (NMP) developed by a certified nutrient management planner in accordance with § 10.1-104.2 of the Code of Virginia and approved by the Department of Conservation and Recreation and maintain the plan on site. The NMP shall address the form, source, amount, timing, and method of application of nutrients on each field to achieve realistic production goals, while minimizing nitrogen and phosphorus loss to ground and surface waters. The terms of the NMP shall be enforceable through this permit. The NMP shall contain at a minimum the following information: _</p> <p>a. Site map indicating the location of the waste storage facilities and the fields where waste will be applied; _</p> <p>b. Site evaluation and assessment of soil types and potential productivities; _</p> <p>c. Nutrient management sampling including soil and waste monitoring; _</p> <p>d. Storage and land area requirements; _</p> <p>e. Calculation of waste application rates; and _</p> <p>f. Waste application schedules.</p>
Do your NMP/MMPS follow, comply with, or based on NRCS Technical Standard 590?	Yes
Application rates:	Land application requirements. An animal waste end-user who (i) receives

<p><i>State regulations that restrict the rates at which manures are applied and methods needed to determine appropriate rates.</i></p>	<p>more than 10 tons of solid or semi-solid animal waste (solid or semi-solid animal waste contains less than 85% moisture) or more than 6,000 gallons of liquid animal waste (liquid animal waste contains 85% or more moisture) from an owner or operator of an Animal Feeding Operation covered by a VPA or VPDES permit and (ii) land applies animal waste shall follow appropriate land application requirements as outlined in this subsection. The application of animal waste shall be managed to minimize adverse water quality impacts. Soil at the land application sites shall be monitored as specified below Composite, once every 3 years, pH Phosphorus Potash Calcium Magnesium Soil monitoring shall be conducted at a depth of between 0-6 inches, unless otherwise specified in the facility's approved nutrient management plan</p>
<p>Manure application rates for phosphorus are based on: 1) Phosphorus Index Only 2) Soil Test Phosphorus Only 3) Either PIO or STPO 4) Other</p>	<p>Phosphorus index only</p>
<p>Are there any nutrient “caps” to manure application?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Composition testing: <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on manures before application</i></p>	<p>Waste shall be monitored as specified below. Additional waste monitoring may be required in the facility's approved nutrient management plan: Magnesium Moisture Content Total Kjeldahl Nitrogen Ammonia Nitrogen Total Phosphorus Total Potassium Calcium Composite, once a year</p>
<p>Does your state require testing of manure for anything beyond nutrients, such as metals, pathogens, antibiotics, etc.?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Other land application highlights: <i>Additional</i></p>	<p>No other information</p>

<i>restrictions for land application of manures</i>	
Other regulatory details: <i>Additional information on the regulation of land application of manures</i>	http://www.dcr.virginia.gov/soil-and-water/nmplnr_ http://www.dcr.virginia.gov/document/standardsandcriteria.pdf
General Assessment Questions	
Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change:	Undetermined
Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of manures that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links:	Yes
Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of manures beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so:	No
Is the land application of septage,	No other information

composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.

Washington Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2025
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Department of Ecology State of Washington (ECY/Ecology)_ Washington State Department of Agriculture (WDSA)_
Links to regulations	Includes permits, guidelines, regulation etc. links_ https://ecology.wa.gov/Regulations-Permits/Permits-certifications/Concentrated-animal-feeding-operation
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	More than one agency
Other regulator info	Ecology administers, develops, and processes CAFO permits. WSDA inspects permitted facilities and provides technical support.
Definitions	
How CAFOs are defined or categorized:	<p>CAFO: Animals are or will be stabled or confined and fed or maintained for a total of 45 days or more in any 12-month period. The same animal individuals need not be confined for the entire 45 day period. Crops, vegetation, forage growth, or post-harvest residues are not sustained in the normal growing season over any portion of the lot or facility where the animals are confined. _</p> <p>A CAFO permit is required for CAFOs that have a discharge to surface water that is not agricultural stormwater or have a discharge to groundwater, and confines the following numbers of animals mature dairy cows (≥ 200), veal calves (≥ 300), cattle (≥ 300), swine greater than or equal to 55 lbs. (≥ 750), swine less than 55 lbs. (≥ 3000), horses (≥ 150), sheep or lambs (≥ 3000), turkeys (≥ 16500), laying hens or broilers w/liquid waste system (9000), chickens other than layers w/dry waste system (≥ 37500), laying hens w/dry waste system ($\geq 25,000$), ducks w/liquid waste system (10000), ducks w/dry waste system (1500), other animal type (designated by Ecology to be a CAFO). _</p> <p>A Small CAFO (with animal numbers less than above) can be designated as a significant contributor of pollutants to surface or groundwater by Ecology and required to obtain either a CAFO State Waste Discharge Permit or a Combined State Waste Discharge and NPDES CARO Permit. _</p> <p>The WA permits do not make a distinction between large and medium operations, just CAFOs and small CAFOs. Special Condition S1, Table 2.</p>
How animal units are defined (if used):	Not used
NPDES permitting or other permitting requirements:	<p>A CAFO permit is required if the operation meets the definition in permit special condition S1, Table 2. In short, the operation is above a size threshold and has a discharge to surface or groundwater. _</p> <p>— Exception: Agricultural stormwater discharges from land</p>

	<p>application fields. However, the operation must have the documentation to show that a land application field discharge is actually agricultural stormwater._</p> <p>– A small CAFO must obtain a CAFO permit if the permitting authority (Ecology) determines that the operation is a significant contributor of pollutants and designates the operation to be a small CAFO._</p> <p>– Because there are two CAFO permits, one Combined Permit for surface and groundwater discharges, and one State Only Permit for groundwater discharges only, an operation that only has a groundwater discharge may choose which permit to obtain coverage under. Operations with a surface water discharge must obtain coverage under the Combined permit._</p> <p>– Occasionally an individual permit is used if the site characteristics indicate that the general permit will not address _</p> <p>– If operating a digester, an air quality permit may be required._ If accepting of-site waste materials above certain quantities a solid waste handling permit may be required.</p>
Does the state require an NPDES permit for all Large CAFOs?	No
Does the state issue individual or general CAFO permits?	Both
Are any other permits required for CAFOs or other large farms?	Yes
Other definitions needed to understand these regulations:	No other information
Regulatory Details	
<p>Setbacks: <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some geographical feature</i></p>	<p>Combined Permit: Unless the Permittee exercises one of the compliance alternatives provided for in special conditions S4.N.1 through S4.M.3, manure, litter, process wastewater, or other organic by-products may not be applied closer than 100 feet to any down-gradient surface waters, open tile line intake structures, sinkholes, agricultural or drinking water well heads, or other conduits to surface or groundwaters._</p> <p>1. Vegetated buffer compliance alternative As a compliance alternative, the Permittee may substitute the 100-foot setback with a 35-foot wide vegetated buffer where application of manure, litter, process wastewater, or other organic-by-products is prohibited._</p> <p>2. Berm compliance alternative As a compliance alternative, the Permittee may substitute the 100-foot setback with a berm which</p>

	<p>prevents surface water discharge from the land application field and where application of manure, litter, process wastewater, or other organic by-products is prohibited. Berms must be designed, installed, and maintained to perform their function considering the following factors: _</p> <p>a. Weather characteristics for the area where the facility is located such as _ precipitation, storm events, and volume of field run-off. _</p> <p>b. Land application methods used by the Permittee, form of land applied manure, litter, process wastewater, or other organic by-products, timing of land application, and application rates. _</p> <p>c. Field characteristics such as soil types, infiltration rates, field slope, presence of other conduits to surface waters (e.g. drainage ditches, tile drains), crop type, cropping cycles, and flooding. _</p> <p>d. Installation timing, time from installation to full performance, and maintenance period and activities, _</p> <p>3. Alternative practices compliance alternative. _</p> <p>As a compliance alternative, the Permittee may demonstrate that a field discharge management practice is not necessary because implementation of alternative conservation practices or field-specific conditions will provide pollutant reductions equivalent or better than the reductions that would be achieved by the 100-foot application setback. State Only Permit: No buffers defined as no discharge to surface water is allowed by the permit from land application fields. The Permittee must take the actions necessary, or implement the appropriate technologies, to prevent surface water discharge.</p>
<p>Are setbacks more restrictive than CFR?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Timing, weather, or conditional application restrictions: <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather, seasons, or land characteristics (like slope)</i></p>	<p>No land application of manure, litter, process wastewater, or other organic byproducts may occur: _</p> <p>i. To fields with a frozen surface crust (2 inches) or deeper, or if the soil is at or below zero degrees Celsius (32 degrees Fahrenheit). _</p> <p>ii. To fields that are snow covered. _</p> <p>iii. To fields with saturated soil. _</p> <p>iv. If the water table is within 12 inches or less of the surface. _</p> <p>v. If precipitation is forecast in the next 24 hours for the facility location that will cause a discharge from the Permittee's land application fields. _</p> <p>vi. After October 1 and prior to T-SUM 200 unless the manure, litter, process _ wastewater, or other organic by-products are applied in accordance with special condition S4.J.4. _</p> <p>vii. To fields that are bare (no perennial crop) unless the Permittee is preparing the bare field for the current year's annual crop (planting within 30 days of land application). Special condition S4.M applies to fields that are being prepared for a crop.</p>
<p>Is there a restriction for</p>	<p>Yes</p>

land application of manure to saturated soils?	
Is there a restriction for land application of manure within floodplains?	No
Is there a restriction for land application of manure related to future rainfall?	Yes
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to frozen or snow-covered ground?	Yes
Are there restrictions to manure applications based on time of year or time of day?	Yes
Are there restrictions to manure application based on slope?	No
Are there any other seasonal, timing, weather, or physical restrictions to manure applications not captured above?	Yes
Transfer of manure off-site: <i>Requirements related to the transfer of manures to other persons</i>	<p>Manure is exported from the Permittee's CAFO to an unaffiliated party when the Permittee no longer has control of how the manure is used._</p> <p>The Permittee must provide the most recent manure, litter, process wastewater, or other organic by-product nutrient analysis to the recipient as part of export. If the Permittee is exporting digestate, the nutrient analysis must be from within the last 5000 cubic yards (approximately 1,010,000 gallons) of digestate generated. The Permittee must keep records of its manure exports as required by special condition S6.C._</p> <p>1. On-CAFO Processing (composting-or drying) of Manure Solids On-Site by a Third Party: If the Permittee has an agreement with another party (contracted composter) for the contracted composter to process (manure composting-or drying) manure solids from the Permittee on-site, the solids which go to the contracted composter must be tracked as export by the Permittee. After the solids are under the control of the contracted composter, the Permittee is not responsible for tracking sales and movement off-site of the processed manure solids as part of export unless the solids come under the Permittee's control again.</p>
Are receivers of manure transfers from CAFOs	No

required to follow the same regulations?	
Nutrient or manure management plans: <i>Additional details on the NMP requirement. Note that some of this information may overlap with other sections</i>	The Permittee must prepare, keep up-to-date, and implement a Manure Pollution Prevention Plan (MPPP) for their CAFO. The MPPP must be designed and implemented to limit the discharge of manure, litter, process wastewater, other organic by-products, and other sources of pollution related to the operation of a CAFO, to waters of the state for the purpose of complying with state water quality standards. The MPPP is part of the initial permit application.
Do your NMP/MMPS follow, comply with, or based on NRCS Technical Standard 590?	No
Application rates: <i>State regulations that restrict the rates at which manures are applied and methods needed to determine appropriate rates.</i>	<p>Soil Sampling _</p> <p>1. Spring Soil Sampling and Analysis_ Each year prior to starting land application after T-SUM 200, the Permittee must have all land application fields to which they plan to apply manure, litter, process wastewater, or other organic by-products sampled and analyzed for nutrient content. Soil samples must be taken at the depths specified in special condition S4Jdepending on the amount of annual precipitation at the facility location._</p> <p>2. Fall Soil Sampling_ Each year in the fall the Permittee must have all land application fields to which they applied manure, litter, process wastewater, or other organic by-products sampled and analyzed for nutrient content. Post-harvest soil samples must be taken after harvest of annual crops and before 3 inches of rainfall accumulates. Use September 1 as start date for tallying the accumulation of rainfall. Soil samples must be taken at the depths specified in special condition S4.Jdepending on the amount of annual precipitation at the facility location._</p> <p>Soil samples must be representative of the land application field (composite sample), following the most recent guidance provided in either:_</p> <p>PNW 570E Staben, M. L., et. al. (2003). Monitoring Soil Nutrients Using a Management Unit Approach. Pacific Northwest Extension. Pub. No. PNW 570E. A copy of this document is available on the CAFO permit web page:_</p> <p>http://www.ecy.wa.gov/programs/wq/permits/cafo/permit.html OR</p> <p>EM 8832E Sullivan, D., Cogger, C. (2003). Post-Harvest Soil Nitrate Testing for Manured Cropping Systems West of the Cascades. Oregon State University Extension Service. Pub. No. EM 8832E. A copy of this document is available on the CAFO permit web page: http://www.ecy.wa.gov/programs/wq/permits/cafo/permit.html _</p> <p>Soils must be sampled in the spring and fall for Ammonia (NH3)/Ammonium (NH4) as N and Nitrate+Nitrite as N each year, and in the fall every three years for organic matter and phosphorus</p>

(P2O5) as P. _

Field Nutrient Budget_

Each calendar year, the Permittee must develop a field-specific nutrient budget for each land application field they will control at to which they plan to apply manure, litter, process wastewater, or other organic by-products. The yearly nutrient budget specifies the maximum amount of nutrients that may be land applied to the field during the year unless following special condition S4.J.4. Yearly nutrient budgets must be developed before the first land application of the calendar year. If the Permittee makes changes to their yearly nutrient budget for a land application field they must update the nutrient budget to reflect the changes. The yearly nutrient budget must include:_

- a. Current calendar year._
- b. Field ID that is the same as the field ID used on maps in the Permittee's MPPP and acreage (
- c. Soil sample nutrient analysis values
- d. Chemical fertilizer nutrient sources._
- e. Irrigation water nitrate and phosphorus._
- f. Nitrogen and phosphorus from other sources (e.g. precipitation). _
- g. Crop to be planted._
- h. Crop yield estimate for the field based upon (in order of use depending on_ availability): average of the last 3 years of yields from that field, average the last 3 years of yields from similar field in the area, land grant university guidance, commercial chemical fertilizer guides, and national data sources._
- i. Nitrogen and phosphorus required by the crop to reach the yield estimate._
- j. Soil nitrogen and crop residue mineralization_
- k. Nitrogen volatilization during land application._
- l. Adaptive management required by special condition S4.L._

Application Rates_

- a. Land application of manure, litter, process wastewater, and other organic byproducts must be at times and at rates which can be utilized by the crop._
- b. The Permittee must base their application rates on the most current manure, litter, process wastewater, and other organic by-product nutrient analysis required by special condition S4.I and crop needs at the time of application._

Adaptive Management_

The Permittee must adaptively manage their land application fields in order to prevent the build-up of excessive nutrients in the soil. The goal is to reduce land application field fall soil nitrate concentrations to a Risk Level of Medium or less._

1. Determine Field Risk Level_

- a. Use Table 3: Adaptive Management Actions to determine land application field risk level._

	<p>b. In areas with 25 inches or less of annual precipitation, for each field use the second foot (13-24 inches) fall soil nitrate sample analysis results (special condition S4.I) to determine the field risk level._</p> <p>c. In areas with more than 25 inches of annual precipitation, for each field use the first foot (1-12 inches) fall soil nitrate sample analysis results (special condition S4.I) to determine the field risk level._</p> <p>2. Take Required Adaptive Management Actions_ Based on the field risk level, take the required adaptive management actions specified in the corresponding Required Actions column in Table 3: Adaptive Management Actions. Where the risk level remains High or Very High for three consecutive years, in addition to taking the actions in the Required Actions column of Table 3: Adaptive Management Actions, take the actions in the Required Actions Based Upon Trends column in Table 3: Adaptive Management Actions._</p> <p>Yield Estimates_ A realistic production goal is the average yield of the past 3 to 5 years of a single crop, on a single field._</p> <p>– Special condition S4.K Table 3, Adaptive Management Actions has land application caps based on fall nitrate soil test levels.</p>
<p>Manure application rates for phosphorus are based on:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Phosphorus Index Only 2) Soil Test Phosphorus Only 3) Either PIO or STPO 4) Other 	<p>Soil test phosphorus only</p>
<p>Are there any nutrient “caps” to manure application?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Composition testing: <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on manures before application</i></p>	<p>Manure, litter, process wastewater, and other organic by-product sampling and analysis must follow the requirements of special condition S5.B_ The Permittee must sample the manure, litter, process wastewater, and other organic by-products prior to its application to land, up to three times annually as laid out in the schedule in Table 7. During the land application season, if the Permittee begins to use a new source of nutrients for crops, the Permittee must have the new source sampled and analyzed for nutrient content prior to land applying the new source. The Permittee is not required to have commercial chemical fertilizers sampled and analyzed for nutrient content, but is required to record the amount of nutrients applied in special condition S6.B Land Application Records.</p>

Does your state require testing of manure for anything beyond nutrients, such as metals, pathogens, antibiotics, etc.?	No
Other land application highlights: <i>Additional restrictions for land application of manures</i>	No other information
Other regulatory details: <i>Additional information on the regulation of land application of manures</i>	No other information
General Assessment Questions	
Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change:	Yes, pending litigation decision as of 11/2024
Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of manures that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links:	Yes. TMDLs, Nitrate Priority Areas
Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of manures beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so:	Yes
Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.	No other information

West Virginia	
Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2019
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	West Virginia Department of Environmental Protection (WV DEP)
Links to regulations	47 WV CSR 10-13: National Pollutant Discharge Elimination System_ (NPDES) Program - Special NPDES Programs_ https://apps.sos.wv.gov/adlaw/csr/readfile.aspx?DocId=23653&Format=PDF
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Environmental
Other regulator info	No other information
Definitions	
How CAFOs are defined or categorized:	<p>Concentrated Animal Feeding Operation (CAFO) means an AFO that is defined or designated as a Large CAFO or as a Medium CAFO by the terms of this rule. Two or more AFOs under common ownership are considered to be a single AFO for the purposes of determining the number of animals at an operation if they adjoin each other or if they use a common area or system for the disposal of wastes._</p> <p>–</p> <p>Large CAFOs and Medium CAFO are AFOs with the number of animals shown below, and that discharge pollutants into waters of the state either directly into on-site water, or indirectly by channeling wastes through a ditch, flushing system, or other similar device, or which the chief designates under subdivision 13.1.c._</p> <p>–</p> <p>13.1.b.9. Small concentrated Animal Feeding Operation (Small CAFO) - means an AFO that is designated as a CAFO and is not a Medium CAFO as defined above._</p> <p>–</p> <p>Large CAFO_</p> <p>Mature Dairy Cows (milked or dry) > 700 _</p> <p>Cattle (slaughter and feeder) > 1,000 _</p> <p>Veal Calves > 1,000 _</p> <p>Swine (> 55 pounds) > 2,500 _</p> <p>Swine (<55 pounds) > 10,000 _</p> <p>Turkeys > 55,000 _</p> <p>Laying Hens or Broilers (liquid manure system) > 30,000 _</p> <p>Chickens (other than laying hens and other than liquid manure handling systems) > 125,000 _</p> <p>Laying Hens or Broilers (other than liquid manure handling systems) > 82,000</p> <p>–</p>

	<p>– Medium CAFO_ Mature Dairy Cows (milked or dry) 200-699_ Cattle (slaughter and feeder) 300-999_ Veal Calves 300 - 999_ Swine (> 55 pounds) 750-2,499_ Swine (<55 pounds) 3,000-9,999_ Turkeys 16,500-54,999_ Laying Hens or Broilers (liquid manure system) 9,000-29,999_ Chickens (other than laying hens and other than liquid manure handling systems) 37,500 -“ 124,999_ Laying Hens or Broilers (other than liquid manure handling systems) 25,000-81,999</p>
How animal units are defined (if used):	Not used
NPDES permitting or other permitting requirements:	<p>West Virginia regulates its concentrated Animal Feeding Operations (CAFOs) through its National Pollutant Discharge Elimination System (NPDES)._ – The owner or operator of a CAFO must apply for an individual NPDES permit if the CAFO discharges or proposes to discharge into the waters of West Virginia. A CAFO proposes to discharge if it is designed, constructed, operated or maintained such that a discharge will occur._ – Large CAFOs are required to obtain a permit only if the CAFO actually discharges to waters of the state. However, unpermitted large CAFOs must meet the nutrient management requirements of 47 WV CSR 10-13.1.h.1, including recordkeeping requirements.</p>
Does the state require an NPDES permit for all Large CAFOs?	No
Does the state issue individual or general CAFO permits?	Individual
Are any other permits required for CAFOs or other large farms?	Undetermined
Other definitions needed to understand these regulations:	No other information
Regulatory Details	
Setbacks:	Refer to 40 CFR

<i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some geographical feature</i>	
Are setbacks more restrictive than CFR?	Undetermined
Timing, weather, or conditional application restrictions: <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather, seasons, or land characteristics (like slope)</i>	None
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to saturated soils?	No
Is there a restriction for land application of manure within floodplains?	No
Is there a restriction for land application of manure related to future rainfall?	No
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to frozen or snow-covered ground?	No
Are there restrictions to manure applications based on time of year or time of day?	No
Are there	No

restrictions to manure application based on slope?	
Are there any other seasonal, timing, weather, or physical restrictions to manure applications not captured above?	No
Transfer of manure off-site: <i>Requirements related to the transfer of manures to other persons</i>	Refer to 40 CFR
Are receivers of manure transfers from CAFOs required to follow the same regulations?	No
Nutrient or manure management plans: <i>Additional details on the NMP requirement. Note that some of this information may overlap with other sections</i>	<p>Submission of site-specific Nutrient Management Plans (NMPs) are required for permitted CAFOs. Unpermitted large CAFOs must meet the nutrient management requirements of 47 WV CSR 10- 13.1.h.1, including recordkeeping requirements._</p> <p>_</p> <p>13.1.h.1. Requirement to implement a nutrient management plan. Any permit issued to a CAFO must include a requirement to implement a nutrient management plan (NMP) that, at a minimum, contains BMPs necessary to meet the requirements of this section and applicable effluent limitations and standards, including those specified in 40 C.F.R. §412. The NMP must, to the extent applicable:_</p> <p>13.1.h.1.A. Ensure adequate storage of manure, litter, and process wastewater, including procedures to ensure proper operation_ and maintenance of the storage facilities;_</p> <p>13.1.h.1.B. Ensure proper management of mortalities (i.e. dead animals) to make certain that they are not disposed of in a liquid manure, storm water or process wastewater storage or treatment system that is not specifically designed to treat animal mortalities;_</p> <p>13.1.h.1.C. Ensure that clean water is diverted, as appropriate, from the production area;_</p> <p>13.1.h.1.D. Prevent direct contact of confined animals with waters of West_ Virginia;_</p> <p>13.1.h.1.E. Ensure that chemicals and other contaminants handled on-site are not disposed of in any manure, litter, process wastewater or storm water storage or treatment system, unless such system is specifically designed to treat such chemicals and other contaminants;_</p>

	<p>13.1.h.1.F. Identify appropriate site-specific conservation practices to be implemented, including as appropriate buffers or equivalent practices to control runoff of pollutants into the waters of West Virginia;_</p> <p>13.1.h.1.G. Identify protocols for appropriate testing of manure, litter, process wastewater, and soil;_</p> <p>13.1.h.1.H. Establish protocols to land-apply manure, litter and/or process wastewater in accordance with site-specific nutrient management practices that ensure appropriate agricultural utilization of the nutrients in the manure, litter and/or process wastewater; and_</p> <p>13.1.h.1.I. Identify specific records that will be maintained to document the implementation and management of the minimum elements described hereinabove.</p>
<p>Do your NMP/MMPS follow, comply with, or based on NRCS Technical Standard 590?</p>	<p>Undetermined</p>
<p>Application rates: <i>State regulations that restrict the rates at which manures are applied and methods needed to determine appropriate rates.</i></p>	<p>The terms of the NMP with respect to protocols for land application of manure, litter or process wastewater required by paragraph 13.1.h.1.H above and, if applicable, 40 C.F.R. §412.4(c), must include the fields available for land application; field-specific rates of application, properly developed in accordance with paragraphs 13.1.h.5.A through 13.1.h.5.B below, to ensure appropriate agricultural utilization of the nutrients in the manure, litter and/or process wastewater; and any timing limitations identified in the NMP concerning land application on the fields available for such use. The terms must address rates of application using one of the following two approaches, unless the Chief specifies that a certain approach must be used:_</p> <p>13.1.h.5.A. Linear approach. An approach that expresses rates of application as pounds of nitrogen and phosphorus, according to_</p> <p>the following specifications:_</p> <p>13.1.h.5.A.1. The terms include maximum application rates from manure, litter and/or process wastewater for each year of permit coverage for each crop identified in the NMP, in chemical forms determined to be acceptable to the Chief, in pounds per acre per year for each field to be used for land application, and certain factors necessary to determine such rates. At a minimum, the factors that are terms must include: the outcome of the field-specific assessment of the potential for nitrogen and phosphorus transport from each field; the crops to be planted in each field or any other uses of a field, such as pasture or fallow fields; the realistic yield goal for each crop or use identified for each field; the nitrogen and phosphorus recommendations from sources specified by the Chief for each crop or use identified for each field; credits for all nitrogen in the field that will be plant-available; consideration of multi-year phosphorus application; and accounting for all other additions of plant-available nitrogen and phosphorus to the field. In addition, the terms include the form and source of manure, litter and/or process wastewater to be land-applied; the timing and method of land application; and the methodology by which the NMP accounts for the amount</p>

of nitrogen and phosphorus in the manure, litter, and process wastewater to be applied._

13.1.h.5.A.2. Large CAFOs that use this approach must calculate the maximum amount of manure, litter and/or process wastewater to be land-applied at least once each year, using the results of the most recent representative manure, litter and/or process wastewater tests for nitrogen and phosphorus taken within twelve (12) months of the date of land application._

13.1.h.5.B. Narrative rate approach. An approach that expresses rates of application as a narrative rate of application that results in the amount in tons or gallons of manure, litter and/or process wastewater to be land-applied, according to the following specifications:_

13.1.h.5.B.1. The terms include maximum amounts of nitrogen and phosphorus derived from all sources of nutrients for each crop identified in the NMP, in chemical forms determined to be acceptable to the Chief, in pounds per acre for each field, and certain factors necessary to determine such amounts. At a minimum, the factors that are terms must include: the outcome of the field-specific assessment of the potential for nitrogen and phosphorus transport from each field; the crops to be planted in each field or any other uses of a field, such as pasture or fallow fields (including alternative crops identified in subparagraph 13.1.h.5.B.2 below); the realistic yield goal for each crop or use identified for each field; and the nitrogen and phosphorus recommendations from sources specified by the Chief for each crop or use identified for each field. In addition, the terms include the methodology by which the NMP accounts for the following factors when calculating the amounts of manure, litter and/or process wastewater to be land applied: results of soil tests conducted in accordance with protocols identified in the NMP required by paragraph 13.1.h.1.G of this rule; credits for all nitrogen in the field that will be plant-available; the amount of nitrogen and phosphorus in the manure, litter and/or process wastewater to be applied; consideration of multi-year phosphorus application; accounting for all other additions of plant-available nitrogen and phosphorus to the field; the form and source of manure, litter, and process wastewater; the timing and method of land application; and volatilization of nitrogen and mineralization of organic nitrogen._

13.1.h.5.B.2. The terms of the NMP include alternative crops identified in the CAFO's NMP that are not in the planned crop rotation. Where a CAFO includes alternative crops in its nutrient management plan, the crops must be listed in field, in addition to the crops identified in the planned crop rotation for that field, and the NMP must include realistic crop yield goals and the nitrogen and phosphorus recommendations from sources specified by the Chief for each crop. Maximum amounts of nitrogen and phosphorus from all sources of nutrients and the amounts of manure, litter and/or process wastewater to be applied must be determined in accordance with the methodology described in subparagraph 13.1.h.5.B.1 above._

13.1.h.5.B.3. For CAFOs using this approach, the following projections must be included in the NMP submitted to the Chief, but are not terms of the NMP the CAFO's planned crop rotations for each field for the period of permit

	<p>coverage; the projected amount of manure, litter and/or process wastewater to be applied; projected credits for all nitrogen in the field that will be plant-available; consideration of multi-year phosphorus application; accounting for all other additions of plant- available nitrogen and phosphorus to the field; and the predicted form, source, and method of application of manure, litter and/or process wastewater for each crop. Timing of application for each field, insofar as it concerns the calculation of rates of application, is not a term of the NMP._</p> <p>13.1.h.5.B.4. CAFOs that use this approach must calculate maximum amounts of manure, litter and/or process wastewater to be land-applied at least once each year, using the methodology required by subparagraph 13.1.h.5.B.1 above, before land-applying manure, litter and/or process wastewater and must rely on the following data:_</p> <p>13.1.h.5.B.4.a. specific determination of soil levels of nitrogen_ and phosphorus, including for nitrogen a concurrent determination of nitrogen that will be plant-available consistent with the methodology required by subparagraph 13.1.h.5.B.1 above, and for phosphorus, the results of the most recent soil test conducted in accordance with soil testing requirements approved by the Chief; and_</p> <p>13.1.h.5.B.4.b. The results of most recent representative manure, litter and/or process wastewater tests for nitrogen and phosphorus, taken within twelve (12) months of the date of land application, in order to determine the amount of nitrogen and phosphorus in the manure, litter and/or process_ wastewater to be applied.</p>
<p>Manure application rates for phosphorus are based on:</p> <p><i>1) Phosphorus Index Only</i></p> <p><i>2) Soil Test Phosphorus Only</i></p> <p><i>3) Either PIO or STPO</i></p> <p><i>4) Other</i></p>	<p>Soil test phosphorus only</p>
<p>Are there any nutrient “caps” to manure application?</p>	<p>Undetermined</p>
<p>Composition testing: <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on manures before application</i></p>	<p>The WVDA administers the USDA PL534 land treatment program which facilitates litter/manure sample analysis by the Environmental Programs Section's Nutrient Management Laboratory</p>

Does your state require testing of manure for anything beyond nutrients, such as metals, pathogens, antibiotics, etc.?	Undetermined
Other land application highlights: <i>Additional restrictions for land application of manures</i>	No other information
Other regulatory details: <i>Additional information on the regulation of land application of manures</i>	No other information
General Assessment Questions	
Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change:	Undetermined
Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of manures that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links:	No
Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land	No

<p>application of manures beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so:</p>	
<p>Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.</p>	<p>No other information</p>

Wisconsin Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2025
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Wisconsin Department of Natural Resources (WDNR)
Links to regulations	Multiple links to regulations, permits, guidance, etc._ https://dnr.wi.gov/topic/AgBusiness/CAFO/WPDESnr243.html _ _ Chapter NR 243 Animal Feeding Operations_ https://docs.legis.wisconsin.gov/code/admin_code/nr/200/243
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Natural Resources
Other regulator info	No other information
Definitions	
How CAFOs are defined or categorized:	"Concentrated Animal Feeding Operation" or "CAFO" means an Animal Feeding Operation to which any of the following apply: (a) The operation has 1,000 animal units or more at any time and stores manure or process wastewater in a below or at grade level storage structure or land applies manure or process wastewater. (b) The operation has 300 to 999 animal units and has a category I unacceptable practice under s. NR 243.24 (1) (a). (c) Under s. NR 243.26 (2), the operation is designated by the department as having a significant discharge of pollutants to navigable waters or has caused the fecal contamination of water in a well. All CAFOS must have a WPDES permit.
How animal units are defined (if used):	Animal Unit = AU_ Dairy/Beef Calves (under 400 lbs.) = 0.20 AU_ Milking & Dry Cows = 1.40 AU_ Heifers (800-1200 lbs.) = 1.10 AU_ Heifers (400-800 lbs.) = 0.60 AU_ Steers or Cows (400 lbs. to market) = 1.00 AU_ Bulls (each) = 1.40 AU_ Veal Calves = 0.50 AU_ Pigs (up to 55 lbs.) = 0.10 AU_ Pigs (> 55 lbs. to market) = 0.40 AU_ Sows (each) = 0.4 AU_ Boars (each) = 0.5 AU_ Layers (each) -" non-liquid manure system = 0.01 AU_ Broilers/Pullets (each) -" non-liquid manure system = 0.005 AU_ Per Bird -" liquid manure system = 0.033 AU_ Ducks (each) - liquid manure system = 0.2 AU_ Ducks (each) -" non-liquid manure system = 0.01 AU_ Turkeys (each) = 0.018 AU_ Sheep (each) = 0.1 AU_ Horses (each) = 2 AU

<p>NPDES permitting or other permitting requirements:</p>	<p>The U.S. EPA delegates implementation of the Clean Water Act and Federal NPDES CAFO permit program to the Department of Natural Resources (DNR). Wisconsin implements the water quality protection permit program by requiring that CAFOs have a DNR approved Wisconsin Pollutant Discharge Elimination System (WPDES) permit in place when they to operate. CAFO WPDES permits ensure farms use proper planning, nutrient management, and structure/system construction to protect Wisconsin waters. These permits apply only to water quality protection. They do not give the DNR authority to address air, odor, traffic, lighting, land use nor any of the social concerns people may have about large farms.</p>
<p>Does the state require an NPDES permit for all Large CAFOs?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Does the state issue individual or general CAFO permits?</p>	<p>Undetermined</p>
<p>Are any other permits required for CAFOs or other large farms?</p>	<p>Undetermined</p>
<p>Other definitions needed to understand these regulations:</p>	<p>No other information</p>
<p>Regulatory Details</p>	
<p>Setbacks: <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some geographical feature</i></p>	<p>* Manure or process wastewater may not be applied within 100 feet of a direct conduit to groundwater._ * Manure or process wastewater may not be applied on areas of a field with a depth to groundwater or bedrock of less than 24 inches._ * Manure or process wastewater may not be applied within 100 feet of a private well or non-community system as defined in Ch. NR 812 or within 1000 feet of a community well as defined in Ch. NR 811._ — SWQMA application restrictions._ (a) Subject to additional restrictions in subs. (6) and (7) for the winter season, a permittee shall choose and implement one of the following options whenever manure or process wastewater is applied on areas of fields within the SWQMA:_ 1. Not apply manure or process wastewater within 25 feet of a navigable water, conduit to a navigable water or wetland; and inject or immediately incorporate manure and process wastewater in all other areas within the SWQMA._ 2. Not apply manure or process wastewater within 25 feet of a navigable water, conduit to a navigable water or wetland; and surface apply liquid manure and process wastewater in all other areas of the SWQMA provided that all of the following conditions are met:_ a. The application is on long-term no-till ground._</p>

	<p>b. The ground has 30% crop residue or more at the time of application._</p> <p>c. The hydraulic application rate is limited to that specified in Table 3._</p> <p>3. Establish a 35-foot wide vegetated buffer adjacent to the navigable water, conduit to a navigable water or wetland where there is no application of manure or process wastewater on the buffer; and comply with a practice in this subd. 3. a. or b. For the purposes of this subdivision, a vegetated buffer means a narrow, permanent strip of dense perennial vegetation established parallel to the contours of and perpendicular to the dominant slope of the field for the purposes of slowing water runoff, enhancing water infiltration, and minimizing the risk of any potential nutrients or pollutants from leaving the field and reaching navigable waters._</p> <p>a. Inject or immediately incorporate manure and process wastewater in all other areas within the SWQMA, or_</p> <p>b. Surface apply in all other areas of the SWQMA provided the ground has 30% residue or more at the time of application and the hydraulic application rate is limited in accordance with Table 3._</p> <p>4. Establish a filter strip that is a minimum of 21 feet wide adjacent to the navigable water, conduit to a navigable water or wetland; and comply with a practice in this subd. 4. a. or b. The filter strip shall be designed in accordance with NRCS Standard 393, dated January 2001. NRCS Standard 393, dated January 2001, is incorporated by reference in s. NR 243.07._</p> <p>a. Inject or immediately incorporate manure and process wastewater in all other areas within the SWQMA, or_</p> <p>b. Surface apply in all other areas of the SWQMA provided the ground has 30% residue or more at the time of application and the hydraulic application rate is limited in accordance with Table 3._</p> <p>5. Not apply manure or process wastewater within 100 feet of a navigable water or conduit to a navigable water._</p> <p>6. Implement other practices within the SWQMA that are approved, in writing, by the department provided that the permittee demonstrates pollutant reductions are equivalent to, or better than, reductions achieved by not applying manure or process wastewater within 100 feet of downgradient navigable waters or conduits to navigable waters.</p>
<p>Are setbacks more restrictive than CFR?</p>	<p>Undetermined</p>
<p>Timing, weather, or conditional application restrictions: <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather, seasons, or land characteristics (like</i></p>	<p>* Manure or process wastewater may not pond on the application site._</p> <p>* Manure or process wastewater may not run off the application site nor discharge to waters of the state through subsurface drains due to precipitation or snowmelt except if the permittee has complied with all land application restrictions in this subchapter and the WPDES permit, and the runoff or discharge occurs as a result of a rain event that is equal to or greater than a 25-year, 24-hour rain</p>

slope)

event._

* Manure or process wastewater may not be applied to saturated soils._

* On a field with soils that are 60 inches thick or less over fractured bedrock, manure or process wastewater may not be applied on frozen ground or where snow is present._

* Manure or process wastewater may not be applied on fields when snow is actively melting such that water is flowing off the field._

* Where incorporation of land applied manure is required under NRCS Standard 590, the incorporation shall occur within 48 hours of application._

* Manure or process wastewater may not be surface applied when precipitation capable of producing runoff is forecast within 24 hours of the time of planned application._

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Solid manure winter restrictions. The restrictions in this subsection apply to the land application of solid manure on frozen or snow covered ground._

(a) Frozen ground-solid manure. Unless prohibited under par. (c), solid manure may be surface applied on frozen ground if the manure is applied in compliance with the restrictions in Table 4 or otherwise immediately incorporated._

(b) Snow covered ground-solid manure. Unless prohibited under par. (c), solid manure may only be land applied to snow covered ground in accordance with the following:_

1. If less than one inch of snow is present on the area where manure is to be land applied, the permittee may surface apply or immediately incorporate the solid manure._

Note: If there is less than one inch of snow on the ground and the ground is frozen, pursuant to par. (a), Table 4 restrictions must be followed when surface applying solid manure._

2. If one to 4 inches of snow is present on the area where manure is to be land applied, the permittee shall surface apply the manure in compliance with restrictions in Table 4 or otherwise immediately incorporate the solid manure._

3. If more than 4 inches of snow is present on the area where manure is to be land applied, the permittee shall surface apply the solid manure in compliance with the restrictions in Table 4.

Incorporation of solid manure is prohibited._

Note: It is assumed that proper incorporation of solid manure is not achievable if more than 4 inches of snow is present at the time of application._

(c) High-risk runoff period._

1. Beginning January 1, 2008, solid manure may not be surface applied from February 1 through March 31 if any of the following conditions exist on the area of the field where the manure is to be applied:_

a. Snow is present to a depth of one inch or greater._

b. The ground is frozen._

(d) To meet the requirements of par. (c), a permittee may choose to stack solid manure generated at a production area location in accordance with s. NR 243.141 (1) rather than use a storage facility that meets the design requirements in s. NR 243.15. - See PDF for table PDF_

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Liquid manure winter restrictions. The following additional restrictions in this subsection apply to the land application of liquid manure on frozen or snow covered ground:—

(a) Frozen ground-liquid manure. Surface application of liquid manure on frozen ground is prohibited, except for an emergency situation under par. (d) or if allowed under par. (e). Injection or immediate incorporation of liquid manure is allowed on frozen ground, except if prohibited due to snow covered conditions under par. (b).—

(b) Snow covered ground-liquid manure. Unless prohibited under par. (c) and subject to the frozen ground prohibition in par. (a), liquid manure may only be land applied to snow covered ground in accordance with the following:—

1. If less than one inch of snow is present on the area where liquid manure is to be applied, surface application, injection or immediate incorporation of liquid manure is allowed.—

2. If there is one to 4 inches of snow present on the area where liquid manure is to be applied, surface application of liquid manure is prohibited, except for department approved emergencies under par. (d) or if allowed under par. (e). Immediate incorporation or injection is allowed on areas where there is one to 4 inches of snow.—

3. If there is greater than 4 inches of snow on the area where liquid manure is to be applied, surface application and incorporation of liquid manure is prohibited, except for department approved emergencies under par. (d) or if allowed under par. (e). Injection of liquid manure is allowed on areas where there is greater than 4 inches of snow.—

(c) High-risk runoff period.—

1. Unless there is a department approved emergency situation under par. (d), liquid manure may not be surface applied from February 1 through March 31.—

Note: Prior to January 1, 2010, existing source CAFOs may surface apply liquid manure at other times of the winter. Also, during the high-risk period, liquid manure may be injected or incorporated if allowed under pars. (b) and (c) and other requirements in this chapter.—

(d) Emergency applications for liquid manure.—

1. Except as provided in subd. 3., a permittee may surface apply liquid manure on frozen or snow covered ground on an emergency basis in accordance with the restrictions in Table 5 if all of the

	<p>following conditions are met: _</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">a. The manure is from a storage or containment facility that is designed and maintained in accordance with ss. NR 243.15 and 243.17 to provide 180 days of storage for the manure. _b. The application of manure is necessitated by exceedances or expected exceedances of the margin of safety level that were unavoidable due to unusual weather conditions, equipment failure or other unforeseen circumstances beyond the control of the permittee. _c. The permittee has notified the department verbally prior to the emergency application. Unless necessitated by imminent impacts to the environment or human or animal health, the permittee may not apply manure to a field on an emergency basis until the department has verbally approved the application. _d. The permittee submits a written description of the emergency application and the events leading to the emergency application to the department within 5 days of the emergency application. _ <p>2. Allowances for emergency surface applications of liquid manure do not apply to situations where a permittee has failed to properly maintain storage capacity either through improper design or management of the storage facility, including failure to properly account for the number or volume of waste streams entering the facility, failure to empty a storage or containment facility in accordance with permit conditions prior to the onset of frozen or snow covered ground conditions or due to an increase in animal units. _</p> <p>Note: The allowance for emergency surface applications in compliance with permit conditions is intended to avoid more significant impacts to human health and water quality associated with uncontrolled overflows of manure storage facilities. Causes of emergency surface applications could include conditions such as prolonged storm events or early onset of frozen ground conditions that preclude applications of manure prior to the onset of frozen or snow covered ground conditions provided that the operation made all other attempts to maintain storage volume before an emergency application became necessary. _</p> <p>3. The permittee shall conduct emergency surface applications of liquid manure in accordance with the restrictions in Table 5. The permittee may only conduct emergency surface applications on fields that the department has approved for emergency applications, in writing, as part of a nutrient management plan. The department may approve alternate fields and impose alternative restrictions, in writing and on a case-by-case basis, if fields that meet the restrictions in Table 5 are not available at the time of the emergency application, the permittee has explored all other options identified in its emergency response plan and the application results in a winter acute loss index value of 4 or less using the phosphorus index. _</p>
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	<p>Note: The winter acute loss index value is displayed under the heading -acute Loss Frozen Soil PI" in the cropping screen of the Snap-Plus nutrient management software program._</p> <p>Note: Reporting requirements for emergency surface applications are contained in s. NR 243.19._</p> <p>(e) Existing source CAFOs-liquid manure exception. Prior to January 1, 2010, if an existing source CAFO does not have 180 days of storage for liquid manure as specified in s. NR 243.15, the permittee may surface apply liquid manure on frozen or snow covered ground in accordance with the restrictions in Table 5 without satisfying the emergency criteria in par. (d). If a permittee does not have access to sites that meet the criteria in Table 5, the department may approve alternate sites and restrictions, in writing on a case-by-case basis as part of a nutrient management plan provided the application results in a winter acute loss index value of 4 or less using the phosphorus index. This allowance for existing source CAFOs to surface apply liquid manure on frozen or snow covered ground without satisfying the emergency criteria in par. (d) is not applicable after January 1, 2010._</p> <p>Note: An existing source CAFO is defined under s. NR 243.03 (23)._</p> <p>(f) Frozen liquid manure. Liquid manure that is frozen and cannot be transferred to a manure storage facility may be surface applied on frozen or snow-covered ground in accordance with the restrictions in Table 5. Surface applications of frozen liquid manure do not require prior department approval or notification provided application sites for frozen liquid manure are identified in the approved nutrient management plan. During February and March, the permittee shall notify the department if the permittee expects to surface apply frozen liquid manure more than 5 days in any one month.</p>
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to saturated soils?	Yes
Is there a restriction for land application of manure within floodplains?	No
Is there a restriction for land application of manure related to future rainfall?	Yes
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to frozen or snow-covered ground?	Yes
Are there restrictions to manure applications based on time of year or time of	Yes

day?	
Are there restrictions to manure application based on slope?	Yes
Are there any other seasonal, timing, weather, or physical restrictions to manure applications not captured above?	No
Transfer of manure off-site: <i>Requirements related to the transfer of manures to other persons</i>	<p>If a permittee wants to transfer responsibility to another person for the land application, disposal or use of manure or process wastewater that will be distributed in accordance with one of the methods in sub. (2) (b) to (e), the permittee shall obtain written department approval for the distribution. If written approval is not obtained, the permittee remains responsible for the land application, disposal and use of the distributed manure or process wastewater in accordance with the terms of the permit and this chapter. To obtain department approval for the purposes of transferring responsibility, the permittee shall comply with all of the following conditions: _</p> <p>(a) Neither the permittee, its agent or a contract hauler working on behalf of the permittee may land apply the distributed manure. _</p> <p>(b) The permittee shall demonstrate to the department that the distributed manure will be beneficially used. _</p> <p>(c) If the manure is distributed in accordance with sub. (2) (b) or (c), and if the person receiving the manure intends to store the manure, the permittee shall demonstrate to the department that the distributed manure will be delivered to proper storage. For purposes of this paragraph, proper storage means one of the following: _</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The distributed manure will be stored in a facility that complies with NRCS Standard 313, December 2005. _ 2. The distributed manure will be stored in a manner that will not cause exceedances of groundwater and surface water quality standards and will not impair wetland functional values.
Are receivers of manure transfers from CAFOs required to follow the same regulations?	Undetermined
Nutrient or manure management plans: <i>Additional details on the NMP requirement. Note that some of this information may overlap with other sections</i>	<p>Permittees shall submit a nutrient management plan developed by a nutrient management planner qualified under s. ATCP 50.48 to the department for review and approval outlining the amounts, timing, locations, methods and other aspects regarding the land application of manure and process wastewater. A complete nutrient management plan shall be submitted with a permit application in accordance with s. NR 243.12. The nutrient management plan shall comply with the requirements of this section and the permittee's WPDES permit. Subject to additional requirements specified in this</p>

	<p>section and in a WPDES permit, the land application practices identified in the nutrient management plan shall, at a minimum, conform with the nutrient budgeting, soil test recommendations, application practices and restrictions contained in NRCS Standard 590.</p>
<p>Do your NMP/MMPS follow, comply with, or based on NRCS Technical Standard 590?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Application rates: <i>State regulations that restrict the rates at which manures are applied and methods needed to determine appropriate rates.</i></p>	<p>* Land application practices shall maximize the use of available nutrients for crop production, prevent delivery of manure and process wastewater to waters of the state, and minimize the loss of nutrients and other contaminants to waters of the state to prevent exceedances of groundwater and surface water quality standards and to prevent impairment of wetland functional values. Practices shall retain land applied manure and process wastewater on the soil where they are applied with minimal movement._</p> <p>* Nutrient crediting. A permittee's manure and process wastewater application rates shall take into account soil nutrient levels prior to land spreading, nutrient applications from other sources, including commercial fertilizers, biosolids, first and second year manure and legume credits, and other sources of nutrients that are expected to be applied or have already been applied to land where manure or process wastewater will be applied. Adjustments shall be made to assumed nutrient credits based on actual crop yields._</p> <p>Phosphorus delivery._</p> <p>(a) The permittee shall assess and minimize the potential for delivery of phosphorus to waters of the state from fields by applying its manure and process wastewater in accordance with one of the methods specified in subd. 1. or 2. The permittee shall specify the method it will apply to a field in the nutrient management plan._</p> <p>1. Use the soil test phosphorus method specified in NRCS Standard 590. In addition, for applications to fields directly adjacent to, or that have been determined by the department to have a high potential to deliver phosphorus to, 303 (d) listed waters impaired by nutrients or outstanding or exceptional resource waters, the permittee may not increase soil test phosphorus levels over a crop rotation unless the permittee receives department approval, and the permittee can demonstrate that deliverability of phosphorus to these waters will not increase as a result of increases in soil test phosphorus in the field. The permittee may not raise soil test phosphorus levels over a rotation above the optimum level for the highest phosphorus demanding crop in a rotation for a field with soil test phosphorus levels below optimum levels._</p> <p>Note: In accordance with s. NR 243.14 (1) (a) and NRCS Standard 590, a permittee shall determine optimum soil phosphorus levels for various Wisconsin crops as specified in University of Wisconsin-Extension Publication A2809, Soil Test Recommendations for Field,</p>

	<p>Vegetable and Fruit Crops."_</p> <p>2. Use the phosphorus index method specified in NRCS Standard 590._</p> <p>(b) If a permittee applies manure or process wastewater on fields with soil test levels greater than 100 ppm, the permittee shall comply with the requirements in both subd. 1. and 2.:_</p> <p>1. For fields with soil test phosphorus levels between 100 ppm and 200 ppm, the permittee shall calculate the planned average phosphorus index value for the crop rotation or for the next 4-year period, whichever time period is less. If the calculated average phosphorus index value is greater than 6, manure and process wastewater applications to that field are prohibited. If the calculated phosphorus index value is 6 or less, applications are allowed provided that the cumulative application of phosphorus from manure and process wastewater does not exceed 50% of the cumulative annual crop phosphorus removal over the rotation or the next 4-year period, whichever is less._</p> <p>2. For fields with soil test phosphorus levels of 200 ppm and greater, applications of phosphorus from manure and process wastewater are prohibited unless the permittee receives department approval. The department may only approve the application if all of the following requirements are met:_</p> <p>a. The permittee can demonstrate that additional applications of manure or process wastewater will not significantly increase phosphorus delivery to surface waters or wetlands._</p> <p>b. The permittee calculates the planned average phosphorus index value for the rotation or the next 4-year period, whichever is less and the planned average phosphorus index value is 6 or less._</p> <p>c. The cumulative application of phosphorus from manure and process wastewater does not exceed 50% of the cumulative annual crop phosphorus removal over the rotation or the following 4-year period, whichever is less._</p> <p>Note: A permittee that complies with the requirements of this section and its WPDES permit also addresses delivery of nitrogen to waters of the state.</p>
<p>Manure application rates for phosphorus are based on:</p> <p>1) <i>Phosphorus Index Only</i></p> <p>2) <i>Soil Test Phosphorus Only</i></p> <p>3) <i>Either PIO or STPO</i></p> <p>4) <i>Other</i></p>	<p>Phosphorus index or soil test</p>
<p>Are there any nutrient “caps” to manure application?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Composition testing: <i>State regulations that</i></p>	<p>* Subject to other restrictions on application rates in this section, the permittee shall use results of manure, process wastewater and</p>

<i>govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on manures before application</i>	soil analyses to determine nutrient application rates for manure and process wastewater._ * Lab analyses of manure and process wastewater land applied in the previous 12 months, and the most recent soil test analysis completed for fields receiving manure or process wastewater in the previous 12 months.
Does your state require testing of manure for anything beyond nutrients, such as metals, pathogens, antibiotics, etc.?	No
Other land application highlights: <i>Additional restrictions for land application of manures</i>	* During dry weather conditions, manure or process wastewater may not run off the application site, nor discharge to waters of the state through subsurface drains._ * Manure or process wastewater may not cause the fecal contamination of water in a well._
Other regulatory details: <i>Additional information on the regulation of land application of manures</i>	Areas prohibited from receiving nutrient applications to frozen or snow-covered soil: Slopes > 6%_For fields with soil test phosphorus levels between 100 ppm and 200 ppm, the permittee shall calculate the planned average phosphorus index value for the cro
General Assessment Questions	
Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change:	No
Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of manures that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links:	No
Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of manures beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so:	No
Is the land application of septage, composts,	Yes, regulated by NR 113 Septage, NR 204 Sewage Sludge, NR 214 Industrial Wastes.

digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.

Wyoming Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2019
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Wyoming Department of Environmental Quality (WDEQ)
Links to regulations	Regulatory Authority: https://rules.wyo.gov/Search.aspx?mode=1 _ _ General CAFO information: http://deq.wyoming.gov/wqd/cafos/ _ _ Wyoming Nutrient Management Plan Technical Standards: http://deq.wyoming.gov/media/attachments/Water%20Quality/CAFOS%20/CAFO%20Guidance/Nutrient-Management-Plan-Technical-Standards.pdf
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Environmental
Other regulator info	No other information
Definitions	
How CAFOs are defined or categorized :	Animal feeding operation (AFO) - means a lot or facility (other than an aquatic animal production facility) where the following conditions are met:_ (A) Animals have been, are, or will be stabled or confined and fed or maintained for a total of 45 days or more in any 12-month period; and (B) Crops, vegetation forage growth or post harvest residues are not sustained in the normal growing season over any portion of the lot or facility._ Large concentrated Animal Feeding Operation- (large CAFO). An AFO_ is defined as a large CAFO if it stables or confines as many as or more than the numbers of animals specified in any of the following categories._ (A) 700 mature dairy cows, whether milked or dry;_ (B) 1,000 veal calves;_ (C) 1,500 buffalo (Bison bison);_ (D) 1,000 cattle other than mature dairy cows or veal calves. Cattle includes but is not limited to heifers, steers, bulls and cow/calf pairs;_ (E) 2,500 swine each weighing 55 pounds or more;_ (F) 10,000 swine each weighing less than 55 pounds;_ (G) 500 horses;_ (H) 10,000 sheep or lambs;_

	<p>(I) 55,000 turkeys;_</p> <p>(J) 30,000 laying hens or broilers, if the AFO uses a liquid manure handling system;_</p> <p>(K) 125,000 chickens (other than laying hens), if the AFO uses other than a liquid manure handling system;_</p> <p>(L) 82,000 laying hens, (if the AFO uses other than a liquid manure handling system);_</p> <p>(M) 30,000 ducks (if the AFO uses other than a liquid manure handling system); or_</p> <p>(N) 5,000 ducks (if the AFO uses a liquid manure handling system)._</p> <p>Medium concentrated Animal Feeding Operation-² (medium CAFO) means any AFO with the type and number of animals that fall within any of the ranges listed in Appendix G (b) (vii) (A) and which has been defined or designated as a CAFO. An AFO is defined as a medium CAFO if:_</p> <p>(A) The type and number of animals that it stables or confines falls within any of the following ranges:_</p> <p>(I) 200 to 699 mature dairy cattle, whether milked or dry;_</p> <p>(II) 300 to 999 veal calves;_</p> <p>(III) 450 to 1499 buffalo (Bison bison);_</p> <p>(IV) 300 to 999 cattle other than mature dairy cows or veal 362 calves. Cattle includes but is not limited to heifers, steers, bulls and cow/calf pairs;_</p> <p>(V) 750 to 2,499 swine each weighing 55 pounds or more;_</p> <p>(VI) 3,000 to 9,999 swine each weighing less than 55 pounds;_</p> <p>(VII) 150 to 499 horses;_</p> <p>(VIII) 3,000 to 9,999 sheep or lambs;_</p> <p>(IX) 16,500 to 54,999 turkeys;_</p> <p>(X) 9,000 to 29,999 laying hens or broilers, (if the AFO uses a liquid manure handling system);_</p> <p>(XI) 37,500 to 124, 999 chickens (other than laying hens), (if the AFO uses other than a liquid manure handling system);_</p> <p>(XII) 25,000 to 81,999 laying hens, (if the AFO uses other than a liquid manure handling system);_</p> <p>(XIII) 10,000 to 29,999 ducks (if the AFO uses other than a liquid manure handling system); or_</p> <p>(XIV) 1,500 to 4,999 ducks (if the AFO uses a liquid manure handling system); and_</p> <p>(B) Either one of the following conditions are met:_</p> <p>(I) Pollutants are discharged into surface waters of the state through a man-made ditch, flushing system, or other similar man-made device; or_</p> <p>(II) Pollutants are discharged directly into surface waters of the state which originate outside of and pass over, across, or through the facility or otherwise_ come into direct contact with the animals confined in the operation.</p>
How animal units are defined (if used):	Not used
NPDES permitting or other permitting requirements:	<p>Applicability and permit requirement for concentrated animal feeding operations (CAFOs). In accordance with W.S. 35-11-103 (a) (xi) and 35-11-302 (a) (v), CAFOs, are point sources that require WYPDES permits for discharges or potential discharges. Once an operation is defined as a Large CAFO, the WYPDES requirements for CAFOs apply with respect to all animals in confinement at the operation and all manure, litter and process wastewater generated by those animals or the production of those</p>

	<p>animals, regardless of the type of animal. All large CAFOs have a duty to apply to seek coverage under a WYPDES permit as described in these regulations._</p> <p>Exception. An owner or operator of a large CAFO does not need to seek coverage under a WYPDES permit otherwise required by this section once the owner or operator has received from the director notification of a determination under Appendix G (f) of these regulations that the CAFO has no potential to discharge-² manure, litter or process wastewater._</p> <p>Land application discharges from a large CAFO are subject to WYPDES requirements. The discharge of manure, litter or process wastewater to surface waters of the state from a large CAFO as a result of the application of that manure, litter or process wastewater by the large CAFO to land areas under its control is a discharge from that CAFO subject to WYPDES permit requirements, except where it is an agricultural storm water discharge as provided in 33 U.S.C. 1362(14).</p>
Does the state require an NPDES permit for all Large CAFOs?	No
Does the state issue individual or general CAFO permits?	Individual
Are any other permits required for CAFOs or other large farms?	No
Other definitions needed to understand these regulations:	No other information
Regulatory Details	
Setbacks: <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance</i>	<p>Unless the large CAFO exercises one of the compliance alternatives provided below, manure, litter, and process wastewater may not be applied closer than 100 feet to any down-gradient surface waters of the state, open tile line intake structures, sinkholes, agricultural well heads, or other conduits to surface waters of the state._</p> <p>Vegetated buffer compliance alternative. As a compliance alternative, the large CAFO may substitute the 100-foot setback with a 35 foot wide vegetated buffer where applications of manure, litter, or process wastewater are prohibited._</p>

<p><i>must lie between the site of land application and some geographical feature</i></p>	<p>As a compliance alternative, the large CAFO may demonstrate that a setback or buffer is not necessary because implementation of alternative conservation practices or field-specific conditions will provide pollutant reductions equivalent or better than the reductions that would be achieved by the 100 foot setback</p>
<p>Are setbacks more restrictive than CFR?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Timing, weather, or conditional application restrictions : <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather, seasons, or land characteristics (like slope)</i></p>	<p>Land to be utilized for application of manure or process wastewater shall have a slope of less than six (6) percent. Minimize runoff potential by incorporating manure or process waste water as soon as possible after application unless the application site is permanently vegetated or is no-till cropped. Manure or process wastewater shall not be applied to frozen or snow covered ground. If application to frozen or snow covered ground is absolutely necessary, the operator shall notify the WQD prior to any application.</p>
<p>Is there a restriction for land application of manure to saturated soils?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Is there a restriction for land application of manure within floodplains?</p>	<p>No</p>

Is there a restriction for land application of manure related to future rainfall?	No
Is there a restriction for land application of manure to frozen or snow-covered ground?	Yes
Are there restrictions to manure applications based on time of year or time of day?	No
Are there restrictions to manure application based on slope?	Yes
Are there any other seasonal, timing, weather, or physical restrictions to manure applications not captured above?	No
Transfer of manure off-site: <i>Requiremen</i>	Requirements relating to transfer of manure or process wastewater to other persons. Prior to transferring manure, litter or process wastewater to other persons. Large CAFOs must provide the recipient of the manure, litter or process wastewater with the most current nutrient analysis. The analysis provided must be consistent with

<p><i>ts related to the transfer of manures to other persons</i></p>	<p>requirements of this appendix. Large CAFOs must retain for five (5) years records of the date, recipient name and address, and approximate amount of manure, litter or process wastewater transferred to another person.</p>
<p>Are receivers of manure transfers from CAFOs required to follow the same regulations?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Nutrient or manure management plans: <i>Additional details on the NMP requirement. Note that some of this information may overlap with other sections</i></p>	<p>Nutrient management plan development and implementation requirements. At a minimum, a nutrient management plan must include best management practices and procedures necessary to implement applicable effluent limitations and standards._ Nutrient management plan technical standards are here: https://efotg.sc.egov.usda.gov/references/Agency/WY/Archived_WY-ECS-86_CNMP_10_10_fillableform_140530.pdf and include a narrative approach. NMP based on NRCS 590 Standards with some variations, most notably the Nitrogen based manure application threshold for soil phosphorus levels.</p>
<p>Do your NMP/MMPS follow, comply with, or based on NRCS Technical Standard 590?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Application rates: <i>State regulations that restrict the rates at which manures are</i></p>	<p>Soil Testing. The soil profile shall be analyzed a minimum of once every five (5) years for phosphorus content. The results of these analyses are to be used in determining application rates for manure, litter, and other process wastewater. Soil analysis shall be conducted for nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium. Soil analysis shall be conducted by a Proficiency Assessment program (PAP) certified soils laboratory. http://www.naptprogram.org/pap/ __ Nutrient Budget_ The nutrient budget shall include crop nutrient requirements minus nutrient credits.</p>

<p><i>applied and methods needed to determine appropriate rates.</i></p>	<p>Nutrient credits include legume nitrogen, residual soil nutrients, nutrients from commercial fertilizer application, irrigation water nitrate nitrogen, and other nutrient sources. Plant available nitrogen from manure may be calculated with Manure Management Planner http://www.agry.purdue.edu/mmp/ or by using the following nutrient availability factors. (N based: use 0.4 for solids, 0.3 for liquids or slurries, and 0.2 for composted material; P based use 1.0). An assessment utilizing the phosphorus index shall be conducted for each land application area to determine the potential for phosphorus transport to surface water. An assessment utilizing the Colorado Nitrogen Leaching Index Risk Assessment shall be conducted for each land application area to determine the potential for nitrogen transport to ground water. The following restrictions shall apply based on the results of the Phosphorus index: _</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Phosphorus based manure and process wastewater application rates shall apply where the phosphorus transport risk is high. _ 2. No application of manure or process wastewater shall be made to a land application area with a phosphorus transport risk rating of very high or a soil analysis phosphorus value of 154 ppm or higher. _ 3. Nitrogen applications shall follow the Risk Interpretations guidelines of the Nitrogen Leaching Index. _ <p>_</p> <p>P-Index is used for application rates unless excessive P levels in soil. No application of manure if soil P is 154 ppm or above.</p>
<p>Manure application rates for phosphorus are based on:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) <i>Phosphorus Index Only</i> 2) <i>Soil Test Phosphorus Only</i> 3) <i>Either PIO or STPO</i> 4) <i>Other</i> 	<p>Phosphorus index only</p>
<p>Are there any nutrient “caps” to manure application ?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Composition testing: <i>State</i></p>	<p>Manure must be analyzed for nitrogen and phosphorus content a minimum of once annually</p>

<p><i>regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on manures before application</i></p>	
<p>Does your state require testing of manure for anything beyond nutrients, such as metals, pathogens, antibiotics, etc.?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Other land application highlights: <i>Additional restrictions for land application of manures</i></p>	<p>No other information</p>
<p>Other regulatory details: <i>Additional information on the regulation of land application of manures</i></p>	<p>For fields with soil test phosphorus levels of 200 ppm and greater, applications of phosphorus from manure and process wastewater are prohibited unless the permittee receives department approval. The department may only approve the application if all of t</p>
<p>General Assessment Questions</p>	
<p>Do you anticipate changes in these</p>	<p>Undetermined</p>

<p>regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change:</p>	
<p>Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of manures that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links:</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of manures beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these</p>	<p>No</p>

entities if so:	
Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.	No other information